

ACCESS TO JUSTICE FOR WOMEN IN
NIGERIA: A SOCIOLEGAL ANALYSIS OF
FAMILY MEDIATION

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B00360788

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Date: 30/11/2023

Statement of Originality

I hereby declare that this research is entirely my own work and that any additional sources of information have been properly cited. I declare that any internet sources, published or unpublished works from which I have quoted or drawn reference have been referenced fully in the text. I understand that failure to do this will result in a failure of this research due to Plagiarism.

Signed: Marian Nkiruka Wokocha

Date: 30/11/2023

ABSTRACT

“It is amazing how little true communication takes place during the litigation process and conversely how much each side learns about the other side’s case and what the real issues are when they take part in mediation”.

-Alexander Bevan¹

Family mediation as a process of dispute resolution for women is not a topic that has generated particular jurisprudence in Nigeria, not for lack of importance but appears to have been overlooked by society. If there is a family dispute, there are accepted channels of resolution which involve informal and formal procedures. How these procedures affect women’s rights and access to justice is the reason for this study.

My motivation for this study has been my experience as a family dispute mediator for over 20 years during which time I witnessed the helplessness of women in the resolution of family disputes. The lack of freedom of some women to express their desire in their choice of dispute resolution process or have their interests protected during resolution of family disputes is the crux of this study. In most of the cases, the women experienced informal mediation due to its accessibility and familiarity and not because it is their preferred method of dispute resolution. The process is often regulated by members of the family or people whose impartiality might be questioned. Existing literature is yet to capture the absence of women’s choice in the mode of dispute resolution they contend with during informal mediation and the enforcement of agreement from the mediation therein. Therefore, the aim of this research is to verify through empirical evidence, the availability and outcome of family dispute resolution choices for women and the position of family mediation in the legal consciousness of women.

The methodology chosen for this research is the mixed method which comprises of the legal, feminist, and social research methods. The research philosophy for this study is the pragmatic approach to allow flexibility and adoption of the best methods in the conduct, analysis, and interpretation of the primary work. In adopting the socio-legal research methodology, the research is focused on exploring the experiences of women in Nigeria who seek to resolve family disputes through family mediation: this is the original contribution to knowledge made by this thesis.

¹ Alexander Bevan, *Alternative Dispute Resolution – A Lawyer’s Guide to Mediation and other forms of Dispute Resolution*, (Sweet & Maxwell, 1992) 26.

Dedication

This thesis is dedicated to the Almighty God for His faithfulness in my life.

Acknowledgement

The dream to obtain a PhD is one I have had for a long time, and I am grateful to God almighty for making it come true. This journey has been a challenging and intense experience in the academic world which is a sharp contrast from practice in the legal field.

I would like to acknowledge the wonderful support of Federación Internacional de Abogadas (FIDA) in assisting me achieve my objective and completing this research.

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No. 2 of 2022
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Abbreviations

AAA- American Arbitration Association

ADR-Alternative Dispute Resolution

BPFA- Beijing Platform for Action

CEDAW- Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women.

CEDR- Centre for Effective Dispute Resolution

CIArb - Chartered Institute of Arbitrators

CLEEN - Centre for Law Enforcement Education

CSW- Commission on the Status of Women

ECOSOC-United Nations Economic and Social Council

FGM - Female Genital Mutilation

ICC-International Chamber of Commerce

ICMC- Institute of Chartered Mediators and Conciliators

IPV- Intimate Partner Violence

MIAM- Mediation Issues Assessment Meeting

MSA- Mediation Settlement Agreement

NCMG-Negotiation and Conflict Management Group

SDG - Sustainable Development Goals

UNAC-United Nations Convention Against Corruption

UNCITRAL-United Nations Commission on International Trade Law

UNDP - United Nations Development Programme

WID – Women in Development

WINET - Women Information Network

WIP – Women in Politic

Chapter One

Introduction

Background

Justice is an important right to every human being and consequently the right to access justice is universally acclaimed.² Justice is seen in different ways by different people.³ On the issue of gender, it is more challenging to women of the developing world to access justice due to the barriers they encounter, such as poverty and lack of basic infrastructure like roads to access legal services from the police, empowerment support from family and society, etc.

As this study is focused on Nigerian women, the research will examine the barriers to accessing justice by women in developing countries of which Nigeria belongs.⁴ Family mediation is a channel through which women can access justice in relation to interpersonal and family disputes. There is a plethora of literature surrounding mediation and women but most of it consist of mediation in the work environment as seen in the writings of Emami et al.⁵

This study will examine family mediation from the formal and informal perspectives as depicted in the diagram below:

² The Sixth Committee of the United Nations with representatives from 39 countries: Nicaragua, Ukraine, Ethiopia, Vietnam, Philippines, Argentina, Senegal, Brazil, Zambia, Kyrgyzstan, Burkina Faso, Slovenia, Nigeria, Estonia, Turkey, Myanmar, Algeria, Guinea, Maldives, Sri Lanka, Tonga, Indonesia, Bangladesh, Iran, Austria, China, Syria, Mexico, Eritrea, Montenegro, India, Tunisia, Zimbabwe, Mozambique, Armenia, Sierra Leone, Georgia, Malawi and Kuwait. <https://press.un.org/en/2014/gal3478.doc.htm> (Accessed 2 November 2023).

³ David Johnston, *A Brief History of Justice* (1st edn, John Wiley & Sons Ltd 2011) 64.

⁴ World Data Report <https://www.worlddata.info/developing-countries.php> (Accessed 31/08/2023).

⁵ Amir Emami, Shayegeh Ashourizadeh and Mark Packard, 'The Impact of Social Network support on Opportunity Intention among prospective male and female entrepreneurs during 2019 COVID Pandemic' (2023) 29 (11) *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour and Research* 132.

Some countries like Australia officially practise informal family mediation by recognising the role of informal family mediation and incorporating it in their legislation, referred to as family dispute resolution since 2007.⁶ Batagol et al explored the relationship of the law and family mediation in the resolution of family disputes in Australia and found there were provisions of the *Family Law Act* which communicated a non-adversarial method of resolving family disputes to parties.⁷ Unlike formal family mediation which takes place in the court where the judge is bound to follow the law and the principles of the state, informal family mediation has a weak connection to legal enforcement and if legal consent is not formalised in the court, can be defaulted by any of the parties without legal consequence. The same situation occurs in Nigeria because for a legal consent, formal legal procedures with lawyers must be undertaken to obtain them in the court. This study will focus on the connection between informal and formal family mediation as it impacts on the lives of Nigerian women.

Research Problem

Women in Nigeria are usually at the receiving end of family disputes as evidenced by the challenges they encounter whenever there is a dissolution of marriage. Studies have highlighted the challenges women encounter in expressing their rights in family disputes even in matters as mundane as accommodation issues.⁸ Despite these challenges, Bagshaw's research indicated that women prefer to manage family disputes within the family rather than seek outside intervention because of the hardship of accessing justice which range from discrimination to economic factors.⁹

⁶ Becky Batagol and Thea Brown, *Bargaining in the Shadow of the Law: the case of family mediation* (Themis Press, 2011) 225.

⁷ Ibid.

⁸ Ayelet Shachar, 'Group Identity and Women's Rights in Family Law: The perils of Multicultural accommodation' (1998) 6(3) *Journal of Political Philosophy* 285 especially at 287.

⁹ Dale Bagshaw *Handbook of Conflict Management* (Routledge 2003) 36.

The challenges women experience in accessing justice include the lack of enforcement of mediation agreement where one party fails to comply with the decision: something witnessed in practice repeatedly and motivated this research. The non-obligatory enforcement of informal family mediation in the Nigerian environment has created many challenges for women who often suffer the consequences in losing property after divorce or not having adequate support for their children that are left behind with them or the abuses they suffer while in the marriage.¹⁰

Apart from published numerous works that supports the problem highlighted in this study, the researcher witnessed during her years of legal practice, the challenges women encounter with regards to access to justice and right to fair hearing during informal family mediation.

Research Question

The main research question of this study is:

How has family mediation affected the rights of women's access to justice in Nigeria?

In finding the answer to this question, other questions which emerged are as follows:

- a) Do women have freedom and access to alternative dispute resolution when it comes to family disputes?
- b) Is mediation the best form of dispute resolution for women in family disputes especially in Nigeria considering the cultural and ethnic peculiarities which characterise the different regions?
- (c) Are there laws in place to regulate family mediation specifically in Nigeria?

Research Aim

The primary aim of this thesis is to critically examine the use of mediation laws on family disputes and the impact of these laws on women's access to justice. Women have been

¹⁰ Ine Nnadi, 'An Insight into Violence against Women in Nigeria as Human Rights Violation in Nigeria: a Critique' (2012) 5(3) Journal of Politics and Law 48 especially at 51.

recognised as being part of the vulnerable group in society globally, as stated by the Security Council of the United Nations in 1999 to date.¹¹ It is no wonder importance is attached to the protection and promotion of rights of women with the different programmes organised by the UN Women. Part of the aim of this research is to increase awareness on the impact of family mediation in the lives of women generally, but more particularly in Nigeria (as a result of personal observations in practice as a legal practitioner). The researcher's desire to increase the awareness of women's access to justice originates from witnessing the challenges women experience in being limited to the forms of dispute resolution available to them; even where the process is not favourable to them.

Research Objectives

- a) To identify the factors which feature in informal mediation of women's experience in family mediation.
- b) To examine how informal mediation affects women's right to access justice.
- c) To examine if mediation is a practical method of dispute resolution in all family disputes for women.
- d) To contribute positively to the jurisprudence¹² surrounding family mediation in Nigeria especially with respect to informal mediation and the promotion of enforcement of mediation agreements.

- (e) To recommend how informal family mediation can be regulated by legislation to ensure quality and effective facilitation of service in the delivery of justice especially for Nigerian women.

¹¹ United Nation <https://www.un.org/en/fight-racism/vulnerable-groups#:~:text=Persons%20Belonging%20to%20National%20or,Women> (Accessed 28 August 2023).

¹² Oxford Learners Dictionary of Academic English defines jurisprudence as the "scientific study of law".

The above objectives are to be achieved by examining the need for mediation agreements from family disputes to be legally binding on parties without having to first register the agreement as a consent judgement in court to make it enforceable.

Significance of Study

The home front poses numerous challenges for women and when combined with limited access to justice, these difficulties are exacerbated. This study aims to explore the specific challenges faced by Nigerian women on a daily basis, as they often lack sufficient support from legal institutions or their own families. Some of the challenges this research will examine include how women from when they are girls, can be deprived from formal education and forced into early marriages or be stigmatised for fighting for their rights. The women in northern Nigeria have the added difficulty of terrorist activities such as the Boko Haram who oppose anything western education. More explanation will be in the chapters of this study. In many cases, women assume the role of homemakers, responsible for upholding traditional customs and practices, especially in regions like Nigeria and Africa, where customs hold significant importance, and the woman is saddled with maintaining the honour of the family.

To gain a comprehensive understanding of the obstacles preventing women from accessing justice, this research will delve into various forms of dispute resolution. Specifically, it will investigate whether mediation proves to be the most suitable approach for resolving family disputes. The main focus of this study is to analyse the impact of both informal and formal mediation on the accessibility of justice for Nigerian women.

This research will examine how mediation impacts on women in family disputes due to the vulnerable nature of women which has been recognised by international parastatals such as the United Nation as mentioned earlier. In furtherance to the protection of the rights of women, the United Nation promulgated (amongst others), the **Convention on the Elimination of**

Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW),¹³ the Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights on the Rights of Women in Africa (African Women's Rights Protocol)¹⁴ which provides in *Article 8* equality before the law between men and women. It proceeds further to stipulate that State Parties shall take all appropriate measures to ensure effective access by women to judicial and legal services, including legal aid. The significance of this research can also be seen in its focus on Nigerian women in using family mediation as a process to resolve disputes because that focus corresponds with the international convention's theme which is the importance of women's access to justice.

Research Method

This research is the study of Nigerian women's access to justice through family mediation. In order to achieve the objectives, the methodology therefore consists of a combination of the legal, sociolegal, and feminist methods of research. This study adopts the Honeycomb research model¹⁵ to explain the research methods. The research philosophy chosen is pragmatism to allow the best methods to be used to achieve the objectives of this study. The research approach is inductive while the strategy is qualitative. The research design adopts case study as Nigerian women are the focus of this study. The data collection stage consists of secondary data sources for the literature, use of a survey, and semi-structured interviews in accordance with qualitative research methods. The data analysis will adopt the narrative, and grounded theory in analysing the collected data. The conclusions and recommendations will be based on the findings and discussions.

Contribution to Knowledge

¹³ Convention on the Elimination of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) <https://www.un.org/womenwatch/daw/cedaw/> (Accessed 03 August 2023).

¹⁴ Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights on the Rights of Women in Africa (African Women's Rights Protocol) <https://www.un.org/shestandsforpeace/content/protocol-african-charter-human-and-peoples-rights-rights-women-africa-maputo-protocol-2003> (Accessed 03 August 2023).

¹⁵ Jonathan Wilson *Essentials of Business Research* (Sage Publications 2014).

This study makes the following contributions while refuting and confirming some positions associated with family mediation. This thesis contributes to knowledge by confirming the position that the resolutions arrived at from informal family mediation are ineffective where there is lack of compliance due to lack of enforceability by any of the parties. This study confirms that for satisfaction to be achieved from informal mediation, there is a requirement of the formality ascribed to formal mediation which ensures enforcement of mediation agreement. It is the contribution of this research that both forms of family mediation are important and lack of enforcement of the mediation agreement is the key to accessing the justice sought by the disputing parties when they proceed from informal mediation to formal mediation.

This study further reinforces the fact that access to justice should also be considered from the cultural and contextual perspective. Factors such as ethnicity, religion, education, and other social issues influence access to justice and impact on family mediation. It is therefore the original contribution of this research that for family mediation to be successful as a means to access justice for women in Nigeria, there should be legal framework for enforcement of the mediation agreement, including informal mediation. It is the further contribution of this thesis to the jurisprudence surrounding family mediation in Nigeria, to showcase the work of NGOs such as FIDA in promoting the awareness of the legal consciousness of women all over the world, on their rights with emphasis on informal family mediation.

Layout of Chapters

This study has been grouped into eight chapters. The thesis is explained in the following chapters:

Chapter One begins the study with an overview of the research and followed by the Methodology of this research in Chapter Two which explains the philosophy of this study including the approach, strategy, and design of this research. A survey and interviews were

used to collect data. Other research principles such as ethics, validity and the limitations of this study were considered and explained.

. Chapter Three begins the literature by establishing the theoretical framework thus explaining the concept of justice, legal theories and the theory of access to justice. The exploration of the theory of legal consciousness examines the impact on women's access to justice. Chapter Four continues the exploration of published literature by examining the legal framework of women's rights beginning at a global level before focusing on Nigerian laws on women's rights. Chapter Five then builds on this foundation with an examination of family mediation as a process of accessing justice by distinguishing informal from formal mediation. The existing legal framework regulating women's access to justice in Nigeria will also be examined. While Chapter Six begins the findings section with the discussion on the three major themes which emerged from the data collected -: "Informal Mediation as a process to justice", "Accessing the formal system", and "Intimate Partner Violence". This chapter discusses these themes as well as the sub-themes which run through them, namely: *the impact of culture on family mediation, the role of patriarchy in women's access to justice, stigma and social control as a barrier to women's access to justice, and the effect of religion in family mediation.*

Chapter Seven concludes the findings by discussing the second part of the following themes: "Enforcement of Mediation Agreement" and "Government Policy Intervention". Chapter Eight is the last chapter containing the conclusion and recommendations of this study.

The purpose of the recommendations is to impact on the jurisprudence of family mediation in Nigeria and improve women's access to justice by proposing for enforcement of family mediation agreements.

CHAPTER TWO

METHODOLOGY CHAPTER

2.1 Introduction

The essence of this chapter is to outline the research methods through which the questions of this study will be answered. The main question of this research is “how has family mediation affected the rights of women’s access to justice in Nigeria?”

To understand how women’s access to justice is affected by family mediation, this chapter explains the methodology applied in conducting this study. The answers to the research questions will be achieved based on the data analysis of the findings which will lead to the recommendations of this study. The methodology is a combination of legal, feminist, and social approaches to ensure the objectives of this research are achieved. The methods of procuring the necessary data, the challenges and limitations of the study will be discussed in this chapter.

The purpose of this chapter is to illustrate the justification of the research methods adopted in this study which include understanding the legal and social aspect of the research. The following sections will depict the approaches and research philosophy of this study. This chapter explains the research philosophy, strategy and design of this study. It explains the case study design, sampling, the data collection process, data analysis including the challenges associated with the data process. The methodology chosen for this study is the mixed method which is a pragmatic approach due to the sociolegal nature of the research. The family is a social unit and the process of family mediation as a process of dispute resolution is a legal exercise which requires regulation to ensure fairness, equity and justice while preserving the nature of family.

To achieve the aim and objectives of this research, it is necessary to understand the intricacies of family mediation and the factors which impact on women’s access to justice beginning from the family level of dispute resolution. The data analysis was procured from the survey and interviews to provide the evidence of access to justice by women through family mediation. The choice to conduct the data collection through the online process had to be made with the

emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic which altered the preferred face-to-face method of the original plans of the researcher. The emerging themes from the survey will provide the foundation for further investigation in the questions for the interviews. The emergence of sub-themes will be discussed in the data analysis. NVivo was used to code the responses of the participants and the responses were grouped into chapters for clearer discussions. The chapter ends with a conclusion on the limitations of the research including the impact of COVID-19 on the study.

2.2 Definition of Methodology

In explaining how to achieve the aims and objectives of this research, it is necessary to define methodology before embarking on the appropriate research method for this study.

Methodology has been defined as the systematic identification of strategy that outlines the methods to be adopted in research that would define data collection procedure to attain the objective of the research.¹⁶ Coomans et al have described methodology as the approach of a work that addresses the question of how to find relevant information, organise it, and interpret the results.¹⁷ As a researcher, it is preferable to proceed from a place of understanding in seeking the unknown. Understanding the subject of research gives direction to the researcher on how to proceed with the chosen methodology.

Consequently, this chapter is to illustrate the format this research would adopt and how the objectives of this study would be achieved. The reasons for the actions in investigating the impact of family mediation on women in Nigeria, is to ascertain how it affects their access to justice. This study is aimed at examining how family mediation laws affect women's rights to

¹⁶ Kelly E Howell *Introduction to the Philosophy of Methodology* (Sage Publications London 2013).

¹⁷ Fons Coomans, Fred Grunfeld and Menno Kamminga, 'Methods of Human Rights Research' (2010) 32 *Human Rights Quarterly* 179 especially at 183.

access justice. To achieve the aims of this study, different traditional methods of research will be combined as this is a legal study of the social impact of legislation on society.

The methodology of this research includes the legal, social and feminist research methods to investigate the surrounding impact of family mediation in Nigeria and other jurisdictions as they affect the rights of women's access to justice. The chosen methodology is in accordance with the pragmatic approach, which is the research philosophy of this study, as it is a combination of mixed methods to achieve the aims of this study. The researcher agrees with Susan Krieger that "the pot carries its maker's thoughts, feelings, and spirit and to overlook this fact is to miss a crucial truth, whether in clay, story, or science".¹⁸ This research is the fulfilment of the researcher's desire to understand and share the personal experiences of women in understanding the intricacies of family mediation witnessed over the years as a legal practitioner. It is also a reflection of the lawyer the researcher has become in the past years from observing the challenges associated with women's rights especially in Nigeria. Observing the increasing number of family disputes which are reported daily at the FIDA legal centre was an indication that there was a challenge with the informal mediation process usually practiced in most families in Nigeria.

In the determination to achieve the aim of this study, the researcher has uncovered depths of herself she did not know she possessed especially in the art of being able to perceive the different approaches necessary to adopt during the interview phase of the data gathering process. The interpersonal dynamics of the researcher came to the fore in encouraging the interviewees without altering the data but enhancing the quality of the data being proffered to ensure the objectives of the research are achieved. A good illustration was guiding the conversation back along the lines of the questions asked when the interviewee would begin to

¹⁸ Susan Krieger (1991) in Linda Findlay 'Outing- the Researcher: The Provenance, Process, and Practice of Reflexivity' (2002) 12(4) Qualitative Health Research Journal 531.

narrate the entire story surrounding the dispute which might not be relevant to the research question. The researcher found herself totally in agreement with the concept of reflexivity as postulated by Linda Findlay, in her writings that “...researchers from these traditions are sensitive to the way they frame research questions, select participants, and interact with them to produce the observations and texts of analysis”.¹⁹

The research being an analysis on family mediation process in Nigeria with the focus on women, can only be achieved by gathering the necessary data surrounding the dynamics of family mediation including enforcement of the agreement.

2.3. Research Philosophy

The purpose of this study is to understand the impact of family mediation and the relation between informal and formal mediation, especially in the lives of Nigerian women in seeking access to justice. The research philosophy discusses the approaches necessary in understanding the enforcement of mediation agreement while explaining the relationship between informal and formal mediation and the factors which affect them. The objective of this research led to the choice of research philosophy and approaches adopted in this study in order to address the ontological and epistemological questions of this research. The difference in researchers lies in the freedom which they believe individuals should change their lives and the world around them and the constraints of societal structures on the actions of individuals and their lives.²⁰ The choice of research philosophy is based on the need to examine the existing structure and laws which regulate family mediation in Nigeria and whether these laws adequately provide for the rights of women in Nigeria to access justice.

¹⁹ Linda Findlay ‘Outing’ the Researcher: The Provenance, Process, and Practice of Reflexivity’ (2002) 12(4) *Qualitative Health Research Journal* 537.

²⁰ Mark Sanders, Philip Lewis and Adrian Thornhill, *Research Methods for Business Students* (8th edn Pearson Education Limited New York 2019) 133.

In deciding the research philosophy, the researcher had to identify how to achieve the objectives. There was a need to examine the existing laws and how they affect the women. The law in practice, does it achieve the purpose for which it was created? In this case when parties agree to a mediation agreement, is the law of agreement binding enough to compel parties to abide by the agreement, and is the purpose of the mediation achieved? A major focus of this study is to understand why there is still a need for formal mediation after informal mediation has occurred in a family dispute. There is a need to distinguish the law in theory from the law in practice. This study seeks to examine how effective mediation laws are in the reality of family disputes. Consequently, the ontological and epistemological questions of this research will be answered with the Pragmatist approach.

2.3.1. *Pragmatism*

It is the research philosophy which focuses on the research problem while employing the most appropriate methods which answer the research question.²¹ Feilzer in agreement with Creswell and Plano Clark, supports pragmatism as a research method as it uses both qualitative and quantitative research methods.²² Laws are created to guide and regulate society. The adoption of the pragmatist view is to ascertain the most appropriate methods in analysing the impact of family mediation laws and the existing structure in the Nigerian legal system especially in the lives of Nigerian women. The pragmatic approach creates the enabling research methods to study the relationship between informal and formal mediation and the factors which influence family disputes. Social phenomena keep changing because it is constantly being activated by social actors and to determine how these changes occur, there is a need to understand why. The researcher must choose an approach that is in accordance with the research philosophy of the

²¹ Jonathan Wilson *Essentials of Business Research* (Sage Publications 2014) 11.

²² Martina Feilzer, 'Doing Mixed Methods Research Pragmatically: Implications for the Rediscovery of Pragmatism as a Research Paradigm' (2009) 20(10) *Journal of Mixed Methods Research* 1-11.

study. The approach to research can be inductive or deductive in accordance with the chosen research philosophy.²³ The inductive approach is chosen in line with the research philosophy to achieve the aim of this study.

2.3.2. *Inductive Approach*

This study adopts the inductive approach which collects data and arrives at a conclusion based on the data analysis which is usually associated with the qualitative method of research. This is in accordance with Wilson's definition of the inductive approach.²⁴ The inductive approach is traditionally associated with qualitative methods which is more exploratory in nature and will allow in-depth examination on the challenges experienced through informal and formal family mediation in Nigeria. In adopting an inductive approach, the family mediation process will be examined through the feminist lens to understand the perspective of family mediation on the international level and relate it to reality at state level as Nigeria is signatory to some international and regional conventions.²⁵ It is important to understand the strategy necessary for the research. The strategy to be employed by a researcher could be either qualitative or quantitative and, in some cases, both methods are combined as stated by Wilson.²⁶ Mixed method is necessary where the data to be collected is of numerical value and requires in-depth examination due to variable social factors. As earlier mentioned, the pragmatic philosophy of this research allows mixed method which consist of qualitative and quantitative research strategies.

2.4 Research Approach and Design

²³ Jonathan Wilson *Essentials of Business Research*, (Sage Publications 2014) 8.

²⁴ Jonathan Wilson *Essentials of Business Research* (Sage Publications 2014) 14.

²⁵ CEDAW- Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women, Banjul Charter – African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights.

²⁶ Jonathan Wilson *Essentials of Business Research* (Sage Publications 2014) 15.

The approach and design of this research as a socio legal study is a combination of legal and social research methods. A brief explanation on what constitutes legal and social research methods is necessary to enhance the chosen methodology for this research.

2.4.1. Legal Methodology

Western is of the view that the purpose of legal research is not to restore order but to be innovative and discover a new order and rearrange matters in a manner that accommodates the new developments.²⁷ There are different approaches of legal methodology, and it is the responsibility of a legal researcher to decide the best methodology to achieve the aims of the research project based on clear and precise arguments.²⁸

The different approaches in legal methodology as stated by Salter and Mason²⁹ are:

Black- Letter approach, which is best suited for doctrinal research, as this is a positivist approach which analyzes law as it ought to be.

Sociolegal approach, which studies the effect of the law on society as the focus is law-in-action and consequently the choice for this research.

Comparative approach, which allows comparative research between issues and arrives at a conclusion.

Historical approach, which is research based on the history of the subject of study.

This research adopts the sociolegal approach of the legal methodology based on the understanding of this approach and what this study seeks to achieve.

²⁷ Pauline Western ‘Open or autonomous? The debate on legal Methodology as a reflection of the debate on law’ (University of Groningen Faculty of law SSRN 2010) 7.

²⁸ Michael Salter and Julie Mason *Writing Law Dissertations – An Introduction and Guide to the Conduct of Legal Research* (Pearson Education Limited England 2007) 109.

²⁹ Michael Salter and Julie Mason, *Writing Law Dissertations – An Introduction and Guide to the Conduct of Legal Research*, (Pearson Education Limited, England 2007) 44 -182.

2.4.2 *Sociolegal Approach*

In an attempt to define this complex approach several writers have proffered different views on their understanding of the sociolegal approach. Thomas opines that law is a component part of the wider social and political structure and is related to an infinite variety of ways and can only be understood when studied in that regard.³⁰ Another contributor to sociolegal studies, Jolly has stated that it is a kind of research that investigates law in action that exceeds the exclusive doctrinal analysis of authoritative legal texts.³¹ While Baldwin insists that an account of a legal rule is only complete when there is an understanding of how it is selectively used in reality.³² It was stated in some case studies which showed that where legal rules applied in principle, in practice they were selectively enforced or bypassed. Socio-legal studies, of which its focus is 'law-in-action', investigates issues which involve an informed opinion of a legal nature but are beyond the capabilities of doctrinal analysis.³³ All these authors are of the opinion that rules are only effective if they are meaningful to the people they are enacted for. Socio-legal studies has also been described as a wide range of methodological approaches derived from theoretical bases to examine critically, the relationship between law and society.³⁴ In the same vein, Eekelaar and Maclean state that a socio-legal study is the discipline of observing how the law operates through those who assume themselves to be executing the law.³⁵

³⁰ Phil Thomas 'Curriculum Development in Legal Studies' (1986) 20 *Law Teacher* 110 at 112.

³¹ Michael Salter and Julie Mason, *Writing Law Dissertations – An Introduction and Guide to the Conduct of Legal Research* (Pearson Education Limited, England 2007) 125.

³² Robert Baldwin, Martin Cave and Martin Lodge *The Oxford Handbook of Regulation* (Oxford University Press 1995).

³³ Michael Salter and Julie Mason, *Writing Law Dissertations – An Introduction and Guide to the Conduct of Legal Research* (Pearson Education Limited England 2007) 126.

³⁴ Simon Jolly in Philip Thomas (ed) *Socio-Legal Studies* (Aldershot: Ashgate-Dartmouth 1997) 86.

³⁵ John Eekelaar and Mavis Maclean *A Reader in Family Law* (Oxford: OUP 1994) 2.

Sociolegal methodology focuses on the social nature, functions, and implications of the legal rules. Bradshaw postulates that the researcher in adopting a sociolegal methodology is required to gather whatever data that is relevant to the issue of study and by using any method necessary to procure the required data.³⁶ For purposes of this study, the researcher, is in total agreement with the position of Bradshaw as this explanation simplifies what is necessary to achieve the aim of this study. A major feature of socio-legal approach consists of research projects which investigate and analyze the impact of law in action through specific study using individual and group interviews or other methods of qualitative analysis.³⁷ This major feature distinguishes the sociolegal approach from other approaches and is ideal for this study as this research will examine the existing structure of family mediation in Nigeria and its effectiveness through surveys and interviews.

A former Director of the Oxford Centre for Socio-Legal Studies stated that there is no agreed definition of socio-legal studies but describes it as a study of the law and its legal institutions from the perspective of the social sciences and to avoid limiting the development, it should be accorded the widest definition.³⁸ A broad definition of socio-legal methodology would also include interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary research skills as contained in the opinion of the Director of the Oxford Centre for Socio-Legal Studies.

The Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC)³⁹ acknowledges that the jurisdiction of socio-legal studies encompasses various disciplinary concepts in the social sciences and law which relates the legal to the sociological, economic, and political aspects of human activities.

³⁶ Alan Bradshaw *Sense and Sensibility: Debates and Developments in Socio-Legal Research Methods* in Philip Thomas (ed) *Socio-Legal Studies* (Aldershot: Ashgate-Dartmouth, 1997) 107.

³⁷ Michael Salter and Julie Mason *Writing Law Dissertations – An Introduction and Guide to the Conduct of Legal Research* (Pearson Education Limited England 2007) 130.

³⁸ Don Harris 'The Development of Socio-Legal Studies in the United Kingdom' (1983) 2 *Legal Studies* 315.

³⁹ Economic and Social Research Council is a major source of funding for socio-legal research.

Socio-Legal research aims to bridge the gap between law-in-books and law-in-action and rectify the negativity by seeking empirical knowledge of the relationship, actions and attitudes of the parties involved in legal proceedings.⁴⁰

There are different research methods which are employed in Socio-Legal methodology⁴¹ which include the following to be used in achieving the objectives of this study:

Qualitative research which uses in-depth interviews that could be structured or semi-structured.

Quantitative research method which employs official statistics, surveys, and questionnaires to gather data and the statistical information is analyzed.

Computer assisted analysis which uses a computer software to analyze data collated by the different research methods.

There are also certain features which characterize socio-legal methodology irrespective of the methods of research chosen.⁴² They consist of a fully informed consent from the research participants, avoiding issues that could endanger the wellbeing of the participants, protecting and ensuring the confidentiality of the data obtained and its publication, the contributions of fellow researchers must be properly acknowledged and represented. These are principles which guide socio-legal research methods. It is crucial that the researcher procures an informed consent from the research participants to comply with ethical principles.

⁴⁰ Michael Salter and Julie Mason, *Writing Law Dissertations – An Introduction and Guide to the Conduct of Legal Research* (Pearson Education Limited England 2007) 152 -172.

⁴¹ Ibid.

⁴² Ibid.

There is a sample of the standard prescribed by the Code of Conduct in universities for students who engage in socio-legal research to ensure all ethical considerations are complied with.⁴³

These standards are grouped into:

- 1) General principles
- 2) Consent and Welfare of Participants
- 3) Ethics Checklist
- 4) Participant Information Sheet
- 5) Participant Consent Form

In conducting this research, the above ethical considerations of the Code of Conduct of the University of the West of Scotland were complied with. In the book *Writing Law Dissertations* by Salter and Mason,⁴⁴ it was stated that research into the current position of a legal doctrine can only be achieved through the pursuit of sociolegal studies methods as the doctrinal approach of the black-letter methodology lacks the effectiveness of evaluating policy and moral questions. This statement emphasizes the need for this research to adopt the sociolegal approach as the research method for this study as the aim of this research is to evaluate how family mediation affects the rights of women's access to justice in Nigeria, which means investigating law-in-action as it affects women's rights.

2.4.3. *Feminist Legal Methodology*

The objective of this research includes analysing the rights of women in accessing justice through the medium of family mediation and therefore makes the consideration of feminist legal methodology necessary. Feminist legal methodology universally is unified by a common

⁴³ Ibid.

⁴⁴ Ibid 43.

goal of revealing and challenging the role of law in the emancipation of women's inequality.⁴⁵ Legal studies on feminism have revealed how ill-equipped law is in recognizing and challenging the informal gender rules which characterises legal institutions and are of the perception that international law is more receptive to feminist demands and activism.⁴⁶ Feminists have realised that their voices can challenge the legal culture and traditions in a particular jurisdiction to bring about legal cultural change.⁴⁷ In examining the literature, the researcher discovered a project called *Feminist Judgements* which is an international project that cuts across different regions. But unfortunately, such a project is yet to be identified by any representation from an African country or the similarity of such a project in Nigeria.

The desired legal change can occur by reorganising the structure in the production of feminist judgements with the consideration of gender inequality and power dynamics which consist of ethnicity, class, gender identity, sexual orientation, national identity and disability.⁴⁸ A good illustration of this movement to agitate legal change in feminist judgement was the Canadian initiative of the Women's Court of Canada.⁴⁹ Another example of feminist activism was in the administration of feminist judgements in Scotland where Claire McDiarmid, one of Scotland's feminist writers in 2014, explored criminal law and allowed provocation as self-defence for women in cases of sexual infidelity when it was a defence pleaded by men in the past.⁵⁰ These

⁴⁵ Catherine O'Rourke, 'Feminist Legal Method and the Study of Institutions' (2014) 10(4) Politics & Gender 691.

⁴⁶ Ibid.

⁴⁷ Sharon Cowan 'The Scottish Feminist Judgments Project: A New Frontier' (2018) 8 Oñati Socio-Legal Series 9.

⁴⁸ Ibid.

⁴⁹ Diana Majury 'Introducing the Women's Court of Canada' (2006) 18 (1) Canadian Journal of Women and the Law 1-26.

⁵⁰ Sharon Cowan 'The Scottish Feminist Judgments Project: A New Frontier' (2018) 8 Oñati Socio-Legal Series 1390.

contributions to feminist legal methodology influence the policy and effect the desired changes in the rights of women. It is important to include feminist legal methodology in this research as it is the researcher's intention to impact positively on women's rights with this study.

2.5 Feminist Methodology

The concept of feminist methods of research elicits all kinds of theories as it relates to conducting research. It is therefore necessary to define the concept which has been described as the theoretical understatements of procedures, practices and rules adopted by feminists in conducting research.⁵¹ This also includes terminologies, the language of the research, methods to be employed, the type of analysis to be used in interpreting collected data, the literature to be used, as well as the research questions the study seeks to answer.

Feminist methodology is usually compatible with the qualitative method of social research in contrast to quantitative methods which have been described as masculine and cannot express the various complexities of the richness of the lives of women.⁵² The notion that there is an affinity between feminism and qualitative research is supported by the view that qualitative research provides a greater opportunity for women's voices to be heard and feminist sensitivity to come to the fore.⁵³ Quantitative research on the other hand has been viewed as being incompatible with feminism because it turns women into objects even when they are the focus of the research and suppresses their voices either by burying them in a flurry of facts and statistics or ignoring them.⁵⁴ The focus of this study is to hear the voices of Nigerian women on the impact of family mediation.

⁵¹ Linda Peake and others *Feminist methodologies* (John Wiley & Sons 2017) 6.

⁵² Ibid.

⁵³ Bryman Alan, *Social Research Methods*, (5th edn, Oxford University Press 2016) 403.

⁵⁴ Maria Miles, *Towards a Methodology for Feminist Research* (Sage Publications London 1993) 66.

The different methods of qualitative analysis which include interviews, focus groups, ethnographies, archival analysis and others are more frequently adopted by feminist researchers as it affords a rich study of the capturing of a woman's life experience.

The objective of feminist research is to conduct the research for the emancipatory goals of feminism to be achieved and alleviate the conditions of oppression and reformulate the traditional research approach.⁵⁵ The qualitative approach being more disposed to the feminist methodology is to be adopted in this research as part of the goal of this study is to emancipate women from the challenges, they encounter in the desire to access and secure justice through family mediation.

2.6. Qualitative Research Strategy

According to Wilson, in this strategy the emphasis is on the socially constructed nature of reality which is translated by the intimate relationship between what is being studied and the environmental factors surrounding the study.⁵⁶ This is applicable in this research as the family relationship is a sensitive one and the factors which influence the mediation process will need to be studied. Quantitative research strategy – focuses on the measurement and analysis of casual relationships between variables and not the process and is usually associated with numerical values.⁵⁷

In this study the qualitative research strategy is adopted to achieve the aims of this study. However, the use of surveys will be adopted as it is a mixed method research. The next step considered is the research design of the study. It provides the direction for the study. Bryman postulates that a research design is the framework which generates evidence to answer the

⁵⁵ Beverly Skeggs, *Feminist Ethnography* (Sage Publications London 2001) 429.

⁵⁶ Jonathan Wilson, *Essentials of Business Research*, (Sage Publications, 2014) 15.

⁵⁷Ibid.

research question of the researcher or investigator.⁵⁸ He suggests that the research design is the guideline for collection and analysis of the data for the research and the choice of the design signifies the importance of the dimensions the research processes will adopt. The chosen design will correspond with the criteria for evaluating social research. The chosen research design is **case study** as Nigerian women are the focus of this research. Qualitative research methods will be used in accordance with rules of conducting social research in examining the impact of family mediation on women's access to justice.

2.7 Data Collection

The process of implementing the methodology was the most challenging aspect of this research. The first challenge was the switch from face-to-face data collection to an online process and the necessary jurisprudence on the data for the research. This research uses survey and interviews as the methods for data collection in accordance with the qualitative methods of research. The questionnaire was distributed and responses of two hundred and twenty-six participants were analysed. The semi-structured interviews were conducted with seventeen participants.

After deciding on the theoretical aspects of the methodology, the practical aspects were next:

Target participants: The targets for the participants were the Nigerian women, especially women who had experienced family mediation previously or were currently undergoing family mediation. The aim was to reach out to women in every sphere of life, the educated, the uneducated, the women in the cities as well as those in the rural areas, whether they were married, single, divorced, or widowed. If they had encountered family disputes and experienced family mediation, their stories were important to this research.

⁵⁸ Alan Bryman, *Social Research Methods*, (5th edn Oxford University Press, 2016) 39.

How to procure the participants: The participants were procured in two stages:

The first stage consisted of two hundred and thirty-four people who responded to the survey, but two hundred and twenty-six participants actually took part and filled the survey, which was executed via Microsoft Forms.

The survey included

- A Participant Information Sheet informing the participant on what the research was about and who was conducting the survey including the authority of the academic environment.
- Participant Consent Form

The survey took about 10 minutes to complete.

- The target participants of the survey were originally females, but the researcher was pleasantly surprised to see some male participants in the column for gender of the participant, which introduced the perspective of men as it concerns women's rights and family mediation. This can be reflected upon while considering the sub-themes especially on the role of patriarchy in women's rights.

The second stage comprised of interviews, which was targeted at twenty participants, representing the four geographical zones of Nigeria.

2.8 Data Analysis Techniques

The analysis of qualitative data is challenging due to the interactive and complex nature of the data as well as the subjective nature of human knowledge.⁵⁹ Data analysis techniques have been described by Wilson⁶⁰ as methods which analyse the data collected. Bryman and Bell⁶¹ suggest there are five strategies of data analysis techniques which consist of the following: conversation analysis, discourse analysis, narrative analysis, analytic induction, and grounded theory.

This research focused on the narrative and descriptive analysis to analyse the data collected in understanding the impact of family mediation on women, especially Nigerian women. Narrative Analysis would reveal the data in a story form, tracing culture and history of the data collected. In analysing the data of this study, the use of themes revealed the findings and led to the recommendations of this research.

Themes play a vital role in establishing connections between various aspects of the research and providing a solid justification for the study itself. Ryan and Bernard postulate that the identification of a theme in qualitative research is one of the most fundamental tasks and go further to say it is the heart of qualitative data analysis.⁶² In fact, identifying and exploring themes is considered one of the fundamental tasks in qualitative research and serves as the core of qualitative data analysis. There are several techniques for identifying themes as stated by the different social scientists⁶³ which include analysis of repeated words, reading of larger

⁵⁹ Mark Saunders, Philip Lewis and Adrian Thornhill, *Research Methods for Business Students*, (4th edn, Financial Times/ Prentice Hall, 2007) 248.

⁶⁰ The Honeycomb Research Methodology.

⁶¹ Alan Bryman and Emma Bell, *Business Research Methods*, (2nd edn, Oxford University Press, 2007) 69.

⁶² Grey Ryan and Russell Bernard, 'Techniques in identifying themes in Qualitative Data' (2003) 15(1) *Field Methods* 86.

⁶³ Claudia Strauss, *What makes Tony run? Schemas as motive reconsideration; In Human motives and cultural models* (Cambridge University Press, 1992) 191-224.

blocks of texts and other techniques. D’Andrade is of the opinion that “*the simplest and most direct indication of schematic organization in naturalistic discourse is the repetition of associative linkages*”.⁶⁴ Consequently, words which occur frequently with participants are important in the scheme of events surrounding issues and led to the identification of themes and sub-themes in this study. The following themes were identified:

Informal Mediation as a process to justice

Accessing the formal system

Intimate Partner Violence/Domestic Abuse

Enforcement of Mediation Agreement

Government Policy intervention

In examining the above themes, sub-themes emerged which were interlinked with the themes and identified as: *impact of culture on family mediation, role of patriarchy in women’s access to justice, stigma/social control as a barrier to women’s access to justice and effect of religion on family mediation*. The themes and sub-themes will be discussed in the literature and analysed in the data analysis chapters.

2.9 Documentary Evidence

There was the need for the investigation of documentary evidence where it exists, on the impact of mediation on family disputes and how the women are affected by it. The search included Incident Reports at the FIDA legal Centre, which revealed as much as 3,806 matters for mediation over a three-year period.⁶⁵ The methodology also examined any existing literature from both primary and secondary sources such as legislation, caselaw, journals, government

⁶⁴ Roy D’Andrade, *The Development of Cognitive Anthropology* (Cambridge University Press, 1995) 294.

⁶⁵ International Federation of Women Lawyers (FIDA) Nigeria, Rivers State Branch, “Report of Stewardship” (July 2019- December 2021) 9.

gazette, books from libraries, reports from conferences and other sources of documentary evidence.

2.10 Case Study

At the beginning of this research the desire was to conduct this study with women in villages, as well as cities in the major areas in Nigeria. The researcher had looked forward to moving from one community to another community and talking to the women, interviewing, and understanding their perspectives on family mediation. The observation method of research was used to ascertain the veracity of the evidence of the participants during the interviews. Unfortunately, the intended method of data collection had to change due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Physical meetings would have been preferable as it would have led to a richer observation of participants' experiences.

2.11 Ethical Considerations

Before embarking on the collection of data, the need to comply with the requirements for field research was necessary hence an application was made to the Ethics Committee, containing the Participants Information Sheet and Consent Form including a sample of the questionnaire. The approval was given to conduct an online questionnaire and interviews. The chosen method of data collection is in line with the qualitative method of research process to which the emphasis is on the socially constructed nature of reality, which is translated by the intimate relationship between what is being studied and the environmental factors surrounding the study.⁶⁶ This is applicable to this research as the focus is women and family mediation.

2.12 Quality, Reliability and Validity

The choice of the FIDA legal centre as the source of data collection, ensured the quality of the data for the singular reason that all the women who come to the centre are women seeking help

⁶⁶ Jonathan Wilson, *Essentials of Business Research*, (Sage Publications 2014) 15.

and need to access the justice mediation offers and where it is inadequate, litigation is available. The FIDA legal centre ensured the cases were genuine and the confidentiality of the participants were preserved.

2.13 Wellbeing of Participants

There was an understanding reached with the Medical Women's Association, who allowed a medical officer to be on stand-by at the FIDA legal centre, if any of the participants needed to seek medical counselling. Family disputes are emotionally challenging for the parties and having medical personnel on hand provided for the wellbeing of the participants who took part in the interviews.

2.14 End of Interview Process

The process of interviewing the participants was an interesting and revealing experience for the researcher. She found herself caught in the dynamics of power shifting roles between “the researcher as a peer – for the middle-aged women who expected her to “understand” and the researcher- who is older, than the younger participant who was trying to justify her position to her. She found herself constantly reading the body language of each participant to make sure they were comfortable enough with her as the interviewer/researcher to be able to share their different experiences with her. To do this, she had to first introduce herself as a female lawyer conducting research on the impact of family mediation in Nigeria and how it affects women's rights to access justice, to reassure the participants they were not speaking with a stranger to the struggles of women, but with a legal practitioner who was just not in the same room with them. She also explained the reason for enlisting the FIDA⁶⁷ legal centre as a source of data collection was to examine the role of FIDA in women's access to justice. After the preliminaries of ensuring the participants consented to the interview, and informing them on

⁶⁷ Federación internacional de Abogadas (FIDA) – International Federation of Women Lawyers.

what the research is about, the researcher found the women were willing to volunteer more information on their experiences and how they felt mediation could be more effective in promoting women's rights. She found herself being drawn in by their stories and had to consciously stop herself from proffering legal /mediation advice on their situation and confine herself to the interview questions while letting the legal officers do their jobs regardless of the invisible expectation of the participants that taking part in the research would somehow make a difference immediately in their lives. One of participants expressed her happiness that a study like this was being done to help other women who were not aware that there are other avenues apart from litigation, to seek justice from an abusive relationship and a toxic situation. It was a good feeling to know that this research was already making a difference.

2.15 Limitations of Research

The COVID-19 pandemic restricted access to information on all levels. From the restriction of physically being unable to access information personally to participants being incapacitated health-wise and unable to take part in the interview process, including limiting the participants to those who could navigate the internet and were technology savvy.

Another major challenge was the topography of the geographical nature of Nigeria in accessing certain rural places such as the riverine areas of the south-south, which is currently being plagued with acts of militancy, kidnapping and unrest⁶⁸ (as at the time this data collection was being conducted). There is also the terrorism of the Boko Haram in northern Nigeria, the herdsmen attacking people and kidnapping women, including the kidnapping of school children and the unrest of IPOB in eastern Nigeria. The researcher was unable to travel to Nigeria and was informed that there was restriction of movement in most local government

⁶⁸ Vanda Felbarb-Brown, 'Vigilante Groups and Militias in Southern Nigeria- the greatest trick the devil played was convincing Nigerians he could protect them' [2021] published 3rd of September by the United Nations University as part of its hybrid peace project <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/world-africa-57860993> (Accessed 20 December 2021).

areas. Hence this resulted in the restriction of the participants for the interview being limited to women who had come to lodge complaints at the FIDA legal centres in the different states and were willing to participate in the research. This necessitated the use of micro-soft forms to administer an online survey and conduct the semi-structured interviews online via Teams.

Another challenge was the challenge of technological know-how for some of the participants. The survey which was first conducted was equally affected by the limitations of technology as only those who were internet literate could access the survey on Microsoft forms. This was not the initial choice on the sample of participants or the category of women, for this research. In conducting the online interviews, the researcher had to first be certain the participants understood the operations of online meetings and the fact that the interviews would be recorded. The use of certain software like Teams is not as popular as WhatsApp and other social media handles. For security and validity of data, Teams was used to record the interviews, and it was saved on the University protected system of One Drive, but some participants had never used Teams and had to go through the process of ensuring the software was correctly downloaded and the participants understood how to navigate the technology and were comfortable with the process. The interviews were conducted at the FIDA legal centre to ensure some of the participants who were using Teams for the first time, understood how to navigate the software to be able to participate in the interviews. Conducting the interviews at the FIDA Centre ensured the participants were genuine and data protection and privacy laws observed with regards to the confidentiality process of family mediation. Some challenges included issues such as network/data availability and had to be addressed, the technical know-how of the legal officer to co-ordinate the online process had to be verified. The environment had to be conducive to allow for quality recording of the interview and other logistics which had to be taken care of according to the issues of each state and venue.

2.16 Funding

In organising the scope of this study, the researcher was unsure as to the exact cost of the entire research. Not only for the academic literature but the logistics in procuring data for analysis. It was daunting for the researcher, in the middle of the study to realise the need to spend more than was bargained for to facilitate the logistics of ensuring there was sufficient wi-fi network data provided to be used in the legal centres which could not afford to provide for the duration of the short online interviews. The researcher also had to ensure there was fuel in the generators in the event there was power outage, which is a frequent problem in Nigeria. This was the challenge that accompanied the online process. The source of funds was personal funds as the researcher was unable to get funding to assist in this research.

2.17 Sampling

The sampling size for this research was in two categories. The first sampling size was not predictable because it was a survey that was released into the 36 states of the Federation via the FIDA platform and other online platforms. The guideline was the time frame in which the survey remained open which was from October 2020 to February 2021.

PROCESS

The responses from the survey were two hundred and thirty-four but only two hundred and twenty-six were viable. This sample was targeted at all of Nigeria but channelled through the online links. The survey responses were from the male and female gender including those who preferred not to say, though women are the focus of this research, this was to justify the themes which were coded during the interview. The result of the survey responses was an indication of the position of family mediation by the different age categories of the different gender. The sampling size for the interview was much smaller to allow consolidation on the themes which developed from the survey. The projected sampling size for the interview was 20-25

participants from the major geographical zones in Nigeria and the participants were only women, who are the focus of this research.

The reason the answer format of the survey, was chosen was to allow the participants provide more insights to their responses which provided the needed background to the answers. The use of Microsoft Form for the survey secured the data with the form being submitted automatically once the participant had concluded filling the form. In administering the survey online, there was no supervision or control over how the participants answered the questions. Once the link was shared, the participants read through the instructions, filled, and submitted the form which was immediately saved on the secured Microsoft database. The 32 branches of the International Federation of Women Lawyers Centres (FIDA), Nigeria was the major source for the data collection to represent the 36 states of the federation of Nigeria.

The following are the questions as contained in the survey:

1. Do you consent to participating in this research?
2. What age are you?
3. What is your sex?
4. What is your nationality/ethnicity?
5. What is your occupation?
6. What is your marital status?
7. What is your religion?
8. If married, which type of marriage are you in?
9. Have you attended mediation as a party to the proceedings?
10. Please provide the location of where the mediation took place.
11. Did a Mediation Information Assessment Meeting (MIAM) take place before the mediation?
12. Was there any Intimate Partner Violence (IPV) involved in your situation?

13. Did you inform the mediator of the IPV?
14. Would you please tell us why you informed the mediator?
15. Would you please tell us why you didn't inform the mediator?
16. Could you please explain your answer to question 15?
17. Would you please tell us why you didn't inform the mediator?
18. Could you please explain your answer to question 16?
19. How old were you when you got married (if applicable)?
20. Did your in-laws ever mediate in your family disputes?
21. Could you please explain your answer to question 20?
22. Could you please tell us about the nature of your case/mediation?
23. Could you please tell us about the outcome of your case/mediation?
24. How do you feel about the mediation process?
25. Were you satisfied with the outcome of your mediation?
26. Do you think family mediation as a form of dispute resolution helps women in family disputes?
27. Do you think the Government should engage in more policies that would promote family mediation and ensure the protection of the rights of women?
28. Do you think lawyers should have mediation training?
29. Could you please explain your answer to the above question?
30. Do you think Alternative Dispute Resolution, in particular mediation, should be taught in law degrees in Nigeria?
31. Could you please explain your answer to the above question?
32. Was it your choice to use mediation to resolve your family dispute?

. The responses and findings were analysed and discussed in the relevant chapters.

The survey led to questions which needed to be explored during the interviews, though with different participants as the online participants could not be invited for the interviews since they were anonymous.

Interview

It is expected that the location for conducting an unbiased interview must be in a neutral environment where the participants feel free and confident to volunteer their responses as highlighted by Taherdoost.⁶⁹ The choice of location for this second stage of data collection was the FIDA⁷⁰ legal centre, as earlier mentioned to ensure the participants were comfortable during the interview and in accordance with the ethics of conducting research as stated above. At this point in the research, it was clear a face-to-face data collection would not be possible, there was therefore a need to collect data from a source where the necessary IT skills would be accessible to the participants and ensure their privacy and confidentiality. The researcher decided upon semi-structured interviews to ensure the extraction of the necessary data required for this study by allowing the participants narrate a little of the nature of their dispute. This gives a background of understanding to the responses of the participants to the questions. The use of interviews allowed the researcher ask direct questions relevant to the themes which developed from the survey to verify the position of the themes in the lives of Nigerian women. The decision to adopt the qualitative research methods in procuring the necessary data is based on the affinity of feminism and insight this approach allows as mentioned by Bryman which was earlier highlighted in this chapter.⁷¹ The questions were simple and open but structured in

⁶⁹ Hamed Taherdoost, 'Data Collection Methods and Tools for Research; A Step-by-Step Guide to Choose Data Collection Technique for Academic and Business Research Projects' (2021) 10(1) *International Journal of Academic Research in Management* 34.

⁷⁰ Federación Internacional de Abogadas – International Federation of Women Lawyers.

⁷¹ Michael Salter and Julie Mason, *Writing Law Dissertations – An Introduction and Guide to the Conduct of Legal Research* (Pearson Education Limited England 2007)126.

a manner to ensure the answers of the participants were not too wide as to be farfetched and irrelevant to the research. The average time for each interview was ten to twelve minutes. The projection was for a total of twenty to twenty-five participants representing the four major geographical areas of Nigeria as mentioned earlier. The expectation was a minimum of five participants from each state. A total of seventeen participants were interviewed at the following FIDA legal centres in the states of Rivers - representing the south, Anambra – representing the east, and Lagos – representing the west. Unfortunately, there was no representation from the north as all avenues to procure women from northern Nigeria to take part in the interviews proved abortive. It is pertinent to state that all the participants of this interview were women who are the focus of this research unlike the survey where men also took part in the research. The analysis of the themes which emerged from the survey led to the framing of the questions of the interviews.

1. How old are you?
2. Are you married?
3. What kind of dispute brought you to the FIDA Legal Centre?
4. Was it easy for you to access the justice you wanted at the FIDA Centre?
5. Have you experienced informal mediation before? – Were you satisfied with the outcome?
6. Was there any challenge in enforcing the mediation agreement?
7. Do you think the government should do more to promote family mediation in Nigeria?

The interviews were conducted in English, which is the official language in Nigeria except where an interpreter was necessary, then one of the FIDA legal officers acted as an interpreter. The interviews were recorded on Teams and transcribed, checked for accuracy and

typographical errors. Transcriptions were coded using the NVivo format according to the themes generated during the study.

2.18 Conclusion

This chapter explained the methodology adopted in this study which is a combination of the legal, feminist, and social approaches of research to achieve the objectives of this study. The pragmatist approach being the chosen research philosophy, ensured the use of the best methods necessary to achieve the desired results based on the analysis reached from the data collected. The sociolegal approach chosen allowed the application of the social methods of research in identifying how the laws in existence function and examine how they affect the society. The process of data collection and analysis of the responses from the data collected from the survey and interviews would be discussed in the themes and sub-themes in Chapters Six and Seven.

In adopting the socio-legal approach, the study is focused on law-in-action as opposed to law-on-paper and how it affects the diverse groups of society, in this instance the focus is on the women in society. The feminist methodology is the thread that holds it all together because this research is about the emancipation of the rights of Nigerian women and their access to justice through family mediation including the enforcement of agreements reached during mediation. The need for the survey and interviews resides in the fact that the evidence and information sought cannot be found in documentary evidence or literature alone. The only avenue to procure the needed data on the research topic is to conduct a survey and interviews on the current position of the impact of family mediation on access to justice in the lives of present-day Nigerian women.

The above methodology was chosen to achieve the objectives of this study because it is important to understand how family mediation impacts women's access to justice, with the legal structures in existence, whether informal or formal. This has informed the

recommendations for reforms to be made by this research especially in the area of enforcement of mediation agreements.

CHAPTER THREE: UNDERSTANDING ACCESS TO JUSTICE AND LEGAL CONSCIOUSNESS

3.1 Introduction

The need to access justice occurs in every aspect of life where there is a perception of wrong or abuse, and it can begin from the home. The process of resolving a simple dispute in the family could determine whether relationships will improve or deteriorate for a lifetime. The resolution of family disputes usually begins from the home and eventually spills into the formal process of dispute resolution involving procedural matters, where the dispute cannot be resolved at the home front.

The formal legal system provides structure for the resolution of disputes and family disputes is no exception. As the focus of this study is Nigerian women, the consideration is women's rights in the resolution of family disputes. The impact of formal legal system in family dispute resolution, can be determined by the value ascribed to women's rights. The assessment of value attributed to rights of women in a country can be determined by the processes of access to justice. Access to justice can be interpreted from different perspectives which include but are not limited to the physical aspect which is that justice sought is easily accessible by those who seek it as it extends beyond legal representation in court.⁷²

Meene and Rooji⁷³ promote the view that access to justice is also interpreted from the perspective of the poor, as their legal consciousness of justice will be formed on the basis of how they are treated by the law. This research considers justice from the perspective of women who seek it. Chopra and Isser are of the view that there are two primary approaches to access

⁷² Olaitan Olusegun and Olatunji Oyelade, 'Access to Justice for Nigerian Women: A veritable tool to achieving sustainable development' (2022) 22(1) *International Journal of Discrimination and the Law* 4 at 5.

⁷³ Ineke Van de Meene and Benjamin Van Rooji, *Access to Justice and Legal Empowerment: Making the Poor Central in Legal Development Co-operation* (Leiden University Press 2008) 6.

justice by women.⁷⁴ The first approach is on the theory that the informal institutions are too weak to provide justice and address the challenges of women which formal institutions can provide.⁷⁵ Another author Fapohunda is also of the opinion that the informal institutions though legal are unorganised and unregulated to be effective in addressing the challenges women face.⁷⁶ The second approach talks about reconciling informal institutions with international standards of justice while retaining accessibility, familiarity, and effectiveness.⁷⁷ This aspect will be considered in the data analysis chapters during the interviews with participants. This also means considering if the geographical location of the place of justice, is accessible to those who seek it. The second aspect to be considered is the aspect of the procedure.

This study examines the issues which affect the procedure, whether it is simple and clearly understood by the party seeking justice. If the procedure for justice is complicated, and the party seeking justice finds it difficult to understand the process, can it be concluded that the party was satisfied in seeking access to the justice sought?

The perspective of the person accessing justice can be influenced by several factors which vary from their gender to social and cultural orientation as stated by Ojelabi et al.⁷⁸ Ojelabi et al explained that what could be interpreted as justice by a society based on cultural and patriarchal beliefs, might be interpreted differently by other society such as the tradition of divorced

⁷⁴ Tanja Chopra and Deborah Isser, 'Women's Access to Justice, Legal Pluralism and Fragile States' [2011] https://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/74991461/Womens_Access_to_Justice_Legal_Pluralis20211121-28,24, (Accessed 06/08/2023).

⁷⁵ Ibid.

⁷⁶ Tinuke Fapohunda, 'Women and the Informal Sector in Nigeria: Implications for Development' (2012) 4(1) *British Journal of Arts and Social Sciences* 35 at 38.

⁷⁷ Tanja Chopra and Deborah Isser, "Women's Access to Justice, Legal Pluralism and Fragile States" [2011] https://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/74991461/Womens_Access_to_Justice_Legal_Pluralis20211121-28,24, (Accessed 06/08/2023).

⁷⁸ Lola Ojelabi, Thomas Fisher and Helen Cleak, 'A Cultural Assessment of Family Dispute Resolution: Findings about cultural appropriateness from the evaluation of a family relationship centre' (2012) 18(1) *Journal of Family Studies* 76 at 83.

women who seek justice in court being isolated from the community and home.⁷⁹ It is necessary to examine the similarities and differences where they exist for Nigerian women when contrasted with a global perspective of women's access to justice. Women all over the world, experience challenges in accessing justice, either from the home or from society as expressed by Olusegun and Oyelade, such as where a woman is discouraged from seeking justice from an abusive spouse by members of the family on the grounds that she will bring dishonour to the family.⁸⁰

This chapter begins with a definition of justice and a discussion of access to justice. It further examines the different legal theories and extant literature surrounding access to justice universally and in Nigeria in particular. In discussing access to justice, it is necessary to understand the legal consciousness which informs the behaviour of society to the procedures of the systems of justice. The legal consciousness of the people reveals the effect of the law on the society as their actions are determined by their consciousness. This chapter is divided into sections which highlight the different parts of this chapter. The opinions of writers such as Dave Cowan, Susan Silbey, and others, on legal consciousness will be discussed in this chapter. This is to allow a basis for comparison if any, with the concept of legal consciousness in Nigeria. Access to justice under the Nigerian legal system will be discussed in this chapter and a brief look at the hierarchy of Nigerian courts to provide an idea of what the formal court system represents.

⁷⁹ Lola Ojelabi, Thomas Fisher and Helen Cleak, 'A Cultural Assessment of Family Dispute Resolution: Findings about cultural appropriateness from the evaluation of a family relationship centre' (2012) 18(1) *Journal of Family Studies* 83.

⁸⁰ Olaitan Olusegun and Olatunji Oyelade, 'Access to Justice for Nigerian women: A veritable tool to achieving sustainable development' (2022) 22(1) *International Journal of Discrimination and the Law* 20.

3.2 Definition of Justice

What is justice? Justice originates from the Latin word “jus” which means right or law.⁸¹ Justice is difficult to define as justice has different meanings for different people. Aristotle in his writings, divides justice into two forms- distributive and corrective.⁸² He defines justice as the treatment of equals equally and un-equals, unequally because he believes justice should be proportional to the individual seeking it. What might be interpreted as justice to a rich man might be interpreted differently by a poor man. Other writers such as Chaim Perelman postulates that a person will define justice as that which puts him in the right and his opponent in the wrong.⁸³

To further illustrate the concept that justice is not restricted to obedience of the law, Gautam Buddha justifies justice as the disobedience to an evil law.⁸⁴ Justice provides the opportunity to exercise rights. Justice has been defined as the process through which institutions and laws resolve disputes and provide remedies for different forms of abuse and exploitation.⁸⁵ Justice is therefore a means to an end. Justice is the opportunity to exercise rights. The principles of justice are the same in any part of the world and they are rooted in equity, fairness, and impartiality.⁸⁶

⁸¹ Komal Parnami, ‘Concept of Justice, Difficulties in Defining Justice’ (2019) 2(5) International Journal of Law Management and Humanities 1.

⁸² David Johnston, *A Brief History of Justice*, (John Wiley & Sons Ltd 2011) 63.

⁸³ Komal Parnami, ‘Concept of Justice, Difficulties in Defining Justice’ (2019) 2(5) International Journal of Law Management and Humanities 1.

⁸⁴ John Rawls, *A Theory of Justice* (Harvard University Press 1971) 624.

⁸⁵ Olaitan Olusegun and Olatunji Oyelade, ‘Access to Justice for Nigerian Women: A Veritable Tool to Achieving Sustainable Development’ (2022) 22(1) International Journal of Discrimination and the Law 5.

⁸⁶ United Nations, Security Council, Report of the Secretary-General, ‘The Rule of Law and Transitional Justice in Conflict and Post-Conflict Societies (para. 7, 23 August 2004, S/2004/616)

<https://interactive.unwomen.org/multimedia/infographic/changingworldofwork/en/index.html> (Accessed 27 April 2023).

In discussing justice, it is necessary to consider procedural and substantive justice as it relates to this study.

3.3 Procedural and Substantive Justice

Access to justice, defined as the ability of people to seek and obtain a remedy through formal or informal institutions of justice, and in conformity with human rights standards, requires the standardization of processes and procedures that will guarantee just and fair outcomes for all parties in a dispute. Understanding the principles of procedural and substantive justice is necessary for providing further context for this thesis. This is because in situations where the formal justice system is structurally weak, and the informal system impaired by issues including but not limited to religious and cultural beliefs, the processes and outcomes are most likely to be challenging to women.

Underlying the principle of procedural justice is the idea that a just and fair process is a prerequisite for a decision to be automatically accepted as just. It is about the fairness and the transparency of the processes by which decisions are made.⁸⁷ A crucial advocate of procedural justice is Ronald Dworkin who claimed that persons who are mistakenly denied their legal rights suffer injustice or ‘moral harm’, and that procedural justice comprises the use of procedures that guard against such forms of injustice.⁸⁸ Dworkin opined further that there is no moral harm other than the harm of a mistaken decision and that the only reason to insist on a procedure such as a hearing, is if it guards against legal error. In the view of Posner, legal

⁸⁷ Solum Lawrence, ‘Procedural Justice’ [2005] University of San Diego Law and Economics Research Paper Series, 12.

⁸⁸ Ronald Dworkin, *A Matter of Principle* (Harvard University Press 1985).

errors, due to inappropriate procedures, make it more problematic to achieve the objectives of substantive law. This, according to Posner, is a social cost and not a moral cost.⁸⁹

Another key advocate of procedural justice is John Rawls who expounded that procedural justice in criminal trials encompasses the use of procedures that result in the accurate outcomes most of the time, and due process is a procedure rationally planned to ascertain the truth. Rawls debated three notions of procedural justice to include: (1) *Perfect procedural justice* which has two features: (a) an independent criterion for what constitutes a fair or just outcome of the procedure, and (b) a procedure that guarantees that a fair result will be achieved; (2) *Imperfect procedural justice* which shares the first characteristic of the perfect procedural justice, but with no method that guarantees fair outcome; and (3) *Pure procedural justice* that describes conditions in which there is no principle for what constitutes a fair outcome other than the procedure itself.⁹⁰

Procedural justice has also been explained from the perspective of respect and dignity of individuals. Jeremy Waldron argued that upholding certain procedures have an essential value that is independent in reaching legally correct outcomes. He argued that the independent 'process value' is the value of respect for the dignity, and that procedural justice requires respect for individuals. This perspective rests on the belief that denying defendants their rights to fair hearing would fail to respect their rational agency, and be unjust in itself, even when their guilt is certain, and an accurate verdict can be reached without their participation.⁹¹

⁸⁹ Richard Posner, 'An economic approach to legal procedure and judicial administration' (1973) 2(2) *Journal of Legal Studies* 399.

⁹⁰ John Rawls, *A Theory of Justice* (Oxford University Press 1999) 14.

⁹¹ Jeremy Waldron, *The Rule of Law, and the Importance of Procedure* (JE Fleming (ed.), Getting to the rule of law, New York University Press, 2011) 9.

It is thus suggested that processes matter to people, and that the understanding of having been treated fairly can be as vital as the favourability of the outcome, and that is whether the outcome leads to personal gain, and fairness.⁹² This proposition implies it is not that individuals are happy to lose, but they are more probably ready to accept such loss if they feel they were treated fairly.⁹³ Thus, the four factors that are crucial to people's assessment of procedural fairness are respect, trustworthiness, neutrality, and voice.⁹⁴

Respect denotes to people that they have been treated with respect and dignity in their communications with the authorities and in the background of decision-making processes. Trustworthiness refers to people's assessments of whether or not the authorities can be trusted to act fairly towards them. Neutrality signifies to people's assessments of whether the authorities are impartial in their dealings with them, rather than biased against them for personal reasons or on the basis of group characteristics, such as gender, race, ethnicity, or religion. Voice describes people's observations that the authorities have offered them with opportunities to participate in the decision-making process and to voice their views.

Generally, if individuals feel they have been treated with respect, if they observe trustworthiness and neutrality, and if they are given the opportunities to partake in the decision-making process, they are more likely to judge the process as being fair. Contrary, individuals are likely to have a sense of injustice if the process fails to satisfy these criteria, even if they accept the flaws in their treatment made no material difference to the outcome.

Procedural justice is also seen as a strategy to promote legal compliance and this is informed by the notion that people who consider the authorities have a right to be obeyed are more likely to obey the law than individuals who are inspired by self-interest, and the experience of

⁹² Steven Blader and Tom Tyler, 'A Four-Component Model of Procedural Justice: Defining the Meaning of a "Fair" Process' (2003) 29(6) *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin* 747.

⁹³ *ibid.*

⁹⁴ *ibid.*

procedural justice is a potent aspect in stimulating the normative judgement that authorities have such a right. It is hence posited that the cheapest and most effective way to secure obedience to the law is for administrators to use power in a way which is acceptable to the procedural expectations of people.⁹⁵

The advocates of substantive justice argue that the allocation or distribution of social advantages among various sections of the society itself should be just. They demand that the opportunities of self-development should be progressively extended to the underprivileged in the society.

Substantive justice requires that there is the need to be sensitive to the facts and context of the individual case, taking it as socially and culturally situated rather than as potentially reducible to some legally recognizable norm.⁹⁶ Every case will consequently be different from any other and to that extent not subject to extrapolation since there can be no universal rules to make them is to deny case-sensitivity.⁹⁷

Thus, the result of separate cases will be mostly unanticipated, and must be contingent on the individual judgment of the judge. It is then in dire threat of arbitrariness, unpredictability, and abuse of the power relations which characterizes social reality if it is unconstrained by rules. Substantive justice, like democracy, may hence be an unrealizable ideal forever trapped between imperfect practice and conceptual purity.⁹⁸

3.3.1 Implications for this research

Women are not a homogeneous group and are mostly hindered by social norms and cultural beliefs, the relevance of procedural justice will largely depend on the context in which it is

⁹⁵ Therese MacDermott and Denise Meyerson, 'Australian Tribunals and Alternative Dispute Resolution: A Procedural Justice Perspective' (2018) 37(4) *Civil Justice Quarterly* 443 at 462.

⁹⁶ Geoffrey Leane, 'Testing Some Theories about Law: Can We Find Substantive Justice within Law's Rules?' (1994) 19 *Melbourne University Law Review* 924.

⁹⁷ *Ibid.*

⁹⁸ *Ibid.*

being applied. Several personal characteristics and situational circumstances combine to deepen women's exclusion and marginalization. The discrimination of women based on sex and gender is linked with other factors such as race, ethnicity, religion or belief, health, status, age, class, caste and sexual orientation and gender identity. Situations where culture forbids women from expressing their views when family disputes are being heard, connotes an informal dispute resolution mechanism that is procedurally flawed due to cultural belief. This confirms the legal realist theory that emphasizes the import of social context in the justice delivery system. To ascertain whether justice is served in informal or formal family mediation, as it affects women's rights would depend on the procedure adopted in the resolution of family disputes.

It is therefore important that women have access to justice to ensure they are not deprived of their rights. Ban Ki Moon in a speech at the UN World Women's Progress Conference in 2011 stated:

“Justice is central to the effort to help women become equal partners in decision-making and development. Without justice, women are disenfranchised, disempowered, and denied their rightful place. But with sound legal and justice systems, women can flourish and contribute to the advancement of society as a whole, including by helping to improve those very same systems for future generations – daughters and sons alike”.⁹⁹

This leads us to the concept of access to justice.

3.4 Access to Justice

The concept of access to justice was traced to Mauro Cappelletti, an Italian jurist who defined it as the most basic human right of a system which suggests a guarantee to legal rights.¹⁰⁰ The

⁹⁹ Ban Ki-Moon, 8th Secretary General of the United Nations at the UN Women, “Progress of the World's Women 2011-2012 in Pursuit of Justice” [2011] <http://www.unwomen.org/./media/headquarters/attachments/sections/library/publications/2011/progressoftheworldswomen-2011, 2> (Accessed 04 April 2023).

¹⁰⁰ Oluyemisi Bamgose, ‘Access to Justice through Clinical Legal Education: A Way Forward for Good Governance and Development’ (2015) 15(2) African Human Rights Law Journal 378 at 380.

United Nations in its development programme, also defines access to justice as “the ability of people to seek and obtain a remedy through formal or informal institutions of justice, and in conformity with human rights standards”.¹⁰¹ By this definition access to justice consequently includes ensuring the structure and environment for justice is enabled. The United Nations in identifying thematic areas of access to justice and rule of law, emphasised on the right to equal justice for all, including members of vulnerable groups to which women belong.¹⁰² As will be explained in this study women have been identified to belonging to the vulnerable group by the UN and consequently entitled to rights to equal justice. Based on the definition of access to justice by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP),¹⁰³ the report by the IANGWE members of the Non-Conflict Settings defined women’s access to justice as:

“Access by women, in particular from poor and disadvantaged groups, to fair, effective, affordable and accountable mechanisms, for the protection of rights, control of abuse of power and resolution of conflicts. This includes the ability of women to seek and obtain a fair and just remedy through formal and informal justice systems and the ability to influence and participate in law-making process and institutions”.¹⁰⁴

This definition is the basis for this research, as this study will examine Nigerian women’s access to justice through family mediation. The aspects of family mediation this study will focus on are the informal and formal mediation processes. All women should have the choice

¹⁰¹ United Nations, “Mapping of Women’s Access to Justice of Select IANGWE Members in Non-Conflict Settings” (2018): **A Practitioner's Toolkit on Women's Access to Justice** <https://www.unwomen.org › Publications › 2018>, 17 (Accessed 04 October 2023).

¹⁰² Charli Carpenter, ‘Women, Children and other Vulnerable Groups: Gender, Strategic Frames and the protection of Civilians as a Transnational Issue’ (2005) 49 *International Studies Quarterly* 296.

¹⁰³ United Nations Development Programme.

¹⁰⁴ United Nations, “Mapping of Women’s Access to Justice of Select IANGWE Members in Non-Conflict Settings” (2018) : **A Practitioner's Toolkit on Women's Access to Justice** <https://www.unwomen.org › Publications › 2018>, 17 (Accessed 04 October 2023).

of access to justice irrespective of where they live or where they come from. The denial of access to justice for women is to hinder the enjoyment of their human rights.

3.4.1 Attaining Access to Justice

The aim of justice is defeated if it is not accessible as the purpose of justice is to resolve the conflicts between rival principles.¹⁰⁵ Access to justice proceeds beyond legal representation in court. Cannon is of the view that it is desirable to have a diverse system of access to justice to facilitate dispute resolution.¹⁰⁶ General opinion is that access to court, is access to justice but the introduction of alternative dispute resolution processes indicates otherwise. Access to justice is not always by the courts as indicated by the ADR¹⁰⁷ methods. The presumption is that to access justice, there should be opportunity to access the court.¹⁰⁸ This research seeks to explore the veracity of this theory.

One of the questions this research seeks to answer is the reason for lack of enforcement of mediation agreement and how this affects women's access to justice. Could it be connected to the fact that as mediation is a voluntary process and lacks the compulsion which accompanies court processes, as parties do not feel the need to comply with the agreement? The data analysis seeks to answer this question.

3.4.2 Barriers to Access to Justice

Access to justice is a fundamental universal right as established earlier but there are existing barriers which emerge to challenge these universal rights. The challenges are in different forms and emerge from different areas of society. The barriers to access justice which women encounter, are not peculiar to Nigerian women alone. Women encounter barriers globally as

¹⁰⁵ Martijn Boot, 'The Aim of a Theory of Justice' (2012) 15 *Journal of Ethnic Theory Moral Practice* 7 at 20.

¹⁰⁶ Andrew J. Canon, *Access to Justice* [2009]
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/264424194_Access_to_Justice (Accessed 08 April 2023).

¹⁰⁷ ADR-Alternative Dispute Resolution.

¹⁰⁸ Bryan Garner, *Blacks Law Dictionary* (7th edn, 1999) 13.

indicated in the research by Uygur and Skinnider¹⁰⁹ which was funded by the Council of Europe, to reveal some of the barriers women encounter in seeking access to justice. They can be categorised into the following:

Bias of professionals, justice delivery personnel and gender stereotyping by legal service providers- Legal service providers who are expected to attend to all issues brought to them, sometimes bring in their personal bias of a situation into their official duties as was disclosed in a 2018 UNDP¹¹⁰ report. The report stated that women who had been victims of abuse and had reported to the authorities, had been accused of lying and being the cause of their misfortunes, which discouraged the women from proceeding with their complaints.

Language and Linguistic barrier- Women have experienced language as a barrier in accessing justice when they do not understand formal language and need the help of an interpreter or someone to explain the procedure of formal system of justice. In 2022, the European Commission had acknowledged the challenges migrant refugee women encounter in accessing legal aid due to language barrier.¹¹¹

Other general factors which impact as barriers in women's access to justice are grouped into the following categories by Uygur and Skinnider:-

¹⁰⁹ Gülriz Uygur and Eileen Skinnider, "Understanding Barriers to Women's Access to Justice and Legal Aid in Türkiye" (Directorate General of Democracy and Human Dignity, Gender Equality Division, Council of Europe, 2022) 59
<https://dspace.ceid.org.tr/xmlui/bitstream/handle/1/2130/Understanding%20Barriers%20to%20Women%27s%20Access%20to%20Justice%20and%20Legal%20Aid%20in%20T%C3%BCrkiye.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y> (Accessed 13 August 2023).

¹¹⁰ Ibid.

¹¹¹ Gülriz Uygur and Eileen Skinnider, "Understanding Barriers to Women's Access to Justice and Legal Aid in Türkiye" (Directorate General of Democracy and Human Dignity, Gender Equality Division, Council of Europe 2022) 55
<https://dspace.ceid.org.tr/xmlui/bitstream/handle/1/2130/Understanding%20Barriers%20to%20Women%27s%20Access%20to%20Justice%20and%20Legal%20Aid%20in%20T%C3%BCrkiye.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y> (Accessed 13 August 2023).

Geographical factors - This is a major factor which hinders women's access to justice especially those in rural and remote areas. Women in the rural areas are restricted to the justice available to them, whether it is the informal mediation of the family or by the council of elders. If there is presence of the judiciary, the Customary, Magistrate or High Courts are usually not located in remote areas. In the areas where there is no presence of formal law enforcement, the women are at a disadvantage as to achieving substantive justice. They make do with what is available or proceed to the nearest town which could be some distance.

Economic factors - These have to do with when a woman is financially disadvantaged or poor and lacks the finances to access the justice she deserves. All over the world, poverty is a major barrier to women and hinders the enjoyment of her rights. If there is no money to pay legal fees to seek counsel from a lawyer, a woman would not be able to take decisions to enforce her rights when she needs legal counsel. For the average woman she needs to be able to transport herself to where she can access justice. This financial barrier is a limit to access to justice.¹¹²

Cultural factors - Culture, especially in most African and Asian countries plays a major role in the lives of women. Some cultures have been stated to be discriminatory to women and affect their ability to seek redress when their rights have been violated.¹¹³ Women are conditioned by their culture and in accessing justice, would rarely proceed with a different way of resolving disputes in the family than the "norm". Women are restricted by culture by the fear of sanctions that can be placed on the women for violating cultural practices. For example, a woman can be sanctioned for sleeping outside her matrimonial home without her husband's consent, even though she was in the hospital or prevented from pursuing her rights if contrary to the wishes of her husband.¹¹⁴ In Somalia, it is against the local norm for a woman to seek justice in court

¹¹² Ibid.

¹¹³ Sahar Maranlau, *Access to Justice in Iran: Women, Perceptions and Reality* (Cambridge University Press 2015) 9.

¹¹⁴ Interview with Participant 2, Lagos State FIDA Legal Centre held on 17/02/2022 at 10:17am.

unless she is represented by her husband or a male family member.¹¹⁵ Women's access to justice is hindered by culture where fairness, equity, and good conscience is not observed, such culture would be repugnant.

Religious factors - Women's access to justice is limited by religious factors by ways of obligation to faith. As a mediator, sometimes women narrated to the researcher the reason they failed to report issues of domestic violence in their homes to the police was because the church was handling the matter. In the Muslim religion it was not so different. The advice of the Imam carries more significance than the letters of the law. This restricts access to justice for women as most religious leaders do not advise women to proceed with law enforcement measures in family disputes but seek alternative measures by following the instructions of their faith.¹¹⁶

Educational factors - Lack of education is a barrier to access to justice for women. Where women are not literate, it is difficult to know different avenues of seeking justice. If she cannot read, she would not have access to information on the internet, newspapers, journals, fliers, or books. We see the power of education in most areas where there is prevalence of early marriages of young girls who do not have the choice in deciding when to get married. Child-brides are a common barrier to access justice in some communities in Africa and in some religions as postulated by authors such as Nnadi.¹¹⁷ Most often when a young girl is given out in marriage, her education comes to an end thus limiting her decision-making powers for herself. A good illustration of how educational factors can limit access to justice of women is

¹¹⁵ Tanja Chopra and Deborah Isser, "Women's Access to Justice, Legal Pluralism and Fragile States" [2011] 28, https://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/74991461/Womens_Access_to_Justice_Legal_Pluralis20211121-28 (Accessed 06 August 2023).

¹¹⁶ Olufadi Malik and Farah Muda, 'The Concept of Reconciliation (Sulh) in Islamic Family Law and Matrimonial Dispute Settlement Practice in Nigeria' (2015) 3(1) Peak Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities 2.

¹¹⁷ Ine Nnadi, 'Early Marriage: A Gender Based Violence and a Violation of Women's Human Rights in Nigeria' (2014) 7(3) Journal of Politics and Law 35 at 39.

the Boko haram situation in Nigeria where terrorists in the north have said no to western education. The activities of the terrorists have caused students and teachers to stay away from the learning environment as schools have been shut down.¹¹⁸ When the young girls are uneducated, they lack the knowledge to access information which will be beneficial to them as they grow into womanhood and make decisions especially in their family life in accessing justice. Odinkalu stated that when women are not educated, they fail to recognise when their rights have been violated and the process of righting the wrong done to them.¹¹⁹

Administrative factors - Another barrier to access to justice is procedural and administrative bottlenecks. The processes of formal justice can be daunting and discouraging especially after a long dispute resolution process. In ADR processes like Arbitration where enforcement of the judgment award is subject to court procedure, this could be discouraging to women who might want to avoid the rigours of litigation. Administrative factors which could hinder access to justice would also include unnecessary demands by unscrupulous officials of the court in the enforcement of agreements from mediation proceedings or judgment awards. There have been allegations of women who go to lodge complaints at police stations being asked to pay fees for typing up the complaint or to provide money for paper or pay for transportation of the bailiff to serve processes.¹²⁰ This could hinder women's access to justice.

The above-mentioned barriers are discussed in greater detail as it relates to Nigerian women during the data analysis.

¹¹⁸ 276 Chibok School girls kidnapping in Borno State of Nigeria on 14/15 night of April 2014. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/world-africa-62324294> (Accessed 28 August 2023).

¹¹⁹ Chidi Odinkalu, "The Impact of Economic and Social Rights in Nigeria: an assessment of the legal framework for implementing education and health as human rights" (in Gauri Vand Brinks D (eds) *Courting Social Justice: Judicial Enforcement of Social and Economic Rights in the Developing World*, New York, Cambridge University Press, 2008) 183.

¹²⁰ Nlerum Okogbule, 'Access to justice and human rights protection in Nigeria: problems and prospects' (2005) 2(3) Sur. Rev. Int. Direitos Human 102.

3.5 Overcoming the Barriers

It is the objective of this research to examine the existing literature and collect data from participants on how women overcome barriers to accessing justice, especially in Nigeria. Olusegun and Oyelade¹²¹ have recommended the following as some of the measures women may embark on in overcoming the barriers which hinder their access to justice.

Availability of Dispute Resolution Centres

Various ways in which the above-mentioned barriers to access to justice can be addressed include ensuring there are dispute resolution centres in every locality. These centres should also consist of police stations within a community that is easily accessible.

Public Enlightenment Programmes

Some of the challenges can be addressed by engaging and creating programmes that will economically empower women and afford financial power to access justice. The government can establish free access to justice related services for women which will educate and inform women.

Compliance with Legal Framework

Governments, especially those that are signatories to international conventions, must ensure compliance with non-discriminatory laws such as the provisions of *Article 2* of *CEDAW*.¹²² This provision undertakes to eliminate all forms of discrimination against women. The government should ensure it complies with the legal framework and enforces the provisions of the law.¹²³

¹²¹ Olaitan Olusegun and Olatunji Oyelade, 'Access to Justice for Nigerian Women: A Veritable tool to Achieving Sustainable Development' (2022) 22 (1) International Journal of Discrimination and the Law 21.

¹²² CEDAW- Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women <https://www.un.org/womenwatch/daw/cedaw/history> (Accessed 3/10/2021).

¹²³ Olaitan Olusegun and Olatunji Oyelade, "Access to Justice for Nigerian Women: A Veritable tool to Achieving Sustainable Development' (2022) 22(1) International Journal of Discrimination and the Law 21.

Improved Administrative Procedure

Most of the women are discouraged by the administrative bottlenecks they must encounter to access justice. If the process is less cumbersome for the women, they would be encouraged to lodge complaints of abuse when they occur. This could be argued to be discriminatory but where the system refuses a woman to take a person on bail or lodge a complaint, unless she is accompanied by a man, is discriminatory.

Judicial Reforms

Cases and complaints brought by women to court must be treated fairly and impartially. Where there is need for judicial review on cases or policies in the judicial system, they should be done, without exerting hardship on the women. Article 11 of the UNCAC¹²⁴ provides *that the judiciary must itself be free of corruption to fight corruption*. Some of the women complain about corrupt officials in the judiciary which hinder their access to justice especially in administrative matters.¹²⁵

Overcoming these barriers to access to justice will be discussed as they affect women's access to justice in subsequent chapters of this research.

3.6 Effect of Lack of Access to Justice

The impact of lack of access to justice for women is far reaching. If women are denied access to the justice they seek, it will be an infringement of their rights as well as affect their mental well-being as lack of justice in a family setting impacts on relationships with family members sometimes involving children. Also, the financial impact of lack of justice following familial breakup can be devastating for women and children. Lack of access to legal assistance when a woman needs it, can lead to complications in other areas of her life. In legal practice, the

¹²⁴ UNAC-United Nations Convention Against Corruption.

¹²⁵ Evidence of participants during the interviews.

researcher recalls listening to stories of women who wanted to move to another town with their children, and sometimes lose their jobs in the bid to avoid abusive marriages.

3.7 Nigeria and the Nigerian Legal System

The aim of this research will not be achieved if the diversity and nature of the Nigerian legal system is not explained in its richness. Nigeria is a multi-cultural nation and vast in its ethnicities. The country is divided into four major geographical territories- north, south, east and west. This chapter will give a history of the entity called Nigeria, explaining the foundation of its legal system. An understanding of the structure of the courts is necessary in the reality of the laws and the intention of creating those laws.

A critique on the Nigerian legal system and the feminist perspective would enhance our understanding on the role of the Nigerian Constitution on the rights of the woman.

3.7.1 Demographics of Nigeria

The country Nigeria came into existence in 1914 and was coined from the Niger River which flowed through the country by Flora Shaw who was married to Baron Frederick Lugard who was the British colonial administrator before independence in 1960.¹²⁶ Nigeria is the most populous country in West Africa with a population of about 210 million people¹²⁷ with a complicated history of the colonial era of different administrative structures and the post-independence history which led to its federal character and ushered in the military and civilian administration.¹²⁸ She is a nation with over 250 ethnic groups speaking 500 different languages,

¹²⁶History of Nigeria <https://web.archive.org/web/20190530151151/http://www.nigeria.gov.ng/index.php/2016-04-06-08-38-30/> (Accessed 5 January 2022).

¹²⁷ Simona Varella, *Demographics of Nigeria – Statistics & Facts* (September 28th 2021) <https://www.statista.com/topics/6477/demographics-of-nigeria> (Accessed 3/11/2021).

¹²⁸ Roger Blench and others, “The role of Traditional Rulers in Conflict Prevention and Mediation in Nigeria: Final Report” (DFID, Nigeria 2006) 11.

with varying cultures and traditions.¹²⁹ Women are said to be 101,669,950 of the entire population of Nigeria as of 2020.¹³⁰

The major ethnic tribes are Hausa, Fulani, Yoruba and Igbo and are ruled by their respective Chiefs, Oba's and Kings.¹³¹

3.7.2 Traditional Structure

Before the emergence of Nigeria as a nation in 1914, the northern and southern protectorates existed as independent entities with separate culture and ways of life.¹³²

Northern Nigeria – The northern part of Nigeria consists of the Hausa and Fulani ethnic tribes and are ruled by the emirs and Imams (who are the religious leaders). Muslims constitute majority of the northern population in Nigeria.¹³³ Islam is said to have come into Nigeria through the activities of the Arab merchants who came to trade in the Kanem Borno Empire.¹³⁴ Other parts of the north which encountered Islam also practiced traditional idol worship which led to the Sokoto jihad in a bid to purify Islam¹³⁵. After the jihad, most of the north embraced sharia law. Parts of the north also practiced Christianity which was introduced by the British missionaries.¹³⁶ Before the advent of the British, the societies were administered by emirs and

¹²⁹ <https://www.ethnologue.com/country/NG> (Accessed 8 November 2021).

¹³⁰ <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.POP.TOTL.FE.IN?locations=NG> (Accessed 5 January 2022).

¹³¹ Toyin Falola, *Culture and Customs of Nigeria* (Greenwood Press, 2001) 6.

¹³² Alhaji Umar Alkali, and Others 'Nature and Sources of Nigerian Legal System: An Exorcism of a Wrong Notion' (2014) 5(4) *International Journal of Business Economics and Law* 1.

¹³³ Mohammed Abdulkadir, 'Islam in the Non-Muslim areas of Northern Nigeria, C.1600-1960' (2011) 1(1) *Ilorin Journal of Religious Studies* 2.

¹³⁴ Alhaji Umar Alkali, and Others "Nature and Sources of Nigerian Legal System: An Exorcism of a Wrong Notion" (2014) 5(4) *International Journal of Business Economics and Law* 2.

¹³⁵ *Ibid.*

¹³⁶ *Ibid.*

chiefs who were assisted by their deputies and there were also some chief-less societies that were administered by rigid political systems.¹³⁷

Western Nigeria – The Yoruba ethnic group mainly occupy western Nigeria but can also be found in the southwest of Nigeria. The system of leadership is patriarchal, and the head of the society is the Oba who is the king and rules with the assistance of the chiefs who are his deputies.¹³⁸ Traditions and customs that are practised though Islam came to Yorubaland through Ilorin via the Islamic scholars in 1830, the practice of traditional idols such as the *Osun* deity is still observed alongside Christianity in certain parts.¹³⁹

Eastern Nigeria – The eastern part of Nigeria is dominated by the Igbos and their administration of leadership is by the council of elders led by the Igwe.¹⁴⁰ Christianity was introduced through the missionaries and is the dominant religion though the traditional ways of idol worship like the celebration of the gods during the new yam festivals is practiced till date.

Southern Nigeria – The coastal areas which represent the Niger-Delta of present-day Nigeria was formerly the southern Nigeria protectorate which was created in 1900 after the withdrawal of the charter of the Royal Niger Company in 1899 and in 1914 the southern and northern protectorates were joined.¹⁴¹ The people of the south are mostly Christians and diverse in culture but similar to eastern Nigeria in mode of leadership where a chief or king rules with the help of deputies.

¹³⁷ Niki Tobi, *Sources of Nigerian Law* (M.J. Professional Publishers Ltd 1996) 1-2.

¹³⁸ Ibid.

¹³⁹ Alhaji Umar Alkali, and others “Nature and Sources of Nigerian Legal System: An Exorcism of a Wrong Notion” (2014) 5(4) *International Journal of Business Economics and Law* 2.

¹⁴⁰ Ibid.

¹⁴¹ <https://www.zum.de/whkmla/region/westafrica/southernnigeria.html> (Accessed 12 January 2021).

Though there does not appear to be a provision for the offices of traditional rulers in the 1999 Constitution, the roles played by traditional rulers in their positions as Kings, Chiefs and Emirs in the resolution of conflicts in the community predates back to pre-colonial era.¹⁴²

Nigeria is governed by the 1999 Constitution which provides for the offices of elected officials¹⁴³ including the establishment of courts at both state and local government levels.¹⁴⁴

The post-colonial era saw the recognition of local authority in the Constitution of Nigeria by the establishment of local government councils in the 1979 Constitution.¹⁴⁵

The 1999 Constitution does not expressly provide for the local government authority, but they have continued to thrive in the administration of government at the local level.

The traditional rulers who govern their communities are recognised by the state governments in different categories as First Class, Second Class, Third Class and even Fourth-Class Chiefs and the authority they possess is equated to their category of the title they hold.¹⁴⁶

3.7.3 Cultural and traditional beliefs

Culture has been described as the cultivation of a usage of common practice-custom by a group of people with common consent over a period which acquires the force of a law over a place or subject matter to which it relates.¹⁴⁷ Customs are dynamic and sometimes evolve into customary law. The cultural and traditional beliefs of society are peculiar to the ethnicity of

¹⁴² Roger Blench, and others “The role of Traditional Rulers in Conflict Prevention and Mediation in Nigeria: Final Report” (DFID, Nigeria 2006) 12.

¹⁴³ 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Chapter V Part I.

¹⁴⁴ 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Chapter VII Parts I and II.

¹⁴⁵ 1979 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Section 7 (1) – (5).

¹⁴⁶ Roger Blench, and others “The role of Traditional Rulers in Conflict Prevention and Mediation in Nigeria: Final Report” (DFID Nigeria, 2006) 12.

¹⁴⁷ Agbonika John Alewo and Matthew Adefi Olong, ‘Cultural Practices and Traditional Beliefs as Impediments to the Enjoyment of Women’s Rights in Nigeria’ (2012) 1(1) International Law Research 134-140.

the people which is why the customary laws differ from each ethnic group. This study also considers the impact of traditional and cultural practices on women's rights. Cultural practices have been cited as justification for depriving women of their basic rights in societies.¹⁴⁸ Some of these customs and traditional practices have been written down as formal law but most are still unwritten and still possess the force of law in application. Women are discriminated against in almost every society daily by traditional practices and customs which hinder the exercise and enjoyment of their rights like the rights of female inheritance to property and capacity to own property.¹⁴⁹ In most societies in Nigeria under customary law, women are not allowed to own properties whether in their biological families or in their marital families. It has remained an uphill task for the judiciary to overturn these practices to the present day. One of such incidents is the woman who narrated her ordeal of being driven out of her matrimonial home at the death of her husband, she went back to her father's house and was not allocated any place to stay because she had no right to any property as she had been married out of the family and was not entitled to any of the houses or lands of her father.¹⁵⁰

The customs and traditions vary but are similar on issues of women's rights in certain areas in Nigeria in relation to the following:

- Rights of widows
- Capacity to own properties
- Occupation of certain public positions, etc.

Burial/Funeral Rites: This is a very common area which cuts across most cultures and traditions in Nigeria where women's rights are abused. In most communities when a man

¹⁴⁸ Ibid.

¹⁴⁹ Ibid.

¹⁵⁰ Personal account of Participant 2 at the FIDA Legal Centre, Anambra State, Nigeria on 13th January 2022 at 13:20hrs.

dies, the first suspect is the wife, and she is subjected to inhuman acts to prove her innocence.¹⁵¹ Some customs require that the woman drinks the water used in bathing the corpse to prove her innocence, she is also required to shave all the hair on her head and not allowed to leave her room for a certain period while wearing only black clothes.¹⁵²

These repugnant practices have led to the passing into law by some state government, laws prohibiting such practices such as the *Enugu State Protection of Widows and Widowers Fundamental Rights Law (2001)*, *Anambra State Malpractices against Widows and Widowers Prohibition Laws (2004)*.¹⁵³

There are so many areas where traditional beliefs and culture have hindered the rights of women especially as the girl child.

Education: Development attempts to occur in every society but deep rooted in most culture is still the preference to educate the boy child in favour of the girl child especially in Northern Nigeria on the premise that if the girl child is educated, she will no longer be humble.¹⁵⁴ Another aspect where culture has been biased against Nigerian women is in the mode of dressing. If a woman ties a wrapper and a head tie to attend a function, she is termed to be more responsibly dressed than a lady who is dressed in trousers or a short skirt, be it a local or formal function.¹⁵⁵ The men on the other hand, have the freedom to wear flowing dresses (northern Nigeria) or tie wrappers (Southern Nigeria- Rivers, Bayelsa

¹⁵¹ Agbonika John Alewo and Matthew Adefi Olong, 'Cultural Practices and Traditional Beliefs as Impediments to the Enjoyment of Women's Rights in Nigeria' (2012) 1 International Law Research, 1, 140.

¹⁵² Ibid.

¹⁵³ <https://laws.lawnigeria.com/2018/08/20/center-for-laws-of-the-states-of-nigeria/> (Accessed 14th January 2022).

¹⁵⁴ Agbonika John Alewo and Matthew Adefi Olong, 'Cultural Practices and Traditional Beliefs as Impediments to the Enjoyment of Women's Rights in Nigeria' (2012) 1 International Law Research, 1, 141.

¹⁵⁵ Ibid.

and Delta states) whenever they like, as their mode of dressing which is part of the traditional dressing.

3.8 Sources of Nigerian Legal System

The sources of the Nigerian legal system consist of four major legal systems, namely: the received English Law¹⁵⁶ (derived from the colonial period), Common law (developed from post-colonial Nigeria), Customary law and Sharia law.¹⁵⁷ Customary law in Nigeria is made up of the indigenous traditional norms and practices of the different regions which were in existence in the pre-colonial era. Sharia law is predominantly practised in the northern and Muslim States. Islam was said to have come into Nigeria through the Kanem Borno Empire by the Arab merchants who came to trade and the people adopted and began to practice Sharia law alongside their Muslim culture.¹⁵⁸

Nigeria began to operate a federal constitution in 1954 by the Nigerian (Constitution) Order Council¹⁵⁹ and the Constitution provides for the existence of 36 states and a federal capital territory in Abuja.¹⁶⁰ Nigeria operates a federal system of government with a written constitution and consist of the following main features: ¹⁶¹

¹⁵⁶ *Ibidapo v. Lufthansa Airlines* (1997) 4 NWLR 124 where the Supreme Court held that subject to the provisions of Section 315(1) of the 1999 Constitution, all received English Laws, bilateral and multilateral agreements concluded, extended to Nigeria and remained valid and in force except where expressly repealed or pronounced invalid by a court of competent jurisdiction or tribunal established by law. The conclusion of the case was to the effect that the **Carriage of Goods by Air (Colonies Protectorates and Trust Territories) Order 1953** which is a colonial legislation that has been held to be part of Nigerian law as it has not been repealed or declared invalid by any court of law.

¹⁵⁷ Luca Siliquini-Cinelli and Andrew Hutchison, *The Constitutional Dimension of Contract Law: A Comparative Perspective* (Springer International Publishing 2017) 173.

¹⁵⁸ Umar Alkali, and others, "Nature and Sources of Nigerian Legal System: An Exorcism of a Wrong Notion" (2014) 5(4) *International Journal of Business, Economics and Law* 1-3.

¹⁵⁹ *Ibid.*

¹⁶⁰ 1999 Constitution of the Federal republic of Nigeria, Section 3.

¹⁶¹ Ngozi Efobi and Naomi Ekop, 'Legal Systems in Nigeria: Overview' [2021] *ÆLEX* <https://uk.practicallaw.thomsonreuters.com/w-018-0292?transitionTy> (Accessed 5 November 2021).

Supremacy of the Constitution- Section 1(1) of the 1999 Constitution provides that the constitution is supreme, and its provisions are binding on all authorities and persons in Nigeria. The provision of this section is binding on the president of the country as well where it was declared by the court in *A.G Lagos v. A.G Federation*¹⁶² that the actions of the president in withholding the federal allocation to Lagos State was contradictory to the provisions of section 162 (5) of the constitution, and thus unconstitutional, null and void.

Presidential form of government – Nigeria operates the presidential system of government where the President as the head of the country combines the executive functions of the office with the ceremonial duties.

Separation of powers – In accordance with the doctrine of separation of powers, the legislature, executive and judiciary are independent of each other while executing the affairs of the country. Federalism – Nigeria operates a federalism wherein power lies at national as well as state levels and the different arms of government through the legislature, executive and the judiciary.

The Rule of Law – the rule of law in Nigeria is governed by the four distinct legal systems mentioned above namely: English law, Common law, customary law, and Sharia law.

As mentioned earlier separation of powers is a feature of the Nigerian Constitution and the Constitution provides for:

The Legislature: The legislative powers of the federal republic of Nigeria reside in the National Assembly which consist of the Senate and the House of Representatives.¹⁶³ The National Assembly is exclusively empowered by the Constitution to legislate on matters on the exclusive

¹⁶² Attorney General, Lagos State v. Attorney General of the Federation & Ors (2003) S.C 353.

¹⁶³ 1999 Constitution of the Federal republic of Nigeria, Section 4(1) <https://www.wipo.int/edocs/lexdocs/laws/en/ng/ng014en.pdf> (Accessed 8 November 2021).

list to the exclusion of the House of Assembly of the States.¹⁶⁴ The Senate shall consist of three Senators from each state and one from the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.¹⁶⁵

The Executive: The executive powers of the federation are vested in the president and state governors respectively, subject to the provisions of the Constitution.¹⁶⁶

The Judiciary: The courts established for the nation are vested with the judicial powers of the Federation as created by the Constitution.¹⁶⁷

The laws promulgated by the National Assembly which has the exclusive jurisdiction to legislate on matters in the exclusive legislative list, are called Acts.¹⁶⁸ The Federal and State Governments can legislate on matters in the concurrent list as provided by **Section 4 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria** and laws made by the state governments are termed law. Where there is any conflict between a State law and the Federal law, the Federal law shall prevail, and the State law shall be void to the extent of its inconsistency.¹⁶⁹

The Constitution provides for a third tier of government known as the Local Government Area¹⁷⁰ which is headed by a Local Government Council Chairman who makes laws called

¹⁶⁴1999 Constitution of the Federal republic of Nigeria, Section 4(1) and (2) <https://www.wipo.int/edocs/lexdocs/laws/en/ng/ng014en.pdf> (Accessed 9 November 2021).

¹⁶⁵ 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Section 48 <https://www.wipo.int/edocs/lexdocs/laws/en/ng/ng014en.pdf> (Accessed 8 November 2021).

¹⁶⁶1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Section 5(1) <https://www.wipo.int/edocs/lexdocs/laws/en/ng/ng014en.pdf> (Accessed 8 November 2021).

¹⁶⁷1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Section 6 <https://www.wipo.int/edocs/lexdocs/laws/en/ng/ng014en.pdf> (Accessed 8 November 2021).

¹⁶⁸ Umar Alkali, and others “Nature and Sources of Nigerian Legal System: An Exorcism of a Wrong Notion” (2014) 5(4) International Journal of Business, Economics and Law 3.

¹⁶⁹ 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Section 4(5).

¹⁷⁰ 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Section 3(6).

Bye laws. Councillors assist the Local Government Chairman in running the affairs of the local government area which are regulated by the Bye laws.¹⁷¹ The narrative of Nigeria's legal system cannot be complete without the role of the military and its impact on the laws and the judiciary. During the military regime when the military would interfere in the political affairs of the country, the modus operandi was to assume both legislative and executive powers and they ruled the country as one controlling power; though the judiciary appeared untouched.¹⁷² The Military era in Nigeria was an uncertain period for the enforcement of human rights and the prosecution of violators. The Military administration in Nigeria was characterised with human right abuses especially in its decree and edicts such as **Decree No 2 of 1984** (as amended).¹⁷³ An example is the provision that gives immunity from any legal liability from any action done pursuant to the Decree such as detention of persons who were threats to state security without charging them to court.¹⁷⁴ Another one of such military decrees is the **Constitution (Suspension and Modification) Decree No. 107** which ousted the jurisdiction of the courts in presiding over civil proceedings pursuant to the provisions of any Decree.¹⁷⁵ The criticism of the military regime for its disrespect for the rule of law and human rights was quite strong during the Buhari/Idiagbon administration.¹⁷⁶ Despite the negativity which surrounded the military era in Nigeria there have been benefits ascribed to the military administration such as the quick dispatch with which decrees were passed without bureaucratic

¹⁷¹ Umar Alkali and others 'Nature and Sources of Nigerian Legal System: An Exorcism of a Wrong Notion' (2014) 5(4) International Journal of Business, Economics and Law 3.

¹⁷² Asien, J.O. *Introduction to Nigerian Legal System* (2nd edn, Ababa Press Nigeria Ltd 2005) 8.

¹⁷³ Federal Military Government (Supremacy and Enforcement) of Powers Decree No. 12 of 1994.

¹⁷⁴ State Security (Detention of Persons) Decree No. 2 of 1984 (As Amended) Section 4.

¹⁷⁵ Umar Alkali and others 'Nature and Sources of Nigerian Legal System: An Exorcism of a Wrong Notion' (2014) 5(4) International Journal of Business, Economics and Law 3.

¹⁷⁶ Ibid.

bottle necks and political considerations¹⁷⁷ and these became Acts when democracy was restored in accordance with the Constitution.¹⁷⁸ The ‘Decree’ was replaced with ‘Act’ while the ‘Edict’ passed by the States was replaced with ‘Law’. It is pertinent to take into consideration the impact of the military administration on the Nigerian legal system in relation to the adoption and ratification of international laws on human rights and more importantly the rights of Nigerian women.

3.8.1 Structure of Nigerian Courts

The colonial system framed the structure for a formal judicial system with the establishment of the courts in the Nigerian constitution as follows:

Figure 3.1
Hierarchy of Court

¹⁷⁷ Umar Alkali and others “Nature and Sources of Nigerian Legal System: An Exorcism of a Wrong Notion” (2014) 5(4) International Journal of Business, Economics and Law 4.

¹⁷⁸ 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Section 315.

The Supreme Court is the apex court of justice in Nigeria and is presided over by the Chief Justice of Nigeria and the number of justices as prescribed by the Constitution or an Act of the National Assembly.¹⁷⁹ Only states can initiate matters with original jurisdiction at the supreme court and it hears matters on appeal from the Court of Appeal. The Court of Appeal is presided over by the President of the Court of Appeal and the number of justices prescribed by the Constitution.¹⁸⁰ The Court of Appeal also has appellate jurisdiction to hear matters from the Federal High Court, High Court, the Sharia Court of Appeal of the Federal Capital Territory, the Sharia Court of Appeal of a State, Customary Court of Appeal of the Federal Capital Territory Abuja, Customary Court of Appeal of a State, decisions from court martials and other tribunals as prescribed by an Act of National Assembly.¹⁸¹ The Sharia Court of Appeal has appellate jurisdiction over questions of Islamic personal law¹⁸² while the Customary Court of Appeal of the Federal Capital Territory has appellate jurisdiction in civil proceedings over questions of customary law.¹⁸³

The Customary Court of Appeal of a State has appellate jurisdiction to preside over matters in civil proceedings on questions of customary law.¹⁸⁴ The hierarchy of the courts is structured to receive appeals from different levels except the courts which have exclusive or original jurisdiction on certain matters like the Supreme Court and the Federal High Court¹⁸⁵ as provided by the Nigerian Constitution.

¹⁷⁹ 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria Section 230.

¹⁸⁰ 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria Section 237.

¹⁸¹ 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria Section 240.

¹⁸² 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria Section 262(1).

¹⁸³ 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria Section 267.

¹⁸⁴ 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria Section 282(1).

¹⁸⁵ 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria Section 251.

3.8.2 Access to Justice under the Nigerian Legal System

Nigeria as signatory to some international conventions such as the **Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948**, complies with the obligations of member States on judicial provisions.¹⁸⁶

The 1999 Nigerian Constitution provides for the domestication of international conventions in *Section 12* by the different states. It is postulated that under the Nigerian legal system, laws cannot be enforced except they are codified.¹⁸⁷ Consequently, once the law provides for a situation, such actions must be performed in accordance with the law. The foundation of access to justice is based on existing statutory provisions. The presumption of Nigerian jurisprudence appears to be that access to justice lies in the courts as was stated by Oputa JSC (as he then was) in *Attorney General Kaduna State v. Hassan*¹⁸⁸ when the Supreme Court held that access to justice, was access to the court as this was the essence of adjudication.

Access to justice is provided for and enshrined in Chapter IV of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria which provides for fundamental rights. The Constitution provides for access to justice in the right to fair hearing in Section 36 (1) in the following words:

“In the determination of his civil rights and obligations, including any question or determination by or against any government or authority, a person shall be entitled to a fair hearing within a reasonable time by a court or other tribunal established by law and constituted in such manner as to secure its independence and impartiality”.

The Constitution further protects the citizens from discrimination from any law in force, or any executive or administrative decision in Nigeria by the provisions of *Section 42(1)*. The Court is empowered by the Constitution to preside over matters between persons or governmental

¹⁸⁶ Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948, Article 8.

¹⁸⁷ Pontian Okoli, ‘Access to Justice and Fair Hearing: An Evaluation of Pre-Action Notice In Nigerian Jurisprudence’ (2012) 20(1) African Journal of International and Comparative Law 70.

¹⁸⁸ [1985] 2 N.W.L.R. Part 8 SC 552.

authorities and all related matters pertaining to the determination of questions on civil rights and obligations.¹⁸⁹ The implication of this provision of the law is that access to justice is subsumed in the right to a fair hearing and this can be found in the courts.

Onnoghen JSC in *Bill Construction Co. Ltd v. Imani and Sons Ltd*¹⁹⁰ emphasised that the court guarantees the right to fair hearing. But does fair hearing guarantee justice? Okoli postulated that access to the courts means compliance with the Rules of Court such as compliance with rules of procedure.¹⁹¹ He has also stated that this is not a guarantee of justice based on the procedures which accompany court procedure because people are discouraged by the bureaucracy of the court proceedings. Bamgbose also emphasises on justice not being attainable where people are not aware of their rights and consequently do not know they should access justice.¹⁹² Under the Nigerian legal system, these are some of the factors which affect access to justice. Other factors which affect effective access to justice are deprivation of the basic necessities of life such as food, shelter, healthcare, water and access to protection of the state.¹⁹³ The Nigerian Constitution recognises that not all citizens are able to afford the services of a lawyer and justice should not be available to only well to do people. *Section 46(4)(b)(i) provides:*¹⁹⁴

“The National Assembly shall make provisions for the rendering of financial assistance to any indigent citizen of Nigeria where his right under this Chapter has

¹⁸⁹ 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria Section 6(6).

¹⁹⁰ [2006] 19 N.W.L.R, Part 1013 SC 4.

¹⁹¹ Pontian Okoli, ‘Access to Justice and Fair Hearing: An Evaluation of Pre-Action Notice In Nigerian Jurisprudence’ (2012) 20(1) African Journal of International and Comparative Law 79.

¹⁹² Oluyemisi Bamgbose, ‘Access to Justice through Clinical Legal Education: A Way Forward for Good Governance and Development’ (2015) 15(2) African Human Rights Law Journal 378.

¹⁹³ OECD Guideline Series, ‘Participatory Development and Good Governance Co-operation’ (1995) in Oluyemisi Bamgbose, ‘Access to Justice Through Clinical Legal Education: A Way Forward for Good Governance and Development’ (2015) 15(2) African Human Rights Law Journal 379.

¹⁹⁴ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria of 1999.

been infringed or with a view to enabling him to engage the services of a legal practitioner to prosecute his claim...”

But in practice, is legal aid available to all indigent citizens to access justice? Especially women in a family dispute.

Another legal instrument in Nigeria that dwells on the issue of access to justice is the National Policy on Justice 2017. The policy highlights that the 1999 Constitution as amended, guarantees access to justice for everyone and that the government agency responsible for providing free legal assistance to indigent people is the Legal Aid Council of Nigeria. The challenges of access to justice as stated in the National Policy on Justice, 2017 include under-resourced access to justice programs, inadequate legal literacy and awareness among the public and unavailability of gazettes of legislation.

To ameliorate the problems of access to justice in Nigeria, the strategic intervention measures as put forward in the National Policy on Justice 2017 include expanding the Legal Aid Council programmes, setting up of legal assistance agencies in more States of the Federation, raising public awareness, and publication of laws in official gazettes and regular law reviews. One of the objectives of this study is to use the findings of the research as a platform to raise awareness about access to justice, especially among women who are involved in family mediation.

3.8.3 Critique on Nigerian Legal System

Academic writers have criticised some of the Nigerian laws as being unsuitable in the present day as a result of changes and development in the world. Alkali et al stated in their article, “Nature and Sources of Nigerian Legal System: An Exorcism of a Wrong Notion” that there are English laws which were promulgated into Nigerian laws that have been repealed or amended in England but are part of Nigerian laws which are not suitable for the

communities.¹⁹⁵ They also criticised the fact that the adoption of a Child's Rights Law which did not take into consideration Islamic principles, was not all inclusive of the Muslims who occupy the northern part of Nigeria. It is believed by some critics that the colonial administration made the traditional practices and culture less significant in the Nigerian legal system using validity tests that were subject to English standards.¹⁹⁶

The overview of the hierarchy of courts under the Nigerian legal system is necessary for this study to understand the structure in dispensing justice. Women need to know which courts have the jurisdiction to enforce the resolutions reached at family mediations and the procedure for enforcement. They also need to know they have the right to access the courts and for that they need to be able to meet their financial needs such as being able to travel to seek legal advice, educational needs when younger, etc.

3.9 Legal Theories and Implications for this research

To further provide context for understanding the subject matter of access to justice for women in Nigeria using the sociolegal analysis of family mediation, this subsection will consider some important legal theories and their implications for this research. The theories are formalism, realism, idealism and critical legal studies, which will be explained and their relevance to achieving the objectives of the study.

3.9.1 Theory of Legal Formalism

The theory of legal formalism is described as a scientific jurisprudence which considers law's ideal situation as a sequence of rules, not informed by any moral discourse, but only a matrix of rules that are evolving from several cases and statutes, and lays the foundation for positivist law

¹⁹⁵ Umar Alkali and others 'Nature and Sources of Nigerian Legal System: An Exorcism of a Wrong Notion' (2014) 5(4) International Journal of Business, Economics and Law 5-8.

¹⁹⁶ Ibid.

which may be applied without recourse to morality, ethics or ideology.¹⁹⁷ This theory assumes no link between law and morality but finds and applies the suitable rule, and it is the rule-orientation that makes law. It sees law as a seamless fabric, a system without gaps, in which the ‘solution’ to any dispute can be found through the proper rule. Under the theory, the goal of law is to be self-sufficient in its rules, independent and untroubled by external social realities since the rules are supreme.

In legal formalism, substantive justice is not considered a contradiction to it as one flows from one to the other. This is because the application of the rules should result in a just outcome. Furthermore, formalism explains that the internal logic and integrity of law must prevail even in problematic cases where substantive injustice may result in a regrettable but unavoidable outcome. In legal formalism, there is no question as to where the rules come from, other than from precedence. Hence, any query as to what law is or ought to be is foreshortened by the claim of the supremacy of rules.¹⁹⁸

Some proponents of legal formalism have however proposed a milder version, including a degree of rule scepticism by admitting a degree of discretion in the rules. This is because any effort to achieve substantive justice where formalism in its original version fails will be problematic.¹⁹⁹

3.9.2 Theory of Legal Realism

Legal realism ideology was championed by Karl Llewellyn.²⁰⁰ Due to the limitations of legal formalism, especially the perceived rigidity of the rules, the theory of legal realism became

¹⁹⁷ Geoffrey Leane, ‘Testing some Theories about Law: can we find substantive justice within law’s rules?’ (1994) 19 Melbourne University Law Review 949.

¹⁹⁸ Geoffrey Leane, “Testing some Theories about Law: can we find substantive justice within law’s rules?” (1994), 19 Melbourne University Law Review, 924.

¹⁹⁹ Margaret Davies, *Asking the Law Question*, (Law Book Company 1994) 79.

²⁰⁰ William Twining, *Karl Llewellyn and the Realist Movement*, (Cambridge University Press, 2012).

popular in the 1920s and 1930s, and the influence continued until the 1960s.²⁰¹ The advocates of legal realism criticised the rule-boundedness of legal formalism, as being weak. The position was the execution of law as rules empty of moral and political debate. Rather than take refuge from indeterminacy in the rules of formalism, the realists argued for acknowledgment and embracing indeterminacy. They posited that in any situation, there are a variety of possible rules available, and they are often sometimes contradictory. The realists then argued that the role of the judge is to *choose*. The imperative of the choice should be recognized, and the use of choice should be one that is case-sensitive and aware of the policy implications and social outcomes.²⁰²

The realists argued further that logic offers catalyst, but it does not guarantee the success of a just outcome, and to assume that all cases can be rationally resolved within the self-defining legal logic is not optimal since there are social, economic and ethical matters at stake.²⁰³ Thus the realists acknowledge the role of social policy in law and are against the primacy of abstract rules. They demanded that focus be on the consequences of laws, which reflect policy judgments and social facts. Also, realists opined that the life of the law is not logic, but experience and that realism represents a wider philosophical movement grounded in empirical experience rather than rules.²⁰⁴

Legal realism recommends consciousness of substantive justice in its demands that the ‘real’ legal background of politics and social life be recognised. It explains that law does not and cannot function in isolation from society, and to the extent that it tries to do so through

²⁰¹ Felix Cohen, ‘The Ethical Basis of Legal Criticism’ [1931] *Yale Law Journal*, 201- 216.

²⁰² *Ibid.*

²⁰³ *Ibid.*

²⁰⁴ Oliver Wendell Holmes, *The Common Law* (Little Brown and Company, 1963) 143.

formalism, distorts and truncates its practice and potentials. Law is thus to be judged by its social costs and not by its formalism but by its ability to deliver substantive justice.²⁰⁵

Oliver W. Holmes explained that ‘the life of the law has not been logic: it has been experience’²⁰⁶ and legal realism represents an aspect of a broader philosophical movement grounded in empirical experience rather than abstract rules.²⁰⁷ It suggests a realization of substantive justice in its demands that the real legal background of politics and social life be admitted and honored. In conclusion, realists aided the *understanding* of the social and political realities of law.

3.9.3 Theory of Legal Idealism

The theory of legal idealism attempted to reconcile formality and indeterminacy by considering some guiding unity in the principles, policies and purposes underlying the law. The proponents sought to uncover issues by looking deeper within law itself or outside law to society. The aim is that if one digs diligently then one can find embedded within the law, if not a uniting morality or higher moral discourse, then at least certain principles, policies, and purposes which inform it and to which one can look for guidance.

The Idealists are anti-formalist in rejecting faith in legal rules, but go beyond the realists in an attempt to redeem those rules by justifying them through their underlying morality. An early form of Idealism, present after the Second World War until the early 1960s, confirms the anti-formality of the realists but attempted to deal with the problem of indeterminacy. This early

²⁰⁵ Geoffrey Leane ‘Testing some Theories about Law: can we find substantive justice within law’s rules?’ (1994) 19 Melbourne University Law Review 928.

²⁰⁶ Oliver Wendell Holmes, *The Common Law* (Little Brown and Company 1963).

²⁰⁷ *Ibid.*

version looks to society for the situation-sense which will expose inherent law, but a later version from the late 1960s instead looks within law itself for a combining narrative.²⁰⁸

Overall, Idealism can be characterized as a more refined, extended kind of formalism because while simple rules may not provide all the responses, particularly in rigid cases, they nevertheless include within them the seeds of an answer to difficult cases through their inherent political morality. Thus, formalism lies not in the rules but in their combining, motivating spirit, and so, the Idealists would argue that any observed tension between formalism and substantive justice which is difficult to deliver in hard cases, is simply the unfortunate result of incorrectly applied Idealism.

3.9.4 Theory of Critical Legal Studies

The critical legal theory asks the procedural question by resonating the Realist assessment of the choice between competing rules, and the substantive question of what is the nature of the moral and political structure to which the Idealists turn. This theory is considered to be more in the nature of a movement than a theory itself.²⁰⁹ One stand takes up and presses forward with the proposition of the earlier Legal Realists, specifically the open-endedness and indeterminacy of law, where judges merely select from a range of contrasting rules and principles. Similarly with the realists, this part of the Critical Legal theory seeks to uncover law's hypocritical claim to deliver determinate answers, determinate solutions in specific cases, without recourse to political or ethical choice.²¹⁰ As with the rule-scepticism of the realists, this

²⁰⁸ Charles Fried, 'The Laws of Change: The Cunning of Reason in Moral and Legal History' [1980] *Journal of Legal Studies* 335.

²⁰⁹ Geoffrey Leane, 'Testing some Theories about Law: can we find substantive justice within law's rules?' (1994) 19 *Melbourne University Law Review*, 949.

²¹⁰ Clare Dalton, 'An Essay in the Deconstruction of Contract Doctrine' (1985) 94 *Yale Law Journal* 997, 1007.

component of the Critical Legal Theory sees legal rules competing with each other in a petty, unstructured conflict, devoid of any Grand Theory.²¹¹

A second stand postulates a fundamental version of the Critical Legal theory addressing the original structures of law and its implicit ideology, trying to link law to its social purposes and political interests.²¹² Whereas the Idealists seek to find the core principles, policies and purposes which inform law and legitimise it, the Critical Legal theorists take the question a step further, seeking to uncover and challenge the legitimacy of the underlying ideology which truly motivates legal decisions. They see the Idealists and the formalists as not simply accepting the *status quo* but as legitimizing it, not just in an interpretive role, but an instrumental one. Thus, the Critical theorists have the view that theory legitimizes ideology.²¹³

The Critical Legal theorists also posit that the object of legitimacy is rooted in social structure of unjustified hierarchy and control which is the real impairment to substantive justice.²¹⁴ For example, they argue that one way of creating and continuing a set of power relations is to depoliticise law and invoke principles of objectivity and neutrality through formal rules, so that any probable investigation into substantive justice within those power relations is foreclosed.

The Critical Legal theorists also clarified a structural challenge that if institutional morality of the Idealists exists, then whose morality, is it? If it is admitted that it is socially created, then whose social construct is it? The Critical Legal theorists describe it as the morality of the dominant class, the class of property, wealth, and power, who controls the legislature, the

²¹¹ Mark Tushnet, 'The Dilemmas of Liberal Constitutionalism' (1981) 42 Ohio State Law Journal 411.

²¹² Morton Horwitz, *The Transformation of American Law, 1780-1860* (Oxford University Press, 1977) 160-188.

²¹³ Ibid.

²¹⁴ Ibid.

courts, the legal profession and the business sector. In such circumstance it is not morality but the legitimacy which hides unfair inequality and hierarchy in the society.

3.9.5 Implications for this research

All the theories (formalism, realism, idealism, and critical legal studies) as described in the preceding sub-sections, have implications for this study in examining the access to justice for women in Nigeria using the sociolegal analysis of family mediation. The theories also have consequences for legal consciousness among the Nigerian public, especially women. This is because the government, through diverse policy and regulatory reforms, have been putting in place mechanisms to enhance consciousness about certain aspects of law.

The underlying principle of formalism exists in both the formal and informal family mediation processes in Nigeria as it considers law as a sequence of rules not informed by morality but evolving from case law and statutes. Informally, cultural and societal beliefs, which can be termed as rules, are instrumental in the format of resolving certain family disputes. This is particularly true in societies where women are culturally constrained, and religiously limited, to undertake certain actions that will protect their fundamental rights. Formally, there are laid down procedures, for example, as enshrined in Nigeria's National Policy on Justice 2017, of how some civil cases can be resolved through Alternative Dispute Resolutions (ADR), which include mediation in certain family matters. However, and as highlighted in the Policy, there is the challenge of non-enforcement of judgments and decisions reached for some mediation cases. With respect to the consciousness of the public about the formal rules, government agencies and some civil society organizations whose interest is in law and justice, usually hold sensitization programmes aimed at enlightening people about important aspects of the law. For example, the Federal Ministry of Justice of Nigeria, has been leading advocacies about the advantages of using ADR mechanisms.

The legal realism theory is also relevant for this thesis as revealed when women from northern Nigeria who were to participate as interviewees declined to do so. In Northern Nigeria for example, the culture and religious background makes it difficult for certain rules to be applicable in similar cases in other parts of Nigeria. In a situation, for instance, where a non-indigene and a non-Muslim woman is married to an indigene Muslim man, applying the rules that are alien to the woman's culture and faith in the event of a dispute with the husband, will mean an unfair treatment devoid of the reality that the woman has a fundamentally different cultural background and faith. Thus, the realists argue that the applicable rules should provide fair hearing and adjudication for the woman, not based on culture or religion. The consciousness of women to certain legal matters is influenced by the realities that some societal, cultural, and religious constraints place on them.

The theory of legal idealism which attempts to find a middle ground between formalism and realism considers the guiding principles, policies and purposes underlying the law. The Idealists are anti-formalist in rejecting faith in legal rules but go beyond the realists in an attempt to redeem those rules by justifying them through their underlying morality. The relevance of this to the thesis is that the investigation will seek to scrutinize if in the formal and informal family mediation process, the underlying issue of morality is given preference. For example, if in a family mediation case, the mediator uses discretion to choose among contrasting rules to give a resolution which is considered unfair, can the use of such discretion to select a rule be seen to be morally fair? To challenge the fairness of a process and ascertain if the ideal principles were applied, the woman must have the understanding, or knowledge to engage lawyers who can help challenge the process.

Lastly, the critical legal theory which asks the procedural question by resonating the realist's assessment of the choice between competing rules, and the substantive question of what the nature of the moral and political structure is, is also relevant to the thesis. This is because the

issue of procedural and substantive justice remains topical in the literature. In seeking to scrutinize access to justice for women in Nigeria using family mediation, the process is guided by the contentious issue of procedural and substantive justice. In addition, the study will seek to ascertain if the women are conscious about the outcome of mediations being affected by the processes which lead to the resolutions.

Overall, because the society is evolving, legal theories are also growing to reflect societal dynamics and their effect in the dispensation of justice. The empirical aspects of this thesis are therefore guided by the principles of legal formalism, idealism, realism, and critical legal theory. These theories provide a guide to this study in understanding women's access to justice in family mediation.

3.10 Theory of Legal Consciousness and Access to Justice

The theory of legal consciousness will be discussed from the perspective of the rights of women as it relates to this study. This study seeks to examine the extent of legal consciousness of Nigerian women as it impacts on access to justice.

3.10.1 What is Legal Consciousness?

A universal wording of a definition of legal consciousness is challenging as legal consciousness is understood based on individual perception. There are four different approaches to understanding legal consciousness – (a) critical, (b) interpretive (c) comparative cultural and (d) law-in-action.²¹⁵ These approaches are necessary in understanding socio-legal research of legal consciousness as it is defined based on the perspective of the approach being considered in this research.

The International Encyclopaedia of the Social & Behavioural Sciences states that “the study of legal consciousness traces the ways in which law is experienced and interpreted by specific

²¹⁵ Simon Halliday, ‘After Hegemony? The Varieties of Legal Consciousness Research’ (2019) 28(6) *Social and Legal Studies* 859 at 863.

individuals as they engage, avoid, or resist the law and legal meanings”.²¹⁶ Hertogh in his critique of legal consciousness talks about the hegemonic power of state law and how people respond to the law.²¹⁷ One of the issues which influence the concept of legal consciousness is the response of people to the law in action. Some of the argument surrounding legal consciousness is centred on the classes of the people.²¹⁸ Halliday in his writing identified the gap between the law and the response of the people as their legal consciousness.²¹⁹ Other researchers such as Ewick and Silbey postulate that consciousness is revealed in what people do and not just what they say.²²⁰

Some writers have opined their ideas on legal consciousness and this study will consider a few. Cowan in his writings examines legal consciousness by the structure in place by the government for the under privileged to access basic amenities with emphasis on housing.²²¹ He stated how the system makes available aids and benefits which the people who are aware of the provision, sometimes try to exploit the system. The point he makes is the fact that there is structure in place and the people are aware of these provisions and the emphasis is on how the people respond to these provisions. In relating this perception of legal consciousness to Nigeria, the situation is different. On paper, the provision for legal aid exists but it is not the same in reality when women seek to enforce their rights. There are government parastatals where legal

²¹⁶ International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences (Elsevier Science Ltd, 2001) 8626.

²¹⁷ Mark Hertogh and Marina Kurkchiyan ‘When politics comes into play, law is no longer Law’: images of collective legal consciousness in the UK, Poland and Bulgaria (2016) 12(4) International Journal of Law in Context 404.

²¹⁸ Some of the writers like Austin Sarat discuss the difference between the welfare poor and the respected poor and their level of legal consciousness.

²¹⁹ Simon Halliday, ‘After Hegemony? The Varieties of Legal Consciousness Research’ (2019) 28(6) Social and Legal Studies 859.

²²⁰ Patricia Ewick and Susan Silbey, *The Common Place of Law: Stories from Everyday Life* (Chicago University Press, 1998) 10 at 14.

²²¹ Dave Cowan, ‘Legal Consciousness: Some Observations’ (2004) 67(6) Modern Law Review 928 at 932.

aids are provided as channels through which justice can be accessed but the barriers as mentioned earlier on in this chapter sometimes hinder women's access to these services.

Legal consciousness begins from knowing what constitutes legal rights and the structure available for the enforcement of those rights. It is described as the production and revelation of what they say.²²² Cowan in his writing explains legal consciousness from the point of view of homeless people which include asylum seekers, pregnant teenagers etc.²²³ He discusses how access to justice by the homeless is affected by their legal consciousness. From the explanation of Cowan, some homeless people see the legal system as an avenue to obtain benefits while others see it as an avenue to procure social housing. The homeless applicants see law from different perspectives which include a process to a means to an end, or barrier to their needs.²²⁴ However, the system as perceived by the homeless persons is determined by the extent of their legal consciousness.

Other writers have explained legal consciousness from the point of everyday lives and how it determines their actions as it affects access to justice.²²⁵ Nielsen explains legal consciousness from the point of view of discrimination as to gender, class, or race and how people respond.²²⁶ She stated that people developed an attitude as a form of legal consciousness in dealing with the injustice they encounter daily. Their responses to challenges vary and depend on their gender, race, or class. Some of the illustrations included the following words, as stated by the people she interviewed:

²²² Dave Cowan, 'Legal Consciousness: Some Observations' (2004) 67(6) *Modern Law Review* 929.

²²³ *Ibid.*

²²⁴ *Ibid.*

²²⁵ Austin Sarat and Thomas Fern, *Beyond the Great Divide: Forms of Legal Scholarship and Everyday Life* (University of Michigan Press 1995) 55.

²²⁶ Laura Beth Nielsen, 'Situating Legal Consciousness: Experiences and Attitudes of Ordinary Citizens about Law and Street Harassment' (2000) 34(4) *Law and Society Review* 1055.

“I hate women; they're all sluts.”²²⁷ Or
“You ... people need to go back where you came from, I'm sick of this, you come
over here and think you can take everything away from us.”²²⁸

The two responses above reveal the different level of legal consciousness of the people in accessing justice through government infrastructures.

Nielsen examines how people of different class, gender, and race address offensive public speech and how this affects their legal consciousness of the system. Some did not respond and walked away while others felt the system allowed such behaviour due to their prior experiences.²²⁹ In relating this to Nigerian women's experiences, the way women of a certain class would respond to discrimination would vary as well. A woman who is well educated and has a good paying job will respond differently to a discriminatory remark than a poorly educated woman as her level of legal consciousness would be assumed to be higher due to awareness of resources of enlightenment. For example, a woman journalist who rose to become an executive manager stated that during board meetings, she still has to contend with remarks like; “she's a woman! What can she say?”²³⁰ In reacting to such discriminatory statement, her legal consciousness would be different from a woman who is uneducated and has no independent financial source of income. This research in discussing Nigerian's women's access to justice will examine how the awareness of their rights affects their decision to choose the most appropriate process in enforcing their rights, in this case family mediation as a method of dispute resolution in family disputes.

²²⁷ 24-year-old woman interviewee in Laura Nielsen's study.

²²⁸ 29-year-old African American woman in Laura Nielsen's study.

²²⁹ Laura Beth Nielsen, 'Situating Legal Consciousness: Experiences and Attitudes of Ordinary Citizens about Law and Street Harassment' (2000) 34(4) *Law and Society Review* 1056.

²³⁰ Tawa Yusuf, 'Discrimination Against Women Journalists takes Different Forms' [2022] International Press Institute, April 11 edition, <https://ipi.media/ipinetwork/discrimination-against-women-journalists-in-nigeria-takes-many-forms/> (Accessed 04 April 2023).

Sarat from his perspective of legal consciousness, explains it as the view of the respectable poor and the welfare poor.²³¹ He postulates that both categories take advantage of the system and respond to the bureaucracy by appointing lawyers to act on their behalf because of their legal consciousness. The awareness to employ the services of lawyers is borne out of the recognition of the display of power by the caseworkers and the use of lawyers is the resistance. One of the beneficiaries of the welfare poor had this to say:

“They got so much going down that I'm just one more person trying to get emergency relief. They don't pay no mind, but when they call, I mean when the lawyer calls, then I'm somebody, something...”²³²

Sarat's study of “welfare of the poor” and how it affects their legal consciousness can be likened with the position in Nigeria in relation to the sense that, the legal consciousness of the poor in Nigeria is likely to affect their access to justice. This will be examined in this study in the data collection as factors affecting women's access to justice through family mediation.

Silbey explains legal consciousness as “a theoretical concept and topic of empirical research; legal consciousness developed among socio-legal scholars to explain how law sustains its institutional power across wide spans of time, space, and variable performance”.²³³

Silbey echoing the authors mentioned above, is of the view that legal consciousness investigates the manner in which the law is experienced and interpreted by particular persons and how they respond to the law.²³⁴ The response to the law could be to engage the law, resist or avoid it. In looking at the theory of legal consciousness this study seeks to examine the legal

²³¹ Austin Sarat, ‘Law is All Over: Power, Resistance and the Legal Consciousness of the Welfare Poor’ (1990) 2(2) *Yale Journal of Law and the Humanities* 343.

²³² Austin Sarat, ‘Law is All Over: Power, Resistance and the Legal Consciousness of the Welfare Poor’ (1990) 2 *Yale Journal of Law and the Humanities*, 363.

²³³ Susan Silbey, “After Legal Consciousness” [2005] *Annual Review Law Society*, 1, 323.

²³⁴ *Ibid.*

consciousness of Nigerian women and how their everyday experience translates into their response to the structures of the legal system. Silbey's position of legal consciousness can be traced to the need to understand how the institutions of the law remain steadfast despite the gap which exists in reality in the application of the law. She sought to find out why people accepted a legal system which promised justice and delivered injustice to the everyday person. This response is what is explained as legal consciousness. The foundation appears to be rooted in law and society philosophies, where the "haves" ensure that the "have nots" do not cross the divide therefore maintaining the gap of inequality.²³⁵ Early writers like Galanter focused on legal consciousness from the perspective of organisational structure of the system which promotes the gap of inequality.²³⁶ The resistance to power by the people is the expression of legal consciousness which could be in different forms. The concept of hegemony as explained by Silbey suggest that hegemony is as a result of everyday transactions which has been produced and reproduced and did not originate from a singular social function.²³⁷ She explains that hegemony occurs as a result of the institutionalisation of power which has become the norm and the people have become complacent and subordinate to the structures of power.

The argument that people are compliant in the face of hegemonic decisions and laws; was canvassed by Gillman with an example of the 2000 US elections.²³⁸ Gillman stated the reason the decision of the elections was accepted by the American people was as a result of a long history of trust in the judiciary as the custodians of the American Constitution and by default law and justice. Legal consciousness consequently is the behaviour of the people to the law in

²³⁵ Susan Silbey, "After Legal Consciousness" [2005] *Annual Review Law Society*, 1, 325.

²³⁶ Marc Galanter, 'Why the "Haves" Come Out Ahead: Speculations on the Limits of Legal Change' (1974) 9(1) *Law and Society Review* 26.

²³⁷ Susan Silbey, 'After Legal Consciousness' [2005] *Annual Review Law Society* 331.

²³⁸ Howard Gillman, *The Votes that Counted: How the Court Decided the 2000 Presidential Election* (University of Chicago Press, 2001) 306.

action. Ewick and Silbey in a bid to demonstrate that legal consciousness was not based on individuals but on the legality of the law, conducted interviews of over 400 random participants in a state.²³⁹ From the theories of the above cited authors, legal consciousness of people determines the extent of their access to justice.

3.10.2 Legal Consciousness in Nigeria

In relating the theory of legal consciousness to Nigeria as discussed above with relevance to this research, the perspective is considered from family mediation. The consensus from the authors cited above suggest that legal consciousness is the response of the people to the law. This study explores the legal consciousness of Nigerian women as it relates to family mediation. The power and resistance as described by Sarat can be illustrated in the power and resistance of Nigerian women's refusal to be content with the norm of informal mediation if they are not satisfied with the outcome. Do they make the choice to proceed to formal mediation when not satisfied with the outcome of the mediation process? How does legal consciousness of Nigerian women affect their access to justice? These are part of the questions this study will consider during the data collection stage of this research.

The above cited provisions of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria clearly provide for access to justice and specifically legal aid.²⁴⁰ It is the responsibility of the citizens to avail themselves of the benefits of the legal system by contacting the Legal Aid service centre. This can only be achieved based on their legal consciousness. From the examples of some of the interviewees in Sarat's work, some of the welfare poor felt the system treated them with disdain but had respect for the affluent in society. This research examines the veracity of this theory of how legal consciousness affects Nigerian women in accessing justice during the

²³⁹ Patricia Ewick and Susan Silbey, *The Common Place of Law: Stories from Everyday Life*, (University Chicago Press 1998) 14.

²⁴⁰ Section 46(4)(b)(1).

data collection of this study. In Chapter Four, this study examines how NGOs like FIDA, and other international organisations sensitise women on their rights and the legal options in accessing justice. This mobilisation by agencies fosters a sense of empowerment and promotes the awareness of Nigerian women on their rights and how to enforce them. The study will proceed to draw on illustrations of legal consciousness of Nigerian women in Chapters Six and Seven from the data analysis as examples of women's journey in family mediation as an access to justice.

3.11 Conclusion

This chapter in defining justice provides the foundation from which this research explores access of justice. The importance of access to justice is reflected in the recognition accorded by the World Bank in the projects such as the judicial reforms. Access to justice under the Nigerian legal system is ensured in the court system as provided in the Nigerian Constitution. The various provisions in the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria illustrate that access to justice is enshrined in the Constitution. The data collection will test the legal theories as they affect Nigerian women.

Legal consciousness as a concept in Nigeria appears to be a grey area as procuring the literature on the subject was challenging but lack of jurisprudence on legal consciousness in Nigeria does not reduce the concept as this study will examine the reality of the theory during the interviews. The writings of Cowan, Sarat, Silbey and the others have revealed the dynamics at work in the minds of the citizens of a society in their interpretation of how they understand the law. This culminates in the overall response to the justice system. The following chapters will discuss the rights of women, internationally and in Nigeria as it relates to family mediation.

CHAPTER FOUR

LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR WOMEN’S RIGHTS AND ACCESS TO JUSTICE IN THE NIGERIAN LEGAL SYSTEM

4.1 Introduction

Laws are the foundation for the enjoyment of rights and a deterrent to chaos in the face of violation of those rights. This chapter focuses on the legal framework surrounding women’s rights, from the international sector and emphasise on the Nigerian legal system and how they impact on women’s rights.

The roles of the international convention and their impact on local laws is discussed in this chapter to understand women’s rights in relation to their access to justice in Nigeria. The purpose is to examine the international conventions and how effective they are in protecting the rights of women as women have been recognised as being part of the vulnerable group of society.²⁴¹

International conventions are binding on parties to the conventions. The **Maputo Protocol**²⁴² as an example of an international convention which provides for women’s rights, directs the governments of member States to provide access to judicial services for women through programmes such as legal aid which promote access to justice.²⁴³

This chapter discusses the women’s rights to access justice as a fundamental right and an instrument of the rule of law. Provisions of the Nigerian Constitution which protect the rights

²⁴¹ Marian Roberts, *Mediation in Family Disputes – Principles of Practice* (3rd edn, Ashgate Publishing Limited 2008) 37.

²⁴² Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights of Women in Africa is an international human rights instrument established by the African Union which came into effect in 2005 to protect the rights of African women.

²⁴³ Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights on the Rights of Women in Africa (Maputo Protocol) Article 8.

of women in accordance with international laws will be highlighted. Access to justice as stated in the previous chapter is as a result of the understanding of the legal consciousness of the people. To understand how the legal consciousness of women in Nigeria is influenced by their access to justice, this study highlights the work of Federación Internacional de Abogadas (FIDA)²⁴⁴ as an NGO in sensitising women on their rights.

The objective of this chapter is to illustrate how laws, both national and international, impact on the gap of women's rights in accessing justice, particularly in Nigeria. The purpose for examining international laws is to understand the relevance and how much of international laws are domesticated in national laws, as will be considered in the provisions of laws such as the *Violence Against Persons Prohibitions (VAPP) Act of 2015*.²⁴⁵ Specifically, this chapter highlights the fact that, although laws exist at various levels, the rights of women are not protected, and women continue to be failed by the laws which should protect them.

As part of this chapter, the cultural aspects of Nigeria will be explored as it affects women's access to justice. The argument being that Nigerian legal system is influenced by various aspects of culture and tradition, as well as religion, foreign rule, and laws etc. This chapter highlights how despite the range of laws in place, women are denied access to justice in Nigeria, which questions the ability of the law itself to address the needs of women in Nigeria. This further invites the question of whether the challenges faced by Nigerian women in accessing justice, is because of lack of enforcement of the plethora of laws in existence.

²⁴⁴ Federación Internacional de Abogadas – International Federation of Women Lawyers
<https://www.devex.com/organizations/international-federation-of-women-lawyers-fida-nigeria> (Accessed 17/02/2023).

²⁴⁵ The VAPP Act is the Violence Against Persons Prohibitions Act which is the domestication of international convention of laws on domestic violence against persons.

This study seeks to understand the mystery behind the challenges of access to justice by women in Nigeria and the factors which contribute to this position. There are factors which plague Nigerian women in the bid to access justice, and this study will not be complete without capturing these issues.

In answering the questions of this research, the evidence collected from the data analysis from the survey and interviews as well as the wealth of experience of the researcher in practice as a mediator in family disputes will be discussed. Although before focusing on the challenges Nigerian women encounter in accessing justice, a brief look at the international perspective on feminism and the position of women in the western world is necessary.

4.2 Women's Access to Justice as a Fundamental Right and Instrument of Rule of Law

History has shown that women who are seen as vulnerable members of society (even in times of war), have a unique place universally in mankind. Writers like Thompson²⁴⁶ are of the opinion that Women's rights are human rights hence their recognition in the provisions of the United Nations programs such as the Commission on the Status of Women which is held every year in New York at the United Nations Buildings and its environs.²⁴⁷ The rights of women are universal as they are human rights and should consequently be protected by the law as contained in the provisions of the **Universal Declaration of Human Rights**. The researcher agrees with Bachiochi's view that women as human beings have rights and proceeds further to state that women's rights are natural rights and consequently should be protected by law.²⁴⁸ The difference in the importance attached to women's rights resides in the value placed on

²⁴⁶ Karen Brown Thompson, 'Women's Rights are Human Rights - Restructuring World Politics' [2002] 14 *Transnational Social Movement, Network, and Norms*, 97.

²⁴⁷ Commission on the Status of Women (CSW) <https://www.unwomen.org/en/csw> (Accessed 01 May 2023).

²⁴⁸ Erika Bachiochi, *The Rights of Women: A Natural Law Approach* (Ethics and Public Policy Centre, January 2, 2024) <https://eppc.org/publication/the-rights-of-women-a-natural-law-approach/> (Accessed 29 April 2024).

these rights by different society based on cultural or ethnic orientation. But society places women in categories based on the roles assigned to them as daughters, sisters, wives, mothers, and any role it decides to assign to women. The rights of women should be protected by the law as human beings and not based on the roles, duties, and expectations of society. Based on the challenges women encounter in the protection of their rights as evidenced in the enactment of the various laws on women, it is not out of place to state that women deserve equal if not more access to justice to address the different forms of injustice they encounter daily. Women's rights and struggles are universal, but the challenges could vary as a result of different factors such as religion, culture, etc.

Though in western countries such as the UK, and USA, the challenges women encounter might differ from the challenges of women in Ghana, South Africa, and Nigeria, particularly in the cultural aspects. The struggles women have encountered are from generation to generation in different aspects of life, whether in the workplace, in marriage, in matters of rights of inheritance, widowhood practices, access to reproductive preferences, and right to property are universal. The rule of law should be the refuge and the weapon through which women overcome the struggles for justice but, the reverse is the case.²⁴⁹ Patriarchal structures and institutions in the society have been quoted as been responsible for the weakness of the rule of law to function effectively in women's access to justice.²⁵⁰ Women are judged by the role assigned to them by society. For example, the evidence of the widow who was evicted from her matrimonial home by her in-laws without any properties at the demise of her husband because she did not give birth to children in the marriage.²⁵¹

²⁴⁹ The Elders, *Strengthening the Rule of Law to Protect Women's Rights and Access to Justice* (Access to Justice Policy Paper, 2022) 8 <https://theelders.org/sites/default/files/newsarticledocument/The-Elders-Access-to-Justice-for-Women-and-the-Rule-of-Law.pdf> (Accessed 26 April 2023).

²⁵⁰ Ibid.

²⁵¹ FIDA Anambra State Incident Report, 13th January 2022.

The different ways in which the rule of law is weakened has been highlighted by the Elders²⁵² as through discriminatory laws, inaccessible justice systems, and discrimination in the application of laws. Some of these discriminatory laws affect women's right to work. In some establishments, women who are married are not employed as they would need time off for maternity leave, child-care, be expected to work late after office hours, if necessary, travel on official trips with little or no notice, etc. The World Bank is of the opinion that social protection such as health insurance, and paid sick leave are attached to permanent employment which is not available to women on a temporary basis, is a limitation to the rule of law.²⁵³ These discriminatory laws discourage women from gainful employment which restricts economic power and hinders their access to justice.

Data statistics worldwide show that women earn 77 cents for every dollar earned by men and the gap widens for mothers.²⁵⁴ Women who have children suffer the motherhood penalty. In South Asia the gender pay gap for women with children is 35% and in Sub-Saharan Africa its 31% when compared to 14% and 4% of women without children.²⁵⁵ Women who are immigrants or whose race or ethnicity makes them a minority in the country they live in, also suffer from this discrimination. Some discriminatory practices which affect the rule of law on women's access to justice originate from customs and traditions.

²⁵² The Elders- A group of independent leaders formed by Nelson Mandela in 2007 who contribute to world peace, human rights and justice through their wealth of experience.

²⁵³ World Bank (Women, Business, and the Law, 2021)
<https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/bitstream/handle/10986/35094/9781464816529.pdf> (Accessed 26 April 2023).

²⁵⁴ UN Women (Women in the changing world of work, 2020)
<https://interactive.unwomen.org/multimedia/infographic/changingworldofwork/en/index.html> (Accessed 27 April 2023).

²⁵⁵ Ibid.

It is important for societies to ensure that their laws do not contravene the provisions of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW).²⁵⁶ Most of the traditional practices which infringe on the rights of women such as Female Genital Mutilation (FGM)²⁵⁷ are discriminatory against women and girls and violate the provisions of international conventions on human rights. Discrimination in the application of laws also affects women's access to justice and the rule of law. Women are discouraged from reporting cases of gender base violence to authorities where no penalty is awarded to the perpetrator based on the response of the police.²⁵⁸ The manner in which the parastatal of government responds in the application of laws affects women's access to justice.

As this study is focused on family mediation, women's access to justice and the rule of law is considered from the mediation process. ADR²⁵⁹ and other justice dispensing mechanisms such as the courts, are the channels through which the injustice to women's rights can be addressed and rectified. Some of the inhibitions which plague and limit women's access to justice reside in customs and tradition of a community. There are contentions that for ADR, (of which mediation is a part of) to be effective for marginalised groups or persons like women, certain customs and cultural inhibitions have to be addressed to ensure access to justice.²⁶⁰

It is important to recognise the challenges women encounter daily in seeking justice especially in the family environment which should not be hindered by formal procedures. It has been

²⁵⁶ CEDAW is an international convention to which member nations are signatories.

²⁵⁷ Female Genital Mutilation a cultural practice for women.

²⁵⁸ The Elders, *Strengthening the Rule of Law to Protect Women's Rights and Access to Justice* (Access to Justice Policy Paper, 2022) 8 <https://theelders.org/sites/default/files/newsarticledocument/The-Elders-Access-to-Justice-for-Women-and-the-Rule-of-Law.pdf> (Accessed 27 April 2023).

²⁵⁹ ADR- Alternative Dispute Resolution.

²⁶⁰ Kwadwo Appiagyei- Atua, 'Alternative Dispute Resolution and Its Implication for Women's Access to Justice in Africa – Case Study of Ghana', (2013) 1(1) *Frontier of Legal Research* 41.

contended that the adoption of ADR processes without taking into cognisance the foundational issues which form a major part of notions and biases in a community hinders the process of promoting access to justice for women.²⁶¹ It is necessary to examine the different cultural situations which affect the effective dispensation of access to justice for women through mediation, especially in the family when there is a dispute. These cultural situations affect the rule of law and will be discussed in the following chapters.

Women all over the world are confronted with the same type of challenges when it comes to enforcing their rights and welfare. There are various factors which contribute to the access of justice by women. Some of these factors are based on the orientation the women have which has been influenced by their environment. Literature has identified the following factors as contributors to the environment which influence women's decisions in the access of justice in matters of family disputes:

- Social Factors
- Economic factors
- Health factors
- Legal factors

The above factors when broken down, can be summarised in the following issues when examined in reality as factors which affect women's access to justice:

Cultural and traditional issues- In some African traditional societies it is considered a waste of time and resources to formally educate a girlchild.²⁶² Custom and traditional beliefs expect the role of women to revolve round the home and procuring a formal education is not viewed

²⁶¹ Ibid.

²⁶² Stella Patrick Essien, 'Feminism in Culture and Religion' (2020) 8(5) World Journal of Innovative Research 30 at 31.

as a necessity. This becomes a challenge in the access of justice where the woman is uneducated and does not understand the process which is available when her rights are being abused.

Domestic violence issues – Domestic violence is a major factor in the abuse of women’s rights as has been written by many Nigerian authors such as Professor Ine Nnadi. The barrier as access to justice for women remains the refusal of women to speak about it especially in public. Research done in 2003 in Ibadan, Lagos State, Nigeria showed that 40% of urban woman were victims of domestic violence and had accepted it as part of the marriage.²⁶³ This will be expanded on further in Chapter Six of this thesis.

Early marriage – This form of barrier to women’s access to justice is widely practised despite the inhuman affliction on the girlchild. Early marriage in young girls appears to be supported by the Islamic faith as was witnessed in the case of Hawa Abubakar, a 9year-old girl who was married to Mallam Shehu Garuba Kiruwa, a 40year old man because her father owed him some money.²⁶⁴ Hawa ran away twice and was brought back forcefully to her husband who used a poisoned cutlass to cut off both her legs. Though in reaction to the heinous act, the Government of Bauchi State (Nigeria where it happened), enacted a decree which made it illegal to withdraw children from school for marriage purposes. Another case was the popular one involving one of Nigeria’s politicians, Senator Yerima (also from northern Nigeria) who took a 13year old girl from Egypt, as a bride.²⁶⁵ This contravened the Child’s Rights Act²⁶⁶ of Nigeria for which the minimum age for marriage is 16 years and the Egyptian law requirement minimum age is 18 years.²⁶⁷ His reason was his religion allows him to do so.

²⁶³ Morolake O. McDonnel, *Gender Inequality in Nigeria, Ibadan* (Spectrum Books Ltd, 2003) 10.

²⁶⁴ Ine Nnadi, ‘Early Marriage: A Gender Base Violence and a Violation of Women’s Human Rights in Nigeria’ (2014) 7(3) *Journal of Politics and Law* 36.

²⁶⁵ *Ibid.*

²⁶⁶ Child’s Rights Act of 2003.

²⁶⁷ Umar Alkali, and others “Nature and Sources of Nigerian Legal System: An Exorcism of a Wrong Notion” (2014) 5(4) *International Journal of Business, Economics and Law* 3.

Financial challenges – Poverty has been highlighted as one of the major barriers to women’s access to justice and Soetan²⁶⁸ explained how African women are handicapped by financial challenges. Women who lack empowerment will find it difficult to pursue the enforcement of their rights.

Fear of stigmatization- The fear of being stigmatised for a wrong that has been perpetrated against a woman is another form of barrier to access to justice. Victims who have been raped have a distinct fear of being stigmatised, even by family members and will prefer to be silent than risk stigma by reporting the crime. This position was stated by Bazza when she highlighted in her article that majority of rape cases go unreported because of the social stigma attached to it and the burden of proof which requires corroborated testimony.²⁶⁹

Lack of education and awareness of human rights - The lack of education is a major factor which hinders women’s access to justice. If women are not literate, they would be unable to understand availability of the provisions of the law when their rights are being abused. In line with the United Nations SDGs, education is highlighted as one of its recommendations for promoting women’s access to justice.²⁷⁰ Access to justice and the application of the rule of law is universal to women worldwide. This research will discuss the above factors in detail in the following chapters. In the following section we will consider the impact of international conventions as it affects Nigerian women’s access to justice and rule of law.

4.3. International Laws on Women’s Rights and the Role of International Conventions:

²⁶⁸ Funmi Soetan, ‘The Economic Empowerment of Nigerian women; Some determinants of access to resources’ (1999) 27 *Journal of African Economic History* 117- 135.

²⁶⁹ Hadiza Iza Bazza, ‘Domestic Violence and Women’s Rights in Nigeria’ (2009) 4 *Journal of Societies Without Borders*, 175 especially at 181.

²⁷⁰ OECD, ‘Delivering- Access-to-justice’ [2016] 12 <https://www.oecd.org>. (Accessed 20 September 2023).

The International Justice Resource Centre in its publications supports the view that women's rights are human rights and should be protected by the international conventions by stating that "*Women are entitled to enjoy the same human rights and fundamental freedoms as other individuals. International human rights treaties require State parties to take proactive steps to ensure that women's human rights are respected by law and to eliminate discrimination, inequalities, and practices that negatively affect women's rights*".²⁷¹

This position is supported by the researcher in executing this study as women who as human beings, are entitled to the equal protection of their rights as well as the enjoyment of those rights.

Consequently, this study examines the following conventions which were adopted by member states of the United Nations for the promotion of the rights of women.

United Nations Charter of 1945: The United Nations Charter was signed on the 26th of June 1945 but had been adopted as the "Declaration of the United Nations" on the 1st of January 1942 in Washington.²⁷² The United Nations Charter is an agreement of countries which have come together to support the protection of human rights including women's rights amongst other goals. The aim was to reaffirm the fundamental human rights, promote dignity and equal rights of men and women without discrimination as to gender, religion, sex, language.²⁷³ The Charter mandates its member States to uphold international law and maintain international peace and security, and addresses health, social, economic, and other related matters of its member States. Human rights are matters that occur traditionally between the State and the individual and for international laws and conventions to apply in the jurisdiction of member

²⁷¹ International Justice Resource Center, <https://ijrcenter.org/thematic-research-guides/womens-human-rights/> (Accessed 29 April 2024).

²⁷² <https://www.archives.gov/milestone-documents/united-nations-charter> (Accessed 20 September 2021).

²⁷³ www.lawtimesjournal.in/international-convention-women (Accessed 23 September 2021).

States, the laws must be ratified and domesticated. Critics²⁷⁴ have questioned the usefulness or otherwise of the United Nations Charter especially in matters where human rights violations would occur in member States and there would be confusion as to how to proceed. In relation to Nigeria, fundamental human rights are provided for in **Chapter IV** of the **1999 Constitution** of the Federal Republic of Nigeria.²⁷⁵ The 1999 Constitution was modelled after the United Nations Charter in the protection of human rights which includes the rights of Nigerian women. *Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR)*: This resolution was adopted in 1948 and proclaimed that all human beings are born free and have equal rights which should not be discriminated against on basis of sex.²⁷⁶ It was recognised that gender equality was essential and express provision necessary for women²⁷⁷ because of the widespread human rights violations being perpetrated against women. The Global Citizenship Commission acknowledged the need to read the UDHR in a manner that highlights the activities that are gender blind.²⁷⁸ It was necessary to highlight the importance of gender blindness to stop the violations against women and give equal opportunity to women. This convention is to strengthen further the position on the rights of women universally. In relation to this study, as it concerns Nigerian women, all women in Nigeria are born free and should not be discriminated against which is provided for in Section 42 of the 1999 Constitution.²⁷⁹

²⁷⁴ Thomas Weiss, *What's Wrong with The United Nations and How To Fix It* (3rd edn Polity Press, 2016) 55.

²⁷⁵ <https://www.lawglobalhub.com/constitution-of-nigeria-1999-2/> (Accessed 17 May 2023).

²⁷⁶ www.lawtimesjournal.in/international-convention-women (Accessed 23 September 2021).

²⁷⁷ Universal Declaration of Human Rights, Article 2.

²⁷⁸ Gordon Brown, *The Universal Declaration of Human Rights in the 21st Century: A Living Document In A Changing World* (2016) <https://www.openbookpublishers.com> (Accessed 26 October 2021).

²⁷⁹ Section 42(1) (a) provides; “ A citizen of Nigeria of a particular community, ethnic group, place of origin, sex, religion or political opinion shall not, by reason only that he is such a person be subject either expressly by or in the practical application of any law in force in Nigeria or any executive or administrative action of the government, to disabilities, or restrictions to which citizens of Nigeria of other communities, ethnic groups, places of origin, sex, religion, political opinions are not made subject to;” <https://www.lawglobalhub.com/constitution-of-nigeria-1999-2/> (Accessed 17 May 2023).

Convention on the Political Rights of Women: This convention came into force on the 7th of July 1954 but had been adopted on the 20th of December 1952.²⁸⁰ The Convention was a recommendable step after World War II and was adopted to provide equal political rights to women as was attributed to the men. This major step was taken in furtherance of the provisions of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights that all people have the right to participate in the government of their country either directly or through chosen representatives and have equal access to public services.²⁸¹ The United Nations Commission on the Status of Women had conducted a survey on the political status of women in its member States and the responses gave rise to the Convention which was adopted by the General assembly of the United Nations at its 409th plenary meeting. In relation to this study, the Nigerian Constitution makes provision for the political rights of women in Section 42 of the 1999 Constitution.²⁸²

*Convention on Consent to Marriage, Minimum Age for Marriage and Registration of Marriages.*²⁸³ This treaty came into force on the 9th of December 1964 and the aim is to promote the respect for human rights universally without discrimination as to sex, race, religion or language in accordance with the United Nations Charter. The provisions of the Convention cover a jurisdiction of freedom of consent of both parties before entering the marriage, the specification of the minimum age for marriage for both genders and the compulsory registration of marriages. This Convention is in furtherance of **Article 16** of the **Universal Declaration of Human Rights** which states that “(1) men and women of full age, without any limitation due to race, nationality or religion, have the right to marry and to found a family.

²⁸⁰ www.lawtimesjournal.in/international-convention-women (Accessed 23 September 2021).

²⁸¹ Universal Declaration of Human Rights, Article 21
https://www.ohchr.org/en/udhr/documents/udhr_translations/eng.pdf (Accessed 26 October 2021).

²⁸² <http://lawsofnigeria.placng.org/laws/C50.pdf> (Accessed 17/01/2022).

²⁸³ www.lawtimesjournal.in/international-convention-women (Accessed 23 September 2021).

*They are entitled to equal rights as to marriage, during marriage, and at its dissolution. (2) Marriage shall be entered into only with the free and full consent of the intending spouses ”.*²⁸⁴

Some scholars are of the view that this Convention is an achievement in human rights and has set an international standard in the advancement of women especially in Asia and Africa.²⁸⁵

Convention on Consent to Marriage, Minimum Age for Marriage and Registration of Marriages came into existence as a result of the actions of the United Nations Commission of the Status of Women. The Commission supported the incorporation of the general principle that each member State stipulates the minimum age of marriage for their citizens to address the challenge of a uniform age of marriage.²⁸⁶ Different State Parties in adopting the Convention made provisions for amendments in their legislation and withheld ratification of the convention in their jurisdictions as was the case in India as illustrated by the report of the delegation during one of its sessions.²⁸⁷ The delegate from India had stated that India was a multi-religious and multi-racial nation with different communities which are regulated by different traditional laws and legislative enactments to which the Convention would impose its obligations.²⁸⁸ The difficulties in implementing the provisions of the Convention in India are depicted in the provisions of the different legislation on the consent of marriage in India. *Hindu Marriage Act*

²⁸⁴ UN General Assembly, *Convention on Consent to Marriage, Minimum Age for Marriage and Registration of Marriages*, 7 November 1962 <https://www.refworld.org/docid/456d89064.html> (Accessed 26 October 2021).

²⁸⁵ Professor B Sivaramayya, ‘Convention On Consent To Marriage, Minimum Age For Marriage And Registration Of Marriages 1962, With Special Reference To India’ (1966) 8(3) *Journal of the India Law Institute* 402.

²⁸⁶ *Ibid.*

²⁸⁷ Res. 821 IIIA(XXXII), U.N. Eco. Soc. Council Ojj. Rec., 32nd Sess., Supplementary No. 1 (E/ AC7 1 SR43) (1961) <https://www.jstor.org/stable/pdf/43949910> (Accessed 26th October 2021).

²⁸⁸ Professor B Sivaramayya, ‘Convention on Consent to Marriage, Minimum Age for Marriage and Registration of Marriages 1962, With Special Reference to India’ (1966) 8 *Journal of the India Law Institute*, 3, 403.

1955,²⁸⁹ *Indian Christian Marriages Act 1872*,²⁹⁰ *Parsee Marriage and Divorce Act 1936*²⁹¹ which stipulate different ages for marriageable age and consent of guardian when the person is a minor. Critics have pointed out that the Convention is more of a “promotional” convention as it does not make provisions for non-compliance and places no obligations on member States to make provisions for its citizens who contravene the provisions of the convention.²⁹² There is a general agreement amongst member states that the mandatory requirement for the registration of marriages serves as a check on child marriages and proof of marriage.²⁹³ The Indian Constitution recognises the different tribes in India and their peculiarities as has been pointed out by Weber in his *Essays in Sociology*²⁹⁴ that as long as a tribe remains a tribe, it possesses a fixed tribal territory and this should be preserved as far as possible. In the writings of Sivaramayya, the position of India on the Convention appears to be conservative and laid back in its ratification and promotion of humane and social ideals and principles which are universal to the rest of the world.²⁹⁵ The writer submits that the usefulness of being a signatory to a Convention resides in the provisions of the Constitution not being in contravention of the Conventions, as long as it is in accordance with the reservations and territories.

²⁸⁹ Hindu Marriage Act 1955, Section 5, Clause (VI) provides 18years.

²⁹⁰ Indian Christian Marriage Act 1872, Section 60(3) stipulates 18years.

²⁹¹ Parsee Marriage and Divorce Act 1936, Section 3(3) stipulates 21years.

²⁹² Professor B Sivaramayya, ‘Convention on Consent to Marriage, Minimum Age for Marriage and Registration of Marriages 1962, With Special Reference to India’ (1966) 8(3) Journal of the India Law Institute 408 - 410.

²⁹³ Ibid.

²⁹⁴ Max Weber, *Essays in Sociology* 398 (Gerth and Mills eds. 1946); Professor B Sivaramayya, ‘Convention on Consent to Marriage, Minimum Age for Marriage and Registration of Marriages 1962, With Special Reference to India’ (1966) 8(3) Journal of the India Law Institute 411.

²⁹⁵ Professor B Sivaramayya, ‘Convention on Consent to Marriage, Minimum Age for Marriage and Registration of Marriages 1962, With Special Reference to India’ (1966) 8(3) Journal of the India Law Institute, 412.

International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR):²⁹⁶ The General Assembly of the United Nations adopted this resolution on the 16th of December 1966, but it came into force on the 23rd of March 1976.²⁹⁷ State parties to this Covenant are expected to observe and respect the civil and political rights of individuals, including the right to life, freedom of religion, freedom of speech, freedom of assembly, electoral rights, rights to due process and a fair trial. Parties undertake to ensure that men and women enjoy equal civil and political rights as set out in the treaty.²⁹⁸ The rights of women are further protected by the provisions of **Article 26** which provides that: “*All persons are equal before the law and are entitled without any discrimination to the equal protection of the law. In this respect, the law shall prohibit any discrimination and guarantee to all persons equal and effective protection against discrimination on any ground such as race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth, or other status.*” Over three quarters of the United Nations members are parties to the ICCPR²⁹⁹ and the expectation would be a high compliance and respect for civil and political rights in individual countries. Critics have questioned the effectiveness of these international human rights instruments and have stated that due to the weak monitoring systems, they appear to be more for promotional or social functions for the State Parties.³⁰⁰ Assertions made by the results of studies conducted by scholars suggest that the structures for implementation of the treaty are too weak and rely on the goodwill of the member State to

²⁹⁶ <https://www.ohchr.org/EN/ProfessionalInterest/Pages/CCPR.aspx> (Accessed 7 October 2021).

²⁹⁷ <https://www.equalityhumanrights.com/en/our-human-rights-work/monitoring-and-promoting-un-treaties/international-covenant-civil> (Accessed 8 October 2021).

²⁹⁸ International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, Article 3.

²⁹⁹ Linda Camp Keith, ‘The United Nations International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights: Does It Make a Difference in Human Rights Behaviour?’ (1999) 36(1) *Journal of Peace Research* 95.

³⁰⁰ Jack Donnelly, *Universal Human Rights in Theory and Practice* (Cornell University Press, 1989) 36.

effect the change in the human rights attitude.³⁰¹ These same studies reveal that States may genuinely intend to honour their commitments to the covenant but domestic situation such as a civil unrest could interfere with their willingness to abide by their commitment. The ICCPR is not domesticated in Nigeria in accordance with the provisions of the Constitution, but it is enshrined in the provisions of Chapter IV of the Nigerian Constitution. *Section 42* of the *1999 Constitution* makes provision for the protection of women's political rights in Nigeria.³⁰²

Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW).³⁰³

This resolution was adopted by the General Assembly of the United Nations on the 18th of December 1979.³⁰⁴ The purpose of this Convention is to promote equal status between women and men and discourages all forms of discrimination. The Convention was as a result of over 30 years of work by the United Nations Commission on the Status of Women which was established in 1946 to assess the situation of women as well as promote women's rights.³⁰⁵ The Convention has served as a guide to member States to illuminate areas where women have been denied equality with men and the work of the Commission on the Status of Women has led to the existence of several declarations and treaties. There have been reservations as to the implementation of the provisions of the Convention by the member States. Being a signatory to the treaty and domesticating the law to be applicable by State Parties are separate situations as was highlighted in a critique on the domestication of CEDAW by member States. Critics have stated that where countries fail to domesticate CEDAW to make it applicable in their

³⁰¹ Linda Camp Keith, 'The United Nations International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights: Does It Make a Difference in Human Rights Behaviour?' (1999) 36(1) *Journal of Peace Research* 112.

³⁰² <https://laws.lawnigeria.com/2018/03/26/center-for-laws-of-nigeria/> (Accessed 17 May 2023).

³⁰³ www.lawtimesjournal.in/international-convention-women (Accessed 3 October 2021).

³⁰⁴ <https://www.un.org/womenwatch/daw/cedaw/history> (Accessed 3 October 2021).

³⁰⁵ <https://www.ohchr.org/en/professionalinterest/pages/cedaw> (Accessed 28 October 2021).

jurisdiction, they are merely paying “lip service” to the Convention.³⁰⁶ How effective a treaty is, lies in the behavioural pattern of the way of life of the member States. The provisions of CEDAW on the elimination of discriminatory practices against women are provided in Chapter IV of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria.³⁰⁷ This provision protects women’s rights and ensures access to justice.

Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women:³⁰⁸ This resolution was reached on the 20th of December 1993 and is seen to be complementary to the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women as they share the same principles. The distinction between the *Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women* and the *Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women* lies in the emphasis of violence. One of the objectives of this treaty is the acknowledgement that violence against women requires state intervention. The General Assembly of the United Nation made this proclamation in resolution 48/104 of 20th December 1993 recognising the necessity for the universal application to women, the rights and principles of equality, security, liberty, integrity, and dignity of all human beings.³⁰⁹ The different international instruments provide for the universal human rights, but the *Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women* particularly recognises violence as a universal abuse to the rights of women, irrespective of where it occurs whether in private (domestic violence) or in public. Regrettably authors have stated that despite the existence of this Convention and the domestication in member states including promulgating legislation to combat violence to women, domestic violence persists in

³⁰⁶ Ifemeje Sylvia Chika and Umejiaku Nneka, “Discriminatory Cultural Practices and Women’s Rights Among the Igbos of South-East Nigeria: A Critique” (2014) 25 *Journal of Law, Policy, and Globalization*, 24.

³⁰⁷ <https://constitution.lawnigeria.com> (Accessed 25 October 2021).

³⁰⁸ www.lawtimesjournal.in/international-convention-women (Accessed 3 October 2021).

³⁰⁹ <https://www.ohchr.org/en/professionalinterest/pages/violenceagainstwomen>. (Accessed 28 October 2021).

most countries, largely due to unequal power relations between men and women as a result of patriarchal inclinations of society.³¹⁰

Other regional legislation which protects women’s rights include, but are not limited to the following:

African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights (Banjul Charter).³¹¹ The Banjul Charter came into existence after so much difficulty and tension amongst the African nations and was finally adopted by the then OAU³¹² Assembly on the 28th of June 1981 in Nairobi, Kenya. The Charter came into force on the 21st of October 1986 after being ratified by an absolute majority of the member States of the OAU. The Charter set out to put an end to human violations in Africa and promotion of human rights. *Article 18(3)*³¹³ ensures the elimination of every form of discrimination against women and ensures the protection of the rights of women and children as provided by international human rights declarations. The entire provision of Article 18 provides for the protection of the family and vulnerable groups.

Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights on the Rights of Women in Africa (Maputo Protocol).³¹⁴ This protocol was adopted by the African Union in 2003 but came into effect in 2005 in Maputo, Mozambique. It is an international human tool which guarantees comprehensive rights to women including protection of their reproductive rights especially in Africa. An illustration of some of the provisions is contained in *Article 8* which states:

“Access to Justice and Equal Protection before the Law

³¹⁰ Ine Nnadi, ‘An Insight into Violence against Women as Human Rights Violation in Nigeria: A Critique’ (2012) 5(3) *Journal of Politics and Law* 67.

³¹¹ <https://www.achpr.org/legalinstruments> (Accessed 7th October 2021).

³¹² Organisation of African Unity.

³¹³ <https://www.achpr.org/legalinstruments> (Accessed 7th October 2021).

³¹⁴ https://www.achpr.org/public/Document/file/English/achpr_instr_proto_women_eng.pdf (Accessed 7th October 2021).

Women and men are equal before the law and shall have the right to equal protection and benefit of the law. States Parties shall take all appropriate measures to ensure:

a) effective access by women to judicial and legal services, including legal aid:

b) support to local, national, regional, and continental initiatives directed at providing women access to legal services, including Legal aid:

c) the establishment of adequate educational and other appropriate structures with particular attention to women and to sensitise everyone to the rights of women;”

*American Convention on Human Rights:*³¹⁵ was adopted at the Inter-American Specialized Conference on Human Rights in San José, Costa Rica, on the 22nd of November 1969. The objective of the Convention is to ensure that State Parties who are members respect the rights and freedoms of all persons without discrimination as to race, colour, religion, political, sex, economic or social status. This Convention also stipulates amongst its provisions that all forms of slave trade or trafficking in women are prohibited.³¹⁶

*Arab Charter on Human Rights:*³¹⁷ The League of Arab States had adopted the first version of the Arab Charter on Human Rights in 1994 during its 50th anniversary to demonstrate its respect for human rights.³¹⁸ State Parties to the Charter undertake to ensure that individuals within their

³¹⁵ https://www.cartercenter.org/resources/pdfs/peace/democracy/des/amer_conv_human_rights.pdf (Accessed 8th October 2021).

³¹⁶ American Convention on Human Rights, Article 6
https://www.cartercenter.org/resources/pdfs/peace/democracy/des/amer_conv_human_rights.pdf (Accessed 9th October 2021).

³¹⁷ https://www.eods.eu/library/LAS_Arab%20Charter%20on%20Human%20Rights_2004_EN.pdf (Accessed 9th October 2021).

³¹⁸ Susan Akram, ‘Arab Charter on Human Rights 2004’ (2006) 24 Boston University International Law Journal, 147.

territory and subject to their jurisdiction, enjoy the right to freedom and all rights recognized herein, without any discrimination on grounds of race, colour, sex, religion, language, national or social origin, opinion or thought. It also recognises the equality in human dignity of men and women in rights and duties with positive discrimination in favour of women by Islamic Shari'a laws, international instruments, and other legislation.³¹⁹

European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (Article 14):³²⁰ This provision prohibits the discrimination of the enjoyment of rights set out in the Convention on grounds of sex, race, colour, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, association with a national minority, property, birth, or other status.

Council of Europe Convention on Preventing and Combating Violence against Women and Domestic Violence (Istanbul Convention):³²¹ The aim of this is the creation of a legal framework in addressing violence against women and focuses on the prevention of domestic violence, protection of victims and the prosecution of accused culprits in its member states.

All the above-mentioned laws have been replicated in the different provisions of the laws of the Nigerian legislation.³²² This is relevant in this study to appreciate the volume of laws in existence for the protection of women's rights, universally and particularly in Nigeria. Where then lies the challenges in access to justice?

4.4 The Impact of International Conventions on Cultural Practices in Nigeria

Nigeria has adopted some international conventions as part of her laws in the promotion of the rights of women. Some of these Conventions have been mentioned earlier on in this chapter

³¹⁹ Arab Charter on Human Rights, Article 3(3).

³²⁰ Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (As amended by Protocols No 11 and 14) Council of Europe, European Treaty Series- No. 5
https://www.eods.eu/library/CoE_European%20Convention (Accessed 11th October 2021).

³²¹ <https://www.coe.int/en/web/gender-matters/council-of-europe-convention-on-preventing-and-combating-violence-against-women-and-domestic-violence> (Accessed 11th October 2021).

³²² Chapter IV of the 1999 Constitution and other federal laws such as the VAPP Act of 2015.

such as the *Convention on the Elimination of all Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) 1979* which was ratified by Nigeria in 1991.³²³ Others include the *Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR)* which was adopted in 1948, the *African Charter on Human and Peoples Rights* in 1986 which was also ratified and domesticated, the *Convention on the Rights of the Child* was adopted in 1989 and ratified by Nigeria in 1992 (Child's Rights are sometimes associated with women's rights during discussions as the most vulnerable in society) and the *Protocol to the African Charter on the Rights of Women in Africa (Maputo Protocol)* in 2003.³²⁴

Feminist scholars have criticised the adoption of international laws and conventions in the Nigerian Constitution stating that in the face of traditions and customs of everyday reality, the laws are not adhered to or complied with. A perfect example as argued by Aduba in her writing, "A Critique on Some Aspects of the Law Relating to the Dissolution of Marriage"³²⁵ that payment and refund of bride price of a customary law marriage portrays a commercial picture of the woman being transacted for. The writer argues that this process negates the provisions of Sections 34 and 42 of the *1999 Nigerian Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria* which provide for the respect of dignity of persons and freedom from all forms of discrimination. The writer is of the view that it is hardship and oppressive to expect the woman to refund the bride price of a failed marriage especially if the marriage has lasted for a long duration and rather canvasses that in the event of a divorce, the women, should be compensated by their husbands. Though this position is provided for marriages under the Act but sadly lacking when it concerns customary marriages as the woman leaves the home with nothing if

³²³ Agbonika J. Alewo and Matthew A. Olong, 'Cultural Practices and Traditional Beliefs as Impediments to the Enjoyment of Women's Rights in Nigeria' (2012) 1(1) *International Law Research* 135.

³²⁴ *Ibid.*

³²⁵ Nnamdi Aduba, 'A Critique on Some Aspects Of the Law Relating To The Dissolution Of Marriage' [1991] *Abia State University Law Journal* 66.

the marriage breaks down. The impact of the international convention on the protection of women's rights and dignity appears to be a slow unending uphill task when it comes to customs and traditions.

As a signatory to CEDAW and other international conventions to which Nigeria belongs, it is expected to adhere to the provisions of the Conventions to which some of its indigenous practices are contrary to. It is therefore worthy of mention when the Nigerian judiciary acknowledges the significance of international Conventions in dispensing justice as was the situation in the case of *Mojekwu v. Mojekwu*³²⁶ wherein the Court of Appeal in person of Niki Tobi JCA, (as he then was) in his leading judgment gave credence to CEDAW and made obsolete the Nnewi "Oi-Ekpe" custom of disinheriting a deceased man's biological daughter from inheriting her father's land and instead awarding the land to the uncle, a law that was repugnant to natural justice, equity, and good conscience.³²⁷ There are other violations of women's rights which contravene international Conventions such as Female Genital Mutilation (FGM)³²⁸ and the harm it does to women, harmful widowhood practices- forcing the widow to drink the water used in bathing the corpse to prove she was not responsible for the deceased's death³²⁹, and many more. It is disheartening for Nigeria to be a signatory to almost all the international treaties on the protection and empowerment of women with these harmful traditional practices still occurring at the rural settings.

³²⁶ *Mojekwu v. Mojekwu* (2000) 5 Nigeria Weekly Law Report (Pt. 657) 402.

³²⁷ Ifemeje Sylvia Chika and Umejiaku Nneka, 'Discriminatory Cultural Practices and Women's Rights Among the Igbos of South-East Nigeria: A Critique' (2014) 25 Journal of Law, Policy, and Globalization, 6.

³²⁸ Nahid Toubia, 'Female Genital Mutilation and the Responsibility of Reproductive Health Professionals' (1994) 46(2) International Journal of Gynaecology and Obstetrics 127-135.

³²⁹ Hadiza Iza Bazza, 'Domestic Violence and Women's Rights in Nigeria' (2009) 4 Journal of Societies Without Borders 175 at 183.

Further critics³³⁰ of the Nigerian laws have commented on how the law appears to make laws to protect women but takes away their human rights such the provisions of *Section 142 of the Criminal Procedure Code* where a woman cannot make a complaint in relation to offences under *Sections 387, 388 and 389* of the *Penal Code*.³³¹ The complaints must be made by her father, husband, or male guardian. An in-depth consideration of these international conventions and their impact on Nigerian women is necessary as part of this study to evaluate their relevance to Nigerian women. In analysing women's access to justice and the rule of law, the relevance of international conventions is necessary when contrasted with traditional practices.

4.5 Feminist Perspective on International Conventions

The school of feminist jurisprudence is of a diverse nature as no single voice can capture the totality of women's experience in the expression of their rights. Some feminist scholars are of the view that international law challenged the norms of the traditional law-making processes of independent States which is a consequence of decolonization.³³² The use of these non-traditional method of law-making process by the developing states have emphasised decision making through negotiation with the introduction of the "soft law" of the General Assembly resolutions of bodies such as the United Nations.³³³ The people for whom these laws are made need to be able to relate to the international laws and convention in their lifestyle.

³³⁰ Agbonika J. Alewo and Matthew A. Olong, 'Cultural Practices and Traditional Beliefs as Impediments to the Enjoyment of Women's Rights in Nigeria' (2012) 1(1) *International Law Research* 142.

³³¹ *Section 387* provides for adultery by a man, *Section 388* provides for adultery by a woman, while *Section 389* provides for enticing or taking away or detaining with criminal intent a married woman. <https://moj.jg.gov.ng/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/PENAL-CODE-LAW-compressed.pdf> (Accessed 19 May 2023).

³³² Hilary Charlesworth, Christine Chinkin and Shelley Wright, 'Feminist Approaches to International Law' (1991) 85(4) *American Journal of International Law* 613 at 616.

³³³ Christine Chinkin, 'The Challenge of Soft Law: Development and Change in International Law' (1989) 38(4) *International and Comparative law Quarterly* 850.

Feminist author Jayawardena in her book *Feminism and Nationalism in The Third World*³³⁴ has posited in her writings that international law has shown little concern to the “different voices” of women in developing nations. The argument of this feminist perspective is that the decision-making processes and power structures are exclusive of women just as it is in the societies and women continue to remain worse off at the receiving end.³³⁵ The feminist authors postulated in their criticism of international laws, the lack of proper consideration of the reality in adopting these laws and how women’s rights will be impacted upon. The argument of writers such as Enloe centres on the contributions women make to the different sectors of the economy and should consequently be more involved in the decision-making process.³³⁶

Critics of international law in relation to women’s rights profess the differences in the various regions should be considered when adopting international practices. A clear example is the distinction between the ideologies of the western women and the non-western women as to what is perceived as promoting women’s rights. Bulbeck illustrated this theory in a paper she delivered at the University of Melbourne during a women’s conference, “Hearing the Difference: First and Third World Feminism”³³⁷ where she stated that the demand by western feminists for women to be treated equally as men in every way physically possible, is of less significance to non-western women for example in the area of a woman’s right to abortion. For the western women the right to have an abortion is her choice to make which makes her rights equal to that of a man. For a non-western woman, this expression of her rights holds a

³³⁴ (1986) <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2203269> (Accessed 23 October 2021).

³³⁵ Cynthia Enloe, ‘Making Sense of International Politics: Bananas, Beaches and Bases’ (1989) 53(1) *Journal of Politics* 290.

³³⁶ *Ibid.*

³³⁷ Chilla Bulbeck, ‘Hearing the Difference: First and Third World Feminism’ (1991) 15(1) *Asian Studies Review* 77.

different significance. To many Third World women this population control programs would deny them the chance of having the number of children they desire.

Another example of the differences between the First and Third World feminist is on the issue of female genital mutilation (FGM). In some cultures, FGM is seen as a ceremony of honour and a woman's transition to womanhood and the fight for the abolition would be resisted by some communities. The perspective of the international feminist is to rethink the principles of international law which exclude most of women's voices on certain issues. The criticism of the feminist writers finds its roots in the reservations State parties make in signing international conventions. For instance, the case of Egypt which made a general reservation to *Article 2 of the Women's Convention of the Multilateral Treaties Deposited With the Secretary General*³³⁸ which condemns all forms of discrimination against women, stating that "Egypt is willing to comply with the content of this article provided such compliance does not run counter to Islamic sharia".³³⁹ Egypt proceeded with a particular reservation to *Article 16* to the same Convention which mandates parties to eliminate all forms of discrimination against women in marriage but under the provisions of sharia law a man pays a bridal price during the marriage and maintains family relations with his wife and takes care of her during the marriage, on dissolution, the husband also makes a payment, but the woman is not permitted that right of divorce payment. Most states make reservations based on their religious and cultural practices and the United Nations are aware of these reservations hence the provisions in the conventions. These reservations by member states weaken the implementation of international conventions

³³⁸ Multilateral Treaties Deposited with the Secretary General, Status as at 31st December 1989, at 170 – 179, UN Doc. ST/LEG/SER.E/8 (1990) <https://www.equalityhumanrights.com/en/our-human-rights-work/monitoring-and-promoting-un-treaties/international-covenant-civil> (Accessed 8/10/2021).

³³⁹ Hilary Charlesworth and Christine Chinkin and Shelley Wright, 'Feminist Approaches To International Law' (1991) 85(4) *American Journal of International Law* 613 at 633.

and give an impression of a ‘toothless bulldog’ as reiterated by Matshega³⁴⁰ who stated that failure of African governments to abide by the international conventions to which they were signatories, when human rights violations occurred in their countries, weakened the conventions.

In the 1986 meeting, members of the CEDAW Committee who monitor the implementation of the Convention but do not have the authority and jurisdiction to determine the level of compatibility of reservations of member states, in complying with the Convention requested the Secretary General to seek the views of the representatives of member states.³⁴¹ This was in furtherance of assessing the compliance of member states with the Convention. From the perspectives of the feminist writers, it appears the international community is willing to acknowledge that there are particular challenges faced by women which border on inequality issues, but the individual states are not willing to fully commit to making the necessary changes which would alter their patriarchal philosophies of women being subordinate to men. It is the view of the critics that the limited scope of the Convention is restricted by the accommodating attitude and general tolerance of the international community of the reservations of state parties.³⁴²

Another criticism of the international conventions is the view supported by scholars that the *Universal Declaration of Human Rights* is fashioned after western ideals and philosophies and consequently are not tailored for all the “peoples” of the universe as it professes hence the numerous reservations.³⁴³ Contemporary debates have arisen as to the universality of human

³⁴⁰ James Matsheka, ‘Toothless Bulldogs? The Human Rights Commissions of Uganda and South Africa: a comparative study of their independence’ (2002) 2(1) African Human Rights Journal 68.

³⁴¹ Hilary Charlesworth and Christine Chinkin and Shelley Wright, ‘Feminist Approaches to International Law’ (1991) 85(4) American Journal of International Law 633 -634.

³⁴² Ibid.

³⁴³ Susan Waltz, ‘Reclaiming and rebuilding the history of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights’ (2002) 23(3) Third World Quarterly.

rights, whether international human rights standards would be amenable with the different world cultures. Evidence of this disconnect is clearly seen when human right violations by international standards, occur in a state which is signatory to the international conventions on human rights, but the State fails to prosecute the offenders as was the case in Nigeria when a Senator married a 13year old girl on the basis of culture and religion.³⁴⁴ This contravened the *Child's Right Act of 2003* which prohibited child marriage.³⁴⁵ Despite the penalty provision in *Section 23(a)* which provides;

“A person who marries a child commits an offence and is liable on conviction to a fine of N500,000.00; or imprisonment for a term of five years or to both such fine and imprisonment”.

Nothing was done to the Senator who was serving a current term in the House of Senate, at the time of the marriage. In the controversy as to whether the international conventions are based on western philosophy or ideals, over the years the development in the legislation of different nations have culminated in the protection of humanity in its different forms. This position was summarised by non-governmental organisations in Bangkok which affirmed that universal human rights standards are rooted in many cultures which deserve protection of all humanity including women's rights, while advocating cultural pluralism.³⁴⁶

4.6 Access to Justice by Nigerian Women

There are expectations on the roles of every member of a family and the Nigerian society is no exception. Daughters being female identify with their mother, sisters, and other female

³⁴⁴ Ine Nnadi, 'Early Marriage: A Gender-Based Violence and a Violation of Women's Human Rights in Nigeria' (2014) 7(3) Journal of Politics and Law 36: <https://www.theguardian.com> - 25th July 2013 (Accessed 22 September 2023).

³⁴⁵ Section 21 of the Child's Rights Act 2003- "No person under the age of 18 years is capable of contracting a valid marriage, and accordingly a marriage so contracted is null and void and of no effect whatsoever".

³⁴⁶ Susan Waltz, 'Reclaiming and rebuilding the history of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights' (2002) 23(3) Third World Quarterly 446.

members of the family to fulfil (or oppose) those expectations, while sons identify with their father, brothers, and other male family members. Gender stereotyping begins as an institution within the family unit.³⁴⁷ The average Nigerian girls grow up into women, with the orientation of the roles assigned to them by family and society. These roles influence the actions women take especially in fighting for their rights in the family as is illustrated in cases where certain culture prohibits certain acts by women such as inheritance of land. It is gratifying though to see that the courts are working hard to erase some of these repugnant cultural practices as expressed in the decision of the courts in *Ukeje v. Ukeje*³⁴⁸ wherein it was stated that the Igbo customary law disinheriting female children from inheriting property from their deceased father was contradictory to the non-discriminatory provisions of the 1999 Nigerian Constitution and therefore void.

There are several challenges encountered by Nigerian women and access to justice is major challenge. Access to justice might appear as a simple concept which is straightforward to women in the western world as there is an organised structure which ensures enforcement. But for Nigerian women there are several factors which influence the decision to seek justice. Embarking on this research has revealed the remote and immediate challenges Nigerian women encounter in their desire to attain satisfaction of wrongs which occur in the family setting. Some of these challenges have been with the women from birth and they go from a range of “knowing her place as a woman” to not having the chance of a formal education in some cases. As one writer puts it; *“In Nigeria, it could be said that the abuse of the natural rights of a woman begins from the time of her birth and only comes to an end at the time of her death. In many parts of Nigeria, particularly the North, women who are prematurely and compulsorily*

³⁴⁷ Godiya Alanana Makama, ‘Patriarchy and Gender Inequality in Nigeria: The Way Forward’ (2013) 9(17) European Scientific Journal 115 at 133.

³⁴⁸ *Ukeje v. Ukeje* (2014) S.C. 224.

*betrothed to a man at birth are not allowed access to basic education and are generally burdened with domestic household chores ”.*³⁴⁹

Against this background, Nigerian women contend with lack of economic empowerment which is limited by the influence of her family or lack thereof and her environment. The rights of Nigerian women have been provided for in the various provisions of international and national legislation. Where then lies the challenge in the enjoyment of those rights? Which is what this study seeks to examine.

4.7. National Laws in Nigeria on the Rights of Women

Nigeria has a plethora of laws for the protection of the rights of women including ratifying international legislations to make them applicable in Nigeria, by an act of the National Assembly.³⁵⁰ There are various laws which govern family law issues in Nigeria and are administered by the courts, some of which are:

Chapter IV of the 1999 Constitution

Violence Against Persons Prohibition Act (VAPP) 2015

Marriage Act, Chapter 218, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 1990

Married Women’s Property Act 1882

Matrimonial Causes Act – Cap 220 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 1990

Matrimonial Causes Rules

Chapter IV of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (Fundamental Human Rights):³⁵¹ These rights are general human rights that are enforceable for the benefit and enjoyment of all. This position is supported by the Court of Appeal in the dictum by His

³⁴⁹ Ngozi Oluchukwu Odiaka, ‘The Concept of Gender Justice and Women’s Rights in Nigeria: Addressing the Missing Link’ (2013) 2(1) *Journal of Sustainable Development Law and Policy* 190.

³⁵⁰ 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Section 12.

³⁵¹ Sections 33 – 44 <https://nigerian-constitution.com/chapters-sections-nigerian-constitution/> (Accessed 18th October 2021).

Lordship Mojeed Adekunle Owoade JCA, in *Akwa Savings & Loans Ltd v. Udoumana & Ors*³⁵² wherein he stated that it is a settled position of law that Chapter IV is an enforceable provision not just against the state but also against artificial persons as was the situation in the instant case.

Violence Against Persons Prohibition Act (VAPP) 2015.³⁵³ This is an Act to eliminate violence in private and public life, prohibit all forms of violence against persons and provide structure for protection and adequate remedies for victims and effective punishment for offenders; and other related matters. The Act was originally presented as the *Violence Against Women (Prohibition) Bill* but the opposition in both Houses of the male dominated body of the National Assembly with issues relating to marital rape, resulted in the bill being renamed the *Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act*.³⁵⁴ The Act defines violence in its various forms and criminalizes on a national level, acts such as FGM³⁵⁵ and evicting a spouse from his/her matrimonial home.³⁵⁶

Marriage Act, Chapter 218, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 1990.³⁵⁷ A major contribution of this law is the fact that a married woman under the Act enjoys equal rights to the family assets acquired while the marriage subsisted and to be involved in the disposal of the assets

³⁵² [2009] LPELR 8861.

³⁵³ <https://www.ilo.org/dyn/natlex/docs/ELECTRONIC/104156/126946/> (Accessed 18th October 2021).

³⁵⁴ Felix Amadi and Aladokiye Gabriel-Whyte, 'The Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act 2015: Legislative Asset or Liability?' (2018) 5(1) University of Maiduguri Journal of Public Law 146.

³⁵⁵ Female Genital Mutilation. Section 6 of the VAPP Act.
<https://www.ilo.org/dyn/natlex/docs/ELECTRONIC/104156/126946> (Accessed 18th October 2021).

³⁵⁶ Section 9 of VAPP Act 2015
<https://www.ilo.org/dyn/natlex/docs/ELECTRONIC/104156/126946> (Accessed 18th October 2021).

³⁵⁷ <https://lawsofnigeria.placng.org/laws/M6.pdf> (Accessed 18th October 2021).

during or after the marriage or upon the death of her husband. The Act recognises customary marriages to be valid.³⁵⁸

Married Women's Property Act 1882.³⁵⁹ This Act is a Statute of General Application in Nigeria because it is a UK Act of Parliament that was inherited when Nigeria adopted the Common law system. The Act altered the rights of married women concerning their rights to own and control property. There are *Maintenance Orders Act, Cap M1*³⁶⁰ which provide for the application and enforcement in Nigeria of maintenance orders made in England and other countries.³⁶¹

Matrimonial Causes Act – Cap 220 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 1990.³⁶² This Act regulates marriages and the dissolution of marriages. It recognises the three types of marriages in Nigeria – statutory, customary, and Islamic marriages. It has been contended that there are shortcomings in the Act and the process of reconciliation be isolated to enable it to serve its purpose of marital stability by not including it with dissolution in the same Act.³⁶³ Reconciliation could be extra judicially.

Matrimonial Causes Rules of 1983, M7 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 1990.³⁶⁴ These Rules were made pursuant to the Matrimonial Causes Act and set out the procedure to regulate marriages including the dissolutions.

³⁵⁸ Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 1990, Chapter 218 Section 35 of the Marriage Act <https://lawsofnigeria.placng.org/laws/M6.pdf> (Accessed 18 October 2021).

³⁵⁹ <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/Vict/45-46/75/body/> (Accessed 18 October 2021).

³⁶⁰ Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004.

³⁶¹ <https://uk.practicallaw.thomsonreuters.com/> (Accessed 18 October 2021).

³⁶² <https://lawsofnigeria.placng.org/laws/M7.pdf> (Accessed 18 October 2021).

³⁶³ Oluwakemi Mary Adekile, 'Legal Framework for Settling Marital Disputes Through Reconciliation in Nigeria' [2009] <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1503384> (Accessed 18 October 2021).

³⁶⁴ <https://lawnigeria.com/2019/11/matrimonial-causes-rules/> (Accessed 19 October 2021).

Additional State laws which protect the rights of women in Nigeria³⁶⁵ are listed below:

S/N	STATE	LAW
	Adamawa	Adamawa State Administration of Criminal Justice Law, 2018 Adamawa State Violence against Persons Prohibition (VAPP) Law Adamawa State Inheritance Law
	Anambra	Anambra State Malpractices against Widows and Widowers (Prohibition) Law No. 2005. Anambra State Gender and Equal Opportunities Law, 2007. Anambra State Women's Reproductive Rights, Anambra State, 2005. Anambra Administration of Criminal Justice Law 2010
	Akwa Ibom	Akwa Ibom State Violence against Persons Prohibition (VAPP) Law, 2022 Administration of Criminal Justice Act, 2017
	Bauchi	Bauchi State Withdrawal of Girls from Schools for Marriage (Prohibition Law No 17 of 1985) Administration of Criminal Justice Act, 2022 Bauchi State Violence against Persons Prohibition (VAPP) Law, 2020
	Bayelsa	Bayelsa State, The Female Genital (Prohibition) Law, 2000. Bayelsa State Violence against Persons Prohibition (VAPP) Law, 2020 Administration of Criminal Justice Act, 2019
	Benue	Administration of Criminal Justice Act, 2019 Benue State Violence against Persons Prohibition (VAPP) Law, 2019.
	Borno	
	Cross River	Cross River State Law to Prohibit Girl-Child Marriages and Female Genital Circumcision or Genital Mutilation, 2009.

³⁶⁵ <https://www.refworld.org/pdfid/582d75584.pdf>,
https://www.justice-security.ng/sites/default/files/mcn_policy_brief_genderrelations_adamawa_web_final.pdf,
<https://www.refworld.org/pdfid/582d75584.pdf>, <https://www.partnersnigeria.org/vapp-tracker> (Accessed 9 May 2023).

		<p>Cross Rivers State Law to Prohibit Domestic Violence against Women and Maltreatment. No. 10 of 2004.</p> <p>Administration of Criminal Justice Act, 2017</p> <p>Cross Rivers State Violence against Persons Prohibition (VAPP) Law, 2021.</p>
	Delta	N/A
	Edo	<p>Edo State Inhuman Treatment of Widows (Prohibition) Law 2004.</p> <p>Edo State Law for Monitoring of Maternal Mortality in Edo State and Other Matters Connected Thereto, 2001.</p> <p>Edo State Law for Monitoring of Maternal Mortality and Other Matters Connected Thereto, 2001.</p> <p>Edo State Female Circumcision and Genital Mutilation (Prohibition) Law No.4 of 1999.</p>
	Enugu	<p>Enugu State HIV/AIDS Anti-Discrimination and Protection Law, 2007.</p> <p>Enugu State Prohibition of Infringement of a Widow's and Widower's Fundamental Rights Law No. 3 of 2001.</p>
	Ekiti	Ekiti State Gender-Based Violence (Prohibition) Law, 2011.
	Gombe	
	Imo	<p>Imo State Gender and Equal Opportunities Law No 7 of 2007.</p> <p>Imo State Widows (Protection) Law 2003.</p>
	Kaduna	N/A
	Katsina	N/A
	Kebbi	N/A
	Kano	N/A
	Kogi	N/A
	Kwara	N/A
	Lagos	<p>Lagos State Street Hawking (Prohibition) Law.</p> <p>Lagos State Protection Against Domestic Violence Law 2007.</p> <p>Lagos State Administration of Criminal Justice Law, 2011.</p> <p>Lagos State Protection of People Living with HIV and Affected by AIDS Law 2007.</p> <p>Lagos State Law to Provide Rules on Criminal Conduct, Regulate Public Order and for Connected Purposes, 2011.</p>

		Lagos State Same Sex (Prohibition) Law 2007. National Human Rights Commission Amendment Act 2010. National HIV/AIDS anti-stigma law, 2014.
	Nasarawa	N/A
	Niger	N/A
	Ogun	N/A
	Ondo	N/A
	Osun	N/A
	Oyo	N/A
	Plateau	N/A
	Rivers	Rivers State Reproductive Health Service Law No. 3 of 2003. Rivers State Schools Rights (Parents, Children and Teachers) Law No.2, 2005. Rivers State Dehumanizing and Harmful Traditional Practices Law of 2003 and Rivers State Dehumanising and Harmful Traditional Practices (Abolition)(amendment) Law No. 11 2019 Rivers State Abolition of Female Circumcision Law, No. 2 of 2001. 5. Rivers State Violence Against (Prohibition) Law No. 4 of 2020 Rivers State Persons Living with Disability Welfare (enhancement) Law No. 11 of 2012 Rivers State Administration of Criminal Justice Law (ACJL) No. 7 of 2015 Rivers State Prohibition of the Curtailment Rivers State Child Rights Law, No. 10, 2009 Amended as No. 2 of 2021
	Sokoto	N/A
	Taraba	N/A
	Yobe	N/A
	Zamfara	N/A
	FCT/Abuja	N/A

It is pertinent to point out that though there are no statistics but from the table above, the states which predominantly have N/A in the column are the states in the north and northwest region of Nigeria where Islam is the major religion practised.

4.8. Critique on Nigerian Legal System

Academic writers have criticised some of the Nigerian laws as being unsuitable in the present day as a result of changes and development in the world. Umar Alkali et al stated in their article, “Nature and Sources of Nigerian Legal System: An Exorcism of a Wrong Notion” that there are English laws which were promulgated into Nigerian laws that have been repealed or amended in England but are part of Nigerian laws which are not suitable for the communities.³⁶⁶ They also criticised the fact that the adoption of a Child’s Rights Law which did not take into consideration Islamic principles, was not all inclusive of the Muslims who occupy the northern part of Nigeria.

It is believed by some critics that the colonial administration made the traditional practices and culture less significant in the Nigerian legal system through the use of validity tests that were subject to English standards.³⁶⁷ The position of the critics is that not all English laws which were adopted into the Nigerian Constitution by the Statutes of General Application are suitable for the Nigerian legal system. To further emphasise the position of the critics, for illustration is the introduction of formal mediation processes in the resolution of family disputes. The adoption of technical and formal procedures in resolving family disputes are not best suited for informal family mediation which is regulated by customs and traditions.

4.9. Challenges of Nigerian Women’s Access to Justice

³⁶⁶ Umar Alkali and others ‘Nature and Sources of Nigerian Legal System: An Exorcism of a Wrong Notion’ (2014) 5(4) International Journal of Business, Economics and Law 5.

³⁶⁷ Umar Alkali and others ‘Nature and Sources of Nigerian Legal System: An Exorcism of a Wrong Notion’ (2014) 5(4) International Journal of Business, Economics and Law 8.

The challenges encountered by Nigerian women could also be termed as systemic barriers to access to justice. Some writers are of the opinion that the problems faced by Nigerian women are rooted in the words of the Nigerian Constitution.³⁶⁸ The manner in which the Constitution is drafted, does not recognise women as women as it is in the South African legal system, but Nigerian women are categorised with the men and as such the issue of gender equality appears to be making very slow progress. Nigerian women should be recognised in their own rights as women and the issue of gender equality taken more seriously in respecting the role of women in society.

The challenges experienced by Nigerian women could be linked to the explanation by this 1998 UNESCO report³⁶⁹ which classified traditional women's roles as:

Taking care of domestic chores

Rearing children

Providing water and firewood

With societal prohibitions on – participation in village council meetings or chieftaincy matters, ownership of familial lands by women especially where she has no male child.

Though Nigerian women have progressed from these roles and there have been decisions which have allowed women to own family lands,³⁷⁰ the struggle for her rights remains an uphill task. The introduction of Christianity by the colonialist laid the foundation for the emergence of women from some of these archaic traditional roles. The progress has been ongoing over the years as Nigerian women struggle to fight for their rights and some of the challenges women encounter in the bid to access justice include the following:

³⁶⁸ Emeka Chegwe, 'A Gender Critique of Liberal Feminism and its Impact on Nigerian law' (2014) 14(1) *International Journal of Discrimination and the Law* 1, 67.

³⁶⁹ Francis Akubuilu and Monica Omeje, 'Women Education in Nigeria: Predicaments and Hopes' (2012) 1(5) *International Journal of Advancement in Research and Technology* 2.

³⁷⁰ *Onyibor Anekwe & Anor v. Maria Nweke* (2013) S.C 129.

4.9.1 Cultural and Traditional Practices

Culture has been described as the cultivation of a usage of common practice-custom by a group of people with common consent over a period which acquires the force of a law over a place or subject matter to which it relates.³⁷¹ Customs are dynamic and sometimes evolve into customary law. The cultural and traditional beliefs of society are peculiar to the ethnicity of the people which is why the customary laws differ from each ethnic group.

This study also considers the impact of traditional and cultural practices on women's rights. Cultural practices have been cited as justification for depriving women of their basic rights in societies.³⁷² Some of these customs and traditional practices have been written down as formal law but most are still unwritten but possess the force of law in application. Women are discriminated against in almost every society on a daily basis by traditional practices and customs which hinder the exercise and enjoyment of their rights like the rights of female inheritance to property and capacity to own property.³⁷³ In most societies in Nigeria under customary law, women are not allowed to own properties whether in their biological families or in their marital families. It has remained an uphill task for the judiciary in Nigeria to overturn these practices till present day. This was illustrated by the evidence of one of the participants during the data collection who narrated her ordeal. She narrated how at her marital home, after being driven out of her matrimonial home at the death of her husband, she went back to her father's house and was allocated any place to stay because she had no right to any property as

³⁷¹ Agbonika J. Alewo and Matthew A. Olong, 'Cultural Practices and Traditional Beliefs as Impediments to the Enjoyment of Women's Rights in Nigeria' (2012) 1(1) International Law Research 135.

³⁷² Ibid.

³⁷³ Agbonika J. Alewo and Matthew A. Olong, "Cultural Practices and Traditional Beliefs as Impediments to the Enjoyment of Women's Rights in Nigeria" (2012) 1(1) International Law Research 1, 140.

she had been married out of the family and was not entitled to any of the houses or lands of her father.³⁷⁴

The customs and traditions vary but are similar on issues of women's rights in certain areas in Nigeria such as rights of widows, capacity to own properties, occupation of certain public positions, etc. Another area where women's rights are abused are in burial/funeral rites. This is a very common area which cuts across most cultures and traditions in Nigeria where women's rights are abused. In most communities when a man dies, the first suspect is the wife, and she is subjected to inhuman acts to prove her innocence.³⁷⁵

Some customs require that the woman drinks the water used in bathing the corpse to prove her innocence, she is also required to shave all the hair on her head and not allowed to leave her room for a certain period while wearing only black clothes.³⁷⁶ These repugnant practices have led to the passing into law by some state government, laws prohibiting such practices such as the *Enugu State Protection of Widows and Widowers Fundamental Rights Law (2001)*, and *Anambra State Malpractices against Widows and Widowers Prohibition Laws (2004)*.³⁷⁷

There are so many areas where traditional beliefs and culture have hindered the rights of women especially the girl child. Education is another common area where women's rights are hindered from girlhood. Development attempts to occur in every society but deep rooted in most culture is still the preference to educate the boy child in favour of the girl child especially in Northern Nigeria on the premise that if the girl child is educated, she will no longer be

³⁷⁴ Interview of Participant 2 at the FIDA Legal Centre, Anambra State, Nigeria, held on 13/01/2022 at 13:20hrs.

³⁷⁵ Agbonika J. Alewo and Matthew A. Olong, 'Cultural Practices and Traditional Beliefs as Impediments to the Enjoyment of Women's Rights in Nigeria' (2012) 1(1) International Law Research 140.

³⁷⁶ Ibid.

³⁷⁷ <https://laws.lawnigeria.com/2018/08/20/center-for-laws-of-the-states-of-nigeria/> (Accessed 14 January 2022).

humble.³⁷⁸ Another aspect where culture has been biased to the Nigerian woman is in the mode of dressing. If a woman ties a wrapper and a head tie to attend a function, she is termed to be more responsibly dressed than a lady who is dressed in trousers or a short skirt, be it a local or formal function.³⁷⁹

One of the major challenges women have faced in the access of justice all over the world and particularly in Nigeria, has been the influence of culture and tradition. Traditional and cultural practices have always influenced Nigerian women in the different stages of their lives, from girlhood to womanhood. This position was confirmed by the testimonies of the participants who took part in the survey and the interviews during the data collection of this research. Culture conditions women on expected behaviour from birth, which begins with her family members and extends into the society at large. By the time the women get married or proceed into a relationship outside their biological family setting, the orientation of the culture and tradition they know affects the choices they make in their life's decisions.

In seeking to enforce their rights, women in Nigeria are sometimes faced with cultural practices which are a direct contrast with their fundamental and constitutional rights. *Chapter IV of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria* provides for the Fundamental Rights, part of which includes that:

“In the determination of his civil rights and obligations, including any question or determination by or against any government or authority, a person shall be entitled to a fair hearing;”³⁸⁰

³⁷⁸ Agbonika J. Alewo and Matthew A. Olong, ‘Cultural Practices and Traditional Beliefs as Impediments to the Enjoyment of Women’s Rights in Nigeria’ (2012) 1(1) International Law Research 141.

³⁷⁹ Ibid.

³⁸⁰ 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Section 36(1).

The first point to note in this law is the fact that the law mentions the pronoun “his” representing a male rather than a person to signify either gender. On the premise that this provision is for all citizens, the rights of women are handicapped in cultures where women are not permitted to speak in certain traditional gatherings. The evidence of one of the participants during the interview gave credence to this theory when she stated that she was not allowed to state her own side of the story when her husband summoned her to the village before the chiefs on the grounds that she had abandoned her matrimonial home for months.³⁸¹ All attempts for her to speak and inform the gathering that she had been ill and residing with her elder sister who was looking after her proved futile. Other cultural inhibitions which were revealed during the interviews include the ritual cleansing of a woman who left her matrimonial home as a result of a dispute, which must be performed before she is allowed back into the home.

The Islamic scholar Jellini, posited in his writings that “a wife is culturally and traditionally in Nigeria responsible for the maintenance of the house and care of the husband and children and where she fails to carry out her duties and responsibilities, this may cause conflict between the parties”.³⁸² His position suggests that where a woman fails to do what is expected of her culturally, there would be disputes in the family. Some of these cultural practices are scary and discouraging to women who want to press further to enforce their rights as narrated by some of the participants. The consequences of traditional implications from family members and the society, most times seems to be the reason most women are reluctant to step outside the informal mediation process. This is hoped to be ascertained from the analysis of the interviews. The grip of culture and tradition in the lives of Nigerian women is such that despite the level of education and success a woman attains, she is bound by the bonds of tradition. Two real life

³⁸¹ Interview of Participant 2, Lagos State FIDA Legal Centre held on 17/02/2022 at 10:17am.

³⁸² Yusuf Jelili Amuda, ‘The Concept of Mediation In a Conflictual Family: Nigerian Customary Law And Shari’ah System As A Case Study’ [2008]
http://www.asiapacificmediationforum.org/resources/2008/8yusuff_jelili_amuda.pdf.
(Accessed 21 November 2022).

scenarios would illustrate this theory, one witnessed by the researcher and the other narrated by a participant during the interviews.

First Scenario: A female lawyer who had lost her husband but occupied a very senior position in one of the government parastatals had to take time off to observe cultural practices of mourning her husband. She was absent from the office for an extended period as by culture she was not allowed to go out and engage in social activities until after the burial. She did not receive a query from her superiors as it was understood that she was in mourning.

Second Scenario: This scenario was given by one of the participants during the interview in Anambra State. The participant had relocated back to Nigeria from the United States of America after a failed marriage and consequently could not reside in her husband's village. She returned to her father's house with the hope of being allocated one of the numerous houses owned by her father. Unfortunately, her brothers refused on the grounds that by culture, she did not have a right to any property in the family as she was married out. Rather than contest for her rights in court, she decided to seek mediation at the FIDA legal centre.

The above scenarios are the reality of the impact of culture in the lives of Nigerian women irrespective of education and social standing. Various laws provide for the rights of women but the impact of culture and tradition in the daily lives of the women would make the laws appear ineffective or non-existent.

A further illustration on the influence of culture in the lives of Nigerian women and its impact was illustrated in the case of *Ugbomia v. Ibeneme*³⁸³ where the court had decided that according to Ibo custom the female children could not inherit directly from their father but could be maintained by their brothers until they were married out of the family. Also under customary law, in most traditions women were not allowed to inherit from their husband's side of the

³⁸³ [1967] F.N.L.R 257.

family either. Where they get married and if for some reason the husband is deceased, the wife is “taken over” by a surviving male relative of the deceased and if the wife is young and has no children, she is expected to continue the marriage and bear children in the lineage of her late husband.³⁸⁴ Though the courts are slowly but consistently trying to change the negative effect of the patriarchal system of Nigerian customs and traditions as was illustrated in *Mojekwu v. Mojekwu* per Nikki Tobi J when he said:

*“Is such a custom consistent with equity and fair play in an egalitarian society such as ours where the civilized society does not discriminate against women? Day after day, month after month and year after year we hear of and read about customs which discriminate against the womenfolk in this country. They are regarded as inferior to the men folk. Why should it be so? All human beings, male and female are born into a free world and are expected to participate freely without any inhibition on grounds of sex and that is constitutional. Any form of societal discrimination on grounds of sex apart from being unconstitutional is antithesis to society built on the tenets of democracy...On my part, I have no difficulty in holding “Oli-Ekpe” custom of Nnewi is repugnant to natural justice, equity, and good conscience.”*³⁸⁵

The above dictum of Justice Nikki Tobi (as he then was) in the above case, was in respect to the Oli-Ekpe custom which did not allow female children inherit property in Nnewi, in the eastern part of Nigeria. Though the courts are challenging this position of custom daily, and bills are being passed to change the position. A good example is the recently passed bill which was signed into law by the Rivers State Government; *“The Rivers State Prohibition of the Curtailment of Women’s Right to Share in Family Property Law No.2 of 2022.”*³⁸⁶ This law

³⁸⁴ *Ogunkoya v Ogunkoya* Suit No. CA/L/46/88, 56 (unreported); Ngozi Odiaka, ‘The Concept of Gender Justice and Women’s Rights in Nigeria: Addressing the Missing Link’ (2013) 2(1) *Journal of Sustainable Development Law and Policy* 201.

³⁸⁵ *Mojekwu v. Mojekwu* (1997)7 N.W.L.R, Part 512, 283.

³⁸⁶ www.fida.org.ng; www.thisdaylive.com (Accessed 18 September 2022).

allows women to inherit property in their biological families, which is a breakthrough for women in Rivers State particularly, and Nigerian women generally.

When a woman knows the custom, it influences her decision to seek her choice of justice. Family mediation might give her the forum to discuss and negotiate better to ensure she gets satisfactory justice and not just justice according to the letters of the law as provided by customary law. Where a woman is conscious that custom or tradition is not equitable to the rights of women, her choice in the form of justice would be influenced.

The previous parts of this study have referred to culture as it affects the rights of women. This section focuses on culture as it impacts on the rights of women in the process of family mediation as an access to justice.

Impact of Culture and Tradition in Family Mediation

The influence of culture and tradition on the rights of women as mentioned earlier, is far reaching and affects every sector of their lives. Culture being the background which influences the lives of women from their biological homes to their matrimonial homes, plays a major role in determining how women seek to access justice especially in family mediation. It would be challenging for women who come from a background where women are “seen” and not “heard” to enforce their rights in their matrimonial home if their spouse is also from the same cultural background. In such a situation the process of mediation will not be as smooth as a situation where there is no influence of culture.

Cultural frameworks have been expressed to be impactful on mediation processes which can lead to lengthy and costly situations especially where children are involved.³⁸⁷ The international sector acknowledges the importance of culture in the regulation of family disputes

³⁸⁷ Helen Stalford, ‘Crossing Boundaries: Reconciling Law, Culture and Values in International Family Mediation’ (2010) 32(2) *Journal of Social Welfare and Family Law* 155 at 156.

through mediation by providing guidelines where the parties to a family dispute are from different member States as is contained in the EU³⁸⁸ Regulations. The EU regulations provide for jurisdiction issues and parental responsibilities in two major instruments³⁸⁹ which could be a challenge to achieving a resolution due to the different culture of the parties. Despite the support given to resolving cross-national family disputes by international conventions, mediation practitioners are not quick to adopt mediation in resolving cross-national family disputes due to the challenges of the proceedings.³⁹⁰ Stalford has reiterated how cultural practices influences the actions of individuals which are sometimes responsible for the breakdown in the relationship, and which also impacts on the dispute resolution process³⁹¹.

In Nigeria, culture plays a major role in the home, of which the legality of the marriage contract is determined by the payment of the dowry traditionally. It is common knowledge that when there is a dispute in the marriage and informal mediation is adopted, the cultural practices and tradition of the parties regulate the proceedings. It has been stated that mediation does not exist in vacuum but is shaped by the cultural 'baggage' of the parties which determines how the entire dispute process will be regulated.³⁹²

In analysing the reality, one would wonder how the freedom which the mediation process should represent can be adopted to regulate the dispute process which is regulated by culture and tradition.

³⁸⁸ European Union.

³⁸⁹ Regulation 2201/2003 and regulation 4/2009 respectively.

³⁹⁰ Helen Stalford, 'Crossing Boundaries: Reconciling Law, Culture and Values in International Family Mediation' (2010) 32(2) *Journal of Social Welfare and Family Law* 159-160.

³⁹¹ *Ibid.*

³⁹² Sonia Shah-Kazemi, 'Cross-Cultural Mediation: a critical view of the dynamics of culture in family disputes' (2000) 14(3) *International Journal of Law, Policy and the Family* 302.

Often times, in practice as a mediator during a family dispute, the researcher would come across a situation where parties would say according to their custom they are not allowed to act in a certain way in marriage. There was a particular case³⁹³ where the woman had brought a complaint to the FIDA legal centre that her husband had thrown her out of her matrimonial home and was denying her access to the children. The husband was invited for a mediation, and he honoured the invitation. During the proceedings, he stated that his wife could not come back into their matrimonial after their dispute and sleeping outside their home without performing certain traditional rites to cleanse herself and not endanger his life. The wife vehemently refused to do this on the grounds that he chased her out of their home, and she was a Christian.

The question whether mediation can achieve the satisfaction of the parties without compromising its processes is peculiar to each situation. The values of justice, self-determination and equality are the core of mediation which are universal and must be adapted to the particular cultural and social environment they are applied to.³⁹⁴ But where a woman's cultural background has conditioned her to succumb to the will of the man and the social expectations of the wider family and society, how would an agreement reached in such a situation be said to comply with the values of mediation?

It is the observation of the researcher that when the mediator shares the same cultural practices with the parties, the mediator understands the language of the parties which enhances the quality of the proceedings.

³⁹³ Incidence Report, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre, 2009.

³⁹⁴ Sonia Shah-Kazemi, "Cross-Cultural Mediation: a critical view of the dynamics of culture in family disputes" (2000) 14(3) *International Journal of Law, Policy and the Family* 311.

Some writers like Shah-Kazemi, are of the opinion that cultural values provide a platform for the appreciation of universal principles of mediation in family dispute.³⁹⁵ In her view the difference in cultural practices does not restrict the adoption of mediation principles but allows the appreciation of the specific culture of the parties in the reality of the dispute. In other words, the culture is expressed in the course of the mediation proceedings. In expressing the culture of the parties in the proceedings, the ideal situation would be for the mediator to be from the same cultural background as the parties. This would reduce the areas of tension as the mediator would appreciate the consequences of the actions of the parties and provide adequate guidance. Universally, this would be the ideal situation as the mediator would not require prior training.³⁹⁶

4.9.2. Early Marriages

All over the world early marriage has always been a challenge to the development of the girl child, Nigeria is no exception. In every part of Nigeria, the custom of early marriage is practiced but prevails more in some areas like the northwest of Nigeria where most girls especially in the rural areas, are betrothed or married off at 18 years.³⁹⁷ The effect of early marriage is that the girl is married into a family where she has to learn how to be a wife, daughter-in-law, mother and perform other responsibilities without necessarily possessing the maturity for the performance of those duties. Some girls mature in their matrimonial homes as they are married sometimes at the tender ages of 9 years in northern Nigeria provided the husband does not have sexual relations with her until she attains puberty.³⁹⁸

³⁹⁵ Sonia Shah-Kazemi, "Cross-Cultural Mediation: a critical view of the dynamics of culture in family disputes" (2000) 14(3) *International Journal of Law, Policy and the Family* 318-320.

³⁹⁶ *Ibid.*

³⁹⁷ Ine Nnadi, 'Early Marriage: A Gender-Based Violence and a Violation of Women's Human Rights in Nigeria' (2014) 7(3) *Journal of Politics and Law* 35-38.

³⁹⁸ *Ibid.*

This leads to a lot of early pregnancies which results in Vesicovaginal fistula also known as VVF, a medical condition which occurs when a girl gives birth at a very tender age. When a girl becomes a mother before she is equipped for the responsibilities, her abilities to discern the best choices in decision making, are hindered by the reality of her situation. She would be used to taking instructions from older members of the family and would be reluctant to explore other dispute resolution processes which are contrary to those of the family. This is a challenge to her rights to access to justice.

4.9.3. Religious Obligations

Women also experience pressure from the religious groups they belong to when they seek to enforce their rights through the formal process of the law. The religious leaders in the different sects all preach the message that women should honour and be submissive to their husbands and resolving family disputes through formal legal is sometimes discouraged.

As mentioned earlier in this study, religion plays a major role in the lives of Nigerian women as the religious leaders are revered and possess a lot of influence in the lives of the members of their congregation. It is common practice for a pastor or church leader to advise their members who are experiencing family conflicts to seek informal mediation either through the family or church. It is the same expectation with the Islamic religion where the Imam is the spiritual head.

The impact of religion in family mediation is a subtle but a real factor which must be mentioned in this research. During the researcher's years of practice as a legal practitioner and mediator at different legal centres, it was not strange to encounter testimonies of women who would state that they reported their family disputes to their pastors or spiritual heads for resolution. During the interviews, some of the participants testified that they had reported their disputes to their church leaders who had mediated in the matters but as they had not received the satisfaction they sought, they eventually came to the FIDA legal centre. This method is not

peculiar to the south, west or east of Nigeria alone, it also occurs in northern Nigeria where the Imams are the spiritual heads and preside over disputes brought to them. It is the teaching of the Holy books of Islam that:

“...there is a Sadaqa to be given for every joint of the human body; and for every day on which the sun rises there is a reward of a Sadaqa (charitable gift) for the one who establishes justice among people”.³⁹⁹ The belief is that it is the responsibility of the Imam or the family head to resolve family disputes or any quarrels quickly and this is done in accordance with the Holy scriptures.⁴⁰⁰

During the interviews, one of the participants had stated that when she decided to report her husband to the police and get him arrested for domestic abuse, her pastor discouraged her and invited him to come to church for counselling. She invited her husband to church, but he did not honour the invitation. The domestic abuse continued which led her to the FIDA legal centre. Some authors like Ojelabi et al have stated that the advice from religious leaders who are not trained in matters of domestic violence are detrimental to women.⁴⁰¹

Though some religious leaders are beginning to educate their members on the need for formal intervention especially where domestic violence is involved and all attempts at informal mediation has failed. The pressure to observe religious practices of keeping family matters in the family even where it will be beneficial to all parties concerned to seek legal redress is common to every ethnic group. Though women in northern Nigeria appear to experience more of the challenge in this regard due to the activities of Boko Haram religious sect who believe

³⁹⁹ Sahihi Al-Bukhar, Volume 3, 543.

⁴⁰⁰ Yusuff Amuda, 'The Concept of Mediation in a Conflictual Family: Nigerian Customary Law And Shari'ah System As A Case Study' [2008] http://www.asiapacificmediationforum.org/resources/2008/8-yusuff_jelili_amuda.pdf (Accessed 20 September 2022).

⁴⁰¹ Lola Ojelabi and others 'A Cultural Assessment of Family Dispute Resolution: Findings about Cultural Appropriateness from the Evaluation of a Family Relationship Centre' (2012) 18(1) Journal of Family Studies, 76 at 83.

activities outside the Islamic faith is corruption by western education and punish offenders with terrorist acts.⁴⁰² It is understandable to see how women can be discouraged in seeking justice when it is contrary to the religious expectations of society.

4.9.4 Poverty and Lack of Financial Empowerment

The economic hardship caused by poverty in the family environment especially for low-income earners, is also felt by Nigerian women. The hand of poverty could stretch from inability to feed her children, to not having health insurance to take care of the children when they are ill and need medical attention. From the analysis of the data collection of this research, Nigerian women are more concerned with the welfare of their children than making a case for themselves. The results showed that most of the women remained in their challenging situations because they had no alternative source of income for the welfare of their children.

The World Bank estimates that 95.1 million Nigerians live below the poverty line in 2022 which is not unconnected to the COVID 19 pandemic.⁴⁰³ Out of the approximately 210 million people cited as the population of Nigeria, approximately 104.25 million are women as revealed by the research conducted from 2011- 2021.⁴⁰⁴ If the poverty level of the country is so high, the women will also be affected if they make up about half the population. The poverty level which translates to lack of financial empowerment is a major challenge which hinders access to justice for Nigerian women.

Female scholars such as Soeton have expressed the extent to which women can be hindered from acquiring economic independence and stated that the economy of a nation is stronger

⁴⁰² Francis Akubuilu and Monica Omeje, 'Women Education in Nigeria: Predicaments and Hopes' (2012) 1(5) International Journal of Advancement in Research and Technology 4.

⁴⁰³ <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/news/headlines> (Accessed 1 December 2022).

⁴⁰⁴ Aaron O'Neil, 'Total Population of Nigeria by Gender, November 2022' <https://www.statista.com/statistics/967908/total-population-of-nigeria-by-gender> (Accessed 2 December 2022).

when women are empowered.⁴⁰⁵ Soetan is of the view that individual empowerment of women is a basic requirement for the socioeconomic development of national economies. She argues that economic power would enable financial independence. Financial independence will ensure freedom to access to justice for Nigerian women. When a woman is economically empowered, she is free to make the best decisions for herself and the welfare of her children and her access to justice is unhindered. Limitations such as not having money for transportation to travel to urban areas to seek legal assistance, as was revealed during the interviews by some of the participants.

The result of the analysis of the data collection was a confirmation of the suspected view of the researcher that most women remained in abusive environments due to lack of financial empowerment. During the interviews, some of the participants disclosed that they had refrained from seeking formal mediation because of the financial cost of transporting themselves to seek help from legal institutions, which sometimes was not in the same town they resided in. Some of the women were either housewives or low-income earners and had to manage their resources according to priority especially when they are children in the home. This sometimes leads to the women having to make do with whatever ‘justice’ they can get at informal mediation which is usually easily accessible. This form of informal mediation could be from relatives or elders in the community as revealed by the evidence of the participants of the interview during the data collection.

4.9.5 Procedural Bottlenecks

Some of the challenges women encounter in accessing justice include procedural bottlenecks which are associated with either lodging a complaint or enforcing a judgment passed. In reality, most women who have undergone the legal hurdle of a dispute especially if it was through the

⁴⁰⁵ Funmi Soetan, ‘The Economic Empowerment of Nigerian Women: Some Determinants of Access to Resources’ (1999) 27 *African Economic History* 117 at 131.

litigation process, will not want to experience the procedural bottlenecks. The researcher had observed in practice the challenges parties to a dispute encounter in the enforcement of a judgment of the court. In an instance where judgment had been given in favour of the woman, and the husband ordered to pay monthly upkeep for the welfare of his children, the woman informed the researcher that the husband was yet to comply months after the judgment. When asked why she had not sought an order for enforcement, she stated that she lacked the financial empowerment to comply with the procedural bottlenecks which accompany enforcement of judgment in the Nigerian society.

4.9.6 Lack of Enforcement of Laws

As mentioned in the above paragraph, the lack of enforcement of laws is a major challenge to the access of justice. For example, where judgement is passed and the court orders the man to pay alimony and the man fails to pay, the structure to ensure enforcement of the judgment though exists by law, but in reality, hardly functions except the woman takes extra steps to ensure she secures her judgment. This might involve further legal processes which most often the women do not wish to engage in, as usually by this time in the matter they are exhausted. This will be explained further in the subsequent chapters.

4.9.7 Family and Friends Pressure

Women experience pressure from their family members and friends in the bid to exercise their rights. The pressure is usually mounted on a woman when it is felt she is “overstepping her boundaries”. In accessing justice, women are forced to undergo pressures to desist from pursuing any action that is frowned upon such as reporting an abusive husband to the police and he is arrested. Women who take their family disputes outside the immediate family control sometimes risk being punished in some ways by their family members such as rejection or ostracization. This form of control and manipulation to ensure women are kept in their place is not peculiar to Nigeria alone.

In other African countries such as Egypt, women can be disowned for proceeding to court to enforce claims of inheritance.⁴⁰⁶ The consequences for a woman who decides to go outside the family to seek justice range from being shunned in the family, to being pressurised by friends. This is very discouraging for women and represents one of the forms of discrimination women encounter in the desire to access justice.

4.9.8. Lack of Education

The challenge of lack of education as a barrier to access to justice, is one which plagues not only Nigerian women but African women generally. This originates from when the woman is a girl and she is deprived of the necessary formal education which exposes her mind and broadens her horizons on her choices in life, including the different forms of access to justice. The impact of lack of education for the girl child was emphasised by Femi after conducting a research on 1,200 female children between the ages of 6-14 years, from 3 states in Nigeria where it was revealed that lack of education leads to abuse of human rights of the girl child.⁴⁰⁷ Education particularly formal education does not only ensure the ability to read and write but enables the individual to develop the personal capacity to make informed choices. Studies have shown how girls are either prevented from going to school in favour of their brothers if the money at home is not sufficient or she is enrolled in school and is stopped from continuing her education at a certain point.⁴⁰⁸

⁴⁰⁶ Mohamed Awaad, 'Egypt: Denying Women Inheritance Is a Crime Subject to Imprisonment' [2018] <http://legal-agenda.com/en/article.php?id=4259>. (Accessed 19 November 2022).

⁴⁰⁷ Tinuola Femi, 'The Challenges of the Girl-Child Education in Nigeria and Alternative Jobs' (2011) 2 *Corvinus Journal of Sociology and Social Policy*, 101 at 106.

⁴⁰⁸ Nora Omoregie and Ihensiekhen Abraham, 'Persistent Gender Inequality in Nigeria Education' [2009] National Universities Commission, 8 (the research conducted over 2001-2005 revealed 76.43% of males obtained doctorate degrees against 23.57% of females in period the research was conducted) <https://in.nau.edu/wp-content/uploads/sites/135/2018/08/Persistent-Gender-Inequality-in-Nigerian-Education-ek.pdf> (Accessed 23 September 2023).

This position has been traced back to the colonial era when formal education was introduced by the colonialists through Christianity.⁴⁰⁹ Gaidzwanwa posits that domestic education in colonial times enshrined the ideology that women were primarily homemakers which was aimed at making them suitable wives for indigenous colonial employees.⁴¹⁰ With this background to formal education, the struggle to educate the girl child has been continuous in Nigeria. Education of women is very important for the development of women which led to the WID⁴¹¹ theory in the 1970s which was adopted by the United Nations and has culminated in the several international conventions such as the CSW.⁴¹² The international recognition of the right to education by women is expressly stated in *Article 12* of the *Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights on the Rights of Women in Africa*⁴¹³ which provides as follows:

“(1) State parties shall take all appropriate measures to:

- (a) Eliminate all forms of discrimination against women and guarantee equal opportunity and access in the sphere of education and training.
- (b) Eliminate all stereotypes in textbooks, syllabuses, and the media, that perpetuate such discrimination.
- (c) Protect women, especially the girl-child from all forms of abuse, including sexual harassment in schools and other educational institutions and provide for sanctions against the perpetrators of such practices.

⁴⁰⁹ Tola Olujuwon, ‘Transforming the Educational System in Nigeria: Implication for School leaders’ (2017) 16(1) *Journal of Educational Research and Development* 208 at 209.

⁴¹⁰ Rudo Gaidzwanwa, ‘Bourgeois Theories of Gender and Femi-nism and their Short Comings with Reference to Southern African Countries’ [1992] www.wunrn.com/news/2007/11_07/.../110507_nigeria.htm (Accessed 1 December 2022).

⁴¹¹ Women In Development.

⁴¹² Commission on the Status of Women.

⁴¹³ <https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/Documents/Issues/Women/WG/ProtocolontheRightsofWomen.pdf> (Accessed 1 December 2022).

- (d) Provide access to counselling and rehabilitation services to women who suffer abuses and sexual harassment.
 - (e) Integrate gender sensitisation and human rights education at all levels of education curricula including teacher training.
2. States Parties shall take specific positive action to:
- (a) Promote literacy among women.
 - (b) Promote education and training for women at all levels and in all disciplines, particularly in the fields of science and technology.
 - (c) Promote the enrolment and retention of girls in schools and other training institutions and the organisation of programmes for women who leave school prematurely”.

Nigeria is a State Party to the *African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights* which it ratified on the 22nd of June 1983.⁴¹⁴ There are consequently laws in existence which provide for the education of girls and women and the challenge lies in the application of these laws by the citizens. Other international instruments like CEDAW⁴¹⁵ and BPFA⁴¹⁶ also recognise the millennium development goals which recognise the need to educate and train women.

It is the opinion of some Nigerian academics that if women are encouraged to engage in formal education, in the next ten to fifteen years Nigerian women would surpass men in most sectors of the economy.⁴¹⁷ The need for education of Nigerian women at every level, from the grassroots being the rural areas, and the orientation she receives from birth as she grows up

⁴¹⁴ <https://www.achpr.org> (Accessed 1 December 2022).

⁴¹⁵ Convention on Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women.

⁴¹⁶ Beijing Platform for Action.

⁴¹⁷ Francis Akubuilu and Monica Omeje, ‘Women Education in Nigeria: Predicaments and Hopes’ (2012) 1(5) *International Journal of Advancement in Research and Technology* 1.

into adulthood is important as this will determine the choices, she makes including enforcing her rights in accessing justice.

4.9.9. Lack of Awareness and Exposure

Some women are not aware that they are provisions like ADR processes for the resolution of family disputes apart from litigation. Sadly, this occurs in the rural areas where the women think the only options available for resolution of family dispute is the informal mediation with their family members or the community as mediators, or the courts. Most women are discouraged by the technical issues which surround litigation including the cost and would prefer to settle for the familiar process of informal mediation they know rather than the unknown terrain of formal dispute procedures. The challenge of sensitizing women on the different forms of accessing justice is a task embarked on by NGOs and most legal aid parastatals like FIDA. One of the participants in the interview testified that she knew about the services FIDA provided when she witnessed the mobile clinic they conducted in the market. She listened and decided to visit the office to lay her complaint.

4.10 Feminist Perspective on the Impact of International and National Laws on Nigerian Women.

Feminist theory, as it is often discussed in literature, needs to be critiqued particularly in the exploration of its usefulness when applied to Nigerian women as it concerns this study. Feminist theory as understood in relation to this study, should be acknowledged as a product of the West which emanates mainly from the USA, UK, and to some extent wider Europe (although there is a distinct French feminist movement in itself but the western feminism is viewed in the same category as distinct from feminism in Africa). Therefore ‘feminist theory’ as a concept and theoretical movement is only somewhat relevant to this thesis because the cultural specificity of feminism often goes unappreciated.

What is therefore important is how and where women are situated in particular societies and cultures at a particular point in time. This is well articulated by Chegwe wherein he emphasised

in his work on the need to harmonise common law principles of the western culture vis a vis the cultural and traditional practices of the indigenous communities in the implementation of laws.⁴¹⁸ Thus, this thesis is particularly interested in the developing African Feminism, or more specifically the developing Nigerian feminism which appreciates the constraints of African and Nigerian culture and familial structures and expectations on women's place within civil society and women's ability to seek justice and claim their rights within these specific systems.

In conducting this study, it became necessary to consider feminism as viewed from the universal point of view to assist our understanding from the Nigerian perspective. Was there a difference? If there was, does it have any impact on access to justice for women? The consideration that legal consciousness of women could be affected by the feminist ideologies is an interesting concept. Randall states that feminism began as a movement of ideas to promote the status of women and enhance power for women.⁴¹⁹ Though different ideas emerged as to what feminism represents, the word itself, which was credited to Charles Fourier, is understood to call for equality in social, economic, cultural, political, legal and linguistics spheres between the sexes.⁴²⁰ The different schools of thought which have emerged over time consist of the Liberal and Marxist, radical feminism, and postmodernism.⁴²¹

All these different schools focus on feminism from the western perspective. The criticism of Nigerian scholars is on how these schools of thought impact on African women. The schools of thought have also influenced different waves of feminism. Chegwe described the different

⁴¹⁸ Emeke Chegwe, 'A Gender Critique of Liberal Feminism and Its Impact on Nigerian Law' (2014) 14(1) *International Journal of Discrimination and the Law* 68.

⁴¹⁹ Vicky Randall, 'Feminism' (2002) in D. Marsh and G. Stoker (eds.): *Theory and Methods in Political Science*; Emeke Chegwe, 'A Gender Critique of Liberal Feminism and its Impact on Nigerian law' (2014) 14 (1) *International Journal of Discrimination and the Law* 67.

⁴²⁰ Emeke Chegwe, 'A Gender Critique of Liberal Feminism and its Impact on Nigerian law' (2014) 14(1) *International Journal of Discrimination and the Law* 66.

⁴²¹ Hilaire Barnett, *Introduction to Feminist Jurisprudence* (Routledge Cavendish, 1998) 121-200.

waves of feminism as follows; the first wave was driven by educated middle-class white women while the second wave attracted coloured women of developing nations forming sisterhoods on the basis that women's challenges were class struggles.⁴²²

According to Martha Rampton⁴²³ the third wave of feminism represented women who saw themselves as subjects and not objects, a combination of beauty with brains and a strong sense of empowerment in themselves. The third wave was described as a phase of "universal womanhood" where it was possible to have a combination of beauty and brains as described by Martha Rampton⁴²⁴ who stated that modern feminism meant defining beauty for themselves as subjects and not objects of sexist patriarchy. This third wave of feminism is the challenge African women struggle with to be seen as subject and not objects as stated in the argument of Nigerian feminist researchers such as Chegwe.

Through the different waves of feminism, Nigerian researchers have criticised the failure to recognise the major features of African women, stating that the discourse has been centred on "educated" middle-class white women.⁴²⁵ Oluwole in her essay *Womanhood and Feminism in African Traditional Thought*, highlights the differences between western and African philosophies on feminism and emphasises that the difference lies in the perspectives.⁴²⁶ She stated that the women desire the same objectives with regards to gender equality, but their perspective of feminism was where the difference existed. In considering the different waves

⁴²² Emeka Chegwe, 'A Gender Critique of Liberal Feminism and its Impact on Nigerian law' (2014) 14 *International Journal of Discrimination and the Law*, 1, 67.

⁴²³ Martha Rampton, 'Four Waves of Feminism' (2008) 4(2) *Pacific University*, <https://www.pacificu.edu/magazine/four-waves-feminism> (Accessed 10 December 2022).

⁴²⁴ Martha Rampton, 'Three Waves of Feminism' (2008) 4 *Pacific University*, 2 Fall edition <https://www.pacificu.edu/magazine/four-waves-feminism> (Accessed 12 November 2021).

⁴²⁵ Gail Presbey, 'Sophie Oluwole's Major Contributions to African Philosophy' (2020) 35(2) *Hypatia Journal* 223.

⁴²⁶ *Ibid.*

of feminism from the perspective of the western world, an understanding of how African women, especially Nigerian women being the focus of this study, practice their version of feminism would not be out of place.

Nigerian scholars like Chegwe posit the need for Nigerian women to be part of the global discourse on feminism while maintaining a consciousness on issues peculiar to Nigerian women.⁴²⁷ The major factor is the influence of culture and how it impacts on feminism for African women. Some of the areas where culture affects the rights of women and affects the perspective of feminism in Nigeria include but are not restricted to female inheritance of landed property, harmful traditional widowhood practices, FGM⁴²⁸, and protection of female reproductive rights.

The features of feminism include the empowerment of women and protection of women's rights. The argument of African and Nigerian scholars with feminism from the international perspective is the erroneous belief that theories on political science, sociology, law, and gender issues are culturally neutral universally and any reference to an African perspective is considered out of date and stigmatised.⁴²⁹ Chegwe, in his work emphasised the need to harmonise common law principles of the western culture vis a vis the cultural and traditional practices of the indigenous communities in the implementation of laws.⁴³⁰

Oluwole in criticising the feminist perspective on Nigerian laws stated that the Nigerian and African researchers failed to analyse the gender discourse with the Nigerian perspective in

⁴²⁷ Emeka Chegwe, 'A Gender Critique of Liberal Feminism and its Impact on Nigerian law' (2014) 14(1) *International Journal of Discrimination and the Law* 66.

⁴²⁸ Female Genital Mutilation.

⁴²⁹ Sophie Oluwole, 'Reproductive Health and Rights: Philosophy and an African Perspective' [2006]: In Ezeilo J (ed.) *Law, Reproductive Health, and Human Rights*, WACOL, 68.

⁴³⁰ Emeka Chegwe, 'A Gender Critique of Liberal Feminism and its Impact on Nigerian law' (2014) 14(1) *International Journal of Discrimination and the Law* 67.

mind.⁴³¹ Nigerian feminists like Funmilayo Ransome-Kuti (of blessed memory) began fighting for the rights of the Nigerian woman in recognition of the challenges when it comes to having her voice heard in the enforcement of her rights.⁴³² The liberal feminist in Nigeria believes the subordination of women which limit their capacity in the public domain with men, is as a result of constitutional and cultural gaps in gender.⁴³³ All of these writers have highlighted the difference in feminism perspective between the western and African women to be rooted in culture.

The exclusion of women in the workings of the Nigerian legal system is seen in the process of the committees which draft the laws before they are passed. Another critic Atsenuwa stated that the process of precluding women in the Constitution making process was from the colonial era and proceeded into the drafting of the 1979 Constitution of Nigeria.⁴³⁴ The Drafting Committee for the 1999 Constitution was made up of men and the Provisional Ruling Council was made up of 26 male military officers.⁴³⁵ The feminists criticise the language of the Nigerian Constitution (as earlier mentioned) to be worded to promote the patriarchal tradition and limit the powers accorded to Nigerian women.⁴³⁶ The word “he” is used 233 times in the 1999 Constitution while “woman” is used just twice supporting the position of the feminist that

⁴³¹ Sophie Oluwole, ‘Reproductive Health and Rights: Philosophy and an African Perspective’ [2006]: In Ezeilo J (ed.) *Law, Reproductive Health, and Human Rights*, WACOL, 68.

⁴³² Cheryl Johnson-Odim and Nina Mba, ‘For Women and the Nation: Funmilayo Ransome-Kuti of Nigeria’ (University of Illinois Press, 1997) 6-8.

⁴³³ Emeke Chegwe, ‘A Gender Critique of Liberal Feminism and Its Impact On Nigerian Law’ (2014) 14(1) *International Journal of Discrimination and the Law* 69.

⁴³⁴ Ayo Atsenuwa, ‘Jurisprudential Issues in Reproductive Health’ (2007) paper presented at Capacity Building Workshop for Law Lecturers on Reproductive Health and Rights organised by Legal Research and Resources Development Centre, Golden Gate Hotel, Abuja, 24 October 2007, p. 9 -Available at <https://www.vangaurdngr.com>, (Accessed 12 November 2021).

⁴³⁵ Emeke Chegwe, ‘A Gender Critique of Liberal Feminism and Its Impact on Nigerian Law’ (2014) 14 *International Journal of Discrimination and the Law*, 1, 69.

⁴³⁶ *Ibid.*

there is a need to de-robe the Nigerian Constitution of its masculine clothes and make it gender sensitive to include women.⁴³⁷

Another issue which is prevalent in the Nigerian Constitution that has come under criticism is the issue of a woman who marries a man from a different tribe or ethnic group in Nigeria, concerning her “rights”. In reality, women who have married out of their ethnic group are sometimes denied rights and positions on the basis of their marriage and they are also denied appointments and political posts in their marital homes on the grounds that they were married into the family and not originally from the same ethnic group as their husbands. *Section 42(1) of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria* prohibits the discrimination of a citizen of Nigeria on grounds of ethnic group, place of origin, sex, religion, amongst others but the same law in *Section 42(3)* limits the right to freedom concerning the application of public offices including the armed forces.⁴³⁸

The plight of Nigerian women is not made any easier by the fact that Nigeria is a federal republic, and each state has the legislative authority by the Constitution to draft its own laws. The different regions are governed by different laws but with a federal character and it is difficult to harmonise legislation and eradicate all discriminatory measures in the legal system. The Nigerian legal system is a combination of common law, civil, customary, and religious laws which makes it a complicated system of laws.

The following questions which come to the mind of the researcher are these; Is Nigeria ready to accept the western form of feminism? Are Nigerian women willing to embrace western feminism and do what is necessary to protect and promote their rights? These questions arose based on some of the responses from the survey especially in the analysis as was revealed

⁴³⁷ Ibid.

⁴³⁸ Ibid.

during the data collection with emphasis from the northern region of Nigeria. This might not be unreasonable in tracing its origin when reflected on regarding the activities of the Boko Haram sect who say no to western education for girls. Part of the purpose of this study is to close the gap between feminism by Nigerian women and feminism by western women, by understanding their differences in facilitating access to justice and expression of their rights as women. This gap can be closed by educating society and women especially on the cultural differences which exist between them. For example, a Nigerian woman could choose to mourn her husband in the traditional ways of their culture which is her right as his wife (which might include being indoors for a period of time and wearing mourning colours) but a western woman might perceive that to be an imposition on her rights as an individual or a woman. It is necessary to understand how feminism is understood and expressed by women, considering factors such as cultural, religious, and other values in the promotion of their rights in accessing justice.

4.11 Feminist Perspectives of Family Mediation

There has been some criticism from feminist writers on the efficacy of mediation as it affects women's rights in family dispute resolution. Some feminists like Maxwell have stated that mediation is another form of patriarchal control over women's rights.⁴³⁹

These feminists criticise mediation as another form of male dominance over women's rights so long as the sexist culture exist as there is no check on how the process is regulated due to the private nature of mediation. To which they argued mediation should be avoided as this could be more harmful to women who participate as there is no public scrutiny to ensure women's rights are not abused by male partners or non-feminist mediators. Part of the reason for the criticism of mediation is the unequal bargaining power between men and women. The patriarchal structure established over centuries have systemised women as the weaker vessel

⁴³⁹ Nancy Maxwell, 'The Feminist Dilemma in Mediation' (1992) 4(1) *International Review of Comparative Public Policy*, 67 at 68.

to men and consequently reduced their bargaining power in negotiations during mediation.⁴⁴⁰ Other writers like Semple have emphasised the power imbalance which exists in the family mediation as the women usually bear the responsibility of considering the welfare of the children and there are parenting issues to be considered in the resolution of the dispute.⁴⁴¹ On the other side of this argument is the position that mediation is compatible with women as it affords the avenue to address the roots of the dispute and arrive at a sustainable resolution.⁴⁴² Maxwell has described mediation as the only form of conflict resolution which accommodates female traditional values and fosters relationships.⁴⁴³ Other conflict resolution methods such as litigation, arbitration, etc do not foster female values. The purpose of feminist perspective is to analyse the impact of mediation on women's rights in the resolution of family disputes. It is the position of Maxwell and other like-minded writers that mediation is too important as a conflict resolution process to be dismissed but should be structured in a manner to address the power imbalances and protect the weaker party. This could be achieved by training mediators to recognise tell-tale signs of abuse or dominion by one party and infuse the process with feminist values and goals. The researcher agrees with this position that mediation is very useful as a dispute resolution process in family conflicts and proper training of mediators in recognising the issues of power imbalance, neutrality of mediators amongst other issues will address the criticisms of family mediation by feminists.

4.12 The Role of Non-Governmental Organisations in Nigeria and International Conventions.

⁴⁴⁰ Martha Shaffer 'Divorce Mediation: A Feminist Perspective' (1988) 46 Faculty of Law Review 162 at 181.

⁴⁴¹ Noel Semple, 'Mandatory Family Mediation and the Settlement Mission: A Feminist Critique' (2012) 24(1) Canadian Journal of Women and the Law 207 at 212.

⁴⁴² Nancy Maxwell 'The Feminist Dilemma in Mediation' (1992) 4(1) International Review of Comparative of Public Policy 68.

⁴⁴³ Ibid.

This section of the study reveals the role of non-governmental organisations in promoting women's access to justice in Nigeria. The importance of international conventions, regional treaties, and national laws and how they affect women's rights will be discussed. The activities of NGOs like FIDA and the impact they have in the lives of women will be evaluated. This is the heart of this study, to tell the story of Nigerian women as they navigate the halls of justice through the process of family mediation. Countries like Nigeria are quick to be members of international organisations or signatories to international conventions because of the grants and benefits they receive from the international community. Implementing the conventions, to which they are signatories is a different matter. NGOs strive to implement these conventions when they have been ratified and domesticated in the promotion of rights of women and children as provided by the Nigerian Constitution. The purpose of this section is to highlight how FIDA as an NGO promotes the rights of women.

Nigeria as signatory to treaties and conventions which protect human rights, is yet to fulfil its obligations in enforcing the treaties on the protection of women's rights in the daily lives of Nigerian women.⁴⁴⁴ International conventions such as CEDAW⁴⁴⁵ and other treaties which provide for the welfare of women are applied by NGOs in Nigeria in the enforcement of rights of women as mentioned earlier in this study. Most of the international and regional conventions and treaties have not been domesticated according to the provisions of the Nigerian Constitution and consequently cannot be implemented.⁴⁴⁶ The Nigerian Constitution stipulates

⁴⁴⁴ Bolanle Eniola, 'Gender Parity in Parliament: A Panacea for the Promotion and Protection of Women's Rights in Nigeria' (2018) 3(34) *Journal Frontiers in Sociology* 1.

⁴⁴⁵ United Nations Convention on the Elimination of Discrimination Against Women.

⁴⁴⁶ Bolanle Eniola, "Gender Parity in Parliament: A Panacea for the Promotion and Protection of Women's Rights in Nigeria" (2018) 3(34) *Journal Frontiers in Sociology* 1.

that no treaty shall have force of law in Nigeria except it has been domesticated.⁴⁴⁷ The conventions and treaties which promote women's rights seek to enforce gender parity in member countries. This is a major challenge in Nigeria which NGOs seek to improve on. Other NGOs such as the Women in Politics (WIP)⁴⁴⁸ strive to increase the participation of Nigerian women in governance and politics to affect the passing of laws which would lead to more favourable laws for women. The lack of sufficient involvement of women in the legislative process in Nigeria has had a negative impact on the empowerment of women.⁴⁴⁹ A good illustration of this position was expressed in 2016 when the Bill on Gender and Equal Opportunity failed at its second reading at the Nigerian Senate on the 15th of March 2016. Out of the 109 senators in the house, only 7 of them were women. It is logical to conclude this was as a result of low representation of women in the Nigerian Senate.

It is common knowledge that Gender equality is No 5 of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) of the United Nations. SDG No 5 is targeted at ensuring quality education for girls, prohibiting child bride marriages, empowerment of women's right through legal processes, amongst others.⁴⁵⁰ The pandemic has slowed down the progress of this goal as presently only 25.6% of national parliament and 28.2% of managerial positions are occupied by women and an there is an increase of 10 million girls at risk of child marriages.⁴⁵¹ The 35% affirmative

⁴⁴⁷ Section 12 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria provides: "*No treaty between the Federation and any other country shall have the force of law to the extent to which any such treaty has been enacted into law by the National Assembly*".

⁴⁴⁸ Women in Politics, an NGO.

⁴⁴⁹ Bolanle Eniola, 'Gender Parity in Parliament: A Panacea for the Promotion and Protection of Women's Rights in Nigeria' (2018) 3(34) *Journal Frontiers in Sociology* 2.

⁴⁵⁰ <https://greenly.earth/en-gb/blog/ecology-news/what-are-the-united-nations-sustainable-development-goals> (Accessed 8 February 2023).

⁴⁵¹ <https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/report/2021/goal-05/> (Accessed 8 February 2023).

action policy directed at increased participation of Nigerian women in governance and politics is yet to be implemented since its proclamation in 2015.

World Bank data has stated that, in comparison to other African countries such as Rwanda where the women have 56% of the seats at parliament, Nigeria has a low 7% women representation.⁴⁵² In South Africa, the women constitute about 40% of the members of parliament, while in Burundi, 42% of the members of parliament, who are also deputies in the National Assembly are women.⁴⁵³ These African countries are signatories to various international conventions and regional treaties and are obligated to implement the provisions of the treaties in their respective countries. Sadly, from the above statistics, Nigeria does not seem to be making rapid progress.

4.12.1. Convention on Elimination on All Forms of Discrimination Against Women, (CEDAW) 1979

To illustrate the role of international conventions and the importance of the provisions on the rights of women, we will examine CEDAW in detail. As mentioned earlier CEDAW was established by the United Nations in 1979 to eliminate all forms of discrimination against women. It defines discrimination as, *“any distinction, exclusion or restriction made on the basis of sex which has the effect or purpose of impairing or nullifying the recognition, enjoyment or exercise by women, irrespective of their marital status, on a basis of equality of men and women, of human rights and fundamental freedoms in the political, economic, social, cultural, civil, or any other field”*.⁴⁵⁴ Nigeria signed the convention on the 23rd of April 1984, ratified it on 13th of June 1985 without reservations and ratified the Optional Protocol to

⁴⁵² Bolanle Eniola, ‘Gender Parity in Parliament: A Panacea for the Promotion and Protection of Women’s Rights in Nigeria’ (2018) 3(34) Journal Frontiers in Sociology 6.

⁴⁵³ Ibid.

⁴⁵⁴ United Nations, Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women, Article 1.

CEDAW on the 8th of September, 2001.⁴⁵⁵ As at May 2001, 168 countries had ratified CEDAW without reservations, and 46 were African countries.⁴⁵⁶ With this act the expectation would be greater protection for women's rights, but the reports as earlier stated in the statistics and the data from the survey and interviews, women in Nigeria still encounter challenges in the enforcement of their rights. This is despite the periodic reports given by Nigeria in accordance with *Article 18* of CEDAW.⁴⁵⁷

The discrimination and challenges women encounter in the enforcement of their rights, has been linked to ideological and structural factors.⁴⁵⁸ It is the opinion of writers like Okome that with the provisions of international conventions and regional treaties, women should not suffer discrimination. The persistence of these challenges is due to structural factors of member States. Some of the provisions of the conventions which protect the rights of women include protection from discrimination against gender.⁴⁵⁹ Nigeria became a signatory to this convention on the 29th of July 1993. Consequently, if the provisions of the convention were being complied with, the women in Nigeria should experience low if any discrimination as to gender. But we can see from earlier literature highlighted in this study that women in Nigeria experience discrimination like their counterparts in other regions. Women's productive rights consist of personal rights in the family, social, economic, and political rights in society. The objective of the international conventions and regional treaties are to alleviate the rights of women including their reproductive rights. Which is why the laws prohibit child bride marriages in the

⁴⁵⁵ Mojbol Okome 'Domestic, Regional and International Protection of Nigerian Women against Discrimination: Constraints and Possibilities' (2002) 6(3) African Studies Quarterly 33.

⁴⁵⁶ Ibid.

⁴⁵⁷ Ibid.

⁴⁵⁸ Mojbol Okome 'Domestic, Regional and International Protection of Nigerian Women against Discrimination: Constraints and Possibilities' (2002) 6(3) African Studies Quarterly 45.

⁴⁵⁹ International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights 1966, Article 2(1).

different provisions. The reproductive rights of a woman include the right to decide what to do with her body and control the size of her family, including family planning decisions.

CEDAW emphasizes on gender parity in its provisions by stating that Signatories, “modify the social and cultural patterns of conduct of men and women, with a view to achieving the elimination of prejudices and customary and all other practices which are based on the idea of the inferiority or the superiority of either of the sexes or on stereotyped roles for men and women”.⁴⁶⁰ Despite these provisions, women are first still being defined by their reproductive and accompanying roles in Nigeria. Society recognises men as predominantly the head of the household and this transcends to administrative capacities outside the home. An example of some of the inequalities between men and women in Nigeria which CEDAW attempts to balance with gender parity is the unfairness of how adultery is grounds for divorce only when it is the woman who commits it.

The inability of CEDAW to be effective in the protection of women’s rights as it was established to do, is as a result of the inadequate compliance with its provisions by member States. Some of the States are slow in submitting reports and have introduced so many reservations which have made CEDAW a ceremonial convention.⁴⁶¹ The challenge with international conventions and regional treaties is when the member State Parties fail to provide international guarantees by providing periodic reports, it leads to self-policing which results in abuses.⁴⁶² To eliminate the discrimination against women in Nigeria, the activism to protect and promote women’s rights must continue, from the grassroots to the highest levels in society.

⁴⁶⁰ Convention on Elimination of all forms of Discrimination Against Women, Article 5(a).

⁴⁶¹ Mojbol Okome, ‘Domestic, Regional and International Protection of Nigerian Women against Discrimination: Constraints and Possibilities’ (2002) 6(3) African Studies Quarterly 53.

⁴⁶² Ibid.

For this objective to be achieved, the assistance of NGOs and well-meaning organisations, including government parastatals are needed.

4.12.2 FIDA as A Non-Governmental Organisation (NGO) and Women’s Access to Justice

There are several NGOs involved in the protection of women’s rights, but this research will focus on FIDA and the Nigerian Chapter particularly. The International Federation of Women Lawyers – *Federacion Internacional de Abogadas (FIDA)*⁴⁶³ was founded in 1944 by a group of 5 women lawyers in Mexico. They were Rosalind Bates (America), Esther Talamantes (Mexico), Luisa Maria Capo (Puerto Rico), Isabel Sierro Pérez (Cuba) and Alma Paredes (Salvador).

The IBA⁴⁶⁴ Conference had held in Mexico that year and Rosalind Bates was a candidate for the board of the Association. She was not accepted because she was a woman. As a result of the discriminatory culture of the IBA, Rosalind Bates and Esther Talamantes decided to form a women lawyers association⁴⁶⁵, which gave birth to FIDA. Esther Talamantes was the first president hence the Spanish name. She had met Rosalind Bates at the Congress of International Association of Lawyers in Mexico, 1944. FIDA currently has members from 73 countries. As an association of women lawyers, FIDA has grown beyond looking out for the welfare of its members to the protection and promotion of rights of women and children.

Aim of FIDA

The aim of FIDA globally is the organisation of women lawyers in different nations, regions, and internationally in promoting the study of comparative law and maximising opportunities

⁴⁶³ www.fidafederation.org (Accessed 31 January 2023).

⁴⁶⁴ International Bar Association.

⁴⁶⁵ www.fidafederation.org (Accessed 31 January 2023).

for women.⁴⁶⁶ The aims of FIDA include the protection, promotion of the cultural, social, civil, and political rights of women as well as the welfare of children. FIDA has possessed consultative status with United Nations Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC) since 1954. To effectively execute its duties, the various chapters over the world partner with various bodies and groups as well as government parastatals.

FIDA Nigeria

In 1964, the Nigerian branch was established by Ambassador Aduke Alakija.⁴⁶⁷ There are 44 branches of FIDA legal centres in the 36 states of Nigeria.⁴⁶⁸

Funding

The members of the association pay annual dues and make donations which are used in overseeing the daily activities of the association and annual events such as the Children's Day and International Widows Day celebrations. FIDA also partners with well-meaning individuals and corporations to raise funds to execute the programs of its objectives.

Some of the partners include the MacArthur Foundation and Goal Global.⁴⁶⁹ The funding received allows FIDA expand the scope of work and ensures a wider range of women are reached. Examples of some of the contracts awarded to FIDA by the MacArthur Foundation include:

1. Effective use and Strengthening the Criminal Justice System to Reduce Corruption in Nigeria

⁴⁶⁶ <https://fidafederation.org/en/> (Accessed 16 February 2023).

⁴⁶⁷ <https://fida.org.ng> (Accessed 1 May 2023).

⁴⁶⁸ Abia, Adamawa, Anambra, Akwa Ibom, Akwa Ibom-Eket, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Delta-Warri, Ebonyi, Edo, Enugu, Ekiti, FCT-Abuja, Abuja-Gwagwalada, Gombe, Imo, Katsina, Kaduna, Kaduna-Zaria, Kano, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Lagos-Badagary, Lagos-Ekpe, Lagos-Ikorodu, Lagos-Ikeja, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Rivers, Taraba, Yobe, Sokoto, and Zamfara.

⁴⁶⁹ <https://www.devex.com/organizations/international-federation-of-women-lawyers-fida-nigeria> (Accessed 17 February 2023).

2. For Work with Gatekeepers, Including Traditional Rulers, Women, Religious Leaders to Social Norms That Entrench Violence Against Women and Girls Values That Negatively Affect Their Status in Society
3. Strengthening The Capacity of Legal Professionals
4. Adoption of the Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act (VAPP) to Achieve Gender Equality

The aim of these contracts is to alleviate the plights of Nigerian women and FIDA combines the execution of the above projects with their daily activities at the FIDA Legal Centre.

Duties of FIDA

The average Nigerian girl grows up into womanhood under the patriarchal system of being treated to second place in a male dominated society.⁴⁷⁰ She becomes a woman, knowing the enforcement of her rights is an uphill task which sometimes begins with her family. FIDA Nigeria being aware of this reality, in its daily activities in line with its mission and vision statement seeks to alleviate the struggles of Nigerian women by implementing the laws which promote and protect women's rights. The duties of FIDA are regulated by the FIDA Bye Laws which regulate the activities. Some of the constitutional duties of FIDA include but not limited the following:

- Sensitization of the public on the rights of women and children
- Conducting legal mobile clinics, especially in rural areas where complaints are heard
- Hosting town hall interactive meetings with the public
- Mediating over family disputes and representing women in pro bono cases in court. In some litigation matters, FIDA holds watching brief to ensure justice is served to in the protection of human rights.

⁴⁷⁰ Godiya Makama, 'Patriarchy and Gender Inequality in Nigeria: The Way Forward' (2013) 9(17) European Scientific Journal 115.

FIDA performs its duties by enforcing the provisions of international laws which have been domesticated and included in the provisions of the national laws such as the *VAPP*⁴⁷¹ Act of 2015. FIDA also has several publications of articles and journals on the protection of women's rights.⁴⁷²

Sometimes members have to rescue women who are in a violent situations at home by alerting the police and proceeding to the scene with the police. If the woman has no safe place to go to, as there are no women shelters, members sometimes provide refuge for the women. Other times members contribute money for indigent women who have spent their last money in transporting themselves to the FIDA centre to complain and have no means of going back home. One of the recent incidents reported at the centre was of a FIDA member who had rescued a baby by the roadside and taken the child to the hospital and police station before dropping off the child at the motherless babies' home situated in Port Harcourt, Rivers State.⁴⁷³

Impact of NGOs in the Lives of Nigerian Women

NGOs such as FIDA provide the platform for women in Nigeria to exercise their rights and grant access to justice which would have been impossible for some women. The provision of family mediation services has allowed families resolve family disputes which have resulted in better welfare and improved relations in family life as revealed in the interviews. The mobile legal clinics conducted causes sensitization and raises awareness on the rights of women and informs the public on different paths to access justice.

In relating legal consciousness of Nigerian women with the work done by NGOs, empirical evidence was gathered during the interviews, which will be discussed in detail in Chapters Six

⁴⁷¹ Violence Against Persons Prohibition Act.

⁴⁷² <https://fida.org.ng/articles-publications/> (Accessed 1 May 2023).

⁴⁷³ FIDA Legal Centre Incident Report, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, 28/04/2023.

and Seven of this research. Several participants stated that their access to justice was ensured by FIDA, as represented in the statement below by one participant:

“Question: Do you think the Nigerian government is doing enough for women, when it comes to enforcing their rights?

Response: I can’t talk about Nigerian government, the one that helped me is FIDA”.⁴⁷⁴

The above response is evidence of the impact of FIDA on the legal consciousness of Nigerian women in accessing justice. Women benefit from the sensitization programmes and are aware of their rights including the structures available for assistance such as legal aid. The effect is that less women are willing to submit to abuse of their rights and have better quality of life. The NGOs and FIDA, influence public policy with their activities as it concerns women and children in Nigeria. Corporate bodies and institutions are compelled to recognise the existence of NGOs like FIDA with the publicising of women’s rights and ensure the welfare of female employees. The impact of FIDA is felt in the home and in the corporate world. It provides a sense of security to the women, knowing there is a place of refuge where their complaints can be heard and acted upon.

4.13. Conclusion

The Nigerian environment needs to acknowledge the prevailing reality of the social, cultural, political, and economic impact of women and the fact that the world of women has evolved beyond what it used to be. The literature as stated above has shown that there is a plethora of international laws which protect the rights of women. Most of them have been replicated in the national laws of Nigeria and the challenge appears to be the implementation of these laws.

What this research seeks to reveal is to unearth the reason Nigerian women are subjected to the form of “control” by culture, religion, procedural bottlenecks, and other challenges they encounter. In seeking satisfaction in the justice, they seek, and not just the justice handed to

⁴⁷⁴ Interview with Participant 2, FIDA legal centre Anambra State, held on 13/01/2022 at 13:20hrs.

them by culture or society, NGOs such as FIDA with sufficient support from the government can achieve more. This chapter has established the above challenges as the reasons why Nigerian women's access to justice is restricted.

CHAPTER FIVE

ACCESS TO JUSTICE THROUGH FAMILY MEDIATION

5.1 Introduction

The objective of this chapter is to provide an understanding of family mediation as a process to justice, for purposes of this research. This chapter defines dispute resolution and alternative dispute resolution which is sometimes used interchangeably in the resolution of disputes and conflicts. The objective is to ensure a background understanding of the dispute resolution process. In discussing Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR), the various types will be highlighted to facilitate our appreciation of the ADR process. The existing laws on mediation universally and in Nigeria as it concerns women's access to justice will be discussed.

The scope of this study revolves around family mediation and its impact on the Nigerian legal framework including informal family mediation. It is necessary to understand the difference between informal and formal mediation and how they influence family mediation. The role of culture and tradition and their impact on informal and formal mediation as it relates to women's rights will form part of the focus of this chapter and this study. This section will conclude with an explanation of the perspective of Nigerian women on family mediation in Nigeria.

5.2 Types of Dispute Resolution

Dispute resolution methods consist of any process adopted to resolve a dispute. Some of the recognised types of dispute resolution consist of the following: Litigation, Negotiation, Mediation, Arbitration, Conciliation, Collaborative law, Facilitation, Avoidance, and many more.⁴⁷⁵ Dispute resolution processes can be divided into:

- Adjudicative: where the dispute is presided over by a judge or arbitrator, such as litigation and arbitration.

⁴⁷⁵ Albert Fiadjoe *Alternative Dispute Resolution: A Developing World Perspective* (Routledge Cavendish Publishing Limited 2004) 20.

- Consensual: the parties attempt to resolve their dispute through the help of a third party through processes such as mediation, negotiation, conciliation, and other collaborative law.

5.3 Difference between Adjudicative and Consensual Processes

Adjudicative processes include litigation and arbitration methods of dispute resolution which are adversarial in nature. The litigation system was overloaded in many countries which led to delays in court hearings and judgment, and this was not limited to civil matters.⁴⁷⁶

The consensual process is inquisitorial in nature and consist of mediation, negotiation, and other ADR processes.

5.4 Dispute Resolution and Alternative Dispute Resolution

Family mediation as a method of dispute resolution is classified in the alternative dispute resolution category. The term dispute resolution and alternative dispute resolution are used interchangeably which has made it difficult to define the concepts in clear terms. Alternative dispute resolution is subsumed in dispute resolution in reality. A dispute arises when one party fails to respond satisfactorily to an aggrieved party, and a legal dispute arises when a claim is founded on a legal entitlement as defined by some writers.⁴⁷⁷ Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) is therefore viewed as dispute resolution processes which are alternatives to court procedures as depicted by writers such as Mackie.⁴⁷⁸ The term “Dispute Resolution” is a dynamic process which is broad as it is all encompassing of all methods of settling disputes between parties. It is therefore necessary to understand the connotations which make up the

⁴⁷⁶ Karl J. Mackie, *A Handbook of Dispute Resolution -ADR in action*, (Routledge, 1991)18.

⁴⁷⁷ Jethro Liebermant and James Henry, ‘Lessons from the Alternative Dispute Resolution Movement’ (1986) 53(2) University of Chicago Law Review 2, 426.

⁴⁷⁸ Karl J. Mackie, *A Handbook of Dispute Resolution -ADR in action*, (Routledge, 1991) 14.

dispute resolution process. There is the view that conflicts are deeper than disputes and is an indication as to the manner in which the dispute should be resolved.

In this research conflicts and disputes are used interchangeably as the focus of this work is not the definitions of the terms but in the meaning of the concept they represent. Disputes can occur at any place, at home, at work, during commercial transactions, in religious places, and any public place. There are different types of disputes, and this research is based on the disputes which arise in the family environment between a husband and a wife, or a man and a woman cohabiting together in a domestic environment, etc. The concept of family as understood within this research will be explained in detail later in the chapter. One of the most fundamental elements of human existence is the ever-present phenomenon of conflict and disputes.

Dispute resolution is a practice as old as time. Conflicts and disputes arise wherever human beings live and reside. Resolution of dispute is a natural expectation when there is a conflict, and it adopts different forms. The desire to seek the intervention of a third party when a dispute arises is as natural as human existence and was practised from the days of old.⁴⁷⁹ History shows us in various stories of ages past how disputes arose from biblical times and how the disputes were resolved. A very popular story is the story of King Solomon who had to decide which of the two women was the mother of the baby who was alive as opposed to the other baby who was dead.⁴⁸⁰ This story is traditionally considered to be the philosophical foundation of ADR.⁴⁸¹ Conflicts and disputes are an inexplorable part of human existence.

⁴⁷⁹ Thomas McFarlane, 'Mediation: The Future of Dispute Resolution in Contemporary Scots Family Law' (2012) 3(28) Aberdeen Student L. Rev. 1.

⁴⁸⁰ 1 Kings 3: 16-28.

⁴⁸¹ Joseph Nwazi, 'Assessing the Efficacy of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) in the Settlement of Environmental Disputes in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria' (2017) 9(3) Journal of Law and Conflict Resolution 26.

Disputes, disagreements, and conflicts are unavoidable in relationships in every environment whether family, social, commercial, or business. Though conflict and dispute are sometimes seen to be the same, the understanding of the concepts have been interpreted to be different as conflict has been described as being more complex than the background of a dispute.⁴⁸² The implication is that a conflict goes deeper than a dispute. Dispute resolution has been described as the process of resolving disputes or conflicts between parties, though conflicts are termed to be long standing and deeper than disputes.⁴⁸³ John Burton is of the view that conflict resolution is aimed at resolving the issue by analysing the generic nature of the problem and not merely the immediate social or ethnic dispute.⁴⁸⁴ Which promotes the objectives of ADR as futuristic in its processes.

There are different types of disputes which occur in various dimensions and environment such as the home, workplace, marketplace, in the streets even business transactions and when a dispute arises, the next course is to seek a resolution.⁴⁸⁵ In seeking the resolution of a dispute, it is advisable the appropriate resolution process is chosen. There is a school of thought which postulates that there is a spectrum of dispute resolution mechanisms designed to match the different disputes of the universe.⁴⁸⁶ The adversarial methods of dispute resolution which include litigation, would be best suited to contentious issues which require adducing of

⁴⁸² Anna Nylund 'Access to justice: Is ADR a help or hindrance?' in Laura Ervo and Anna Nylund (eds): *The Future of Civil Litigation - Access to Courts and Court-annexed Mediation in the Nordic Countries* (Springer 2014) 325-344.

⁴⁸³ John Burton, *Conflict: Resolution and Prevention* (St Martin's Press, New York 1990) 7.

⁴⁸⁴ John Burton, *Conflict as A Political System* (Centre for Conflict Analysis and Resolution, 1988) 8.

⁴⁸⁵ Sunday Fagbemi, 'Assessing the Efficacy of Mediation as a Form of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) Mechanism in Nigeria' (2020) 8(2) *Humanities, Management, Arts Education & the Social Sciences Research Journal* 2.

⁴⁸⁶ Karl J. Mackie, *A Handbook of Dispute Resolution -ADR in action*, (Routledge, 1991) 17.

evidence. This approach popularly known as the “win/lose” as distinguished from the “win/win” of the non-contentious approaches which does not require formalities of procedures.

5.5 Understanding Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR)

The literature surrounding alternative dispute resolution suggests that it is an alternative to the traditional process of litigation but, in reality it is a part of the dispute resolution process which includes court annexed procedures.⁴⁸⁷ The realization that not all disputes fit into the narrow straight requirements of litigation has led to the need for alternative dispute resolution. In litigation the outcome is win/lose and not problem solving which focuses on the relationship between the parties taking into cognisance the past, present and the future.⁴⁸⁸

Proponents of ADR do not seek to oust the jurisdiction of the courts and lawyers from resolving disputes but desire to promote more skills in the dispute resolution processes targeted at an appropriate resolution of the dispute. The term ‘Alternative Dispute Resolution’ is the widest description of dispute resolution processes other than litigation.⁴⁸⁹

ADR arose from the criticisms of the early reformers of the judicial system who blamed the technicality, formality, and adversarial nature of the courtroom as the reason for the dissatisfaction of parties. It is believed that the relations between parties and their attitude to legal actions is marred by procedural obstacles and legal wrangling of lawyers who are obsessed with scoring technical victories.⁴⁹⁰ Liebermant and Henry are of the school of thought that ADR processes can settle current disputes and prevent the development of disputes.⁴⁹¹

⁴⁸⁷ Karl J. Mackie, *A Handbook of Dispute Resolution -ADR in action* (Routledge, 1991)17-18.

⁴⁸⁸ Ibid.

⁴⁸⁹ Karl J. Mackie, *A Handbook of Dispute Resolution -ADR in action* (Routledge, 1991) 19.

⁴⁹⁰ Karl J. Mackie, *A Handbook of Dispute Resolution -ADR in action* (Routledge, 1991) 18.

⁴⁹¹ Jethro Liebermant and James Henry, ‘Lessons from the Alternative Dispute Resolution Movement’ (1986) 53(2) University of Chicago Law Review 424.

They define ADR as a set of practices and techniques which allow legal disputes to be resolved outside the courtrooms to the advantages of the disputing parties; reduces the delays of conventional litigation and cost; as well as prevent certain disputes from being brought to the courts.⁴⁹²

ADR can be viewed as either a process where parties privately choose to avoid litigation, or the legal provisions allow the courts refer the matter to a court annexed process. The range of procedures of ADR serve as alternatives to litigation through the court processes, resolving disputes which involve the intercession and assistance of an impartial neutral third party.⁴⁹³

5.5.1 Development of Alternative Dispute Resolution

ADR evolved out of an annual convention of the American Bar Association in Hawaii with the theme, 'Resolving Disputes in Pacific Ways' after over two decades of reflecting on the concept of 'Alternative Dispute Resolution'.⁴⁹⁴ ADR means an alternative to litigation as a means of dispute resolution which introduces new legal mechanisms for resolving conflict.

The American Bar Association (ABA) is of the view that ADR evolved to supplement and not supplant the traditional approaches to resolving conflict. ADR has provided a stimulating platform for the varied forms of dispute resolution with its new applications of older methods of dispute resolution and emphasis on the broader education of lawyers, both in America and the UK.⁴⁹⁵

⁴⁹² Jethro Liebermant and James Henry, 'Lessons from the Alternative Dispute Resolution Movement' (1986) 53(2) University of Chicago Law Review 426.

⁴⁹³ Adrian Pop, 'Traditional Approaches in Alternative Dispute Resolution: A brief overview' [2014] Conflict Quarterly Studies No 7, 35.

⁴⁹⁴ Karl J. Mackie, "Dispute resolution: a new wave" in *A Handbook of Dispute Resolution-ADR in action* (Routledge, 1991) 14.

⁴⁹⁵ Karl J. Mackie, "Dispute resolution: a new wave" in *A Handbook of Dispute Resolution-ADR in action* (Routledge 1991) 15.

Goldberg *et al* ⁴⁹⁶ identified four goals of the ADR as:

To relieve the congestions of the courts and reduce delay.

To enhance community involvement in the dispute resolution process.

To facilitate access to justice.

To provide more “effective” dispute resolution.

ADR IN NIGERIA

ADR process is not new to Nigeria but part of the culture and was in existence before the advent of colonialism. Disputes were settled traditionally by reporting to elders in the family or community. The formalisation of the ADR process in Nigeria began with the Negotiation and Conflict Management Group (NCMG)⁴⁹⁷ in 1999, which was the pioneer foundation for ADR practice in Nigeria.⁴⁹⁸ Presently in Nigeria, there is the Institute of Chartered Mediators and Conciliators (ICMC), Chartered Institute of Arbitrators (CI Arb) -Nigeria, and the Institute of Advance Legal Studies which also promotes ADR processes. The ICMC is responsible for the training of mediators in Nigeria.

5.6 Mediation as a Form of Alternative Dispute Resolution

The crux of this research is family mediation as distinguished from the other forms of ADR. It is therefore necessary for an in depth understanding of mediation and its origins as this will assist our understanding of why some countries like Alabama, Florida, etc make mediation mandatory.⁴⁹⁹ In countries like Australia and China, where mediation is mandatory, it is as a court annexed process with exceptions on domestic violence. In Nigeria, mediation is not a

⁴⁹⁶ Stephen Goldberg, Eric Green and Frank Sanders (1985) in Karl J. Mackie, “Dispute Resolution: a new wave” -*A Handbook of Dispute Resolution, ADR in action* (Routledge 1991) 16.

⁴⁹⁷ Negotiation and Conflict Management Group, <https://ncmginternational.org/> (Accessed 9 May 2023).

⁴⁹⁸ Joseph Nwazi, ‘Assessing the Efficacy of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) in the Settlement of Environmental Disputes in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria’ (2017) 9(3) *Journal of Law and Conflict Resolution* 26 at 28.

⁴⁹⁹ https://csrcm.cass.anu.edu.au/sites/default/files/docs/2019/2/CSRM_WP2_2017_60ICERT_APPENDIX_B.pdf (Accessed 19 May 2023).

mandatory process of dispute resolution for family disputes, but the courts provide the structure for formal mediation and can refer parties to mediation as it deems fit.

5.6.1. Definition of Mediation

To understand family mediation, there must first be an understanding of mediation. The word ‘mediate’ is derived from the Latin word “mediare” which means to be in the middle.⁵⁰⁰ Mediation has been defined as the “intervention into a dispute or negotiation by an acceptable, impartial and neutral third-party who has no authoritative decision-making power to assist disputing parties in voluntarily reaching their own mutually acceptable settlement of issues in dispute”.⁵⁰¹ In the 1980s, Mediation was defined as an intervention by a third party who assists parties to resolve their disputes: even further described as a sleeping giant as a result of the possibilities of positive contributions which could enhance the development of dispute resolution.⁵⁰²

One school of thought defines mediation as a procedure based on the voluntary participation of the parties, where an intermediary (or several intermediaries) with no adjudicatory powers in a systematic process facilitate(s) communication between the disputing parties with the focus of ensuring the parties take responsibility for resolving their dispute.⁵⁰³

Another legal opinion expresses mediation as a non-binding process where a neutral third party called the Mediator with no decision-making power, assists disputing parties in a negotiation

⁵⁰⁰ Sunday Fagbemi, ‘Assessing the Efficacy of Mediation as a Form of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) Mechanism in Nigeria’ (2020) 8(2) Humanities, Management, Arts Education & the Social Sciences Research Journal 6.

⁵⁰¹ Christopher Moore, *The Mediation Process: Practical Strategies for Resolving Conflict* (Jossey Bass San Francisco, 1986) 14.

⁵⁰² Jethro Lieberman and James Henry, *The Manager’s Guide to Resolving Legal Disputes: Better Results Without Litigation*, (Harper & Row, New York, 1985) 169.

⁵⁰³ Klaus J. Hopt and Felix Steffek, *Mediation: Principles and Regulations in Comparative Perspective*, (Oxford Scholarship 2012) 34.

to achieve an agreed resolution of the mediation.⁵⁰⁴ Centre for Effective Dispute Resolution (CEDR) defined mediation as a flexible process of dispute resolution conducted by an impartial neutral in confidentiality, where disputing parties are assisted in achieving terms of resolution or negotiated agreement while in control of the process.⁵⁰⁵ Mediation is also defined as a non-binding process where a neutral third party called the Mediator with no decision-making power, assists disputing parties in a negotiation to achieve an agreed resolution of the mediation.⁵⁰⁶

The various definitions broaden the mind on the key components and features of mediation and our understanding is facilitated with the following quote by Alexander Bevan:

*“It is amazing how little true communication takes place during the litigation process and conversely how much each side learns about the other side’s case and what the real issues are when they take part in mediation”.*⁵⁰⁷

The key components in the above definitions remain the involvement of an impartial or neutral third party assisting the disputing parties arrive at a mutually agreed resolution while observing the process in confidentiality.

5.6.2 History of Mediation

The origin of mediation, as a form of ADR, can be traced to traditional societies where the building and maintenance of long-term relationships were the foundation of the society.⁵⁰⁸

Mediation is natural to all society. Legal literature has stated that at about 350 BC, a popular

⁵⁰⁴ Albert Fiadjoe, *Alternative Dispute Resolution: A Developing World Perspective* (Routledge Cavendish Publishing Limited, 2004) 57.

⁵⁰⁵ The Centre for Effective Dispute Resolution, Europe’s largest service provider published this definition in 2004.

⁵⁰⁶ Albert Fiadjoe, *Alternative Dispute Resolution: A Developing World Perspective* (Routledge Cavendish Publishing Limited, 2004) 57.

⁵⁰⁷ Alexander Bevan, *Alternative Dispute Resolution – A Lawyer’s Guide to Mediation and other forms of Dispute Resolution*, (Sweet & Maxwell, 1992) 26.

⁵⁰⁸ Albert Fiadjoe, *Alternative Dispute Resolution: A Developing World Perspective* (Routledge Cavendish Publishing Limited, 2004) 57.

historian Plutarch had told the story of two men who appointed the King Archidamus II to resolve the dispute between them. The story states that he took them to an isolated temple, extracted an oath from them to abide by his decision, then gave his decision as: “stay here till you have made up your quarrel”.⁵⁰⁹ In doing so, the core feature of mediation being the ability of the Mediator not to control the resolution process but allowing the parties to explore the cause of their dispute and the best possible solution, is illustrated. The concepts of confidentiality, neutrality of third party and the desire for an amicable settlement to promote the relationship of the parties is also illustrated in this story which are the core values of mediation as a form of dispute resolution.

Alexander had stated that “mediation is a process which is both new in terms of its emergence in the legal arena and old in terms of its timeless universality.”⁵¹⁰ Contrary to the view that mediation is a modern alternative to the traditional methods of dispute resolution, it must be pointed out that mediation has existed in different forms in the different cultures around the world. Fiadjoe postulates that, “mediation is a folk concept which existed prior to the evolution of state law, legal system and lawyer-litigators.”⁵¹¹

Different peoples and races have their traditional methods of dispute resolution of which some can be traced to mediation as far back as ancient times, such as the Malaysian race where the traditional method of dispute resolution is mediation based on their Confucian and Adat beliefs on compromise and yielding, in a conflict.⁵¹² In Trinidad & Tobago, mediation has long ago been the traditional method of dispute resolution which has reinforced community and societal

⁵⁰⁹ Ibid.

⁵¹⁰ Albert Fiadjoe, *Alternative Dispute Resolution: A Developing World Perspective* (Routledge Cavendish Publishing Limited, 2004) 58.

⁵¹¹ Ibid.

⁵¹² Reginald Hickling, *Malaysian Law* (Professional (Law) Books Publishers 1987) 136 -141.

cohesion during conflicts, whether individual or communal.⁵¹³ It is reported that in most cultures of the world, the origin of mediation lies in the traditional process of dispute resolution where a respectable person in the society is called upon to mediate in a dispute between neighbours, spouses, etc as was in the Hindu villages in India and in African societies.⁵¹⁴

The African communities are not excluded. In some communities, there were (and still are) village councils, which oversee the activities of the villagers especially in resolving disputes and it was mandatory that disputes be brought to the village council before recourse was made to the courts.⁵¹⁵ Similar to the African system is the Panchayat, which means ‘settlement of dispute by the elders within the East Indian Community’ where these elders presided over disputes, ranging from family to property disputes.⁵¹⁶ In this manner, family relationships were preserved, marriages were saved, and family properties restored. The Panchayat system is also recognised by the High Court of Trinidad & Tobago that a decision reached by the Panchayat and agreed to by the disputing parties can be enforced by a Court Order.

5.6.3 Features of Mediation

As a process of dispute resolution, mediation possesses certain characteristics which sets it apart from the other processes of dispute resolution. Part of the attraction of ADR resides in the flexibility and control by the parties which accompany access to justice processes. Hopt and Steffek in their opinion on dispute resolution, have identified certain features as the characteristics of mediation.⁵¹⁷ The distinguishing feature of mediation in contrast to the other

⁵¹³ Helen Alves, ‘Mediation: A Method of Alternative Dispute Resolution’ [1999] *Hugh Wooding Law School Journal- The Junior Counsel*, 36.

⁵¹⁴ *Ibid.*

⁵¹⁵ Philip Britton ‘Alternative Dispute Resolution’ (1999) *The Guyana Law Review* 108 -109.

⁵¹⁶ *Ibid.*

⁵¹⁷ Klaus J. Hopt and Felix Steffek, *Mediation: Principles and Regulations in Comparative Perspective*, (Oxford Scholarship 2012) 36.

forms of dispute resolution such as negotiation, arbitration, adjudication, and others including other professional interventions such as social work⁵¹⁸ lies in the following features:

Mediation is voluntary: An essential feature of mediation is the free will of the disputing parties in the entire process, without any form of compulsion.

Neutrality: In mediation, the third-party neutral who is the mediator, has no authority in making decisions for the disputing parties. The parties agree to resolve their dispute and bear the consequences of their agreement while the mediator remains neutral.

Impartiality: Another distinguishing characteristic of mediation is the impartiality or neutrality of the mediator who cannot be partial to any of the parties despite his personal convictions. This characteristic enhances the confidence of the parties and promotes openness which leads to faster and more agreeable resolutions.

Confidentiality: The confidentiality of the mediation process is part of its attractiveness to disputing parties especially if the dispute is a sensitive one as in most family matters.

Non-binding: The mediation procedure is straightforward, non-binding and without prejudice.

5.6.4 Advantages of Mediation

It is necessary to highlight the advantages of mediation to enhance our study in appreciating mediation as a process of dispute resolution. The following advantages as stated by Alexander Bevan⁵¹⁹ are:

Flexibility-The pace of the process is dictated by the parties which is guided by the phrase “as fast as the clients want it” and it usually does not exceed 5 hours. Parties are not bound by precedents and are free to make and follow their own rules, within reason. There is also

⁵¹⁸ Marian Roberts, *Mediation in Family Disputes- Principles of Practice* (3rd edn, Ashgate Publishing Limited, England, 2008) 2.

⁵¹⁹ Alexander Bevan, *Alternative Dispute Resolution – A Lawyer’s Guide to Mediation and other Forms of Dispute Resolution* (Sweet & Maxwell London, 1992) 18 – 25.

certainty of hearing date as parties have the power to choose the time, date, and location of the hearing which is a great advantage over the court system. There is freedom of will of the parties, as they can walk out anytime (except where there is a court order).⁵²⁰

Control and Confidentiality- The process is private and strictly confidential. Parties have control over who is in attendance, thereby ensuring no unwanted presence and maintaining confidentiality.⁵²¹ In mediation the client can control his lawyer in a positive way unlike litigation where the client has no say on the procedure adopted by his lawyer and sometimes the lawyer can become personally involved in the outcome. Mediation enables the parties to control the settlement process and eliminate risks on the outcome of the dispute rather than at the whims and caprices of an arbitrator or judge who wakes up on the wrong side of the bed.

Cost Effective- It is less expensive as early settlement saves managerial time as the process is cheaper than arbitration and litigation in terms of professional fees and incidentals.⁵²²

Preservation of relationship between parties- mediation aims at solutions which satisfy the interests of all.⁵²³ Where one side suffers more, the engaging process of the parties which leads to a settlement, can enhance the relationship due to the process.

Variety of Resolution remedies- The mediation process proffers a greater variety of remedies than litigation. Settlements which include face-saving concessions which are non-legal and satisfying. The first sign to settle is a sign of strength and not weakness as is usually interpreted

⁵²⁰ Alexander Bevan *Alternative Dispute Resolution – A Lawyer’s Guide to Mediation and other Forms of Dispute Resolution* (Sweet & Maxwell London, 1992) 18.

⁵²¹ Ibid.

⁵²² Alexander Bevan *Alternative Dispute Resolution – A Lawyer’s Guide to Mediation and other Forms of Dispute Resolution* (Sweet & Maxwell London, 1992) 19.

⁵²³ Ibid.

in a conflict. If the parties are in agreement, the mediator can float the settlement proposals without either side making that so called weak first offer.⁵²⁴

Neutral Expert- Mediation enables a truly neutral expert to be selected who can dispassionately advise and suggest novel options previously not considered to address complex technical issues.⁵²⁵

In highlighting the advantages of mediation, Bevan has also stated that it is necessary to acknowledge what disadvantages exist, such as: the non-binding nature of the process could result in any party walking out at any time before a resolution is reached, the lack of procedural protection for the disputing parties, no measures for checks and balances to assess the objectiveness of the process.

Other literary jurists⁵²⁶ are of the opinion that mediation is preferable to adjudication, especially in neighbourhood disputes resolution based on the following assumptions: mediation addresses the roots of problems, mediation is fairer and speedier. Other justifications for mediation as stated by Tomasic and other writers are that mediation enhances communication between the disputing parties. Mediation encourages the parties to be cordial and the mediator is seen as a “friend” by the parties and not a “stranger”. Parties solve the problem themselves as they have control over the process and choose the best solution themselves with guidance from the mediator. With mediation, it is easier to access the legal system as it is simple and easy to understand. Due to mediation centres being less formal than the courts, and therefore non bureaucratic due to their flexible structure, parties are more at ease. Other advantages of

⁵²⁴ Alexander Bevan *Alternative Dispute Resolution – A Lawyer’s Guide to Mediation and other Forms of Dispute Resolution* (Sweet & Maxwell London, 1992) 20.

⁵²⁵ Alexander Bevan *Alternative Dispute Resolution – A Lawyer’s Guide to Mediation and other Forms of Dispute Resolution*, (Sweet & Maxwell London, 1992) 21.

⁵²⁶ Roman Tomasic, *Mediation as an Alternative to Adjudication: Rhetoric and Reality in the Neighbourhood Justice Movement*, (Longman, New York, 1982) 215.

mediation over adjudication include reduction of court congestion and delays, and it allows a wide range of disputes to be resolved through mediation.

The uniqueness of mediation lies in the fact that mediators do not have to be professionally trained to practise particularly in informal mediations. But in formal mediation, formal training is required with emphasis on court annexed matters. Previously specialised training was not needed but this position has changed in modern times as mediators are now trained professionally as promoted by institutes such as the Institute of Chartered Mediators and Conciliators.

5. 7. International Legislation on Mediation

Mediation has evolved from the simple process of oral hearings of a dispute by a neutral 3rd party or parties, to laid down legislations which regulate the mediation process. Various jurisdictions and countries have legislations which regulate the ADR processes which include the process of mediation.⁵²⁷ The purpose of discussing international legislation on mediation is to show the universal nature of mediation and in countries where family mediation is practised if relevant. The international sector is not left out but provides legislation which regulates mediation processes. Though documentation of international legislation on family mediation was scarce, this study considers mediation under civil and commercial transactions to highlight the principles of mediation which are inherent in the process when adopted in family mediation. Some of the international legislation considered though mostly regulates commercial mediation, consist of the following:

UNCITRAL Model Law on International Commercial Conciliation: provides suggestions for the regulation of mediation with regards to commercial transactions.

⁵²⁷ Arbitration and Conciliation Act, Cap A18 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004: Family Law (Scotland) Act 2006.

The Cross-Border Mediation (Scotland) Regulations 2011:⁵²⁸ This regulation serves as a guide to member states of the European Union on civil and commercial matters in the promotion of the use of mediation as a process of alternative dispute resolution. The Directive 2008/52/EC imposed certain standards in respect of cross-border dispute mediation where at least one of the disputing parties is a domiciled member state. Though the directive was issued on civil and commercial matters, it included domestic mediation, of which Scotland had already provided for in its Sheriff Court rules. The exit of some countries from the European Union with Brexit will affect the application of this directive. Different authors have opined in their views the different effect this regulation has on different countries.⁵²⁹ The uniformity of the regulations would be affected by the exit of member states with Brexit.

UNCITRAL Model Law on International Commercial Mediation and International Settlement Agreements Resulting from Mediation 2018 (the Singapore Convention): This Model Law was adopted by the United Nations in 2002 and amended in 2018. It is structured to serve as a guide to States in reforming and updating their laws on mediation procedure. The Model Law acts as a uniform set of rules concerning the mediation process. It promotes the use of mediation and ensures stability and predictability in its application.

European Code of Conduct: The European Union in expressing its support for mediation, in 2004 developed these guidelines for the training and regulation of mediators and was adopted on the 21st of May 2008.⁵³⁰ These guidelines served as directives to member states.

⁵²⁸ <https://www.lexology.com/library/detail> (Accessed 18 October 2021).

⁵²⁹ Klaus Hopt and Felix Steffek, *Mediation: Principles and Regulation in Comparative Perspective* (Oxford University Press, 2018) 24.

⁵³⁰ Bryan Clark, *Lawyers, and Mediation* (Springer Heidelberg New York 2012) 23.

Australian Mediation Act 1997 (Repealed):⁵³¹ This Act though repealed, has been republished under different editorial changes.⁵³² The repealed provisions make regulations for the standards to which mediators would be expected to adhere to and the procedure which governs the mediation process.⁵³³ Some authors like Carroll have agitated the need for a uniform legislation for mediation that would be all inclusive and not restricted to a particular category as the repealed Act appeared to provide more for the mediators.⁵³⁴

Alternative Dispute Resolution Act, 2010, Act (798):⁵³⁵ Ghana makes provision for the different methods of alternative dispute resolution in this Act but specifically provides for mediation in Part 2 where it regulates the process of mediation.⁵³⁶ There have been arguments that despite the tremendous legislative efforts made in the alternative dispute resolution process, the process is unlikely to succeed if certain important issues are not taken into consideration. Fundamental issues such as the appropriateness of the dispute to mediation, the informed participation of parties, maintenance of confidentiality, the role of the court in the enforcement of the outcome of the mediation agreement and other issues.⁵³⁷ The recognition of these fundamental issues expresses the practical nature of the Act.

⁵³¹ <https://www.legislation.act.gov.au/a/1997-61> (Accessed 13 October 2012).

⁵³² Republication No 5, Effective April 8 2016, <https://www.legislation.act.gov.au/a/1997-61> (Accessed 13 October 2012).

⁵³³ Mediation Act 1997, Sections 4-6 <https://www.legislation.act.gov.au/a/1997-61> (Accessed 13 October, 2012).

⁵³⁴ Robyn Carroll, 'Developments in Mediation Legislation' (2002) 5 ADR Bulletin 5, <http://epublications.bond.edu.au/adr/vol5/iss5/5> (Accessed 13 October 2021).

⁵³⁵ Ghanaian Constitution <https://lawsghana.com/post-1992-legislation/table-of-content/Acts%20of%20Parliament/ALTERNATIVE%20DISPUTE%20RESOLUTION%20ACT> (Accessed 14 October 2021).

⁵³⁶ Alternative Dispute Resolution Act 2010, Act 798, Sections 63 – 88 www.lawsghana.com (Accessed 14 October 2021).

⁵³⁷ Clara Kasser-Tee, *Mediation in Ghana: A Critical Examination of How Act 798 Seeks to Improve Mediation And The Mediation Process In Ghana* (2017) 179 <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341741968> (Accessed 14 October 2021).

The Constitution of the Republic of South Africa 1996 (Bill of Rights - Chapter 2):⁵³⁸ This chapter makes provision for voluntary court annexed mediation rules to assist in the reduction of case management in civil proceedings. They are provided for in Chapter 2 of the Magistrates' Court Rules and are distributed over the different provinces. The seriousness of the court to annex mediation as a judicial method of dispute resolution was illustrated in the case where a judge capped the fees of counsel for not first advising parties to explore mediation in a family dispute before rushing to court.⁵³⁹

Indian Code of Civil Procedure 1908 – Section 89:⁵⁴⁰ This provision allows the court refer matters for mediation and are often used in matrimonial disputes involving divorce cases. Mediation in India developed from the judgment of the Supreme Court in the case of *Salem Advocate Bar Association v. Union of India*.⁵⁴¹ The Court constituted a committee from this case which drafted the *Model Rules 2003* that served as a model for the High Courts and ensured the better implementation of *Section 89* and the quicker dispensation of justice.⁵⁴²

All the above legislation provides for conventional mediation and some of which regulate family disputes in the various regions. From the above-mentioned legislation, there appears to be no apparent international recognition or convention which provides expressly for family mediation. It would seem from the legislation, each country or region formulates laws and policies that are best suited to its society and those laws are adopted in the regulation of family disputes.

⁵³⁸ <https://www.justice.gov.za/mediation/mediation.html> (Accessed 14 October 2021).

⁵³⁹ MB v NB 2010 (3) SA 220 (GSJ) 15.

⁵⁴⁰ <https://www.legalserviceindia.com/legal/article-2762-mediation-in-india.html> (Accessed 16 October 2021).

⁵⁴¹ Salem Advocate Bar Association v. Union of India (2005) AIR SC 3353.

⁵⁴² Deepika Kinhal and Apoorva, "Mandatory Mediation in India – Resolving to Resolve" (2021) 2(2) Indian Public Policy Review 49 at 51.

5.7.1. International Legislation on Mediation and Women

It is trite that women's rights are human rights. Part of the objective of this chapter is to identify or lack of international legislation on family mediation with a focus on an in-depth analysis of the different international conventions as they impact on women's access to justice. There are numerous regulations which guide the international practice of ADR in different regions and this research considers some of them to examine the relation of these laws in the protection of the rights of women particularly in dispute resolution of family conflict. It is the intention of this study to consider the impact of these conventions on local laws of Countries like Nigeria. International Conventions such as the sections of the *Maputo Protocol* which provide for the protection of women's rights⁵⁴³ are yet to include any provisions on women's access to justice to which family mediation would be included regarding this research.

5.8. Types of Mediation

The scope of mediation as a process of dispute resolution includes commercial, workplace, diplomatic, family, and matrimonial causes. These different disputes occur in various environments and can be resolved through mediation – commercial, environmental, workplace, neighbourhood, and family. Though these types of disputes are regulated by the principles of mediation, there are features which accompany the different types of mediation, but we will focus on family mediation in relation to this study.

5.8.1 Family Mediation

Before we proceed to family mediation, it is necessary to define family for the purpose of this research. Colins et al have described family from the perspective of structure and the safety it provides for its members.⁵⁴⁴ From the 1970s, a straightforward criterion of the definition of

⁵⁴³ Section 8 of Maputo Protocol highlights the rights of women while promoting equality between men and women and protecting women from discrimination.

⁵⁴⁴ Donald Colins, Cathleen Jordon and Heather Coleman, *An Introduction to Family Social Work* (Cengage Learning, 2010) 28.

family was given from the unit of a household.⁵⁴⁵ This was understood to mean members of a household living as a family. Widmer explains in his article, the “bridging” factor between family configurations such as stepparents, and relatives, while the “binding” factor in family is blood.⁵⁴⁶ There is a need to understand pseudo-family such as people who have lived a lifetime in a household and are considered part of the family. For purposes of this research family will be understood from the perspective of persons who are connected by consanguinity or affinity. Family mediation occurs when there is a dispute between family members, including divorce and post-divorce matters.⁵⁴⁷ This does not however mean that all disputes which arise in the family should be resolved by mediation, as there are exceptions such as domestic violence, wills, public policy, and capital offences. The distinct nature of family mediation does not allow it to be effectively regulated by the general procedures of mediation. Family mediation consists of family members who have a disagreement amongst themselves, usually couples whose relationships are in crisis and need the intervention of a third party to assist in facilitating a resolution.

Family disputes are distinguished from other forms of disputes due to the involvement of emotions which encompass hostility, bitterness, fear, resentment, and embarrassment.⁵⁴⁸ The different forms of dispute settlement people value or cherish are based on their personal perceptions of themselves and the quality of relationships they have with others, whether they prefer to encourage conflicts, avoid them or resolve disputes amicably.⁵⁴⁹ It has been proposed

⁵⁴⁵ Eric Widmer, ‘Who are my family members? Bridging and binding social capital in family configurations’ (2006) 23(6) *Journal of Social and Personal Relationships* 980.

⁵⁴⁶ *Ibid.*

⁵⁴⁷ Amanda Boniface, ‘African -Style Mediation and Western – Style Divorce and Family Mediation: Reflections for the South African Context’ (2012) 15 *PER / PELJ* 5, 4.

⁵⁴⁸ Thomas McFarlane, ‘Mediation: The Future of Dispute Resolution in Contemporary Scots Family Law’ (2012) 3(28) *Aberdeen Student L. Rev.* 1.

⁵⁴⁹ Jerome Auerbach, *Justice Without Law?* (Oxford University Press, New York, 1983) 3-4.

by some authors that the use of family mediation, which evolved from ancient methods of settling quarrels, is probably better in resolving family disputes as a result of the special characteristics that are peculiar to family disputes.⁵⁵⁰ The core values of mediation practice namely: respect for the authority of the parties and the right to make their own decisions is the main reason why mediation is advocated for in the resolution of family disputes. It is trite that when parties are the architects of the solution to their dispute, it is more valued and ensures compliance with the resolution reached. Mediation provides a calm and safe environment for disputing parties, whose emotions might already be running high due to the sensitive issues which characterise family disputes. It provides the opportunity for self-determination and independence as well as ensuring parties retain control over the issues arising from the dispute.

5.8.2 Understanding Family Mediation

Family mediation is the service technology intended to help divorcing couples resolve their differences.

- Michael Benjamin and Irving Howard.

Cleak et al are of the view that the use of mediation as a process of dispute resolution in the family would ensure the continuity of a cordial relationship between the parties especially where children are involved, without the challenges of litigation.⁵⁵¹ The advantages that were promoted by mediation activists led to scholars and researchers exploring and developing the theories of mediation. From the 1970s when modern mediation formed its roots, researchers kept developing theories based on outcomes of resolutions which culminated in the establishment of the first family mediation service in Britain in 1978.⁵⁵² The rising prominence

⁵⁵⁰ Marian Roberts, *Mediation in Family Disputes -Principles of Practice*, (3rd edn Ashgate Publishing Limited, England, 2008) 1.

⁵⁵¹ Helen Cleak, Margot Schofield and Andrew Bickerdike, 'Efficacy of Family Mediation and the Role of Family Violence: Study Protocol' [2014] BMC Public Health 4.

⁵⁵² Helen Cleak, Margot Schofield and Andrew Bickerdike, 'Efficacy of Family Mediation and the Role of Family Violence: Study Protocol' [2014] BMC Public Health 5.

of family mediation resulted in some academics conducting research, which amounted to fifty-one studies in terms of the processes and outcome of family mediation, though the studies are based on English and North American works. The conclusion of the studies was that family mediation is an effective and efficient mode of dispute resolution that if maximised can be more resourceful in assisting disputing couples going through a divorce, than litigation.⁵⁵³ This led to some jurisdictions like Connecticut and Massachusetts making family mediation mandatory in 1980 and California had done the same in 1981.⁵⁵⁴ Other jurisdictions in America also made family mediation mandatory by 1989 and the number was at 4,500.⁵⁵⁵

The research literature has shown that the outcome of the administration of family mediation must be interpreted with caution as a result of the varying influencing factors which characterise different regions.⁵⁵⁶ There are varying procedures of family mediation in the different regions, but a main dimension is the dispute resolution forum which is the court based public mediation in contrast to the private mediation.⁵⁵⁷

Some of the differences between the court or public mediation and the private mediation are portrayed in the following situations:⁵⁵⁸ the hours of a court-based mediation are an average of four hours of service over a period of one to three sessions, while private mediation offers

⁵⁵³ Michael Benjamin and Howard Irving, 'Research in family mediation: Review and Implications, (1995) 13 *Mediation Quarterly*, 3.

⁵⁵⁴ Connie Beck and Bruce Sales, *Family Mediation: Facts, Myths and Future Prospects* (1st edn, Washington DC, American Psychological Association, 2001) 7.

⁵⁵⁵ James Melamed, 'Attorneys and Mediation: From Threat to Opportunity' (1989) 23(13) *Mediation Quarterly* 15.

⁵⁵⁶ Michael Benjamin and Howard Irving, 'Research in Family Mediation: Review and Implications' (1995) 13 *Mediation Quarterly*, 4.

⁵⁵⁷ Jessica Pearson, 'The Equity of Mediated Divorce Settlements' (1991) 9(2) *Mediation Quarterly* 179 – 197.

⁵⁵⁸ Michael Benjamin and Howard Irving 'Research in family mediation: Review and Implications' (1995) 13 *Mediation Quarterly*, 3.

about ten hours of service over a duration of five to ten sessions. The second situation is that private mediation is either on a profit-based fee for service or non-profit cost recovery basis while court-based mediation is free of charge. Other variations which result in the differences between court and private based mediation reside in the client groups, the model of mediation procedure, the different legal environment in operation, including the identity and training of the mediators providing the service. These variations make it difficult to ascertain the extent of knowledge of mediation practice.⁵⁵⁹ The style of resolving mediation and calculating billable hours is not the usual practice in Nigeria but the difference between private and court-based mediations are the same. The court allows and encourages private based mediation by ensuring that agreements from other forms of ADR are enforceable.⁵⁶⁰

There were also further studies conducted which confirmed the view that court-based mediators who were lawyers and had received forty hours of mediation training only, were not qualified to address the complexities of family conflicts especially in marital disputes.⁵⁶¹ This lack of adequate mediation skills resulted in the mediators' inability to assist their clients understand the deep relational challenges which characterises family disputes which culminated in the failure of couples to reach a compromise on the dispute.

It was also postulated that there was a higher tendency for family mediation to end in agreement especially where there existed an ongoing relationship between the parties in the dispute, such as children in common⁵⁶² when compared to other forms of mediation such as neighbourhood

⁵⁵⁹ Michael Benjamin and Howard Irving Research in family mediation: Review and Implications (1995) 13 *Mediation Quarterly* 3.

⁵⁶⁰ *K.S.U.D.B. v. Franz Const. Co. Ltd* ((1990)4 *NWLR* pt. 142, 183-184.

⁵⁶¹ William Donohue, Laura Drake and Anthony Roberto, 'Mediator Issue Intervention Strategies: A Replication and Some Conclusions' (1994) 11(3) *Mediation Quarterly* 261-274.

⁵⁶² Raymond Whiting, 'Family Disputes, Nonfamily Disputes, and Mediation Success' (1994) 11(3) *Mediation Quarterly* 247-260.

mediation. It was contended that the multiple issues of family mediation allowed more flexibility to the mediators to guide the parties to an agreement, as opposed to the single-issue other forms of mediation such as the neighbourhood mediation addressed.

5.8.3 The Rights of the Child and Family Mediation

In discussing women, it is common to include children especially on issues of welfare, rights, and infringement of those rights. Though the focus of this study is women and the impact of family mediation, a very brief mention would be made of children as they are often the beneficiaries and considerations of most family mediations.

As a legal practitioner conducting legal matters over the years, one salient fact stands out in every family dispute where there are children, the woman is reluctant to leave the home or marriage because of the children. Consequently, a brief mention of the rights of a child to family life is necessary.

5.8.4 International Conventions on the Rights of the Child

*Convention on the Rights of the Child:*⁵⁶³ This international treaty was adopted and ratification by the United Nation's General Assembly resolution 44/25 of 20 November 1989 and entered into force 2nd September 1990, in accordance with Article 49. The implementation of this convention is monitored by the Committee on the Rights of the Child. *The Convention on the Rights of the Child* is premised on four core principles- *the best interest of the child, the right to life and development, non-discrimination, their views in the decisions affecting them according to their age and maturity.*⁵⁶⁴

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights recognises the need for special protection and assistance for motherhood and childhood the right for all children to have social protection.⁵⁶⁵

⁵⁶³ <https://www.ohchr.org/documents/professionalinterest/crc.pdf> (Accessed 30 October 2021).

⁵⁶⁴ <https://www.unicef.org/child-rights-convention> (Accessed 30 October 2021).

⁵⁶⁵ Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948), Article 25(2) <https://www.ohchr.org/en/udhr> (Accessed 30 October 2021).

Child's Rights are defined in numerous ways and classified into civil, social, cultural, political, and economic categories.

The African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child.⁵⁶⁶ This Convention was adopted on the 1st of July 1990 by the Organisation of African Unity (OAU) (now the African Union) and entered into force 29th of November 1999. The African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child is drafted alongside the principles of the *Convention on the Rights of the Child*.

Nigeria makes provision for the rights of a child, in the *Child's Rights Act of 2003*⁵⁶⁷ of which the best interest of the child is the paramount consideration in all legal matters involving children. The *Child's Rights Act* clearly states that children have a right to private and family life.⁵⁶⁸ As part of a family, children have the right to the benefits of family life which most women usually fight for in the lives of their children. The duty of women to protect the rights of their children is trite and is common in Nigeria (most traditions are silent on this issue). It is an unspoken rule that the mother is responsible for the welfare of her children. In some of the family disputes the researcher has mediated on in the past where the man is deceased, the family members leave the widow to fend for herself and her children, irrespective of the properties of their late father except where he has left a will and the widow is educated enough to fight for her children. This is the connection between protecting women's right and the rights of children in access to justice in the resolution of family disputes.

5.9 Legal Framework for ADR, Mediation in Nigeria

The development of ADR has provided alternative to the resolution of disputes which is instrumental to the growth of a nation's economy. Due to the limitations of the adversarial process of dispute resolution, which is basically litigation, the need for a legal framework on

⁵⁶⁶ <https://au.int/en/treaties/african-charter-rights-and-welfare-child> (Accessed 17 January 2022).

⁵⁶⁷ <http://lawsofnigeria.placng.org/laws/C50.pdf> (Accessed 17 January 2022).

⁵⁶⁸ Child's Right Act 2003, Section 8.

ADR became necessary. The lack of sufficient legislation in Nigeria to regulate the process of mediation as an ADR process has not stopped the process as a form of dispute resolution.

The High Court (Civil Procedure) Rules makes provision for procedures such as consent judgment.⁵⁶⁹ The courts allow provisions such as consent judgment⁵⁷⁰ to be entered on behalf of parties which allows the practice of mediation as the parties can record their settlement from mediation and the court enters it on their behalf. As was illustrated in *Vulcan Gases Ltd v. Okunlola*⁵⁷¹ where the Court of Appeal held per Achike, J.C.A that the terms of agreement reached by the parties out of court settlement, formed part of the court's judgment. The major legislation which regulates ADR processes in Nigeria is the *Arbitration and Conciliation Act Cap A18 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004*. There have been calls for amendment to this legislation as some of the provisions still contain the Statutes of General Application which were received during the colonial administration.⁵⁷² The Nigerian legal system consists of customary laws as mentioned earlier in this study and the laws should reflect this factor more so in ADR legislation. The need for adequate legislation to regulate ADR process in Nigeria led to the passing of the *Arbitration and Mediation Bill (AMB) 2022* by the Senate on the 10th of May 2022.⁵⁷³ Though it is yet to receive presidential assent, (as at the time of conducting this research) but it is expected to improve the process of mediation as an access to justice in Nigeria. Other legislation which regulates ADR processes in Nigeria include *Section 29(1)* of

⁵⁶⁹ Lagos State High Court (Civil Procedure) Rules of 2019, Order 39 Rules 6 and 7.

⁵⁷⁰ It is the judgment record of the terms of settlement mutually agreed by parties to a dispute and it binds the parties in any lawful court of competent jurisdiction.

⁵⁷¹ *Vulcan Gases Ltd v. Okunlola* (1993) 2 N.W.L.R, Pt 274, 139.

⁵⁷² Greg Nwakoby, 'Arbitration and Conciliation Act Cap A18 Laws of the Federation 2004 – Call for Amendment' [2010] African Journals Online, 6.

⁵⁷³ Denis Ogunbowale, "Reflections and Prospects of the Arbitration and Mediation Bill 2022" (2022) 13(4) Business and Property Law 123.

the *International Chamber of Commerce (ICC) Arbitration Rules 2017* which allows emergency arbitral proceedings.

For the regulation of family mediation in Nigeria, though there is no specific legislation, the applicable legislation begins from the Nigerian Constitution to all the local legislation which regulate family disputes. Sources of Nigerian family law have been identified as customary law, Islamic law and statutory or enacted legislation.⁵⁷⁴ Consequently, all the laws are applicable in the resolution of family disputes, including informal mediation which is influenced by customs and tradition.

Alternative Dispute Resolution is one of the thematic areas of Nigeria's National Policy on Justice 2017. The policy emphasized that there is an increasing recognition and use of formal ADR mechanisms in settling disputes in the country, but the full potential of the method is yet to be fully tapped or realized. As stated in the policy, the problems associated with ADR in Nigeria include low patronage, underdeveloped legal framework, lack of regulation, problem of enforcement, and non-recognition of ADR in criminal matters. The strategic intervention actions to address the problems include the reforming the ADR legal framework, training stakeholders about ADR, setting up additional ADR mechanisms, and the encouragement of the use of the ADR platform.

5.10 Local Laws on Family Mediation and the Rights of Women

The federal laws as highlighted in Chapter Four of this work apply to all the states of the federation. Specific laws on women's rights are enacted by the states in accordance with the provisions of federal laws such as the *Matrimonial Causes Act* and the *Violence Against Persons Prohibition (VAPP) Act 2015*. The traditions and culture in most parts of Nigeria are similar especially in areas of women's rights.

⁵⁷⁴ Angela Obidimma, 'Arbitrating Family Disputes in Nigeria: Benefits and Challenges' (2021) 3(2) *International Journal of Comparative Law and Legal Philosophy* 69.

The rights of women which are enshrined in *Chapter IV of the 1999 Nigerian Constitution*, are violated by various acts under the guise of culture and tradition. The provisions of the Constitution should be upheld for the benefit of all persons without fear or favour. The violations of the rights of women have led to states also enacting their laws. The various states have local laws which are enacted by the state assembly in addition to national laws which protect the rights of women.

Most of the laws are influenced by the traditions and customs of the state. Some of these laws are – *Rivers State Dehumanising and Harmful Practices Abolition Law No 2 of 2003*, *Rivers State Prohibition of the Curtailment of Women’s Right to Share in Family Property Law No. 2 of 2022*⁵⁷⁵, *Rivers State Abolition of Female Circumcision Law No 2 of 2001*. Other laws from other states in Nigeria include⁵⁷⁶; *Enugu State Prohibition of Infringement of a Widow’s and Widower’s Fundamental Rights Law No. 3, 2001*, *Edo State Female Circumcision and Genital Mutilation (Prohibition) Law No. 4 of 1999*, *Ekiti State Gender-Based Violence (Prohibition) Law, 2011*, *Osun State Protection Against Domestic Violence Law, 2013*, *Domestic Violence Law of Lagos State, 2007*, *Jigawa State Gender Policy, 2013*, and others.

Most of the state laws protecting women’s rights and access to justice in Nigeria revolve round inheritance, and harmful traditional practices such as FGM⁵⁷⁷, widowhood practices and basic human rights. The laws on FGM have penalties provisions. For instance, *Section 4* of the *Cross River State Girl-Child Marriages and Female Circumcision (Prohibition) Law 2000* provides:

“Any person who person who performs FGM, offers herself for FGM, coerces, entices or induces another to undergo FGM or allows any female who is either a daughter or ward to undergo FGM is liable on conviction to a fine of not less than 10,000 Naira

⁵⁷⁵ <https://tribuneonlineng.com/women-and-inheritance/> (Accessed 7 May 2023).

⁵⁷⁶ <https://www.justice.gov/eoir/page/file/1227121/> (Accessed 7 May 2023).

⁵⁷⁷ Female Genital Mutilation.

*(US \$27.7011) or to imprisonment not exceeding two years for a first offender (and to imprisonment not exceeding three years without an option of fine for each subsequent offence).*⁵⁷⁸

After the introduction of the *VAPP Act of 2015*, Ebonyi State introduced penalty provisions to include five-year prison sentence for anyone who performs FGM.⁵⁷⁹ The Edo State *Prohibition of Female Genital Mutilation Law 1999* states the penalty for FGM is not less than three years imprisonment or a fine of not less than 3,000 Naira, or both.⁵⁸⁰ The titles of the laws indicate the abuse the laws seek to abolish and the area of the culture and tradition which needs to be challenged. The challenge resides not in the laws but the enforcement of the laws when a dispute has occurred when women's rights have been violated. Some writers like Owoseye have noted that the inconsistency which plagues access to justice lies in the passing and enforcement of laws in Nigeria.⁵⁸¹ On the regulation of family mediation, there is no formal legislation and informal mediation is regulated by culture and traditional practices.

5.11 Informal and Formal Family Mediation

This study focuses on family mediation from the informal and formal perspective as stated earlier. Mediation in Nigeria can be divided into two - Informal and formal. This part of the literature of this study seeks to highlight the features of informal mediation alongside formal mediation with particular focus on Nigeria.

⁵⁷⁸ Cross River State Girl-Child Marriages and Female Circumcision (Prohibition) Law 2000, Section 4 <https://www.refworld.org/pdfid/5b3497357.pdf> (Accessed 8 May 2023).

⁵⁷⁹ Edo State Prohibition of Female Genital Mutilation Law 1999 <https://www.refworld.org/pdfid/5b3497357.pdf> 4 (Accessed 8 May 2023).

⁵⁸⁰ Hon. Justice N. A. Imoukhuede (undated) 'Female Genital Mutilation (FGM) A Crime In Edo State' <http://edojudiciary.gov.ng/wp-content/uploads/2016/10/Femal-Genital-Mutilation-Fgm-A-Crime-In-Edo-State-By-Hon-Justice-N-A.pdf>. (Accessed 8 May 2023).

⁵⁸¹ Ayodamola Owoseye 'Why Nigerian Govt Must Enforce Laws Against Female Genital Mutilation – Expert', (2017) Premium Times, 16 November, <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/news/more-news/249572> (Accessed 08 May 2023).

The following sections examine the features of informal mediation and the rationale for family mediation. As this research is focused on the impact of family mediation on women, it is noteworthy to mention some of these issues which lead to family mediation. The countless stories of women who remained in toxic environments for fear of the unknown especially when they were financially handicapped and had children to provide for, was part of the motivation for this study by the researcher. Some of the causes of family disputes which affect women's access to justice, range from physical and emotional abuse to failure to provide welfare and necessities for children.

The purpose of this research is to evaluate how family mediation addresses the challenges which affect women's rights. The importance of family mediation as it affects women's access to justice, cannot be overemphasised. It is therefore important to understand the roles of informal and formal mediation as it relates to this study.

5.11.1. Informal Mediation

The adoption of informal mediation as a process of resolving disputes is perceived to have direct impact on marital issues involving the welfare of women and children in certain cases. The 2005 UNDP report stated that in developing countries, 80% of disputes are resolved by informal mediation and this represents 90% of parts of Africa.⁵⁸² The practice of informal mediation in Nigeria predates the pre-colonial era and is as natural as going to the stream to fetch water before the advent of boreholes or pipe-borne water. To turn to elders to resolve disputes in the family or resort to elders in the community is to preserve the family and community. Obidinma captures it in this way: "The primary concept behind family dispute

⁵⁸² Rasha Hassan, 'Formal Litigation or Informal Mediation' (2023) 12 (1)(7) Egyptian Journals 89 at 91.

resolution is for peace and tranquillity due to the fact that most of societal problems emanate from family separation”.⁵⁸³

The desire to adopt what the researcher calls the “First Aid Treatment” in mediation by reporting a dispute to an elder in the family rather than seeking formal redress, emanates from the principle of preserving the sanctity of the relationship or the home. This is the first step usually taken in the home when a family dispute arises and part of the objective of this research is to understand the reason for this action especially in cases which involve domestic violence which motivated the use of data collection through survey and interviews.

Certain writers like Michal Bratton are of the opinion that Nigerians despite being a fractious group of people, majority of whom are united in their common desire to seek peace in a community-based manner to resolve disputes and ensure the nation remains intact.⁵⁸⁴

This informs and supports the position of informal mediation which is further enhanced by the notion that traditional and local level political institutions are versed with legitimacy which are utilised in the facilitation of resolution of disputes. Even the judiciary recognises the power of the elders in resolving disputes as was in the case of *Okpururu v. Okpokam*⁵⁸⁵ wherein the court as per the dictum of Justice Oguntade JCA (as he then was),

‘... in the pre-colonial times and before the advent of the regular courts, our people (Nigerians) certainly had a simple and inexpensive way of adjudicating

⁵⁸³ Angela Obidimma, ‘Arbitrating Family Disputes in Nigeria: Benefits and Challenges’ (2021) 3(2) International Journal of Comparative Law and Legal Philosophy 69.

⁵⁸⁴ Michael Bratton, ‘The Resolution of Violent Conflicts in Nigeria: A Public Opinion Perspective’ (2004) 1(3) Journal of Peacebuilding & Development 35.

⁵⁸⁵ *Okpururu v. Okpokam* (1998) 4 NWLR Pt. 90, 554 at 586.

over dispute between them. They referred to the elders or to a body set up for that purpose'.⁵⁸⁶

In an Afrobarometer conducted in 2001, it was shown that only 19% of violent altercations which occur within the families are reported.⁵⁸⁷ Studies from the same report reveal that people are most likely to turn to family, friends, and neighbours to resolve their conflicts before seeking for help in organised channels of justice. The analysis of the Afrobarometer is indicative of the fact that Nigerians prefer to resolve their disputes through an informal community-based process to the formal and officious intervention of the state government or federal parastatal.⁵⁸⁸

The bottlenecks associated with formal processes are usually a challenge especially for women and they would prefer to seek redress through an accessible process as evidenced in the literature in the previous chapters on factors which challenge women's access to justice. Women have to contend with discrimination as to their sex and the challenges of financial capacity which often accompany formal processes. The different ethnic groups have respective titles for the elders who preside over disputes in the family and in the community. In the western part of Nigeria where you have the Yorubas, the Mogajis who are the heads of the lineage, and the Baales who are elderly men who oversee the affairs of the village, they are the ones who preside over disputes⁵⁸⁹ and they adopt different techniques in the mediation process

⁵⁸⁶ Samuel Dike, Boma Toby and Dorcas Elekima, 'Transforming Mediation and Conciliation Practices for Effective Dispute Resolution in Nigeria' [2020] https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343906058_Transforming_Mediation (Accessed 3 August 2022).

⁵⁸⁷ Michael Bratton, 'The Resolution of Violent Conflicts in Nigeria: A Public Opinion Perspective' (2004) 1(3) *Journal of Peacebuilding & Development* 36.

⁵⁸⁸ Michael Bratton, 'The Resolution of Violent Conflicts in Nigeria: A Public Opinion Perspective' (2004) 1(3) *Journal of Peacebuilding & Development* 40.

⁵⁸⁹ Samuel Dike, Boma Toby and Dorcas Elekima, 'Transforming Mediation and Conciliation Practices for Effective Dispute Resolution in Nigeria' [2020] https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343906058_Transforming_Mediation (Accessed 3 August 2022).

to arrive at a decision. Some of the methods adopted during informal mediation include traditional proverbs, cultural precedents, emotional blackmail, and even black magic and can threaten disputants with social excommunication.⁵⁹⁰ These are the avenues through which they ensured compliance with the decisions passed at the traditional mediation sittings and it was binding on the parties.

It has further been reiterated by Dike et al that mediation gives parties the opportunity to discuss issues, address misunderstandings and reach compromises on the agreement in the best interest of the parties, in a way which would not be possible in a litigation process.⁵⁹¹

Informal mediation is guided and regulated by customs and traditions peculiar to the family or community of the parties and is consequently unwritten. Its unwritten nature ensures its flexibility. Informal mediation is not exclusive to Nigeria alone but exists in other African countries and in some countries such as Kenya, there is a preference for disputes to be resolved through the elders of the community and 60% of the population do not resolve their disputes through litigation.⁵⁹²

According to most customs and traditions the elders in the community play the role of custodians in the community such as manage public affairs, maintain the peace, preside over matters, serve as judges and looking after the welfare of the community.⁵⁹³

Some of the factors which characterise informal mediation include the following: parties have no choice as to how the mediation proceeds and progresses as the elders are in control (which

⁵⁹⁰ Samuel Dike and Boma Toby and Dorcas Elekima, “Transforming Mediation and Conciliation Practices for Effective Dispute Resolution in Nigeria” [2020] https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343906058_Transforming_Mediation (Accessed 4 August 2022).

⁵⁹¹ Ibid.

⁵⁹² **Hiil User Friendly Justice, 'Justice Needs and Satisfaction in Kenya 2017'** [2017] <<https://www.hiil.org/wpcontent/uploads/2018/07/hiireport-kenya-JNS-17> (Accessed 5 August 2022).

⁵⁹³ Ali Mazrui, *The Africans London* (BBC Publications, London, 1986)133.

is almost contrary to mediation principles), most times the parties do not choose the mediators as they are either elders in the family or in the community. Other factors are the neutrality of the mediator cannot be guaranteed as they are usually family members and already have knowledge of the dispute, there is no confidentiality in informal mediation as the dispute is common knowledge to all family members. These factors have been identified as some of the issues which are frequently prevalent in informal mediation generally by the responses of the participants of the survey and as observed in practice by the researcher of this study.

Observations of Informal Mediation

The following have been summarised as part of the process which plagues informal mediation in Nigeria by the literature and to be verified by evidence of the data collection in this study. There are no legal precedents, as well as no procedural and constitutional protection guaranteed by the constitutional courts except where the matter is instituted in the customary court which makes it a subject of litigation. Family disputes are in different forms and can be between siblings in a family or inter-family which involves different branches of the family. This study is focused on how family mediation addresses the rights of women in a family dispute, whether it be discrimination on inheritance to property or FGM, especially as not every matter can be resolved through informal mediation such as the involvement of domestic abuse or intimate partner violence which is a crime. This will be discussed in detail in Chapter Six.

Major factors which affect women's access to justice through family mediation especially informal mediation are tradition and culture, the system of patriarchy, which is prevalent in every sphere of society, and fear of stigma which acts as a form of control on women. All of these will be discussed as sub-themes in this study as they affect women's access to justice. Culture influences family mediation in various ways – from the culture of women believing they should accept whatever their husbands do and not take their matrimonial issues outside,

to staying at home to bear children. With enlightenment campaigns ongoing and sensitization, there is hope the awareness is changing, no matter how slowly.

Different writers have their versions of what informal mediation represents and one of them is Onyeozili who presented an exact description of informal mediation in Igbo land which is in Eastern Nigeria, in the following statement:

*“The Council of elders serves as the trial courts and, the age grades serve as the main enforcement arm of the village justice. It is only when litigants chose to ignore or contest the council decision that they resort to formal court system which often takes time to resolve and costs much money to prosecute”.*⁵⁹⁴

As mentioned in earlier on in this chapter on the issue of family disputes, the elders in the family usually mediate when there is a dispute between the younger members of the family. This fact is recognised but the challenge is the lack of statutory backing which informal mediation does not possess as stated by Gadzama to ensure compliance.⁵⁹⁵ In discussing the theme on informal mediation, the connection to formal mediation is revealed from the responses of the participants in the survey and the interviews. It was developed to understand how informal mediation functions in the resolution of family dispute in Nigeria. The survey indicated that majority of the respondents had experienced informal family mediation before formal mediation was sought.⁵⁹⁶ This insight matches the understanding gleaned when it was noted that informal mediation forms part of the fabric of Nigerian society.

⁵⁹⁴ Emmanuel Onyeozili and Obi Ebbe, ‘Social Control in Pre-Colonial Igboland in Nigeria (2012) 6(1)(2) African Journal of Criminology and Justice Studies, 39.

⁵⁹⁵ Joe Kyari Gadzama, ‘Development and practice of ADR and Arbitration in Nigeria’ (2013) conference papers accessed on 22nd July 2020: Angela Obidimma and Vivian Okpalangwu, ‘Arbitrating Family Disputes in Nigeria: Benefits and Challenges’ (2021) 3(2) International Journal of Comparative Law and Legal Philosophy 78.

⁵⁹⁶ No 75 of Survey Respondents.

Part of the purpose of the interview was to investigate the likely reasons for formal mediation after informal mediation had been adopted in the resolution of family disputes.

5.11.2. Formal Mediation

Formal mediation can be traced to the 1970s in the United States of America, when the victory of the mediation process led to analysis by social scientists and reports by legal authorities all over Europe, also set a standard for legislature relating to mediation.⁵⁹⁷ Mediation also developed in the private sector with lawyers eagerly making their presence felt in professional associations of mediation. The Centre for Public Resources Institute for Dispute Resolution (formerly Centre for Public Resources) was created in 1979 by some counsels from different companies and its services was expanded to include mediation by the American Arbitration Association (AAA). Other dispute resolution bodies such as the National Institute of Dispute Resolution (NIDR), Association of Conflict Resolution (formerly SPIDR- Society of Professionals in Dispute Resolution) and the Academy of Family Mediators were also established.⁵⁹⁸

For purposes of this study, formal mediation is examined from the procedural perspective. It is necessary to understand that the difference between the informal and formal mediation resides in the structure and legality of the mediation process. In formal mediation the neutrality of the mediator is guaranteed by the formal system of the legal process which is contrary to the informal system where the process is usually overseen by members of the family or persons who might have prior knowledge of the issues. Formal mediation in the resolution of family disputes arose from the need to reduce the incidents of discrimination against women in the

⁵⁹⁷ Klaus Hopt and Felix Steffek, *Mediation: Principles and Regulations in Comparative Perspective* (Oxford Scholarship, 2012) 26.

⁵⁹⁸ Bryan Clark, *Lawyers and Mediation* (Springer Heidelberg New York, 2012) 8.

patriarchal system of resolving disputes which is prevalent in most societies especially in Africa.⁵⁹⁹

In a private mediation, the parties choose an impartial neutral third party, who they want to be their mediator and for a settled remuneration. For a court annexed mediation, it means it is the directive of the court that the parties go through mediation and the resolution reached at the end of the process is entered as a consent judgment of the court.⁶⁰⁰ Due to the private nature of mediation, there are not many reported cases in Nigeria, but the courts give recognition to the agreements reached at mediation. This was illustrated in the case of *Folarin and another v Idowu & Others*⁶⁰¹ where the Court of Appeal held that settlement agreement made subject to contracts imposed during mediation must be enforced by the courts and will be binding on the parties who have agreed to it.

The ICMC being the professional body trains and certifies professional mediators and conciliators, as well as regulates and sets the standards for the practice of mediation and conciliation as processes of ADR.⁶⁰² The basic feature of formal mediation is the structure and the regulations which guides the process empowered by government. It is court based and consequently the judiciary oversees the functionality for the court annexed mediation while an organised professional body such as the ICMC would oversee the process for a private mediation.

5.12 Perspective of Nigerian Women on Family Mediation

It is necessary to mention the experience of Nigerian women in informal mediation in this chapter as this study is focused on the impact of family mediation in their lives. The perspective

⁵⁹⁹ Mulki Al-Sharmani, *Legal Reform, Women's Empowerment and Social Change: The Case of Egypt* (Zed Books, 2014).

⁶⁰⁰ Order 39 Rules 6 and 7 of the Lagos State High Court (Civil Procedure) Rules of 2019. The State High Court Civil Procedure Rules of the different states provide for consent judgments.

⁶⁰¹ [2013] LPELR 2213.

⁶⁰² Alternative Dispute Resolution.

of Nigerian women is important to ascertain how culture impacts on family mediation and more especially the role of Nigerian laws and where they have incorporated international conventions. Being a lawyer and a woman in Nigeria and one known for active participation in the cause of the promotion of women's rights meant always being on duty when there was a dispute in the environment. Women would instinctively turn to the researcher for advice, which meant a lot of first-hand insight as to how Nigerian women felt and their experiences during informal mediation which was the motivation for this study. The perspective of Nigerian women is expressed in the responses of the participants which reveals the impact of family mediation. For instance, the evidence of the women who had explored informal mediation before proceeding to formal mediation through the FIDA Legal Centre. Their decision to proceed with formal mediation expressed their lack of trust in the sustainability of the process of informal mediation.

The survey conducted during the data collection is necessary to explore and understand the reality of family mediation and aid the development of the jurisprudence in Nigeria. The question this study seeks to answer is why women who have experienced informal mediation, decide to proceed to formal mediation. This question will be answered by the data collection process.

5.13 Themes and Sub-Themes Affecting Family Mediation

The following themes were identified from the responses of the participants and will be explored further with relevance to the data collection during the data analysis.

Informal Mediation as a Process to Justice- This theme has been highlighted above in the literature on informal mediation and will be further illustrated in the data analysis of the responses of the participants in the survey and interviews.

Accessing the Formal System - Accessing formal systems refers to the process by which individuals or groups seek entry into established institutions, organisations, or legal

frameworks to address their concerns, and grievances, or seek a resolution for a particular issue. It specifically relates to accessing the established legal and judicial systems to seek redress for grievances, particularly related to family disputes or other legal matters. Access to formal systems has been described as a form of barrier to women's access to justice as stated by the UN⁶⁰³ in explaining how the geographical location of the judicial parastatal can hinder access to justice.⁶⁰⁴ The analysis examined how geographical factors such as transport and infrastructural challenges, limited access to vehicles, cost of travel, road construction and the general topography of the location of a legal office, can hinder access to justice. In the findings it was uncovered that when individuals or parties choose to access the formal system, they usually engage with legal mechanisms such as courts, tribunals or government agencies to pursue a resolution. This process may involve filing of legal documents, attending hearings or mediation sessions, presenting evidence, and adhering to the procedural rules and requirements set forth by the legal system. However, it is important to note that accessing the formal system may involve complexities, such as the need for legal representation, financial costs, procedural hurdles, and potential delays. These factors can influence the effectiveness and accessibility of the formal system, and individuals may face challenges in navigating the process.

In discussing the issue of “accessing the formal system” as a theme in this chapter, the intention of this study is to examine how easy or difficult it was for the participants to obtain the justice they sought. In this section of the research the study is on the participants seeking formal mediation by coming to the FIDA legal centre. This theme is in accordance with the *Legal Aid*

⁶⁰³ United Nations.

⁶⁰⁴ Hamza Khan, Mohd Imran, and Kamran Fazal, *Access to Justice-Need For Reforms* :Open Society Foundation, ‘Leveraging the SDGs for Inclusive Growth: Delivering Justice for All’ (2016) <https://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/68293316/Book-libre.pdf> 175 (Accessed 18 August 2023).

Act of 1976 which is provided for in the Nigerian Constitution⁶⁰⁵ and allows for free legal services.

Intimate Partner Violence/Domestic Abuse (IPV) - It is important to state that violence and abuse is used interchangeably in describing IPV in family disputes and this study recognises this fact to mean the explanation of the abuse suffered by partners in a relationship.

Before discussing this theme, a definition of gender-based violence is necessary to appreciate the concept. Gender based violence has been defined by the World Bank's Inter Agency Standing Committee as "any harmful act that is perpetrated against a person's will and that is based on socially ascribed (gender) differences between males and females".⁶⁰⁶ The relevance of the IPV theme to family mediation is based on interpersonal relationships and the impact of the justice system on women's access to justice. This theme was developed to understand the reluctance of women to report intimate partner violence or domestic abuse to the police but preferred family mediation as a means of resolving this issue.

The fact that domestic violence is an offence of assault under the Criminal Code of Nigeria⁶⁰⁷ does not appear to compel women to report to the police when it occurs. This theme was developed as part of the interview questions as a follow up on the responses from the survey based on the question asked in the survey on IPV. It called for more reflection when compared with the literature on the "silence culture" which is prevalent in domestic abuse cases as revealed in the report by CLEEN.⁶⁰⁸ (This will be expanded on in the discussion section of this

⁶⁰⁵ 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Section 46(1).

⁶⁰⁶ Jeni Klugman, Lucia Hammer and Juliet Santamaria, 'Voice and Agency: Empowering Women and Girls for Shared Prosperity' [2014] 34 https://www.worldbank.org/content/dam/Worldbank/document/Gender/World_bank_gender_voice_lowres.pdf (Accessed 21 April 2023).

⁶⁰⁷ Criminal Code Act, 1990 of the Laws of Nigeria, Section 252.

⁶⁰⁸ Centre for Law Enforcement Education.

Chapter). On the one hand, the low figures of IPV could be related to the “culture of silence” which surrounds domestic violence as observed by the Executive Director of Women Information Network (WINET)⁶⁰⁹ in reporting on the pro bono cases on domestic violence handled through mediation?⁶¹⁰ Statistics from the reports of Centre for Law Enforcement Education (CLEEN)⁶¹¹ Foundation have shown that cases of domestic violence are under reported in Nigeria and discussions within families and in the community are shrouded in secrecy⁶¹² which encourages the abuse. Another NGO, the ARIKE Foundation has also postulated that the reason victims are reluctant to report domestic violence is because of the fear of being stigmatised.⁶¹³ The reports also state that victims are reluctant to report domestic violence to the police because the police allegedly refuse to take complaints on the grounds that it is a family matter and should be resolved privately.⁶¹⁴

⁶⁰⁹ Women Information Network – a Nigerian based NGO with the objective to promote gender equality, human and political rights through information.

⁶¹⁰ IRB (Immigration and Refugee Board) of Canada, ‘Query response on domestic violence in Nigeria 2016-2019’ [2019]
<https://irb-cisr.gc.ca/en/country-information/rir/Pages/index.aspx?doc=457956&pls=1>
(Accessed 16 June 2023).

⁶¹¹ Centre for Law Enforcement Education- established in January 1998 with the objective of promoting public safety, accessible justice, and providing information through empirical research and publications, legislative advocacy and engaging partnership with government and private sector.

⁶¹² CLEEN Foundation, 18 October, 2019 – Correspondence from representative to the Research Directorate
<https://www.ecoi.net/en/document/2021300.html> (Accessed 16 June 2023).

⁶¹³ ARIKE Foundation et al, *Women, Peace and Security in Nigeria: Joint Shadow Report. CEDAW Committee, 67th Session (July 2017)*. : Women’s International League for Peace and Freedom; Project Alert; NOIPolls Limited *Domestic Violence: Poll Report*, (Accessed 24 September 2019)
<https://www.ecoi.net/en/document/2021300.html> (Accessed 16 June 2023).

⁶¹⁴ Executive Director, WINET 5th October 2019; UN 24 Aug. 2018, para. 78 - Correspondence with the Research Directorate, <https://www.ecoi.net/en/document/2021300.html> (Accessed 16 June 2023).

Other NGOs such as Fund for Peace (FFP)⁶¹⁵ and Project Alert on Violence Against Women (PAVAW)⁶¹⁶ are some of the organisations which provide support for women who are victims of domestic violence in Nigeria. These NGOs advocate for mediation services for victims of domestic violence, particularly fashioned after the Federal Ministry of Women Affairs and Social Development of Switzerland.⁶¹⁷ The Ministry organises mediation meetings between the parties, including the victims, and where the meeting is not successful, it offers the victim the option of lodging a formal complaint and assists them in the process. Which is what FIDA does as testified to by the participants who took part in the interview. But obviously this is not enough as the numbers of reported cases of IPV have not increased while the statistics report a high rate of unreported cases as illustrated by the numbers in the survey conducted by CLEEN.⁶¹⁸

The report from CLEEN revealed a high rate of under reporting of domestic violence in the rural areas largely as a result of patriarchal norms, values, belief systems and weak presence of state law enforcement structure such as the police. Some of these values and belief systems include the myths women are taught to believe as young girls such as it is the responsibility of the woman to ensure the children are well brought up. The 2018 Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey Report⁶¹⁹ conducted a survey of women who had experienced domestic violence between the ages of 15-49. 31% of the women had experienced physical violence from the age

⁶¹⁵ Fund for Peace is an independent NGO based in the United States of America with an office in Abuja, Nigeria.

⁶¹⁶ Project Alert on Violence Against Women is an NGO in Nigeria which promotes women's rights by providing information on violence against women and advocating against tolerance of violence, also provides support for victims of domestic violence.

⁶¹⁷ IRB (Immigration and Refugee Board) of Canada, 'Query response on domestic violence in Nigeria 2016-2019' (2019) <https://irb-cisr.gc.ca/en/country-information/rir/Pages/index.aspx?doc=457956&pls=1> (Accessed 16 June 2023).

⁶¹⁸ CLEEN Foundation, 18 October 2019 – Correspondence from representative to the Research Directorate <https://www.ecoi.net/en/document/2021300.html> (Accessed 16 June 2023).

⁶¹⁹ <https://dhsprogram.com/pubs/pdf/SR264/SR264.pdf> (Accessed 16 June 2023).

of 15 years. 32% of these women resided in the urban areas while 30% resided in the rural areas of Nigeria. The report also recorded women who had been married and experienced spousal violence, whether physical, emotional, or sexual to be 36%: 34% of the women resided in the urban areas and 38% resided in the rural areas of Nigeria.

The *Violence Against Persons Prohibitions Act 2015 (VAPP Act)* is specific on IPV and domestic abuse in its provisions and this simplifies the identification of violations which occurs in the family setting. The *VAPP Act* defines domestic violence as “*any act perpetrated on any person in a domestic relationship where such act causes harm or may cause imminent harm to the safety, health, or wellbeing of any person.*”⁶²⁰

The Act also defines *emotional, verbal, and psychological abuse in its interpretative section to mean, “a pattern of degrading or humiliating conduct towards any person, including-*

(a) Repeated insults

(b) Ridicule or name calling

(c) Repeated threats to cause emotional pain or

*(d) The repeated exhibition of obsessive possessiveness, which is of such a nature as to constitute a serious invasion of such person’s privacy, liberty, integrity, or security.”*⁶²¹

*Section 16(1) of the VAPP Act*⁶²² states that:

“A person who abandons a wife or husband, children or other dependent without any means of sustenance commits an offence and is liable on conviction to a term of imprisonment not exceeding 3 years or to a fine not exceeding N500,000.00 or both”.

Sub section (2) further provides:

⁶²⁰ VAPP Act 2015 , Section 46, Part VI www.ilo.org (Accessed 5 July 2022).

⁶²¹ VAPP Act 2015, Section 46, Part VI www.ilo.org (Accessed 5 July 2022).

⁶²² Violence Against Persons Prohibitions Act as mentioned earlier.

*“A person who attempts to commit the act of violence provided for in subsection (1) of this section commits an offence and is liable on conviction to a term of imprisonment not exceeding 2 years or to a fine not exceeding N200,000.00 or both”.*⁶²³

The above provisions of the VAPP Act are the necessary legislation to ascertain IPV in the resolution of family disputes and considered in the responses of the participants.

Enforcement of Mediation Agreement - Lack of compliance with mediation agreements can lead to issues with enforcement as evidenced in the responses of the participants discussed in this study. In discussing enforcement of mediation as a theme, it is necessary to understand how the concept of enforcement operates. The reason for exploring this theme was to examine if mediation agreements were easily enforced where one party failed to comply with the agreement. The role of the mediator includes creating an enabling environment for the disputing parties to reach an amicable settlement of their dispute of which the primary aim is the preservation of the relationship of the parties where possible.⁶²⁴ This is especially important where familial relationships exist. In a mediation agreement, the parties are free to decide whether their agreement would be irrevocable or if they would commence litigation proceedings if settlement cannot be reached in accordance with mediation principles. The question whether it is necessary to enforce a mediation agreement might seem irrelevant since mediation is a voluntary process agreed to by the parties and the agreement reached is a mutual one agreed upon by the parties. This question has become necessary especially in family disputes where after the mediation agreement is reached, one party fails to honour it: the question being should the agreement be enforced or should the failure to adhere to the

⁶²³ VAPP Act 2015, Section 16(1) and (2) www.ilo.org (Accessed 5 July 2022).

⁶²⁴ Tony Whatling, *Mediation Skills, and Strategies- A Practical Guide* (J. Kingsley Publishers, London, 2012) 22.

agreement result in litigation being the next step? This research is particularly concerned about the experiences of the women in enforcing the agreement from family mediation.

To discover the challenges which surround enforcement of mediation agreement, the data collected during the survey and interviews will be analysed and discussed to help answer this question. The focus of this Chapter is on the enforcement of mediation agreement from the perspective of family mediation. Disputing parties who have adopted family mediation as a process of dispute resolution, should not encounter challenges in enforcing the mediation agreement. Will the presence of law or fear of penalty affect the compliance with resolutions from mediation? Or does the threat of enforcement change the collaborative nature of the pre-litigation process? This study will also consider enforcement of mediation agreements from the perspective of international conventions to examine how family mediation is viewed on an international basis and consider the impact if any exist, on States to provide a global view on enforcement.

The objective of this theme is to analyse the reasons for the challenges which surround enforcement of mediation agreements in family disputes. In Chapter Four this study discussed international conventions and the impact on women's rights especially as it relates to Nigerian women. It is necessary to assist our discussion from the international perspective on the enforcement of mediation agreement. The enforcement of family mediation agreement is a grey area in Nigeria which hopefully this research will throw more light on. The recommendations of this study will be based on the outcome of the analysis of the findings from the survey and interviews.

Philosophy of Enforcement of Family Mediation Agreement

As this study is concerned with family mediation, the technical steps of a commercial agreement would not apply in the strict sense to family mediation, but the principles of mediation remain the same. The question whether or not there is a need for the enforcement of

mediation agreements remains unanswered on the presumption that parties who have voluntarily consented to the mediation process are expected to comply with and naturally enforce the agreement as the agreement ought to reflect the interests of the parties. The procedure for enforcement of family mediation agreement differs from commercial mediation agreement due to factors like gender power imbalance as highlighted in the responses of the participants revealed by the sub-themes as a result of culture, role of patriarchy, stigma/social control and religion. In some jurisdictions like the UK, the enforcement of family mediation agreement is recognised by the courts but with the accompaniment of other documentation such as Maintenance Orders (where children are involved), and the agreement in compliance with current legislation, does not infringe on the other party's rights and in the best interest of the child.⁶²⁵ Roberts emphasises this by stating the court enforces such agreement by the parties but this can only be achieved where the parties bring their dispute within the jurisdiction of the court.⁶²⁶

In several jurisdictions including Nigeria, before a settlement agreement can be enforced, it must be registered as an action of the court and entered as a consent judgement with leave of the court.⁶²⁷ In certain jurisdictions for agreements reached at mediation to be enforceable, they are recorded as arbitral awards and enforceable as arbitral awards.⁶²⁸

Consequently, this study highlights the similarity of commercial and family mediation in terms of enforcement as it concerns jurisdiction. For the family agreement to be enforced the court will have to assume jurisdiction which is given by the consent of the parties.

⁶²⁵ Marian Roberts, *Mediation in Family Disputes: Principles of Practice*, (Routledge Publishing, 2016) 37.

⁶²⁶ Ibid.

⁶²⁷ 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Section 241.

⁶²⁸ Niek Peters, 'The Enforcement of Mediation Agreements and Settlement agreement resulting from mediation' (2019) 1&2 Corporate Mediation Journal, 13 at 16.

In Nigeria, because of the challenges associated with access to justice, as well as the prevalence of the traditional ways of settling family disputes, especially for people in the rural areas, empirical studies have shown that family mediation agreements are more likely to be enforced when such mediations are carried out through traditional mechanisms. Some of the mechanisms for ensuring compliance with informal mediation process consist of stigmatization or social control which is one of the sub-themes of this study. The cultural beliefs and norms of different ethnic groups affect the outcomes of such mediations, especially when such matters involve women and the different ethnic groups ensured compliance in different ways.

The study by Idumwonyi and Ikhidero⁶²⁹ focused on the ethnic group of Benin City in Nigeria, and they postulated that the continual preference for traditional methods of obtaining justice is not unconnected with the inherent limitations of the received English legal system within the Nigerian traditional communities. Compliance with agreement at the traditional level is regulated by customs.

For the Yoruba ethnic group, Onadeko⁶³⁰ explained that the Yorubas developed a hierarchical administrative system in mediating and settling family disputes, in which the Baba who was the head of the household governed his immediate family, while the *Olori Ebi* was the head of the extended family. The *Olori Adugbo* headed his quarter, while the *Oba* together with his *Igbimo (council of chiefs)* governed all the towns within his domain. It was noted that the different cases were treated based on the level it could be handled at each social stratum which ensured the level of compliance with the decision of the elder. Where there was noncompliance, the matter was reported to a higher authority in the society.⁶³¹

⁶²⁹ Itohan Idumwonyi, and Solomon Ikhidero, 'Resurgence of the Traditional Justice System in Postcolonial Benin (Nigeria) Society' (2013) 6 African Journal of Legal Studies, 123–135.

⁶³⁰ Tunde Onadeko, 'Yoruba Traditional Adjudicatory Systems: African Study Monographs' (2008) 29(1) Journal of Philosophy and Theology 15-28.

⁶³¹ Ibid.

Baba settled quarrels among his wives and children; the *Olori Ebi* mediated civil cases within his extended family; the *Olori Adugbo* handled civil and mild criminal cases; and the *Oba* addressed civil cases that occurred between two or more quarters, and heinous criminal cases within his domain.

In examining the East, Igwe et al⁶³² reviewed the relevance of the traditional methods of dispute resolution mechanism among the Igbos in Nigeria. They noted that before the advent of colonial rule and the regular court system to Nigeria, the Igbos had a system of dispute resolution mechanism adjudged to be simple, inexpensive, and friendly. Resolutions of family and communal disputes were handled by family heads, village heads, elders, kindred, age grade, council of elders, chiefs, chief priests, judicial council among others. They employed instruments like oath taking, divination and trial by ordeal to resolve cases especially where the truth or the identity of the party involved cannot be easily ascertained. These traditional methods have continued to be relevant among the people of the South-East of Nigeria, even though the strongholds of the same have been watered-down by the intrusion of western methods of dispute resolution. This form of oath taking was a mechanism to ensure compliance with the dispute resolution process of which the voluntary nature of the proceedings could be argued as items like traditional kola nut, sand and egg were used to ensure the person taking the oath was telling the truth.⁶³³ Women are also subjected to this traditional method of dispute resolution and the impact of culture in family mediation process is further revealed in such a situation for where a woman refuses to comply with the oath taking sanctions are placed on her as was evidenced by the response of the participant who refused to take an oath on the grounds

⁶³² Onyebuchi Igwe and Kevin Udude, and Constance Ogah, 'A Review of Continuous Relevance of the Traditional Methods of Dispute Resolution Mechanism in Southeast of Nigeria' (2020) 11 Beijing Law Review, 34 at 37.

⁶³³ Ibid.

that she was a Christian, when she was summoned to the village by her in-laws for a family mediation.⁶³⁴

For the Urhobos in the middle of Southern Nigeria, Atake⁶³⁵ examined their traditional method of dispute settlement and found a social system, the institutions, laws, courts, and mechanisms among the people. The study noted that the Urhobos developed traditional judicial system that evolved from traditional jurisprudence and encompasses traditional laws and courts in various communities which administer justice.

The settling and enforcement of agreements in a family dispute however has some negative implications, especially for women. Because of tradition and cultural beliefs, the customary means of settling and enforcing family mediation agreements sometimes infringes on the rights of women as mentioned above.

The Nigerian Government acknowledges this challenge by explaining in the National Policy on Justice 2017⁶³⁶ that the traditional justice system is biased, discriminatory and encourages repugnant customs. Through the implementation of the policy, the government has been taking measures to enlighten and create awareness about the negative implications of outdated customs and beliefs in settling and enforcing family mediation agreements.

Through the National Human Rights Commission⁶³⁷ the Nigerian government has also instituted mechanisms through which women and other vulnerable groups can seek redress when they feel aggrieved by any mediation process that infringes on their rights. For example, the National Human Rights Commission has a department called the Human Rights Enforcement Department that caters for issues concerning women, children, and vulnerable

⁶³⁴ Interview with Participant 10, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on 23/05/2022 at 12:37hrs.

⁶³⁵ Odjuvwuederie Atake, 'Traditional Judicial System in Urhobo land' (2019) 2 (8) Journal of African Studies and Sustainable Development 25 at 31.

⁶³⁶ National Policy on Justice, 2017: www.justice.gov.ng (Accessed 7 November 2023).

⁶³⁷ National Human Rights Commission, Nigeria: www.nigeriarights.gov.ng (Accessed 7 November 2023).

groups. The department specifically attends to matters such as harmful cultural practices, forceful marriage, gender-based discrimination, etc. In addition, there is the Sexual and Gender-Based Violence unit, operating within the Citizens Rights Department at the Federal Ministry of Justice. These platforms provide the windows where women can seek redress in the event that their rights are violated in the course of family mediations and enforcements of the agreements. The challenge with this platform is the fact that it is found in the towns and would be challenging for women in the rural area to be aware of its existence and therefore access it.

The philosophy of enforcement of family mediation is centered on the need for compliance by the parties to the dispute, whether informal or formal. Motivation for compliance differs from individual to individual as from ethnic group to ethnic group. The motivation for compliance could be fear of penalty as revealed by the responses of the participants who proceeded to FIDA after informal mediation.

Enforcement of Mediation Agreement and International Conventions

The purpose of understanding how mediation agreements are enforced under the provisions of international conventions gives an insight on the universal impression of mediation on enforcement of mediation agreements in general and family mediation in particular as it relates to this study. Although there is no family mediation legislation in Nigeria (as at the time of conducting this research), this study considers any relevance (where they exist) of international laws and the impact on Nigerian family mediation. As mentioned in earlier chapters, international conventions are domesticated in national laws. Consequently, enforcement of mediation agreements internationally, can be adopted and domesticated in national laws, in commercial disputes as well as family disputes while considering the confidentiality principle hence the need to examine where international conventions can impact on family mediation in Nigeria with amendments where necessary.

In a bid to reduce the challenges of enforcing agreement which result from mediation agreements, the United States proposed that the UNCITRAL⁶³⁸ develop a multilateral treaty on the enforceability of international settlement agreements resulting from mediation. The *Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards*, also known as the *New York Convention*⁶³⁹ which is the foundational instrument in the regulation of international commercial arbitration and applies to foreign awards except where the convention has been domesticated by the parties to the Convention.⁶⁴⁰ In July 2018, the UNCITRAL concluded the *Singapore Convention* after four years of negotiations within the United Nations, and it was adopted by the General Assembly on the 20th of December 2018 to which 70 states attended as delegates, and 46 signed the convention.⁶⁴¹ The scope of the *Singapore Convention* applies to international commercial agreements and expressly excludes family and personal disputes.⁶⁴²

The understanding from the convention above would suggest that though there is no provision for enforcement of agreements resulting from family mediation under international mediation, the agreements are binding on members in relation to commercial transactions. The speculation might be a country wishing to apply the provisions of the convention would need to domesticate the law and adopt it as part of its national laws. This position of the international conventions

⁶³⁸ United Nations Commission on International Trade Law (UNCITRAL).

⁶³⁹ New York Convention of 1958.

⁶⁴⁰ Niek Peters, 'The Enforcement of Mediation Agreements and Settlement Agreement resulting from Mediation' (2019) 1&2 Corporate Mediation Journal 13 at 16.

⁶⁴¹ Ibid.

⁶⁴² Singapore Convention on Mediation, Article 1(2)
https://uncitral.un.org/sites/uncitral.un.org/files/singapore_convention_eng.pdf
(Accessed 16 August 2022).

appears to be at variance with the dictum of Thorpe LJ in *Rothwell v. Rothwell*⁶⁴³ wherein he stated:

*“As a matter of policy, it is important that this court should signify that if the parties arrive at a compromise, a clear compromise, within the mediation process, then that compromise will be robustly upheld by this court.”*⁶⁴⁴ His Lordship’s view indicates that the court would uphold the consent of the parties which should be paramount in a mediation proceeding. It is the argument of this thesis in support of the view of Justice Thorpe that the consent of the parties whether commercial or family mediation should be paramount.

Stalford is of the opinion that agreements reached at international level are not easily enforced at national level but are subject to procedural formalities of private international law which negates the features of mediation.⁶⁴⁵ In this vein mediation laws will apply internationally which points to the “Opt-In” and “Opt-Out” clauses of mediation agreements in international conventions. Though commercial and family agreements are not of the same nature and the same rules will generally not apply in terms of fairness and the inherent balance of power between the parties, but the common feature remains the agreement between the parties which the court will uphold and where there is lack of compliance with the agreement, the requirement for enforcement arises.

For family mediation agreements to be enforced, in line with the international convention provisions of the courts adhering to the agreement between the parties, as stated earlier on in this study, the court can have jurisdiction if the agreement registered is entered as a consent

⁶⁴³ (2008) EWCA Civ 1600.

⁶⁴⁴ Helen Stalford, ‘Crossing Boundaries: reconciling law, culture and values in international family mediation’ (2010) 32(2) Journal of Social Welfare and Family Law 155 at 165.

⁶⁴⁵ Ibid.

judgement. Enforcement of mediation agreement will only be an issue where there has been lack of compliance with the agreement.

The Nigerian Constitution is silent on family mediation but makes provision for commercial matters on enforcement in civil procedure in the *Sheriffs and Civil Process Act* which makes provision for a certificate of judgement but is silent on enforcement of the judgement.⁶⁴⁶ It would appear the certificate of judgement is a guarantee, but the enforcement of the judgment obtained might be a challenge especially for a woman who has been through the emotional and legal battle of whatever right she was fighting for. However, it is pertinent to note that the above provision of *Section 104* of the *Sheriffs and Civil Process Act* provides for commercial transactions and is silent on agreements from family mediation. This can be amended in legislation to provide for family mediation agreements.

Government Policy Intervention - The role of the government in the dispensation of justice does not begin in the judiciary as the analysis of the participant responses to this research has revealed, it begins in the legal consciousness of the citizens with the realisation of being rights holders entitled to seek justice from the state. Governance has been defined by De Vries as “the conduct of government”⁶⁴⁷ and good governance by government consists of willingness to protect the weak and protect the poor.⁶⁴⁸ Thus, the role of government in women’s ability to access justice cannot be treated with levity. The legal framework of national laws plays an important role in the transformation of the social norms around women’s rights, and

⁶⁴⁶ Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 1990, Chapter 407 Sheriffs and Civil Process Act, Section 104 <http://lawsofnigeria.placng.org/laws/S6.pdf> (Accessed 22 August 2022).

⁶⁴⁷ Michael deVries, ‘The Challenges of Good Governance’ (2013) 18(1) *The Innovation Journal: The Public Sector Innovation* 2 at 4.

⁶⁴⁸ Oluyemisi Bamgbose, ‘Access to Justice through Clinical Legal Education: A Way Forward for Good Governance and Development’ (2015) 15 *African Human Rights Law Journal*, 384.

progressive legal framework can promote effective change.⁶⁴⁹ This thesis presented an overview of the domestic Nigerian laws which protect women and children and situated these laws in the context of international protections contained in a range of Conventions. It is clear, however, that despite this legal framework women and children in Nigeria are not afforded full protection of the law and despite the wording of the law, the reality of the law in operation is that the vulnerable parties to a domestic dispute or familial separation remain vulnerable often at the expense of even raising a mediation or of fully participating in one. The importance of this statement is if the legal framework surrounding the rights of women are efficient, their access to justice will not be denied or at best encounter less challenges but the participants to this research often showed otherwise. Olaleye in her writings stated that where women are not aware of their rights and if accessing those rights are expensive, they will be unable to enforce them.⁶⁵⁰ This is a call for the intervention of the government in ensuring all the citizens are protected and have access to basic rights.

Government intervention in family disputes is contentious as it can be seen to be an interference in the sanctity of the family or in aspects of the private lives of citizens. However, such intervention can take many forms and sets a standard for what is considered acceptable within a state. This section will consider government intervention in the form of legislation but other forms of intervention, such as education programmes and consciousness raising campaigns can be just as powerful and a combination of each of these interventions is likely to be the most effective approach.

⁶⁴⁹ Jeni Klugman, Lucia Hammer and Juliet Santamaria, 'Voice and Agency: Empowering Women and Girls for Shared Prosperity' [2014] 34 https://www.worldbank.org/content/dam/Worldbank/document/Gender/World_bank_gender_voice_lowres.pdf (Accessed 21 April 2023).

⁶⁵⁰ Yemisi Olaleye, 'The Contributions of Community Service Initiative Organisations for the needs of Abused Women: Empirical Evidence from Lagos State Nigeria' [2019] 5 <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333172789> (Accessed 9 September 2023).

One example of where a government has intervened in the regulation of family disputes through legislation is the United States of America where arbitration was adopted as a mechanism used in settling their family disputes. This mechanism was drafted by the Uniform Law Commission Executive Committee and enacted as the ‘Uniform Family Law Arbitration Act’.⁶⁵¹ The objectives of the Act are: - *to ensure that family disputes are settled in a flexible manner by means of arbitration and to promote uniformity of laws in arbitrating family dispute as a subject matter among the States which enact it.* Also, the Chartered Institute of Arbitrators (CIArb) created a non- profit organisation called Institute of Family Law Arbitrators (IFLA).

This organization has a scheme known as the IFLA Scheme which went viral years ago in March 2012. The IFLA has reportedly handled over fifty family arbitrations as at the year 2016.⁶⁵² Though the establishment of the IFLA was preceded by the setting up of the Family Law Arbitration Group Scotland (FLAGS) to promote arbitration under the Scottish Arbitration Act 2010. In recent years institutions conducting or regulating family arbitration have also emerged in Germany, Spain, Australia, and Canada. The establishments of all these organizations in different countries have promoted the development of family arbitration in these countries and goes further to prove that arbitration is a scheme available for easy access and fair financial terms for dispute resolution.⁶⁵³ This precedent reveals the intervention of government policies in access to justice processes in family disputes through ADR.

As part of the survey and interviews for this research, participants were asked about government intervention policies in relation to family mediation and the protection of women’s rights because the researcher was of the opinion prior to conducting the research that such

⁶⁵¹ Angela Obidimma and Vivian Okpalangwu, ‘Arbitrating Family Disputes in Nigeria: Benefits and Challenges’ (2021) 3 IJOCLEEP 2, 68 especially at 76.

⁶⁵² Angela Obidimma and Vivian Okpalangwu, ‘Arbitrating Family Disputes in Nigeria: Benefits and Challenges’ (2021) 3 IJOCLEEP 2, 77.

⁶⁵³ Ibid.

intervention was necessary but needed to have that verified, through data collection and also, should there be further government intervention needed, the form that such intervention should adopt.

The above themes will be analysed in the discussion Chapters. Chapter Six analyses – “informal mediation as a process to justice”, “accessing the formal system” and “intimate partner violence/domestic abuse”. While Chapter Seven examines the themes of “enforcement of mediation agreement” and “government policy intervention”. In discussing the above themes, the consequent sub-themes which emerged will be examined as they run through the various themes namely: impact of culture on family mediation, role of patriarchy in women’s access to justice, stigma/social control as a barrier to women’s access to justice, and effect of religion on family mediation.

5.14. Conclusion

This Chapter set out to establish the difference between the different forms of dispute resolution and alternative dispute resolution. The different forms of dispute resolution and the features of mediation as an ADR process in the resolution of family disputes was discussed to enhance understanding of mediation. The enactment of state laws on violations of women’s rights is evidence of the willingness of Nigerian government to put structure in place to address women’s access to justice. But the fact remains as suggested by Owoseye⁶⁵⁴ the challenge remains in the enforcement of the laws. The efficacy of laws especially Nigerian laws and their impact on Nigerian women and family mediation will be examined during the data collection through the survey and interviews and examining how the themes and sub-themes are connected. The next chapter will analyse the data collected for this research.

⁶⁵⁴ Ibid.

CHAPTER SIX

I HAVE NO RIGHTS AS A WOMAN⁶⁵⁵

6.1 Introduction

The purpose of this chapter is to examine how the empirical findings of this study contributes to our understanding of the themes of informal mediation as a process to justice, access to formal system and intimate partner violence and how the sub-themes affect women's access to justice in Nigeria. In answering the research question, **how has family mediation affected the rights of women's access to justice in Nigeria?**

The findings from the analysis of the survey and interview results will be examined and discussed in line with existing literature on family mediation. The main objective of this chapter is to delve into the findings related to the themes which emerged from the survey and were further consolidated during the interview phase. The title of this chapter was taken from a quote made by one of the female participants during the interview who expressed that “as a woman in Nigeria”, she had no rights; this sentiment reveals the perceptions women in Nigeria have regarding their rights and their place within the legal system.

In examining the data collection, the survey laid the foundation for the interview questions which examined the following themes - *Informal mediation as a process to justice, Access to formal system, Intimate Partner Violence (IPV), Enforcement of mediation agreement, and Government Intervention Policy*. As mentioned earlier in consideration of these themes, four sub-themes were revealed which cuts across the above themes on the impact of family mediation on the rights of women in Nigeria, namely:

⁶⁵⁵ Interview with Participant 2, Anambra State FIDA Legal Centre held on 13/01/2022 at 13:20hrs

Impact of culture on family mediation: Culture as mentioned in the research objectives of this thesis, will be discussed from the perspective of family mediation as it impacts on the access of justice by women in Nigeria. It is pertinent to begin the discussion on this sub-theme by defining culture. Culture has been defined broadly by Serrat as the totality of society's distinctive ideas, beliefs, values, and knowledge.⁶⁵⁶ The impact of culture on women's rights is further illustrated in the Ghanaian case of *Quartey v. Martey*⁶⁵⁷ where the court held that by custom, it is the responsibility of a woman to assist the man in his business and the proceeds from the business belong solely to the man. This is a violation of the rights of the woman as she should be entitled to her fair share of the proceeds from the business but because of the culture of the people, the proceeds are deemed to belong to the man irrespective of the contribution of the woman. Culture further influences access to justice as illustrated by Barsky et al⁶⁵⁸ that where elders live with their children as demanded by certain culture such as in Vietnam, it would be difficult for disputing spouses to make decisions without interference from family members. There is further evidence of where culture has impacted on the rights of women as expressed in the decisions of the court in the cases of *Mojekwu v. Mojekwu*⁶⁵⁹ and *Ukeje v. Ukeje*⁶⁶⁰ (as earlier mentioned in Chapter Two) where the women had to fight for their rights to inherit property in their biological families.

Women's rights are influenced by culture on so many levels. In some communities in Nigeria, especially in Igboland, women are not allowed to speak at gatherings where men are taking

⁶⁵⁶ Oliver Serrat, 'Culture Theory' [2017] Knowledge Solution, 32.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/318018641_Culture_Theory (Accessed 28 July 2023).

⁶⁵⁷ [1959] GLR 377.

⁶⁵⁸ Alan Barsky, David Este and Don Collins, 'Cultural Competence in Family Mediation' (1996) 13(3) Mediation Quarterly 171.

⁶⁵⁹ (2005) 5 Nigeria Weekly Law Report (Pt. 657) 402.

⁶⁶⁰ [2014] S.C 224.

decisions as the researcher was informed by one of the participants during the interviews.⁶⁶¹ Culture places a lot of restrictions on women which affect their legal consciousness and compels them to abide by rules which abuse their rights. It is accepted culturally that where a man pays the dowry of a woman, she becomes his property, to do with as he pleases.⁶⁶² This promotes abuses to women's rights and limits her access to justice as we found in the cases when women experienced informal family mediation whether it was their choice or not in the resolution of their family disputes.

In examining culture and the impact, it has on family mediation, the researcher recalls the story of one of the FIDA lawyers who narrated an incident where FIDA had to go to a community with the police to rescue a widow who had been locked up for weeks in the house by her in-laws. Their excuse was that by culture she was to mourn her husband by not stepping outside the house for a period of one month and wear mourning clothes. She was also expected to shave her hair as a sign of respect for her departed husband. This is an example of the power of culture on the rights of women which is an infringement on women's rights, a contravention of the *Maputo Protocol* and other international conventions on the rights of women such as *CEDAW* as discussed in Chapter Four of this thesis. In family mediation, the culture of the family prevails above the rights of the woman in most cases as is evidenced in the findings of this study.

The role of patriarchy in women's access to justice: Patriarchy is a major cultural factor affecting women's rights as it influences women's ability to access justice. The sub-theme of patriarchy is highlighted in this research as it emerged from the interviews as a challenge to women's access to justice. Patriarchy has been described by social scientists such as Weber as the system of government where men ruled societies through their positions as heads of

⁶⁶¹ Interview with Participant 2, Lagos State FIDA Legal Centre held on 17/02/2022 at 10:17hrs.

⁶⁶² Stella Essien, 'Feminism in Culture and Religion' (2020) 8(5) World Journal of Innovative Research 35.

households.⁶⁶³ Walby provides a more apt definition of patriarchy as a system of social structures and practices wherein men dominate and oppress women.⁶⁶⁴ The understanding is that patriarchy exceeds the household and transcends into society. Patriarchy is institutionalised in Nigeria as postulated by Kalunta-Crumpton based on the endorsement of customary and religious practices which infringe on women's rights, such as laws which allow a husband to punish his wife through corporal punishment.⁶⁶⁵

Stigma/ social control as a barrier to women's access to justice: Stigma is a form of control over women exercised by society which hinders her access to justice as reiterated by social scientists. Stigma or social pressure has been described by Barnett et al as a mechanism of social control exercised to maintain the moral order as perceived by society.⁶⁶⁶ Stigmatisation acts as a form of protection of the moral order, and this is achieved through discrimination of survivors who exercise their rights.

Effect of religion on family mediation: The theme of religion was highlighted in this research based on the role religion plays in the resolution of family disputes particularly in family mediation. Mahoney has stated that religion is a salient factor in marriages and parenting, after studies conducted over the past twenty-five years.⁶⁶⁷ Mahoney examines the importance of religion in the resolution of conflict in the home and states that it depends on the beliefs of the parties and if the parties believe in the power of God, they will honour His representative here on earth. For the Christians it could be a priest or a pastor while the Imam will represent the

⁶⁶³ Max Weber, *The Theory of Social and Economic Organisation*, (New York Press 1947) 15.

⁶⁶⁴ Sylvia Walby, 'Theorizing Patriarchy' (1989) 23(2) *Sociology Sage Journals* 214.

⁶⁶⁵ Anita Kalunta-Crumpton, 'Attitude and Solutions towards Intimate Partner Violence: Immigrant Nigerian Women Speak' (2017) 17(1) *Journal of Criminology and Criminal Justice* 3 at 6.

⁶⁶⁶ Jessica Barnett and Eleanor Maticka-Tyndale and Trócaire Kenya, 'Stigma as Social Control: Gender Base Violence Stigma, Life Chance, Moral Order in Kenya' (2016) 63(3) *Social Problems* 447.

⁶⁶⁷ Annette Mahoney 'Religion and Conflict in Marital and Parent-Child Relationships' (2005) 61(4) *Journal of Social Issues* 4, 689.

Islamic faith. Writers such as Essien has posited that religion to women “represents” a place of hope and solution to their plights but on the contrary does the opposite by promoting violence against women and inequality teachings which depict women as subordinates to men.⁶⁶⁸

Religion has been criticised by feminist writers such as Stella Essien and Elizabeth Stanton amongst others, to be in the same category as African culture on the issue of women’s rights based on the teachings of women being subordinates to men, and promoting the “to be seen and not heard” syndrome.

Religious teachings and traditions can be barriers to women’s rights and access to justice where they are misunderstood. The Bible in the Christian religion teaches that God created man and woman to be fruitful, multiply and have dominion over the earth because He created them in His image and likeness.⁶⁶⁹ The understanding is that men and women are deemed equal as joint heirs in the eyes of God but the Bible also teaches that wives should be submissive to their husbands.⁶⁷⁰ This is where misconception appears to be revealed as submission is sometimes interpreted as tolerance of abuse of women’s rights. The Islamic faith also teaches that righteous women are obedient and honour their husbands and those who are rebellious should be convinced and if they refuse, they should be cast aside in the marriage bed, and gives the husband the right to beat them.⁶⁷¹

The Qu’ran also teaches on the subordination of women to men by stating in The Books that men are the maintainers of women, because Allah has made some of them to excel others, and because they spend out of their property.⁶⁷² In this vein religion acts as a challenge to women’s

⁶⁶⁸ Stella Essien, ‘Feminism in Culture and Religion’ (2020) 8(5) World Journal of Innovative Research 35.

⁶⁶⁹ The Holy Bible, Genesis 1: 27 and 28.

⁶⁷⁰ The Holy Bible, Ephesians 5:22-33.

⁶⁷¹ An-Nisa, 34.

⁶⁷² Quran 4:34.

access to justice if women feel compelled to endure and persevere when their rights are being abused under the guise of practicing their religion. Religion can also be a powerful tool of patriarchy when women are denied access to education as illustrated in the situation with Boko Haram in northern Nigeria as mentioned in Chapter Three on the barriers to women's access to justice.

The religious authorities are expected to provide solution during family disputes and not serve as a source of discouragement to seeking justice. Some women reported during the interviews that they were advised against seeking legal redress and were advised to keep praying about the problems and show more respect to their husbands. Meanwhile feminist critic Stanton had opined as far back as 1885, that the moral degradation of women was largely due to theological superstitions more so than all other influences put together.⁶⁷³ This translates into religion acting as a form of check on the rights of women and impacts on their legal consciousness.

These sub-themes were identified as major factors in the themes as they constitute a link to the heart of this study from the outcome of the data analysis based on the research question of this study. The discussions will reveal how the sub-themes are interlinked with the themes.

This Chapter examines the themes of *Informal mediation as a process to justice*, *Access to formal system*, and *Intimate Partner Violence*. The above sub-themes will be discussed as they are interwoven in these three themes while the findings on the themes of *Enforcement of Mediation Agreement* and *Government Intervention Policy* will be discussed in Chapter Seven. Though this Chapter will focus on three themes, two of the significant themes namely, "Informal mediation as a process to justice" and "Accessing the formal system" according to the United Nations, are the necessary institutions for access to justice for the remedy of a

⁶⁷³ Stella Essien, 'Feminism in Culture and Religion' (2020) 8(5) World Journal of Innovative Research 30.

grievance in compliance with human rights standards.⁶⁷⁴ The third theme of “Intimate Partner Violence” is discussed in this chapter as it is a grievance suffered by women and a hindrance to access to justice. This theme is discussed in this chapter as it is linked to the themes of “informal mediation as a process to justice” and “accessing the formal system” for it originates in the home and requires the power of the formal system for resolution of this abuse to women’s rights.

These themes are discussed based on the extensive results of the surveys and interviews, with particular emphasis on the impact in relation to the rights of Nigerian women.

Section one of this chapter explores the theme of “informal mediation as a process to justice”, Section two will discuss “accessing the formal system” and section three will discuss “intimate partner violence”. The responses from the survey and interviews will provide a detailed analysis and findings of the data, shedding light on the significance and implications of these themes and sub-themes within the context of the study.

The findings are discussed with a view to recommending proposals at the conclusion of this study. Before embarking on the discussion of the themes and sub-themes, it is necessary to have an understanding of the data analysis from the survey responses as the themes emerged from the findings from the survey. The data analysis of the responses from the survey is represented in the table below:

Table 5.1 Respondents to the Survey

Age	female	male	prefer not to say
18-30	58	3	1
31-45	74	18	1

⁶⁷⁴ Oluyemisi Bangbose ‘Access to Justice through Clinical Legal Education: A Way Forward for Good Governance and Development’ (2015) 15 African Human Rights Journal, 382.

46-50	19	5	7
50 and above	28	10	2

Table 5.2 Gender Table

Gender	Number
Female	179
Male	36
Prefer Not to Say	11
TOTAL	226

The total number of responses analysed were Two Hundred and Twenty-Six with females representing 79.2% of the total responses. The males represented 15.9% and those who preferred not to state their gender represented 4.8%. This reveals that majority of the respondents who took part in the survey were females.

6.2 Informal Mediation as a Process to Justice

Mediation has been defined in Chapter Five of this study. The purpose for collecting data on “informal mediation” as a theme in the resolution of family dispute, is to highlight the importance of informal mediation as a social process of dispute resolution in Nigeria.

In analysing the findings, the following data stood out from the responses of the survey and were further explored in the interviews:

1. The majority of the survey responses were by people who had experienced some form of informal mediation process in the past and had sought a more formal process in resolving family disputes.
2. Where there was a prevalence of informal mediation as the first step of the dispute resolution process and where family members or in-laws existed in marital situations, they were usually the first mediators in the attempt to resolve the family dispute.

Majority of the survey responses were by people who had experienced some form of informal mediation process in the past and had sought a more formal process in resolving family disputes. In examining the findings which led to this perception, the responses from the survey revealed the following: In the 18-30 age group, 93% of the women sought formal mediation after experiencing informal mediation in resolving family dispute, while the number of men who sought formal mediation in this category were 4.8%. There was no representation for those who preferred not to say as there was no response on this issue. In this age category it is clear that the percentage of women who sought formal mediation after experiencing informal mediation is higher than the men. Also in the 31-45 age category, 79.5% of the women sought formal mediation after experiencing informal mediation in the resolution of family dispute. While 19.3% of men in this age category sought formal mediation after experiencing informal mediation, and 9% of the participants preferred not to say. In this category, again the percentage of the women is higher than the men.

In the 46-50 years age category, according to the data 61.2% of women sought formal mediation after having experienced informal mediation in the past to resolve their family disputes. While for the men 16.1% participants sought formal mediation after experiencing informal mediation. For the group of participants who chose not to state their gender, the data collected represented their value as 63.6% who sought formal mediation after experiencing informal mediation. In the 50 & Above age category, 70% represented women who sought

formal mediation after experiencing informal mediation. For the males, the survey showed 25% sought formal mediation after experiencing informal mediation, while 5% represented the category of those who preferred not to say. In the different age categories, women showed the highest percentage in seeking formal mediation after experiencing informal mediation. This indicates that the percentage of women when compared to the men, is higher for those who sought formal mediation after having experienced informal mediation in the resolution of their family disputes.

The second revelation from the results of the survey was- Where there was a prevalence of informal mediation as the first step of the dispute resolution process and where family members or in-laws⁶⁷⁵ existed in marital situations, they were usually the first mediators in the attempt to resolve the family dispute. In arriving at this perception, the evidence was revealed from the survey as explained below:

In the 18-30 age bracket, the total number of women were 58 and the findings revealed the value of those who experienced informal mediation through family or in-laws were 90% as represented from the data analysis. While only 3.2% of the men had experienced informal mediation with family or in-laws as the first mediators. This analysis suggests that in family disputes for women in this age bracket the involvement of family or in-laws was not out of place. It could not be ascertained at this point if it was the choice of the women to have their family or in-laws as mediators as this question was not asked in this research and can be pursued in future research. 6.4% persons in this age bracket preferred not to comment on this question in the survey.

In the 31-45 age category, the value of women who had experienced informal mediation with their in-laws being the first mediators were 70%, while the men were 12.9%. 10.7% in this

⁶⁷⁵ In-laws represent the relatives of the disputing parties, whether married or cohabiting.

group declined to comment on the issue. In the 46-50 age group, 48.3% of the women had experienced informal mediation where the first mediators in a family dispute were the in-laws. The men were 9.6% in value who had experienced informal mediation with family or in-laws as the first mediators, while 19.3% of this age group chose not to comment on the issue. While in the 50 & Above age group the value of women who experienced informal mediation with in-laws as the first mediators in a marital dispute, were 62.5%. The findings from the data analysis revealed the value of men as 17.5% and 12.5% of the participants preferred not to comment. The data analysis of the survey responses consistently reveals that in the prevalence of informal mediation where family or in-laws are the first mediators in the resolution of family disputes, the result is inclined towards women.

From the findings about informal mediation described above, the researcher was able to deduce that participants, despite having experienced informal mediation, had proceeded to seek formal mediation in the resolution of their family dispute. Some of the responses suggested that the participants would have experienced satisfaction with their mediation process if it had been formal mediation as was indicated in the response by No.130 in the survey, which was – *“the case was mediated upon but it failed as my husband refused to comply but instead went to file for a divorce at the shariah court Dawakin Kudu but I was represented by FIDA and I had my rights protected”*. This statement by this participant unfortunately can only be ascertained by further research as it is not within the scope of the questions asked in the survey. But the participant had sought mediation at the FIDA legal centre and was consequently represented in court as well in the litigation process. Another perspective was expressed in this statement by a respondent who described the process of mediation in the resolution of family dispute as *“a brilliant alternative to litigation,”*⁶⁷⁶ which informs the opinion that satisfaction can be

⁶⁷⁶ Respondent No. 25 of Survey responses.

derived from family mediation. The only issue with this statement is not being able to ascertain if the respondent meant informal or formal family mediation.

A contrary opinion was expressed in another response; *“I feel so disappointed and pained. I feel like I wasted my time and resources going for the mediation. I feel like it is not worth it.”*⁶⁷⁷

This response indicates that the participant was not satisfied by mediation. This further illustrates that mediation does not satisfy all those who seek it as a route to justice and the response did not indicate if it was informal or formal mediation. As this response was from the survey, further research as to the explanation behind the response was not possible hence the need for the interviews to examine if dissatisfaction, where it arises, emanates from informal or formal family mediation.

From the evidence of the data analysis, the number of women who sought formal mediation is highest in the 31-45 age category. In all the age categories, the women represent the highest numbers which indicates that more women seek formal resolutions to their family disputes where informal mediation has failed. The data also revealed the fact that the number of women who sought mediation reduced in the older women. This provoked a further question in this study, do older women perceive formal mediation differently from younger women? This perception was mentioned based on the small percentage of women whose response in the survey indicated that not all women were in support of mediation⁶⁷⁸ - *“It really does more harm than good as it gives women the licence to disrespect their husbands”*. On closer examination of the data, it was revealed that the age category of this respondent was 50 & Above. The responses of the survey reveal the mixed feelings in which family mediation is viewed. On a general level, taking into consideration all the age categories, the result of the analysis indicates more women experienced formal mediation even after the process of

⁶⁷⁷ Respondent No 37 of Survey responses.

⁶⁷⁸ Respondent No 212 of Survey responses.

informal mediation when compared with men as there was no evidence of men lodging complaints at the FIDA legal centre in this regard.

In all the age categories the percentage of women is higher than the men (for those who participated in the survey for the data collection) as those who experienced informal mediation first and with family or in-laws as the mediators. This is a common occurrence in most family settings, especially in the rural areas in Nigeria. When there is a problem in the home, the issue is reported to the family members, usually the elders, before the matter is reported to external parties, no matter the gravity as stated in the literature in Chapter Five and further supported by evidence of the findings of the data collection. It would seem that women report to their in-laws first because they do not want to be accused of airing their ‘dirty linen in public’ by discussing family matters outside the family.

This was further evidenced by the statement of one of the respondents of the survey whose response to the question on the perception of informal mediation was: “this is customary to bring issues to family and in-laws first”.⁶⁷⁹ Another example was illustrated in this survey response; “*It was when the meeting between my in-laws and village chiefs failed that I reached out to FIDA*”.⁶⁸⁰ When examined in this light, can you really say mediation took place when the core principles of neutrality and impartiality of the mediator cannot be guaranteed? The persons acting as mediators are family members and sometimes interested parties to the family disputes, which presupposes the fact that they have opinions about the dispute, and it would be challenging to remain impartial as mediators.

Interview

⁶⁷⁹ Respondent No 182 of survey responses.

⁶⁸⁰ Respondent No 208 of survey responses.

During the interviews, the question on the theme “informal mediation as a process to justice” was developed as a follow up to explore the responses from the survey on informal mediation in more depth, to develop an understanding of why many women experienced the need to seek formal mediation following informal mediation. For the interviews, seventeen participants gave their consent and took part and fourteen out of the number stated that they had experienced informal mediation before proceeding to the FIDA legal centre. Three out of the seventeen participants indicated that they had not engaged in informal mediation before coming to the FIDA legal centre.

The participants were asked, **“Have you experienced informal mediation before?”**

The following were the responses of the participants, one of which was an outright “No”.⁶⁸¹

In response to the question, another participant said, *“No, I didn’t tell anyone”*.⁶⁸² When asked why she did not tell her family members, she responded that her family would tell her to leave him, and she did not want that. The two participants who responded that they had not previously been engaged in informal mediation did not see the need for it as evidenced in their response which followed during the interview. While another participant responded with:

“Yes, I did that in the past and it did not help so I decided to come to FIDA”.⁶⁸³

While another participant also responded to the question with the following words:

“Yes, I reported to my family and our Pastor but to no avail. My parents called us; his parents also called us but there was no change. Then I confided in a friend who told me about FIDA, so I came”.⁶⁸⁴

⁶⁸¹ Interview with Participant 4 Anambra State FIDA Legal Centre, held on 13 January 2022 at 13:55hrs.

⁶⁸² Interview with Participant 2, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on 05 October 2021 at 11:23hrs.

⁶⁸³ Interview with Participant 3, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on 05 October 2021 at 11:34hrs.

⁶⁸⁴ Interview with Participant 5, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on 23 May 2022 at 11:23hrs.

The legal consciousness of this participant shows a lack of faith in the informal family mediation system and her decision to proceed to FIDA to seek formal mediation. Her resort to her Pastor reveals the expected role of religion in family mediation which will be explained as one of the sub-themes in this Chapter.

Another participant in response to the questions she was asked, explained her experience of informal mediation in the excerpt below:

“Question: Was it difficult for you to access FIDA when you came and were they able to help you with your family issues?”

Answer: They really helped me, at least they helped me to be able to have a place to stay in my father’s house since my husband pushed me out.

Question: Before you came to FIDA, was there any time informal mediation took place to try and resolve dispute with your family members?”

*Answer: No, there was no way for us to sit down and resolve anything because they were the ones who wanted to push me out of my father’s house that’s why I ran to FIDA”.*⁶⁸⁵

The narration of this participant tells the story of how informal family mediation did not only abuse her legal right to have place to stay in her father’s house if not for the intervention of FIDA, but also contradicted the principles of mediation. The family members who were to preside over the mediation were not impartial and she had to seek justice at formal mediation by proceeding to the FIDA centre.

A different participant responded to the question on whether she had experienced informal mediation previously with these words: *“Yes ma, the two families, they came together and resolved the matter that was 3 years ago. Then he had abandoned me and my daughter and*

⁶⁸⁵ Interview with Participant 2, Anambra State FIDA Legal Centre held on 13 January 2022 at 13:20hrs.

relocated to a new place".⁶⁸⁶ This statement by the participant revealed the fact that though informal family mediation had provided her with the satisfaction she sought in allowing her family members to mediate in her marital dispute, it was for 3 years as her husband relocated and abandoned her and her daughter. Her decision to seek formal mediation revealed her legal consciousness of hope in formal mediation providing the satisfaction she sought in accessing justice through procedural methods.

Further excerpts from the transcripts provides a vivid picture of how informal mediation operates in reality. The findings on further illustrations with some of the participants are as follows:

(A)

“Question: Did you report them to the elders of the community or the village chiefs?

Answer: Yes, but they could not do anything.

Question: Are you saying informal mediation did not help?

Answer: It did not help me as my husband’s people were not afraid of the village chiefs.

Question: But when FIDA invited them for the mediation, did they come?

Answer: Yes, they came, and they obeyed everything in the agreement we signed".⁶⁸⁷

In analysing the above scenario, informal mediation did not avail the participant of the justice she sought, and she had to seek formal mediation by lodging a complaint at the FIDA legal centre. She informed the researcher during the interview that she was a widow whose husband died, and her in-laws seized her late husband’s property immediately after the burial. In this excerpt the themes of culture and the role of patriarchy are highlighted from the statements of

⁶⁸⁶ Interview with Participant 1, Lagos State FIDA Legal Centre, held on 17 January 2022 at 10:23am.

⁶⁸⁷ Interview with Participant 3, Anambra State FIDA Legal Centre, held on 13 January 2022 at 13:38hrs.

the participant. The in-laws of the participant were not afraid of the village chiefs, and they had seized her late husband's property. But when they were invited to the FIDA legal centre, they honoured the invitation and complied with the agreement reached at the formal mediation. This further emphasises the lack of power of informal family mediation agreement where one of the parties refuses to comply with the agreement and informs the need for legislation to regulate informal mediation. It also illustrates the power of government intervention in family mediation which is one of the themes which emerged in the data collection.

(B)

“Question: Have you experienced informal mediation before coming to FIDA?”

*Answer: Yes, I went to his parents, our pastor in church, and his friends but he refused to hear from them, so I decided to come to FIDA”.*⁶⁸⁸

The response by the participant reveals her legal consciousness in the decision to proceed to formal mediation where informal mediation had failed her. In this excerpt the reference to religion by the participant is revealed which is a sub-theme of this study.

(C)

“Question: Did you report to any other informal mediation body like village chiefs before coming to FIDA?”

*Answer: No ma, they said I want to spoil their family name by publicising the matter that's why they wanted me to close the case and as I refused, they join my husband to chase me out”.*⁶⁸⁹

⁶⁸⁸ Interview with Participant 8, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre, held on 23 May 2022 at 11:38hrs.

⁶⁸⁹ Interview with Participant 4, Anambra State FIDA Legal Centre held on 13 January 2022 at 13:55hrs.

This excerpt further reveals the sub-theme of stigma and social control which is a form of barrier to women's access to justice and will be discussed further on in this chapter. The attempt of the family to stop the participant from continuing with the case by chasing her out of the house illustrates how stigma and social control can infringe on women's access to justice.

(D)

“Question: Did you seek informal mediation with family members before coming to FIDA?”

*Answer: Yes, I did that in the past and it did not help so I decided to come to FIDA”.*⁶⁹⁰

The disappointment in informal family mediation stands out clearly from the statement of this participant. It also reveals her awareness of the fact that formal mediation could provide the satisfaction she sought which expressed her legal consciousness.

(E)

“Question: Before you came to FIDA, did you engage in informal mediation- did you inform family members to resolve the dispute?”

Answer: Yes, I did

Question: What was the outcome?”

Answer: There was no good outcome. It did not change anything.

Question: Were you satisfied with the mediation process at the FIDA Centre?”

*Answer: Yes”.*⁶⁹¹

Based on the findings of the data analysis on informal mediation as a process to justice, it is logical to suggest that the dissatisfaction with the informal mediation process is one of the

⁶⁹⁰ Interview with Participant 3, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on 05 October 2021 at 11:34hrs.

⁶⁹¹ Interview with Participant 6, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on 22 October 2021 at 13:23hrs.

reasons women seek formal mediation. The dissatisfaction of the women with informal mediation is related to the lack of enforcement of the mediation agreement where there is non-compliance, with the underpinnings of cultural and family expectations. Which leads this study to the next section.

6.3 Accessing the Formal System

In line with the objective of understanding access to justice by Nigerian women through family mediation, this theme “accessing the formal system” was analysed in two-folds:

- (a) The challenge of physically accessing the location for those who had to journey into town where the FIDA legal centre is located
- (b) The mediation process and how the participants viewed the process in achieving their objective. Whether the participants obtained satisfaction from mediation process, either from the survey responses or the interview process.

For the first category- in analysing the survey responses which was an online process as the questionnaire was filled and submitted via Microsoft forms, it will be difficult to determine if the participants who responded to the survey questions encountered physical challenges. The physical challenge of accessing the system included having to travel to the town where the FIDA legal centre is located, and this could only be answered by the participants of the interview process. This was evidenced in the response of one of the participants from Rivers State who had to come from Ahoada into Port Harcourt, a journey of about 33.1 miles which is about 1 hour journey.⁶⁹² This signifies how important the participant considers formal mediation. The FIDA legal centre is not in every town, but it is located in most major cities in Nigeria and where it is not located in a particular area, the person desirous of making a complaint makes the effort to locate the nearest office. This was evidenced by one of the

⁶⁹² Interview with Participant 7 at the Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre on 23 May 2022 at 12:06 hrs.

participants, in her response; *“It was a bit difficult as I had to travel into the main town where the office is but when I got here, they attended to me”*.⁶⁹³

The willingness to make the sacrifice to journey into town to access justice is worthy of consideration in the analysis of this research. It is indicative of the legal consciousness of the participant’s faith in the formal system of justice. The action of the participant in making the extra effort to seek justice outside her comfort area, is a reflection of her legal consciousness of the impact of formal mediation which is embedded in the formal system.

In an attempt to do justice to the first category, this section examined the way and manner respondents perceive accessing formal systems. Some participants stated that they found the process easy as testified by Respondent 6 in the survey who said: *“The process was very good as it took care of all my concerns and the welfare of my kids are ensured”*. Other participants appeared to have a negative impression about formal systems because they believe that they do not function in their interests as revealed in some of the responses – *“It is never a strait jacket end result. There are a lot of compromises from both parties. But the woman is made to compromise more for peace to reign”*.⁶⁹⁴ It is unclear if the respondent was speaking about formal or informal mediation as it was from the survey, there was no opportunity to probe further.

In discussing this theme, the findings from the survey were analysed first and informed the questions for the interview on the theme and discussed below. There were several interesting answers in response to the question asked in the survey, **“How do you feel about mediation?”** Some of the responses include: *“No opinion as I’ve never participated before, but I agree with it as a concept for dispute resolution,”*⁶⁹⁵ *“The process was very uncomfortable and depressing*

⁶⁹³ Interview with Participant 4, Anambra State FIDA Legal Centre held on 13 January 2022 at 13:55hrs.

⁶⁹⁴ Respondent 32 of survey responses.

⁶⁹⁵ Respondent 30, Female, age: 50 and above: religion- Christian

as I was not able to express my views and concerns because of cultural reasons”.⁶⁹⁶ Another respondent stated her feelings as *“I felt it to be the easiest way to solve disputes among families. It didn't involve a lot of complexities that court proceedings usually come up with”*:⁶⁹⁷ *“The mediation process which broke down issues and resolved them one by one, helped myself and my wife reconcile”*.⁶⁹⁸ A contrary view was *“It should not be encouraged because it does more harm than good because why will third party be involved in family issues”*.⁶⁹⁹

Though a direct question on formal system of mediation was not asked in the survey to avoid complicating the question and misunderstandings, the responses revealed the position of those who took part, as it expressed the awareness of justice access routes available in the choices made by the participants. From examining the survey results, the satisfaction or dissatisfaction with the mediation process, was revealed in the actions of the parties. It also revealed that the age categories affected the way the participants viewed family mediation. The survey was distributed all over Nigeria and consequently to those who had access to IT,⁷⁰⁰ computer or android phones to access Microsoft forms. As it was a survey, and not a face-to-face query, it was challenging to explain the difference between informal and formal mediation to the respondents to avoid confusion.

In discussing the second category of the theme “accessing the formal system” which is the **Satisfaction on the Outcome of Mediation**, comprising of satisfaction with the process and the procedure, the survey responses and interview process were analysed. This category is in accordance with the second approach of women’s access to justice as postulated by Chopra

⁶⁹⁶ Respondent 12, Female, age: 50 and above: religion- Islam.

⁶⁹⁷ Respondent 54, Female, age: 18-30, religion- Christian.

⁶⁹⁸ Respondent 143, Male, age: 31-45, religion- Islam.

⁶⁹⁹ Respondent 122, Female, age 50 and above, religion- Islam.

⁷⁰⁰ Information Technology.

and Isser as mentioned in Chapter Three of this thesis.⁷⁰¹ The approach highlighted the satisfaction with the procedure whether informal or formal, seeing as the data analysis has revealed the relation between the informal and formal, it is logical to examine it in this theme. The analysis of their responses revealed valuable insights into the participants' perspectives on the satisfaction of the outcome of family mediation. In the survey, the participants were asked the question; **“Were you satisfied with the outcome of your mediation?”** The responses were captured in the findings and represented in the table below:

Table 6.3.1 Satisfaction with Outcome of Mediation for the survey (Age Table)

Age	18-30	31-45	46-50	50 and above
Yes	44	56	15	22
No	4	14	7	3
Partially Satisfied	5	11	8	13
No Response	9	12	1	2
Total	62	93	31	40

⁷⁰¹ Tanja Chopra and Deborah Isser, 'Women's Access to Justice, Legal Pluralism and Fragile States' [2011] [https://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/74991461/Womens_Access_to_Justice_Legal_Pluralis20211121-28, 24](https://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/74991461/Womens_Access_to_Justice_Legal_Pluralis20211121-28,24), (Accessed 06/08/2023).

Table 6.3.2 Satisfaction with Outcome of Mediation (Gender Table)

Gender	Female	Male	Prefer Not to Say
Yes	112	22	3
No	17	8	3
Partially Satisfied	28	4	5
No Response	22	2	0
Total	179	36	11

From the Age and Gender Table on the survey responses as illustrated above, the data represented shows that in all the age categories, the female population is higher than the male, excluding the numbers which preferred not to mention their gender. This should be borne in mind when interpreting the data analysis that more women responded than the men in the survey as the numbers were 179 women to 36 men. This section below presents a more focused and concise analysis of the data related to participants' satisfaction with the outcome of their mediations, based on their gender and age categories. The aim is to provide a clearer understanding of the findings and their implications of family mediation as it affects different gender, with women as the focus which is part of the purpose for this research.

6.3.1. Gender Analysis

For the women, 62.5% expressed satisfaction with mediation process, while 9.4% expressed dissatisfaction and 15.6% were partially satisfied. 12.2% did not respond to this question from those who identified as women. Among the male participants in the survey, there was a total of 36 individuals. Out of these, 61.1% expressed satisfaction with the outcome of their mediations, while 22.2% were dissatisfied. Those who reported being partially satisfied

accounted for 11.1% of the male participants, and 5.5% did not provide a response. In the “Prefer Not to Say” category, which consisted of 11 participants, satisfaction and dissatisfaction rates were both 27.2%, and the partially satisfied percentage was 45.4%. There was no representation for the participants in this category who chose not to respond.

From the analysis of the data, it is evident that both women and men who took part in the survey had almost the same rate of satisfaction with the outcome of the mediation process. The fact that the rate of satisfaction for women is still higher than that of the men, suggests that women appear to prefer family mediation as a process of accessing justice in the resolution of family disputes. This might not be unconnected to societal and family expectation on the women to be the ones who maintain family harmony irrespective of whatever patriarchal injustices she must experience. The finding is significant in understanding the gender dynamics and prevalence of informal family mediation during family dispute resolution, which will contribute to the overall findings of this research.

6.3.2. Age Category Analysis

To further explore the satisfaction levels based on age categories, Table 5.3 provides a breakdown of the participants’ responses according to different age groups: 18-30, 31-45, 46-50, and 50 and Above. In the 18-30 age category, 70.96% expressed satisfaction with the outcome of their mediations, while only 6.45% reported dissatisfaction. For the 31-45 age category, the satisfaction rate was 60.2%, with a dissatisfaction rate of 15%. In the 46-50 age category, 48.3% expressed satisfaction, while 22.5% were dissatisfied. Among participants aged 50 and above, 55% reported satisfaction with the outcome of their mediations, and only 7.5% expressed dissatisfaction. Analysing the data presented in Table 5.3, it is evident that the 31-45 age category had the highest satisfaction rate with the outcome of mediation, while the 46-50 age category had the lowest satisfaction rate.

These findings provide important insights into the relationship between age and satisfaction with mediation outcomes. The results from different age categories contribute to the overall understanding of the research and will influence the recommendations of this study as this will reveal which age category derives more satisfaction from the different forms of family mediation. In the subsequent sections, these findings will be further analysed and interpreted, drawing upon relevant literature and experiences of the participants to provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing satisfaction levels in family mediation. This analysis contributes to the academic discourse and will provide valuable insights for legal practitioners and policymakers as it concerns family mediation in Nigeria. The consolidation of the analysis on the level of satisfaction with the outcome of the type of family mediation, will be determined by the interviews. The responses from the survey does not always reveal the kind of family mediation which led to the satisfaction analysis, whether informal or formal. This can be investigated during the interviews though not with the same participants.

The interviews provided valuable insights into participants' experiences with the process and their satisfaction with the outcomes. Participants were asked a specific question: **“Was it easy for you to access the justice you wanted at the FIDA Legal Centre?”** Their responses painted a narrative of their encounters with the formal system and its effectiveness in the delivery of justice. Seventeen participants took part in the interviews, and sixteen of them testified as to their satisfaction with the process which suggested they received the justice they sought. The exception was the woman who stated that her husband was yet to comply with the mediation agreement and let her have access to her youngest son.⁷⁰² The other women revealed their satisfaction in the following excerpts from the interviews:

One of the participants stated in her response:

⁷⁰² Interview with Participant 2, Lagos State FIDA Legal Centre held on 17 February 2022 at 10:17am.

*“Yes, it was, the process was fair as I got my fair hearing and got my children”.*⁷⁰³

Her response highlighted the fairness of the process and her successful attainment of the desired outcome, which was regaining custody of her children. This narrative underscores the significance of accessing the formal system at the FIDA legal centre in securing just and favourable decisions. This was contrary to her experience at informal family mediation which she informed the researcher had failed because her husband would not listen to anyone.

Another participant during the interview in response to the question stated:

*“Yes, it was, when we got here, they invited my uncle and our other relatives for a mediation and at the end of the whole process, and they gave us back our building documents and properties and returned the money. What we have been fighting for, for the past 8 years”.*⁷⁰⁴

This evidence revealed the anguish of the participant’s prolonged struggle and the instrumental role of FIDA in resolving their family dispute. The successful recovery of their building documents, properties, and finances marked a significant milestone in their quest for justice. Again, the inability of the dispute to be resolved through informal mediation was highlighted in this situation as they only received their satisfaction when they accessed formal mediation at the FIDA centre.

A third participant from another part of Nigeria also testified as to the ease of the mediation process which resulted in her accessing the justice she sought. In her response she stated:

*“Yes, as I came, I met a lawyer and explained to the lawyer, my husband was invited, and he came, and the mediation started, and it went smoothly”.*⁷⁰⁵

⁷⁰³ Interview with Participant 4, Lagos State FIDA Legal Centre, held on 17 February 2022 at 10:01hrs.

⁷⁰⁴ Interview with Participant 9, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on 23 May 2022 at 11:38hrs.

⁷⁰⁵ Interview with Participant 5, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on 23 May 2022 at 11:23hrs.

This narrative emphasized the importance of engaging with a lawyer and the collaborative nature of the mediation process. The participant's satisfaction stemmed from the smoothness and efficiency with which the formal system operated, which led to a successful resolution of their grievances. Further evidence of the effectiveness of accessing the formal system through the FIDA Legal Centre emerged from the interviews with other participants.

An excerpt from the interview with another participant:

“Question: Was it easy for you to access FIDA and have they been able to help you?”

Answer: Yes, they have helped me to recover some of my husband's property that they sold and gave me the money, after they invited them to come for mediation.”⁷⁰⁶

This illustrates FIDA's ability to address family disputes on property related issues and provide restitution as well as satisfaction, thereby reinforcing its role in the delivery of justice to participants. The participant informed the researcher during the interview of how her late husband's brothers had seized and sold their properties but with the help of FIDA she was able to recover the proceeds from the sales. The element of patriarchal control, which is one of the sub-themes, is revealed in this case as it was exercised over the woman even after the death of her husband by her in-laws which is an infringement of her legal rights. Her choice to seek formal mediation by going to FIDA is an expression of her legal consciousness in enforcing her rights as a woman accessing justice.

The impact of this theme in mediation proceedings was also confirmed by this participant below:

Question: Were you satisfied with the mediation proceedings?

⁷⁰⁶ Interview with Participant 3, Anambra State FIDA Legal Centre held on 13 January 2022 at 13:38hrs.

Answer: Yes".⁷⁰⁷

Though brief, this affirmation indicated a positive experience with the overall process, further supporting the effectiveness of accessing the formal system at the FIDA legal centre.

These excerpts from the interview are findings on the satisfaction of the participants on the outcome of their mediation on the theme accessing the formal system. The data analysis on this theme based on the survey responses interviews, indicates more satisfaction in the formal mediation process of family dispute resolution than the informal family mediation process.

6.4 Intimate Partner Violence/Domestic Violence (IPV)

Though the number of responses from the survey on IPV/domestic violence was not as high as those for the other themes, it was included as a theme because it featured in the responses of the participants, as 28.4% testified to the presence of IPV. The decision to code IPV/ domestic violence as a theme was consequently to examine the reason why participants preferred to resolve IPV through mediation rather than reporting to the police. The responses from the survey indicated that where there was the presence of IPV/domestic abuse, and the issue was mentioned to the mediator, there was still a reluctance to report the matter to the police. In discussing the data analysis of the IPV theme, the results of the survey and the responses of the participants during the interview led to the findings of this study. The question on IPV for the survey was:

“Was there any Intimate Partner Violence (IPV) involved in your situation?” The following were the findings from the data analysis of the survey responses-

⁷⁰⁷ Interview with Participant 7, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on 23 May 2022 at 12:06hrs.

Table 6.4 IPV/Domestic Abuse Response from Survey Table

Gender	Yes	No	No Response
Female	51	71	57
Male	3	15	18
Prefer Not to Say	3	2	6

In analysing the data, the result of the findings was 28.4% of the women responded in the affirmative to the evidence of domestic violence in their dispute while 39.6% responded in the negative. 31.8% declined to answer the question. In examining this evidence, the highest number of women responded that there was no IPV in their family dispute, and next highest number declined to comment. Those who acknowledged the presence of IPV is the lowest. This provokes the question whether IPV is a major issue in family disputes or not. For the men, 2.7% responded “yes” to the question, 41.6% responded “no” and 50% declined to comment.

From the analysis of this data, the results show that though domestic violence features in family disputes, the percentage of those who declined to comment in all the categories is higher than the actual responses. For the women it was 31.8%, the men recorded 50% for those who declined to comment. This result was interesting in this study especially when compared with the following statement from one of the respondents in the survey - *“I was hiding the beatings because of shame”*.⁷⁰⁸ The provoking thought arose as to the reasons behind the choice for informal mediation as a process of family dispute resolution in the face of domestic violence.

Could the fact that a higher percentage of the survey respondents’ refusal to comment on the issue be an indication of the “unspoken law” where women are expected to protect the sanctity of the home, no matter the cost to her wellbeing? This will impact on the women’s access to

⁷⁰⁸ No 218 of survey responses.

justice if she is not free to seek justice when her rights are abused or infringed upon. It is beholden on the government and other agencies to ensure that where women feel unsafe opening up, and sharing their experiences, safe provisions are made available for them to fully participate in the judicial process. In this context 'safe' meaning physical safety and psychological safety where they know that what they report will not be used against them.

Part of the objective of this study is to understand what influences the choices women make in accessing justice. Some of the responses from the survey suggest women will not choose a process to access justice if they have no confidence in the system. Evidence of disillusionment women feel in deciding channels of justice when seeking redress was expressed in this statement by one of the respondents in the survey - *"It never worked because they choose sides"*.⁷⁰⁹ This was in response to the question "why the mediator was not informed of the presence of IPV". Another respondent stated, *"I didn't inform the mediator, because I didn't feel comfortable telling the mediator about that"*.⁷¹⁰ To the next question which asked for an explanation of the previous question, she responded- *"I was so scared of what he will do to me"*. The response of this participant illustrates her lack of confidence in the chosen mode of access to justice despite the presence of IPV as was indicated by her answer wherein she responded "yes" to the question on whether there was presence of IPV.

Despite being subjected to IPV, she was still reluctant to report the abuse to the mediator. In interpreting this action, it reveals a lack of confidence in the justice system which illustrates the legal consciousness of the mindset of the woman. If she knew she would obtain justice by reporting the crime of IPV, the reluctance to seek redress might not have been an issue. Her statement revealed her fear was from the consequences of what would follow her action after reporting the abuse. As the responses were from the survey, there was no opportunity for further

⁷⁰⁹ No 14 of survey responses.

⁷¹⁰ No 67 of survey responses.

questioning hence the need for the interviews to explore the reluctance to talk about IPV. The number of those who experienced IPV was also small at the interview stage of data collection.

Interview

During the interviews, seventeen participants took part in the research and six⁷¹¹ of them had experienced IPV and decided to report it for formal mediation at the FIDA centre.

When the participants were questioned on what brought them to the FIDA Legal Centre and the response was domestic violence, the following question was asked:

“Did you report to the Police?”

The participants were expected to state the reasons for their answers, whether in the affirmative or negative to give clarity to the issue the interview sought to address.

One of the participants in her response stated,

*“No, because of the way the police handle issues. I felt they would not handle it well and I preferred to come to FIDA after discussing with my family and they supported me”.*⁷¹²

In analysing her answer, the understanding deduced is that she had no confidence that if she had reported to the police, the matter would be handled to her satisfaction. She also had the support of her family members in going to the FIDA Legal Centre in contrast to reporting to the police.

Another participant in her response to the question on what brought her to the FIDA Legal Centre, replied, domestic violence. She stated the following as her reason for not reporting the matter to the police:

⁷¹¹ Interviews at the FIDA Legal Centres - Participant 3 (Lagos), Participant 2 (Rivers), Participant 4 (Rivers), Participant 5 (Rivers), Participant 6 (Rivers), and Participant 10 (Rivers).

⁷¹² Interview with Participant 3, Lagos State FIDA Legal Centre, held on 17 February 2022 at 09:44hrs.

*“I didn’t want it to end in a bad way, that’s why I came to FIDA, you know the way the Nigerian police are”.*⁷¹³

The statement revealed the negative impression women have of the police especially in the way domestic matters are addressed when reported at the police station. This reveals the legal consciousness of how the police is perceived by women in addressing domestic matters.

A third participant did not disclose whether she desired to involve the police but chose to come to the FIDA Legal Centre and adopt mediation as the form of dispute resolution. She narrated her reason for being at the Centre in the following statement when interviewed:

*“Domestic violence and lack of welfare. I have been married for over 8years and my husband and I have been having serious issues. He has been beating me and not providing for me and the children and also having extramarital issues outside our home. Last year he brought a woman into our matrimonial home and that was the last straw. I heard about FIDA, that’s why I came”.*⁷¹⁴

In addressing the issue of domestic violence, emotional violence was highlighted in the course of the interview and examined in the analysis because emotion does play a major role in the mind of the victim/participant before it becomes physical. The response of one of the participants led to this angle in the research which was not part of the initial research design at the beginning of the interviews. But it arose, and I realised that it is indeed an important part of this study as the emotions of the participants determine the actions they take.

The emotions of the participants affected their legal consciousness which informed their decision to resolve their issues at the FIDA centre rather than the police station as revealed by the participant who stated that she did not report to the police because she did not want to make

⁷¹³ Interview with Participant 2, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on 05 October 2021 at 11:23hrs.

⁷¹⁴ Interview with Participant 4, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on 05 October 2021 at 11:46hrs.

matters worse.⁷¹⁵ Further evidence of preference for FIDA to resolve issues of IPV was in the response of one of the participants when asked what brought her to the FIDA Legal Centre and she mentioned emotional violence

*“I had issues with my husband. There was a lot of emotional violence and abuse going on in my marriage”.*⁷¹⁶

The decision of the above participant to resolve the issues of emotional violence in her marriage by reporting the matter at the FIDA Centre, indicates her legal consciousness which is an awareness of the fact that she preferred FIDA to preside over her matters. Her statement brings emotional violence under the jurisdiction of the IPV theme and is further emphasised by the definition of emotional violence/abuse in *Section 46 of the VAPP Act, 2015*.

Another excerpt below though lengthy, illustrates a clear picture of how the theme of IPV was expressed during the interview stage of data collection:

“Question: What kind of dispute brought you to the FIDA Centre?”

Answer: Domestic violence, several beatings from my husband is what brought me here. We have been married for 13 years and the beatings started some months ago.

Question: Did you report to the police?

Answer: No, I came directly to FIDA

Question: Why?

Answer: I felt as female lawyers they would understand better.

Question: Was it easy for you to access the help you wanted at the FIDA Centre?

⁷¹⁵ Which seems to be in accordance with the CLEEN report of fear of retribution being the main reason for silence on domestic violence.

⁷¹⁶ Interview with Participant 5, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on 23 May 2022 at 11:23hrs.

Answer: Yes, they handled it well

Question: Before you came to FIDA, did you engage in informal mediation- did you inform family members to resolve the dispute?

Answer: Yes, I did

Question: What was the outcome?

Answer: There was no good outcome. It did not change anything.

Question: Were you satisfied with the mediation process at the FIDA Centre?

Answer: Yes

Question: Did you enter into a mediation agreement?

Answer: Yes

Question: Have there been any challenges in enforcing the mediation agreement?

Answer: No, because it is FIDA. My husband has been complying with the agreement and has not raised his hand on me since”.⁷¹⁷

The evidence above by the participants indicate that women suffer IPV/domestic violence and are willing to explore mediation in their attempt to seek justice, rather than report the matter to the police. It reveals the awareness of legal consciousness of Nigerian women and the struggle they go through at different levels and channels to access justice, from the family to the outer society including law enforcement officers. The responses of the women particularly the one who clearly said she did not want the matter to become worse,⁷¹⁸ reveal the distrust Nigerian women have for the police in family matters.

⁷¹⁷ Interview Participant 6, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on 22 October 2021 at 13:23hrs.

⁷¹⁸ Other participants of the interview.

In analysing the data at the interview stage, 35.2% of the total number of participants interviewed reported experiencing domestic violence. These participants had decided to lay their complaint at the FIDA Legal Centre rather than making a report at the police station. The data analysis of the survey revealed a reluctance to comment on IPV and the number of those who testified as to its existence in their relationships, was not a high number. The testimony of one of the participants during the interview, who, when she was asked why she did not report the domestic abuse to the police she responded, “you know the way Nigerian police are”⁷¹⁹ is further proof of how women view the police. This reflects the discussion earlier in this Chapter where participants expressed a lack of faith in the police and a danger of making such reports. The lack of confidence in the state mechanisms for law enforcement (in this case the Nigerian police), is suggested to be one of the fundamental reasons victims of IPV do not report incidents to the police. They prefer to seek assistance in accessing justice from NGOs as evident in the responses from the participants in the interviews conducted in this research. This highlights the important role of NGO’s in empowering women to seek justice when they lack trust in the authorities.

It is noteworthy to highlight one of the statements by a respondent- “I was being physically and emotionally abused by my partner”.⁷²⁰ This respondent was able to highlight emotional abuse, which is a form of IPV. It is unclear if the low numbers on the occurrence of IPV is as a result of the misconception that IPV relates only to physical abuse. Could this be part of the reason of the low numbers for those who openly acknowledged the existence of IPV in their relationships or the high numbers of those who declined to comment? That this finding is also replicated in the interviews is not a coincidence and needs further research (in another study) especially when compared with the fact that domestic violence is one of the core abuses against

⁷¹⁹ Interview with Participant 2, FIDA Legal Centre held on 05 October 2021 at 11:23hrs.

⁷²⁰ No 66 of survey responses.

women which the UN seeks to eradicate as contained in the international conventions on women.⁷²¹

Emotional violence on the other hand is an aspect of domestic violence that is under mentioned as some women who experience physical violence do not understand that they experience emotional violence as well, as was revealed when one of the participants was asked by the researcher if she had experienced IPV and she said no but went on to tell the researcher how her husband was always verbally abusing and putting her down before people.⁷²² This might not be unconnected to it being largely less visible but just as destructive as physical abuse. Though only one participant clearly mentioned emotional violence, the participants who suffered domestic violence had clearly been through the trauma of emotional violence as abuse is also experienced in the mind and can be physical as well, which was captured in the statement of the participant who said she was being physically and emotionally abused by her partner.⁷²³ The analysis of this data collection based on the responses of the participants is that they attached more importance to the physical abuse not realising the emotional abuse is equally a violation to their rights. The responses of the participants reveal that they have all encountered emotional violence as well as physical violence in most of the cases. For the VAPP Act to recognise emotional violence, it means it is an important form of IPV which should be addressed when resolving family disputes through mediation. Emotional abuse from the definition of the VAPP Act is largely an abuse of the victim's psychology and equally as destructive as physical abuse. From the survey and interview responses, emotional violence did not feature as part of IPV/domestic abuse which should have been mentioned during the Mediation Issues Assessment Meeting (MIAM). But from the definition of the VAPP Act on

⁷²¹ CEDAW.

⁷²² Interview with Participant 5, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on 23 May 2022 at 11:23hrs.

⁷²³ No 66 of Survey Responses.

emotional violence, the interpretation would be that more women and men experience emotional violence before it becomes physical. The responses on IPV/domestic abuse would seem to be focused on physical abuse and not the emotional aspect. It was deduced from one of the participants during the interview when asked if there was any issue of IPV/domestic abuse, and she said no. She then proceeded to mention that her husband was always calling her names and abusing her verbally.⁷²⁴

Though no direct question was asked on IPV during the interviews (as that is not the focus of this research), it is mentioned as a theme because it emerged from the survey responses. If the participants from the survey had been the same participants for the interviews, the opportunity to explore this theme by asking direct questions would have been appropriate.

It is pertinent to state at this point that this research began with some theories from practice which needed to be proved or disproved through data collection. One such theory was that family mediation was the best form of dispute resolution for women to access justice. However, the testimonies of the women who had issues with IPV/Domestic abuse have disproved this theory. The evidence of the women from the survey responses and interviews who stated that informal mediation did not stop the occurrence of IPV, disproved that theory. The decision of the participants to address their disputes involving violence through mediation raises questions regarding the impression in which the public appears to hold the law enforcement agents such as the Nigerian Police Force when it concerns issues of IPV or domestic abuse involving women, but it also raises questions around the effectiveness of, particularly informal, mediation if participants cannot fully express themselves.

The willingness of the women to adopt family mediation in addressing domestic violence is a matter that needs studying, irrespective of marital status.

⁷²⁴ Interview with Participant 5, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on 23 May 2022 at 11:23hrs.

The conclusion of this study on this theme is based on the findings of the survey responses and interviews, which is that IPV is major contributor to family disputes where it exists, despite the reluctance to talk about it. The consequence of this is impacted in the legal consciousness of Nigerian women as it affects their access to justice.

6.5. Sub-Themes Affecting Women's Access to Justice

From the data collection, the following sub themes emerged based on the data analysis as highlighted in the introduction of this chapter. The sub-themes which were revealed were found to be interwoven in the narratives of the participants and featured in the above themes. They are consequently discussed below.

6.5.1 The impact of culture on family mediation

From the data analysis of the survey and the interviews, it is evident that culture plays an important role in women's access to justice.

The culture of a people is reflected in their environment and their way of life. This was highlighted in the response from the survey in the words- *“Traditionally, the first step to resolving disputes in families is by way of mediation”*.⁷²⁵

The following interviews depict the sub-theme of culture as identified in the data collection of this research:

Excerpt One

Question: Have you experienced informal mediation in the marital dispute with your husband?

Answer: Yes

Question: Can you tell me about it? And if you were satisfied with the process.

⁷²⁵ No 35 of Survey Responses to the question - Was it your choice to use mediation to resolve your family dispute?

Answer: My husband summoned me to the elders of the village that he was no longer interested in the marriage.

Question: The people who presided over the mediation, were they your husband's relatives or independent chiefs?

Answer: His relatives and some other chiefs.

Question: Did they give you an opportunity to speak?

Answer: No

Question: So, your side of the story was not heard?

Answer: Not really

Question: What happened at the end of the mediation?

Answer: It was divorce

Question: How many times did mediation take place?

Answer: Before he went to the village, a distant relative tried to mediate but he refused to comply

Question: Was it after this process you decided to seek for formal mediation through FIDA?

Answer: Yes.⁷²⁶

The influence of culture interfered in the woman's right to access justice as she was not given the right to fair hearing. She did not tell her side of the story and because it was in the village based on tradition, she could not oppose the proceedings. The power of culture impacts on the legal consciousness of the women and influences the decisions they make.

⁷²⁶ Interview with Participant 2, Lagos State FIDA Legal Centre held on 17 February 2022 at 10:17hrs.

Excerpt Two

“Question: Can you tell me a little of how the dispute was handled at the village setting

Answer: First of all, he said I was wasting his money with my sickness because I was very sick and dying so I went to stay with my elder sister for a while. After a while she died and when I went home and discovered he had moved away from where we were living with my belongings and the children and when I traced him to where he was living, I received summons to the village council. When I got there, I was not allowed to speak or state my own side of the case, I was only told to answer yes or no to anything he says. At the end the man who was presiding said we cannot live together again. I said no problem, I asked about my properties, and they would not give them to me. I came to FIDA for my kids and my properties.”⁷²⁷.

Also in this instance, the impact of culture on the rights of the participant was infringed upon as she was not allowed a fair hearing and further denied the status of rights holder within her community by denying her of her right to be with her children and also denial of her right to her own property.

Excerpt Three

“Question: Have you experienced informal mediation before coming to FIDA, did you report to family members?

*Answer: Yes, but it did not help matters because they said he is an African man and can marry as many wives as he wants and do what he wants in his house”.*⁷²⁸

This clearly addresses the topic sentence of this chapter, which is that a woman’s rights are non-existent when compared with the rights of men in certain culture. The sub-theme of culture

⁷²⁷ Interview with Participant 4, Lagos State FIDA Legal Centre held on 17 February 2022 at 10:01hrs.

⁷²⁸ Interview with Participant 4, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on 05 October 2021 at 11:46hrs.

and the impact on family mediation is revealed from the data analysis and how it affects women's access to justice. It is clear from the words of the participants in this research project that despite Nigerian women having rights in the law, these rights are not reflected in culture and are denied in reality; the participant's comment upon which the title of this chapter was based is correct and women in Nigeria could be said to have no rights if the legal rights given to them cannot be actualised.

6.5.2. The Role of Patriarchy in women's access to justice

In examining the role of patriarchy as it affects the rights of women in Nigeria, the evidence as revealed from the survey and interviews is illustrated and discussed in the following excerpts.

Excerpt One

“Question: Okay, Let's talk about custom. When this issue started, did you complain to your village chiefs or elders of your community?”

Answer: Yes, I went to my kindred and complained.

Question: Did it help?

*Answer: No, it did not help because they said **I have no right as a woman** and my brother is the sole owner of everything”⁷²⁹.*

Patriarchy rules in the affairs of women as depicted in the above statement by the participant and this causes a hardship for women to enforce their rights especially in the resolution of family disputes. The village chiefs being men themselves did not see anything wrong in the participant's brother taking all of their father's property because he is a man. This is not a strange story in Nigeria and in some African countries where a woman is disinherited of her rights to family property because of her gender. The case of *Ukeje v. Ukeje*⁷³⁰ highlights this

⁷²⁹ Interview with Participant 2, Anambra State FIDA Legal Centre held on 13 January 2022 at 13:20hrs.

⁷³⁰ *Lois Chituru Ukeje v. Enyinaya Lazarus Ukeje* (2014) S.C 224.

sub-theme. In the *Ukeje's* case the Supreme Court held that it was unconstitutional, null and void for any customary law to state that a female child cannot inherit her father's property which is beacon of hope for women's rights in Nigeria.

Excerpt Two

“Question: What brought you to FIDA?”

Answer: I came to FIDA because my husband's people accused me of killing my husband and pushed me out of the house even within the one month of mourning after the burial and took away everything from me. They kept my property under the rain, excommunicated me from anything the family was doing. They removed my name from widows' meetings and communal associations that would benefit me. They also locked up the house my husband built and took the keys.

Question: When did your husband die? How long had this been going on for?

*Answer: My husband died in 2009, and they started taking everything from me. They started with the economic trees I planted, to the farmlands and sold my husband's properties. Before somebody directed me to FIDA and I came here”.*⁷³¹

The findings from both excerpts reveal the influence of culture in the role patriarchy plays in women's access to justice in Nigeria. Evidence of Patriarchy was found in their lack of independence of the women to choose their method of dispute resolution, the police treatment of women, even in the Nigerian Constitution which provides that a husband is allowed to “correct” his wife so long as it does not amount to “grievous hurt”.⁷³² Examples like this reveal how the Nigerian laws promote patriarchy at home and in the family life.

⁷³¹ Interview with Participant 3, Anambra State FIDA Legal Centre held on 13 January 2022 at 13:38hrs.

⁷³² Penal Code of Nigeria, Section 55 (1).

6.5.3. Stigma and Social Control as a barrier to women's access to justice

Women have been hindered from exercising their rights for fear of being stigmatised by family members and society and this was further proven in the data collection as shown in the excerpt during the interview of Participant 4⁷³³ where her husband and in-laws chased her out of her matrimonial home because of the stigma of rape being associated with the family name:

Excerpt

“Question: What brought you to FIDA?”

Answer: Someone defiled my daughter that is why I came to FIDA because my husband's family chased me out of the house

Question: Oh, I am sorry to hear that. But why did you come to FIDA and not to the police?

Answer: My husband went and collected N50, 000 as settlement from the man who raped my daughter as payoff and said I should close the matter and I said no, then he beat me up.

Question: Is FIDA assisting you in prosecuting this matter?

Answer: Yes ma

Question: Did you report to any other informal mediation body like village chiefs before coming to FIDA?

Answer: No ma, they said I want to spoil their family name by publicising the matter that's why they wanted me to close the case and as I refused, they join my husband to chase me out”.⁷³⁴

The participant narrated how her husband and in-laws were forcing her to withdraw the case at the police station where she had reported the rape of their daughter. The power dynamics of the stigma of the daughter being raped caused the family to interfere with her access to formal

⁷³³ Illustrating how family can exert pressure on women.

⁷³⁴ Interview with Participant 4, Anambra State FIDA Legal Centre held on 13 January 2022 at 13:55hrs.

justice. The attempt to control her is an infringement on her rights and by culture she ought not to disobey the wishes of her husband, most especially her in-laws. The use of stigmatisation is a form of control which hinders women from enforcing justice when their rights have been violated as such survivors are perceived as troublemakers or women incapable of maintaining family harmony. Wijayati et al⁷³⁵ have described the impact of stigmatisation of women who seek legal redress in the enforcement of their rights as being such that women are denied of their legal rights in family settings and even stigmatised by other women as was experienced by one of the participants who was excommunicated by other widows because she was accused by her in-laws of killing her husband.⁷³⁶ The researcher uncovered more facts from some of the participants and during her practice as an advocate on women's rights that forms of stigmatisation vary. Some women are stigmatised when they go to the market to buy groceries and other women refuse to sell to them because they have been labelled as witches by their in-laws for the death of their husbands or children.⁷³⁷ This form of social control abuses the rights of women and hinders access to justice as she is unable to seek help because she is being excommunicated from society. The fear of stigmatisation hinders some women from seeking justice when their rights have been abused.

6.5.4. The effect of religion in family mediation

This study seeks to examine the sub-theme of religion in family mediation as it affects the rights of women's access to justice. There were some participants who indicated that they had reported the issues they were having to their pastors before proceeding to the FIDA legal Centre. The following are some examples from the interviews:

⁷³⁵ Mufliha Wijayati, Irwan Abdullah, and Sally White and Aden Rosadi and Ade Yamin and Yunair Galuh Larasati, "Justice Brokers: Women's experiences with injustice and dependence in the divorce process" (2021) 7 Cogent Social Sciences, 8.

⁷³⁶ Interview with Participant 3, Anambra State, FIDA Legal Centre held on 13 January 2022 at 13:38hrs.

⁷³⁷ Ibid.

Excerpt One

“Question: What brought you to the FIDA Centre?”

Answer: I had issues with my husband. There was a lot of emotional violence and abuse going on in my marriage.

Question: Did you engage in informal mediation before coming to FIDA?

Answer: Yes, I reported to my family and our Pastor but to no avail. My parents called us, his parents also called us but there was no change. Then I confided in a friend who told me about FIDA, so I came.

Question: Was it easy for you to access the justice you sought at FIDA?

Answer: Yes, as I came, I met a lawyer and explained to the lawyer, my husband was invited, and he came, and the mediation started, and it went smoothly”⁷³⁸.

Excerpt Two

“Question: Have you experienced informal mediation before coming to FIDA?”

Answer: Yes, I went to his parents, our pastor in church, and his friends but he refused to hear from them, so I decided to come to FIDA.

Question: Did he sign a mediation agreement?

Answer: Yes

Question: Was there any challenge in enforcing the mediation agreement?

Answer: No, because FIDA is involved, no challenge. He has been keeping to the agreement and taking care of us”.⁷³⁹

⁷³⁸ Interview with Participant 5, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on 23 May 2022 at 11:23hrs.

⁷³⁹ Interview with Participant 8, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on Rivers State on 23 May 2022 at 11:38hrs.

The analysis of this sub-theme indicates an expectation of religion to influence the resolution of family disputes. The legal consciousness of the parties is revealed in the respect ascribed to their religion or their spiritual head especially from the evidence of the participants who reported their family disputes to their Pastors. From the excerpts narrated above, it is clear the women expected their spiritual leaders to exert some influence in their family disputes and when this failed, they sought formal mediation at the FIDA legal centre.

The status of women in society is as a result of cultural and religious interpretations which have been programmed by the religious institutions and handed down through the passage of time.⁷⁴⁰ It is an invisible uphill task women sometimes do not realise they encounter, and some are stuck in difficult situations because it negates their religious dispositions to disobey spiritual teachings. Those whose legal consciousness have been awakened by empowerment mechanisms by NGOs like FIDA are able to break out of the shackles of societal norms and expectations in the resolution of family disputes. Women are beginning to go outside their comfort zones to access justice, including the women in the rural areas as evidenced by the participant from Ahoada who journeyed to the FIDA legal centre in Port Harcourt.

6.6. Conclusion

In this chapter women's experience of family mediation in Nigeria has been considered through examining survey and interview data. In particular, this chapter considered informal mediation, access to formal mediation, and intimate partner violence. The women have rights which they seek to enforce by accessing justice. From the literature as stated by Onyeozili⁷⁴¹ it is customary for elders to preside over informal family mediations, but the data analysis has shown that informal family mediation does not guarantee satisfaction of justice. For women seeking a fair

⁷⁴⁰ Kamila Klingorova and Tomas Havlicek, 'Religion and Gender Inequality: The Status of Women in the Societies of World Religions' (2015) 23 (2) Moravian Geographical Report 2.

⁷⁴¹ And other cited authorities.

resolution to their dispute involves moving away from informal mediation and seeking formal mediation.

This chapter revealed that, in Nigeria, women's ability to access to justice and legal consciousness is shaped by a complex and intricate web of factors that inform and erode women's rights in Nigeria: culture, patriarchy and stigma and social control. Women who seek formal mediation can be understood to be operating in resistance to this web of factors. From the data analysis, younger women appear to be more courageous or motivated than the older women in seeking access to justice outside informal family mediation. The results of the data analysis are evidence of the impact of family mediation in the lives of Nigerian women.

The issues of the rights of Nigerian women are coloured by the prevalence of the impact of culture, role of patriarchy, stigma/social control and effect of religion which are the sub-themes highlighted in this Chapter and their impact on the themes of informal mediation as a route to justice, access to formal system and intimate partner violence. These sub-themes overlap in some cases as highlighted in the responses of the participants and influence women's access to justice. The results as presented in the findings reveals the legal consciousness of Nigerian women on whether they "have" rights in reality.

In this Chapter the role of FIDA in empowering women by enlightening their legal consciousness is highlighted in the responses of the participants during the interviews. The data analysis revealed the choice to seek formal family mediation outside informal family mediation and illustrates the view that women are enlightened enough to seek justice outside what is available in their comfort zone, even if it attracts stigmatisation.

The evidence supports the position that women are faced with informal mediation due to its availability which is further enhanced by the surrounding factors of culture and economy as culture places expectations on them while economic challenges will limit their choices. Where

they do not find satisfaction in informal mediation family process, they proceed to formal mediation.

For the older women, their legal consciousness is based on the familiar and the fear of the unknown which comes with change. It appears to be a notion of “why rock the boat?” as was revealed in the survey response in the “50 & Above” age category. Some are of the opinion that formal mediation empowers women with control.⁷⁴² The impact of the work of FIDA is revealed by the findings of the data analysis. By enlightening women, FIDA empowers them to influence their legal consciousness which allows the women to choose the form of dispute resolution they want. Women are empowered to decide which form of family mediation will best resolve their dispute.

The participants seeking formal mediation through the FIDA legal centre expressed their trust in the formal system of resolving their dispute better than informal mediation. In embarking on the process to seek the formality in the system to access justice illustrates the fact that Nigerian women are aware of the shortcomings of the informal system of justice. The structure and stability represented in the formal system is what they sought by proceeding to formal mediation after experiencing the informal mediation process.

This Chapter revealed from the findings and the discussion that more women sought formal mediation in the resolution of family disputes where informal mediation did not guarantee the justice they sought. From the evidence of the data analysis and the findings of this study on the above themes, lack of satisfaction at informal mediation is one of the major reasons formal mediations is sought after. It is a further conclusion of this Chapter based on the findings that younger generation of Nigerian women prefer formal family mediation in the resolution of family disputes, than the women of the older generation based on the results of the data

⁷⁴² No 70 of Survey responses –“The process was intimidating to me as I felt my wife had the upper hand”.

analysis. This Chapter further revealed from the data analysis that the reason Nigerian women “have no rights” is because the existing laws have failed to protect the rights of women.

This study will continue with the discussion of the remaining two themes in Chapter Seven.

CHAPTER SEVEN

‘SHE HAS NO RIGHTS’: THE LACK OF ENFORCEMENT OF MEDIATION AGREEMENTS IN NIGERIA AND THE NEED FOR STATE INTERVENTION

7.1. Introduction

The purpose of this Chapter is to examine the themes of “Enforcement of Mediation Agreement” and “Government Intervention Policy” as well as the sub-themes which were explored in Chapter Six consisting of: the impact of culture on family mediation, the role of patriarchy in women’s access to justice, stigma/ social control as a barrier to women’s access to justice, and the effect of religion on family mediation.

An examination on the enforcement of mediation agreements generally is necessary to provide a foundation for the discussion on enforcement of agreements from family mediation even though the literature is mainly commercial in nature. This will assist our understanding of how the themes and sub-themes affect women’s access to justice in Nigeria because, as alluded to in some of the participants’ comments in the previous Chapter, many of the women were critical of informal mediation particularly due to its lack of enforceability; indeed, some participants were critical of the enforceability of even formal mediation. If the mediation agreement cannot be enforced, or is not being enforced, it is a barrier to women using this mechanism to enforce their rights despite possessing legal consciousness and being aware of their rights and seeking to actualise those rights within the legal system.

This Chapter will highlight the existing the legislation which regulate enforcement of mediation agreements and how they impact on women’s access to justice. In Nigeria, (as at the time of writing this thesis) the law which regulates the alternative dispute resolution process is the **Arbitration and Conciliation Act 2004** which provides in **Section 31(1)** that “*an arbitral*

*award shall be recognised as binding, and subject to this section and section 32 of this Act, shall, upon application in writing to the Court, be enforced by the Court”.*⁷⁴³ The implication of this law means for an agreement to be enforced it must follow the formal process of the courts which consist of civil procedure processes. This would also apply to mediation agreements which need to be enforced. This chapter will consequently examine the existing legislation on enforcement of mediation agreement in Nigeria and at the international level to explore what impact the legislation has on family mediation. These themes have been grouped together in this Chapter for ease of structure and discussion as enforcement procedures usually require legal authority which relates to the theme on government intervention policy.

7.2 Enforcement of Mediation Agreement

The theme enforcement of mediation agreement in family disputes is examined in the light of the responses from the survey and interviews as well as the challenges which affect women’s access to justice in Nigeria. Some of the respondents in the survey stated they experienced challenges in the enforcement of the mediation agreement where the other party refused to comply with the agreement. This theme was developed to investigate this position during the interviews. In analysing this theme during the interviews, the kind of mediation, whether informal or formal, was considered as this could impact on the enforcement of the mediation agreement.

The responses of the participants revealed that the sub-themes namely: impact of culture in family mediation, role of patriarchy in women’s access to justice, stigma/social control as a barrier to women’s access to justice, effect of religion on family mediation, can also be barriers to the enforcement of family mediation agreement especially in informal family mediation. In a situation where the mediators in a family dispute are the elders in the family and if they are

⁷⁴³ Arbitration and Conciliation Act 2004 of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Section 31(1) <https://placng.org/lawsofnigeria/> (Accessed 14 July 2022).

in-laws, already culture is at play here as the woman will be unable to object to the proceedings and is bound to abide by their decision which actually negates the fundamentals of mediation. An illustration was in the evidence of the party who was not allowed to say anything in her defence during the mediation proceedings presided over by her in-laws and some chiefs in the village.⁷⁴⁴

7.2.3 Survey Responses

The respondents were asked the question **“How do you feel about the mediation process?”** The question was not directly on enforcement of mediation agreements, but the responses revealed the crux of the issue whether informal or formal mediation. As it was not a face-to-face data collection process, the aim was to allow the respondents a little room to explain their views on mediation and provide more data for the research. Some of the responses received include:

“A brilliant alternative to litigation”.⁷⁴⁵

“The mediation process was okay; the only thing is the lack of enforcement as everything is still to be determined by the courts”.⁷⁴⁶

“I feel so disappointed and pained. I feel like I wasted my time and resources going for the mediation. I feel like it is not worth it”.⁷⁴⁷

“The process in itself tries to help but once there is no enforcement mechanism, I don't really see the point”.⁷⁴⁸

⁷⁴⁴ Interview with Participant 2, Lagos State FIDA Legal Centre held on 17/02/2022 at 10:17am.

⁷⁴⁵ No 25 of survey responses.

⁷⁴⁶ No 214 from survey responses.

⁷⁴⁷ No 37 of survey responses.

⁷⁴⁸ No 107 of survey responses.

*“The mediation process tried it's best but has no enforcement behind it and that would still be for the courts to do that”.*⁷⁴⁹

The statistics for the above responses was not evaluated like the previously discussed themes, which was as a result of the different opinions, but the majority of the responses reveal a lack of faith in the enforcement of mediation agreements.

7.2.4 Interview Responses

In examining the theme of enforcement of mediation agreement during the interviews, the participants were asked the following question: **“Was there any challenge in enforcing the mediation agreement?”**

Some of the responses of the participants were as follows:

*“No, because FIDA was involved, they just gave us back our properties and kept to the agreement we signed in the FIDA Centre”.*⁷⁵⁰

This was a family dispute where the participant stated her late father’s properties had been seized by her uncles and the dispute had lasted for 8years with no progress until the mediation at the FIDA legal centre. The sub-themes of the impact of culture and patriarchy is revealed in the response of this participant as this affected their rights by denying access to their properties for 8years until they proceeded to FIDA. The theme of “Accessing the formal system” also features in this case as FIDA represents formal mediation which allowed them to achieve the justice they sought through the formal system.

Another participant stated in her response:

⁷⁴⁹ No 130 of survey responses.

⁷⁵⁰ Interview with Participant 9, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre, held on 23/05/2022 at 11:38hrs.

*“No, because FIDA is involved, no challenge. He has been keeping to the agreement and taking care of us”.*⁷⁵¹

The response by this participant suggests that the reason he has kept to the agreement is due to the involvement of FIDA. This emphasises the theme “Accessing the formal system” of which FIDA represents formal mediation.

Another participant had testified during the interview that in the previous informal mediation which had been presided over by her in-laws, her husband had been cautioned to desist from physically abusing her. He consented to stop physically abusing the participant and the mediation was concluded but when the parties got home, the husband beat the wife up for ridiculing him before family members. Hence, she felt the need to seek formal mediation where enforcement of the mediation agreement would be guaranteed as was evidenced by her response during the interview:

*“No, because it is FIDA. My husband has been complying with the agreement and has not raised his hand on me since”.*⁷⁵²

The evidence of this participant revealed the fact that informal mediation had taken place in the past as well as the presence of IPV. The fact that the informal mediation had been presided over by her in-laws did not deter her husband from physically abusing her when they got home. It highlights the issues mentioned from the results of the statistics on IPV in Chapter Five especially where one of the respondents had said she did not mention the presence of IPV for fear of what will happen after mediation. This also reveals the lack of compliance with mediation agreement from informal mediation due to no structure for enforcement.

Other responses include:

⁷⁵¹ Interview with Participant 8, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre, held on 23/05/2022 at 11:38hrs.

⁷⁵² Interview with Participant 6, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on 22/10/2021 at 13:23hrs.

*“No, they came, and they obeyed everything we agreed to in the agreement we signed and returned my late husband's property to me because they are afraid of FIDA”.*⁷⁵³

And,

*“No, it is because it is FIDA, he has been keeping to the agreement, no more beating or asking me to leave his house”.*⁷⁵⁴

There was a dissenting view on compliance with the mediation agreement from one of the participants whose response was in the negative. In the data collection, through the testimonies of the participants, there were no challenges of non-compliance with mediation agreements entered into at the FIDA legal centre, except for this participant who stated that her husband was yet to comply with the mediation agreement as at the day the interview was taking place.

*“No, he has not complied with the mediation agreement”.*⁷⁵⁵

The response of this participant is an indication that the mediation process at the FIDA legal centre is not an absolute guarantee. There was no explanation from the participant as to why the agreement was not complied with.

7.2.5. Discussion

An outstanding observation from the responses of the participants indicates that most of the themes and sub-themes are interwoven in the individual stories. It is the understanding of this study that the sub-themes can also act as barriers by promoting lack of compliance with family mediation agreements. From the data analysis informal mediation is more accessible and convenient than formal mediation which consequently makes it prevalent and where there is

⁷⁵³ Interview with Participant 3, Anambra State FIDA Legal Centre held on 13/01/2022 at 13:38hrs.

⁷⁵⁴ Interview with Participant 10, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on 23/05/2022 at 12:37hrs.

⁷⁵⁵ Interview with Participant 2, Lagos State FIDA Legal Centre held on 17/02/2022 at 10:17am.

power imbalance from the impact of culture, enforcement of the mediation agreement will be a challenge.

This study examines the philosophy of enforcement of family mediation by examining the reasons for lack of compliance with the mediation agreement through the responses of the participants. Some of the responses suggested the fear of penalty was the motivation for compliance with the agreement reached at the FIDA legal centre. One of the participants had testified that her husband had ignored the decision from the informal family mediation but had readily complied with the agreement reached at the FIDA legal centre and agreed to begin to provide for herself and their three children.⁷⁵⁶ In exploring further the reason for the need for enforcement of family mediation agreement when by understanding of the principles of mediation, this should not be a challenge based on the voluntary principle of the parties, the impact of the sub-themes on women's rights cannot be overlooked

The consequence of mediation agreement in informal mediation is the feature which accompanies the entire process. Flexibility of the process and the unwritten nature of the proceedings are part of the characteristics of the mediation process which attracts the parties. In a normal mediation setting, the mediator should possess the qualities of a mediator such as impartiality and neutrality as mentioned in Chapter Five of this study. In an informal mediation especially in the family setting where community members or in-laws are the mediators, it is rare to have a neutral and unbiased mediator as evidenced by the testimonies of the participants during the interviews as was presented in the previous chapter.

The decision at the resolution of the mediation proceedings might not be satisfactory to one of the parties who might feel that the mediator could have been biased in one way or the other.

⁷⁵⁶ Interview with Participant 8, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre, held on 23/05/2022 at 11:38hrs.

Consequently, the reluctance to comply with the agreement reached at the conclusion of the proceedings would arise as evidenced in the testimonies of some of the participants.⁷⁵⁷

The mediation process is a voluntary one, but in family dispute resolution especially in informal mediation in Nigeria, (from the evidence of the participants) when the women are “invited” they must attend the proceedings. The familiarity of the parties knowing the mediators and being in familiar surroundings also has an impact on the agreement in informal mediation. The role of the mediator is to guide the parties to arrive at a resolution that is the best solution to the dispute with the aim of preserving the relationship between the parties. Informal mediation might be the easiest in terms of accessibility in family disputes but being the best in all disputes might not be practical. An example would be in areas of domestic violence as was revealed in the testimonies of the participants who suffered domestic violence. Several informal family mediations did not stop the acts of violence until formal reports were made to the FIDA legal centre.

The participants stated they had no challenges with enforcing the mediation agreement they had entered into previously at the FIDA legal centre except Participant 2 of the Lagos FIDA Centre who stated that her husband had not complied with the mediation agreement as at the time the interview was being conducted.⁷⁵⁸ At the conclusion of the interviews, the researcher understood the common factor with the participants on the enforcement of mediation agreement resides in the fact that the participants believe in the structure of the formality which accompanies the formal mediation proceedings conducted at the FIDA legal centre.

From the experience of the women as narrated during the interviews, the reason they proceeded to the FIDA legal centre after experiencing informal mediation was the belief in the

⁷⁵⁷ Interview with Participant 8, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre, held on 23/05/2022 at 11:38hrs.

⁷⁵⁸ As stated during the interview.

involvement of the power of the government to enforce the outcome of the mediation agreement which they had not achieved with informal family mediation. The structure embedded in formal mediation provides the legality and stability of the process and knowing the satisfaction they would derive in this method of accessing justice, would not be lost.

It is necessary to understand why women go the extra mile to access justice after going through informal mediation. As a legal practitioner, the researcher had witnessed how women would abandon pursuing fighting for their rights or for the welfare of their children because they either could not afford the litigation process financially or they had simply lost the heart to keep fighting. The men would prefer the litigation battle, knowing she would probably not be able to pursue her satisfaction after judgement is passed assuming it is passed in her favour.

The interviews revealed some depths as to the reasons why the enforcement of mediation agreements is necessary. The analysis of the interview responses indicates that the women who took part in the interviews had been through some form of informal mediation in the past but had sought a more formal form of mediation hence their presence at the FIDA⁷⁵⁹ legal centre.

Some of the women explained that their reason for coming to FIDA was because the mediations they had engaged in previously had yielded no satisfaction as their husbands/partners failed to abide by the agreements of the mediation.⁷⁶⁰ Part of the purpose of the interview was to confirm whether this was the reality by asking the participants questions on their previous experience of informal mediation and to compile the documentary evidence by conducting this research. During the interviews, it was revealed that where the women had been involved in informal mediation in the past, and the decision reached was not executed, there was no provision for enforcement.

⁷⁵⁹ Federación Internacional de Abogadas (International Federation of Women Lawyers).

⁷⁶⁰ Testimony of the interviewed participants.

A total of seventeen participants took part in the interview and one participant stated her spouse was yet to comply with the mediation agreement, while the other sixteen stated the mediation agreement had been complied with. The participants who had challenges enforcing mediation agreements stated that the lack of enforcement of the informal mediation agreement was the major reason for proceeding to the FIDA legal centre to seek formal mediation. The seventeen women who were interviewed stated that they entered into mediation agreements at the conclusion of the mediation process. They also pointed out the lack of challenges in enforcing the agreement entered at the FIDA legal centre. A common fact in the responses suggest the reason there was no need for enforcement of the mediation agreement was because it was entered into at the FIDA legal centre.⁷⁶¹

According to the testimonies of the participants, in the informal mediations, there were several challenges which they felt influenced the enforcement of the mediation agreement. Some of the challenges include the lack of neutrality of the mediators, who were either in-laws or relations of the parties and would not pronounce sanctions for non-compliance with the decision of the mediation. The husbands or partners were not perturbed regarding failure to comply with the decision of the mediation process because these were people they knew, and they would not be compelled to comply with the agreement. Based on the analysis of the interviews, the major challenge in the enforcement of mediation agreements from informal mediation, stems from the knowledge that there is no sanction for non-compliance with the mediation agreement. The impact of this is a lack of faith in family mediation as a process of accessing justice for the concerned women.

From listening to the women as they answered the questions put to them during the interviews, it was clear women preferred mediation to litigation processes, because it allowed them the

⁷⁶¹ Interviews with participants.

opportunity to express their feelings and opinions on the issues which are the causes of the dispute while being able to enjoy the benefits of justice. This study so far has revealed from the literature and interviews conducted that during mediation, the women were willing to speak and would disclose the reasons why the previous informal mediations failed in the hope of preventing a reoccurrence. The findings of the data analysis revealed that mediation allows the women express the roots of the disputes and where children are involved, it is more of a challenge for women to access justice as seen in the testimonies of the participants as was illustrated in the evidence of the woman who was not allowed access to her children after the informal mediation.⁷⁶² In Nigeria, the social welfare department, which is a parastatal set up by the government, addresses issues of children's welfare in the different states of the federation. The *Child's Rights Act 2003*⁷⁶³ is the major law in Nigeria which protects the rights of the child, and the welfare agencies would seek to prosecute offenders under the provisions of this Act. The Ministry of Social Welfare and Rehabilitation does not proceed against an offending party to a mediation agreement for enforcement because of non-compliance. It is the aggrieved party who decides whether to institute legal proceedings for enforcement of the mediation agreement. The welfare of children was highlighted as it has been observed from literature and the data collected that women remain in challenging situations most times for the welfare of their children.

The interviews conducted during this study answered the questions as to why women take the pains to travel, sometimes far distances to access justice at the FIDA legal centre after going through the Ministry of Social Welfare and Rehabilitation. From the responses of the participants, it is apparent the reason women come to FIDA is to be able to enforce the mediation agreement. The lawyers at the centre are well versed with the provisions of the law

⁷⁶² Interview with Participant 3, Anambra State FIDA Legal Centre held on 13 January 2022 at 13:38hrs.

⁷⁶³ www.lawsofnigeria.placng.org (Accessed 22 August 2022).

and are able to advise the parties accordingly and knowing the mediators are lawyers helps to keep the conducts of the parties in check as well, as some women would courageously disclose information at the FIDA legal centre that they would not disclose elsewhere.

By the characteristics of the mediation process, all parties to the mediation are expected to comply with the mediation agreement as it should be reached freely through agreement between the parties. However, from the literature and data collection, the indication is that compliance with mediation agreement in certain family disputes is attributed to fear of penalty for non-compliance but also it has become clear from the participants that lack of compliance and enforcement was an issue as some parties (usually the males) felt empowered not to comply due to the lack of enforcement mechanisms. In certain family disputes where there is involvement of IPV and domestic abuse, it can be assessed from two differing perspectives: firstly, as an offence with criminal consequences where the matter should be reported to the police and not resolved through mediation due to the imbalance of power between the parties, the lack of truly free consensual participation of the victim of IPV, and because of the potential for further trauma for the victim. However, secondly where IPV exists in the family relationship, mediation can offer an amiable ground for resolving the cause of the IPV which could lead to better relationship between the parties but there needs to be careful handling of these particular mediations by trained mediators or by completely neutral family or community members should the mediation be informal in nature. The analysis of the responses as part of the data collection for this research has shown that such an approach should not be taken. It is clear from the responses of the research participants expressed as part of the interview process that informal mediation was not sufficient to stop IPV and domestic abuse.⁷⁶⁴ It was rather the procedure of formal mediation and fear of penalty which put an end to the IPV, leading to the conclusion that the only way to address this behaviour is through threat of punishment rather

⁷⁶⁴ Interview with Participant 6, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on 22/10/2021 at 13:23hrs.

than through negotiation. However, the argument that IPV, in whatever form it takes, can be resolved by means of mediation is powerful as it relates to one of the core aspects of mediation; the desire to preserve the familial relationship which is often of utmost importance in spousal disputes where there are children of the union. From the stories of the women who took part in the interviews, it was apparent the reason women did not report to the police was the lack of trust that the police would take proper action to resolve the dispute as evidenced by the statement of the Participant who said to the researcher you know how the police are⁷⁶⁵ and to preserve the sanctity of the family. This reluctance could be because of a desire to maintain the familial relationship for the sake of any children but it could also be because of the sub-themes of patriarchy, religion, culture and stigma which were discussed in detail in Chapter Five; women fear the consequences of reporting IPV whether as part of mediation or otherwise and thus it seems that unless there is some form of government intervention, perhaps in the form of legislative reform, then IPV will continue and women and their children will be forced to remain in unhealthy family relationships.

Where mediation agreement is reached, the findings from the survey responses and interviews revealed some of the limitations to enforcement of mediation agreements regardless of whether the mediation was formal i.e. through an organisation such as FIDA or informal i.e. conducted within the community/family. Though formal mediations resulted in more compliance with the agreement; perhaps as a result of the consequences of non-compliance. There are limitations to enforcement of mediation agreements excluding the reluctance of parties to comply with the mediation agreement after the process. Some of the limitations are a consequence of the litigation process and the administrative bottlenecks which accompany execution of judgements in the Nigerian legal system. Part of the concern which affects enforceability of

⁷⁶⁵ Interview with Participant 2, Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on 05/10/2021 at 11:23hrs.

mediation agreement is if it is made a subject of litigation this would consist of adducing evidence and this could lead to apprehension in revealing information during the mediation process.

Carbone in his writings on mediation is of the opinion that participants will be reluctant to disclose information that could be used against them in further litigation.⁷⁶⁶ This position was emphasised by Rifleman in supporting the theory that mandatory mediation as directed by the courts deprives the participants of the confidentiality benefits of mediation.⁷⁶⁷ The fear of sensitive information disclosed in the public domain is a contributory factor to the lack of enforceability of mediation agreements through the litigation process. As mentioned earlier, some of the women are reluctant to pass through the hurdles of the enforcement processes due to the challenges they encounter from physical follow-ups of the officials to “greasing of palms” of the personnel if they want to enjoy the satisfaction of their judgment. There is no easy answer to the lack of compliance with family mediation agreements, whether formal or informally constituted, but it is clear that some thought must be given to ensuring that such agreements can be meaningful and relied upon by particularly vulnerable parties. What has become clear in this research is that despite there being a willingness of women to engage in mediation, either formal or informal, to resolve family dispute issues of IPV, failure to adhere to the agreement and lack of protection to these often-vulnerable women and their children remain and therefore it is important that this social issue receives Government attention and intervention.

7.3 Government Intervention Policy

In examining the relevance of this theme to women’s access to justice through family mediation, the following responses from the data collection were thoroughly considered.

⁷⁶⁶ Michael Carbone, “Enforcing Agreements Made in Mediation” [2001] <http://mediate.com/articles/carbone5.cfm> (Accessed 18 February 2023).

⁷⁶⁷ Jeff Rifleman, “Mandatory Mediation: Implications and Challenges” [2005] <https://mediate.com/mandatory-mediation-implications-and-challenges/> (Accessed 18 February 2023).

7.3.1 Survey

As discussed in the methodology chapter, the first stage of data collection was the survey during the analysis of the response to which the need to examine the theme of government intervention policy on family mediation emerged from the responses of the participants. In the survey, the following question was asked: **“Do you think the Government should engage in more policies that would promote family mediation and ensure the protection of the rights of women?”** the answer to which was a resounding ‘yes’ confirming the researcher’s prior thoughts that such intervention was required. Of the 226 participants who responded in the survey, 194 (85.8%) answered yes to the question, 11(4.8%) responded in the negative, while 15 (6.6%) responded with a maybe. By these statistics, the number of people who think the government should be more proactive with policies that protect the rights of women in family mediation is the highest category: therefore, further investigation was required to explore these answers in more depth to determine why it was necessary and which form the participants thought that the intervention should take.

Therefore, in compiling the questions for the interviews, it became necessary to include a question on government intervention based on the responses from the survey on the need for government to do more. In practice, and from the outcome of the results of the survey, there is always a recourse to government parastatals by the people, in seeking the justice they want. The responses suggested calls for government involvement in dispute resolution processes. The responses were directed at the involvement of the government in conferring legitimacy and legality to the mediation process.

7.3.2 Interview

Consequently, to procure the necessary evidence to evaluate this theme, the participants were asked the following question during the interview:

“Do you think the government should do more to promote family mediation in protecting women’s rights in Nigeria?”

Some of the responses received from the participants include the following:

*“Yes, the government can do more by giving more power to other family welfare agencies to help enforce policies to promote family mediation”.*⁷⁶⁸

Another participant responded in the affirmative and stated her opinion with emphasis on the challenges women experience in their marriages:

*“Yes, I think the government can do more to create the awareness because a lot of women are going through trauma in their marriages”.*⁷⁶⁹

Another participant was of the view that government participation is not restricted to policy making but includes distribution of authoritative powers:

“Yes, I think the government should do more to create awareness especially on the powers of NGO’s like FIDA”. This participant went further to explain the effect of government involvement in family mediation in her response:

*“Yes, I think the government can do more to sensitize people because it helps families and government should be involved because it helps to check the men. Like my husband, when he was invited, when he heard FIDA, there was this fear in him that made him obey unlike when I reported him to the family”.*⁷⁷⁰

In the response of this participant there is a subtle reference to the how informal family mediation was not effective in ensuring the justice she sought.

⁷⁶⁸ Interview with Participant 8 held at Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre on 23/05/2022 at 11:38hrs.

⁷⁶⁹ Interview with Participant 3 held at Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre on 05/10/2021 at 11:34hrs.

⁷⁷⁰ Interview with Participant 5 held at Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre on 23/05/2022 at 11:23hrs.

A different participant expressed her opinion of this question by emphasising on the cultural aspect where the government can play a more effective role:

*“Yes, I think the Nigerian government should do more, especially culturally to help promote family mediation”.*⁷⁷¹

The sub-theme of the impact of culture on family mediation is highlighted in the response of this participant with the hope for government regulation to make a difference.

There was an interesting response from one of the participants whose evidence was direct and captured the reality of this theme. She said:

*“I can’t talk about Nigerian government, the one that helped me is FIDA”.*⁷⁷² From the response of this participant, her lack of faith in the government indicates her legal consciousness of how she perceives the Nigerian government on the issues of women’s rights.

Other excerpts from the interviews illustrate more clearly how the participants view the role they expect the Nigerian government to play in the access of justice for women.

(A)

“Question: Do you think Nigerian government should do more to promote family mediation in protecting women’s rights in Nigeria?”

*Answer: Yes, especially in custom and tradition”.*⁷⁷³

The emphasis by this participant points to the sub-theme of the impact of culture on family mediation.

(B)

⁷⁷¹ Interview with Participant 4 held at Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre on 05/10/2021 at 11:46hrs.

⁷⁷² Interview with Participant 2 held at Anambra State FIDA Legal Centre on 13/01/2022 at 13:20hrs.

⁷⁷³ Interview with Participant 3 held at FIDA Legal Centre, Anambra State on 13/01/2022 at 13:38hrs.

“Question: Do you think the Nigerian government is doing all it can to support women?”

Answer: Yes, they are trying their best.

Question: Do you think more can be done especially at the traditional level?

*Answer: Yes, especially to the stubborn men out there. I think more should be done as tradition is being partial”.*⁷⁷⁴

(C)

To the same question another participant responded:

*“Answer: I don’t think the Nigerian government is doing enough especially in the traditional area and the way matters are handled. I think more should be done to help women”.*⁷⁷⁵

(D)

“Question: Do you think the Nigerian government can do more to promote family mediation?”

*Answer: Yes, I think the government can do more to create the awareness because a lot of women are going through trauma in their marriages”.*⁷⁷⁶

All the seventeen participants who were interviewed, were of the opinion that government intervention was necessary in family mediation. Four out of the participants clearly expressed their opinion for more of government’s intervention in cultural and traditional method of family mediation. During the interview, when asked about whether there was a need for government’s intervention, one of the participants responded in the affirmative of such a need in custom and tradition.⁷⁷⁷ In her opinion, the government should be involved in the way disputes are resolved

⁷⁷⁴ Interview with Participant 2 Lagos State FIDA Legal Centre held on 17/02/2022 at 10:17am.

⁷⁷⁵ Interview with Participant 4 Lagos State FIDA Legal Centre held on 17/02/2022 at 10:01hrs.

⁷⁷⁶ Interview with Participant 3 Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on 05/10/2021 at 11:34hrs.

⁷⁷⁷ Interview with Participant 3 Anambra State FIDA Legal Centre held on 13/01/2022 at 13:38hrs.

especially in the influence of culture and tradition. The responses of the participants further illustrate the role of patriarchy as a barrier to women's access to justice.⁷⁷⁸ The consensus from the responses of the participants is that there is need for government intervention in ensuring the process of family mediation as a dispute resolution mechanism, delivers justice in the protection of the rights of women in Nigeria.

7.4. Conclusion

From the analysis of the responses, it is the finding of this chapter that the participants proceeded to FIDA after experiencing informal family mediation due to the lack of enforcement of the mediation agreement or lack of satisfaction of the decision reached at informal mediation. One of the participants had responded that she felt mediation was a waste of time as there was no provision for enforcement of the agreement where there was no compliance by the other party.⁷⁷⁹ The decision to proceed to formal mediation resides in the power and authority to ensure compliance which FIDA wields. It suggests that the decision of the informal mediation engaged in previously by some of the participants did not succeed due to the lack of power to ensure compliance by the mediating body. Which goes to suggest that a mediation decision given at the conclusion of mediation proceedings, is only as effective as the mediation authority. The findings from the data analysis also revealed the imbalance of power between men and women through the sub-themes of culture, patriarchy, stigma /social control, and religion and how they affect women's access to justice via informal family mediation. FIDA, thus provides a level ground for the power imbalance which occurs at informal family mediation by ensuring the principles of mediation are followed in formal mediation and the rights of women are protected.

⁷⁷⁸ Interview with Participant 4, Lagos State FIDA Legal Centre held on 17 February 2022 at 10:01hrs.

⁷⁷⁹ Respondent 122, Female, age 50 and above, religion- Islam.

The position of the Nigerian legislation on family mediation is summarised in this statement- “...However, amongst the Non-Adjudication Schemes it is only the decision of arbitration that is final and binding, thus decision reached in other schemes still ends up in court due to lack of final and binding decision”.⁷⁸⁰The above quote by Obidimma and Okpalagwu, and the analysis of the data from the survey responses and interviews indicate the lack of enforcement of the agreement reached is the challenge with mediation in family disputes. It appeared to be that the features which accompany formal mediation was what compelled compliance from the men who had been invited to the FIDA legal centre such as the fear of penalty knowing that FIDA comprised of women lawyers. In summary, the findings of this study reveal that enforcement of mediation agreement is guaranteed in formal mediation which is regulated by the structure of the courts. This consequently leads us to the intervention of the government.

The responses of the participants on the question of government intervention revealed how much all the participants are in agreement on the need for the Nigerian government to generate policies and create the enabling environment to allow family mediation to thrive. The analysis of this study on government intervention as a theme in this interview process is that there is a need for the government to take more active participation in family mediation especially at the grassroot level known as local government areas. These are the government authorities which can impact on culture and tradition from the roots.

The summary of this theme reveals the need for the involvement of government intervention which is necessary for the promotion and growth of family mediation in Nigeria. All the participants were of the consensus that the government should be involved in promoting the resolution of family disputes, both at informal and formal sectors. The intervention of the government will even out the imbalance of power which is at work during family mediation

⁷⁸⁰ Angela Obidimma and Vivian Okpalangwu, “Arbitrating Family Disputes in Nigeria: Benefits and Challenges” (2021) 3(2) International Journal of Comparative Law and Legal Philosophy 68.

proceedings especially at the informal level. The recommendations of this study will hopefully enhance the quality of family mediation as it affects women's access to justice.

It is necessary to mention the challenges to government intervention in informal mediation as the control in this area is limited. Informal family mediation is within the private jurisdiction and would require the parties to lodge a formal request to a government parastatal even if it is at the customary court level to allow government interference. It would be different if it was a criminal matter as it will not be private by the provisions of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria.

The conclusion of this study is aimed at affecting women's access to justice in Nigeria through family mediation and the effect on society which will lead to the recommendations of this study to enhance enforcement of family mediation agreement and government intervention policies.

CHAPTER EIGHT

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

8.1 Summary of Thesis

This thesis sought to contribute to knowledge by answering the research question “**How does family mediation affect the rights of women’s access to justice in Nigeria?**” In answering this question, the study identified the roots of family mediation by categorising them into informal and formal. In the course of the research, the literature examined the theory of legal consciousness and the following themes which emerged in the data collection and were highlighted during the responses from the survey and interviews. The themes of “informal mediation as a process to justice”, “accessing the formal system”, “intimate partner violence”, “enforcement of mediation agreement” and “government intervention policy” were discussed.

In examining the above themes, the following sub-themes were revealed from the responses of the participants during the data collection- *the impact of culture on family mediation, the role of patriarchy in women’s access to justice, stigma, and social control as a barrier to women’s access to justice and the effect of religion in family mediation*. Examination of the literature in this study revealed the views of prominent authors like Maclean and Eekelaar⁷⁸¹, and Hitchings and Miles⁷⁸², which in summary expresses the view that in family law not a one-size-fits-all formula is applied to all family disputes. The procedure for resolving a family dispute will vary based on cultural and religious values, which will influence women’s access to justice. It is the summary of this thesis that international conventions act as precedents on the rights of women, to State parties who replicate these laws in their constitution while implementing these

⁷⁸¹ Mavis Maclean and John Eekelaar, *Lawyers and Mediators: The Brave New World of Services for Separating Families* (Hart Publishing, 2016) 162.

⁷⁸² Emma Hitchings and Joanna Miles, ‘Mediation, Financial Remedies, Information Provision and Legal Advice: the Post-LASPO Conundrum’ (2016) 38(2) *Journal of Social Welfare and Family Law* 175.

laws remains the challenge. With these views as a foundation, this thesis began the research as illustrated in the following Chapters.

Chapter One began this research with an overview of this study outlining the aim, objectives, research question as well as the significance of this study. It also provided a brief layout of the structure of this thesis.

Chapter Two explained the methodology of this research. The methodology of this research employed the legal, social, and feminist research methods in achieving the aim of this study. The legal methodology highlighted the sociolegal form of research methodology in examining how the existing laws regulate family mediation in Nigeria. In adopting the social research methods, the Honeycomb model of Jonathan Wilson was chosen based on its structure which suited the purpose of this study. As the research philosophy of this study was the pragmatic approach, it was only logical that an inductive study be conducted based on qualitative research methods which was the most suitable for this study. The data collection through the survey and interview process led to the data analysis which revealed the reality of family mediation in Nigeria based on the themes and sub-themes.

Chapter Three illustrated the concept of justice and understanding different legal theories and the role of legal consciousness of people and women universally and in Nigeria particularly, as it affects access to justice. This study has examined the barriers which hinder women's access to justice and the impact on the legal consciousness of these women. In this Chapter, a brief layout of the hierarchy of the courts illustrated the Nigerian judicial system. This chapter reveals the structure of the court as a support system for formal family mediation. This is to reveal the route women who wish to resolve family disputes through the formal system will have to follow. It submitted that the legal consciousness of women is instrumental in the manner in which they access justice.

Chapter Four set out to discuss the legal framework for women's rights with focus on Nigerian women's access to justice. This Chapter discussed the role of international laws and conventions on the rights of Nigerian women. The discussion of the various international conventions on human rights and women's rights in this chapter, emphasised the importance of women's rights universally. It discussed the relevance of international laws to local laws and the impact on women's access to justice. The Chapter also discussed the rights of women in Nigeria as well as the existing laws. It concluded with a discussion on the roles of Non-Governmental Organisations like FIDA, and the programmes they execute in assisting women enforce their rights.

Chapter Five submitted on the position of family mediation as an access to justice for women in Nigeria. The Chapter began by describing the different types of dispute resolution processes, and examined the factors involved in the decision of women to choose family mediation as the process to resolve family disputes. The existing laws regulating mediation as discussed in the Chapter, illustrated the reality of the adequacy or otherwise of these laws in the resolution of family disputes. The study also examined the literature of informal and formal mediation which was tested during the data collection of this research. The methodology of this study was explained in the methodology chapter.

In the data analysis, the following five themes and four sub-themes were discussed in Chapters Six and Seven: *informal mediation as a process to justice, accessing the formal system, intimate partner violence, enforcement of mediation agreement and government intervention policy*. The themes were linked with the sub-themes and explained from the analysis of the survey responses and interviews namely: *impact of culture on family mediation, the role of patriarchy in women's access to justice, stigma/social control as a barrier to women's access to justice, and effect of religion on family mediation*. The use of NVivo in coding the phrases

from the responses of the participants assisted in analysing the responses and resulted in conclusive discussions on the themes.

Chapter Six began the findings and discussion section of this study with the themes on “informal mediation as a process to justice”, “accessing the formal system” and “intimate partner violence”. The theme of “informal mediation as a process to justice” examined the experiences of the participants in informal family mediation which led to the need to access justice through formal mediation via the FIDA legal system and not court annexed mediation. In discussing the theme “accessing the formal system” this thesis examined the challenges the women encountered in seeking formal mediation by proceeding to the FIDA legal centre after experiencing informal family mediation. The chapter discussed the accessibility of the proceedings and if the participants were satisfied with the process. On the theme “intimate partner violence”, this chapter analysed the responses of the participants from the survey responses and interviews especially on emotional abuse which is not visible. This theme also considered other forms of intimate partner violence including the definition as stipulated by the **VAPP Act** of 2015. The sub-themes were discussed as they featured in the responses of the participants.

Chapter Seven concluded the findings and discussions of this study with the themes on “enforcement of mediation agreement” and “government intervention policy”. The theme “enforcement of mediation agreement” was discussed in this chapter in consideration with the philosophy of enforcement of mediation agreement globally. The responses of the participants provided the evidence of the status of enforcement of family mediation agreement. The last theme of this thesis on “government intervention policy” emerged as a necessity from the data analysis of the survey responses and the interviews. It is the finding of this study on this theme, that there is a need for government intervention in policy making which affect the rights of women’s access to justice in Nigeria.

The last chapter of this thesis is Chapter Eight which summarises this study including the limitations of this research. In this concluding chapter, the recommendations are made based on the findings of the data analysis of this study.

8.2. Findings of this Research

The methodology adopted in conducting this study resulted in the following findings which are the conclusions of this research:

- (a) That the prevalence of younger women for informal mediation is a consequence of the accessibility of informal mediation as a process for resolving family disputes, borne out of some factors such as cultural expectations and economic pressures. The fact that the findings reveal the women seeking formal mediation after informal mediation is evidence of this position.
- (b) The findings revealed that some Nigerian women seek formal mediation after having engaged with informal mediation processes. It appears that a lack of trust and dissatisfaction in informal processes plays a significant role in driving women who have engaged with informal process to formal processes.
- (c) The barriers such as culture, patriarchy, discrimination, stigma, and social control are factors which prevent women from accessing justice through both informal and formal system. Other factors include lack of economic or financial power, administrative bottlenecks, etc.
- (d) That the lack of enforcement of mediation agreement from informal family mediation encourages formal family mediation.
- (e) That NGOs such as FIDA are major contributors to raising the legal consciousness of women specifically, and society in general on the procedures for accessing justice in

the resolution of family disputes. FIDA and NGOs which promote women's rights provides an avenue for women to enforce their rights.

- (f) There is a plethora of laws on the rights of women in Nigeria but lack of enforcement of these laws makes them appear non-existent.
- (g) Family mediation is not always the best form of dispute resolution in all family disputes especially in matters of intimate partner violence or domestic abuse.

8.3 Limitation of Thesis

In conducting this research, this thesis acknowledges the limitations of family mediation in Nigeria. The first challenge was identifying the relevant jurisprudence on family mediation in Nigeria with emphasis on informal mediation. The existing literature on family mediation is silent on informal mediation which is the heart of this study. The lack of sufficient documentary evidence on informal family mediation might not be unconnected to the confidentiality feature which accompanies mediation proceedings. The dearth of current literature on informal and formal mediation as it impacts women's access to justice was part of the limitations to this study.

It was a major challenge not being able to conduct this research the initial way planned as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. In adopting qualitative method of research, the plan was to embark on face-to-face interviews with the participants and it is possible to have received richer results which would be relevant for future research.

A further limitation to this study was the lack of clarity on the difference between informal and formal mediation in conducting the survey. This was largely due to the researcher not wanting to make the questions lengthy and discouraging to the participants as it was an online survey but hoped the general meaning of mediation was conveyed. The researcher carefully read the

responses from the survey in detail and was able to decipher when the participant meant informal or formal mediation from which the data analysis was done.

The interviews were semi-structured and designed to achieve the objective of the research as some of the participants had not been involved in an online interview before. In the Methodology Chapter, some of the limitations mentioned included having to rely on FIDA officials to act as interpreters where the participants did not speak English and having to rely on the FIDA officials as gatekeepers in deciding which of the complainants who came to the Centre could take part in the research.

Another major area of limitation which this study encountered was not being able to procure participants from northern Nigeria to take part in the interviews. It is possible that if a face-to-face interview had been possible with the participants from northern Nigeria, the research would have been enhanced. But unfortunately, the FIDA officials in the northern region were not able to convince the women to participate in an online interview like their counterparts in the rest of Nigeria. This might not be unconnected to cultural and religious beliefs associated with the Islamic faith which is largely practised in northern Nigeria as mentioned in the earlier chapters of this study.

8.4 Future of Family Mediation in Nigeria – Recommendations

The recommendations of this research are based on the five themes generated in this study as this will illustrate their relevance in family mediation in Nigeria.

Theme 1: INFORMAL MEDIATION AS A PROCESS TO JUSTICE

It is recommended that a mechanism be put in place by the government to ensure the smooth transition from informal family mediation to formal family mediation for those who wish it.

Family Mediation Act of Nigeria

It is the recommendation of this thesis that a Family Mediation Act for Nigeria be passed to regulate family mediation processes. The survey responses revealed that informal and formal mediation takes place in all the states of Nigeria. The data analysis of the findings was proof of the need for regulation of informal mediation with a focus on enforcement of mediation agreement as this was the major reason why the participants who took part in the interviews sought formal mediation at the FIDA legal centre as the participants revealed their lack of satisfaction with informal family mediation.⁷⁸³ One of the participants had narrated how her husband had thrown her and their three kids out of their matrimonial home, refusing to provide for them. All avenues including informal family mediation with his parents proved abortive until he was invited to the FIDA legal centre after her complaint and he complied with the agreement reached at the FIDA office.⁷⁸⁴ Consequently, it is the recommendation of this thesis that a uniform Family Mediation Act will provide structure and regulate family mediation in Nigeria and improve women's access to justice for those who wish to subject their mediation to be regulated by legislation to ensure fairness. The Family Mediation Act will ensure the uniformity of the basic principles of mediation such as impartiality of the mediator(s), voluntariness of the parties to the proceedings, etc. This recommendation is motivated by the high rate of satisfaction on the outcome of the survey results.⁷⁸⁵ The need to regulate informal family mediation arises from the evidence of the participants in the interviews such as the woman who stated that the people who mediated over her family dispute where her husband's

⁷⁸³ Interviews with Participant 8 and 9, at Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre in addition to the others.

⁷⁸⁴ Interview with Participant 8 Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on 23/05/2022 at 11:38hrs.

⁷⁸⁵ Chapters 6 and 7 of this thesis.

relatives and she was not allowed to state her side of the story as to why she had been away from her matrimonial home which was due to her illness.⁷⁸⁶

Themes 2 and 4: ACCESSING THE FORMAL SYSTEM AND ENFORCEMENT OF MEDIATION AGREEMENT

Enforcement of Mediation Agreement Act

It is the recommendation of this thesis that an Enforcement Mediation Act be enacted to ensure agreements from mediation proceedings are executed. One of the findings of this study was the theme on enforcement of mediation agreement and the silence of the law on the enforcement of family mediation agreements especially from informal mediation. It will also be necessary for a form of penalty for non-compliance with the mediation agreement to be included in the provisions of the Act. Though such a process will be more familiar in civil proceedings in terms, it can be adapted in enforcement of family mediation agreements.

Financial Legislative Act for Family Mediation

It is the recommendation of this study that a financial legislation be enacted to guide family mediation. This recommendation is as a result of the responses from some of the participants⁷⁸⁷ during the interviews whose stories revealed the financial hardship women encounter when there is resolution through informal family mediation when it concerns the welfare of children and distribution of family assets. In formal mediation, the structure of the courts could direct proceedings and ensure equity and fairness but in informal mediation where there are power

⁷⁸⁶ Interview with Participant 2 Lagos State FIDA Legal Centre held on 17/02/2022 at 10:17am.

⁷⁸⁷ Interview with Participant 2, Anambra State FIDA Legal Centre interview held on 13/01/2022 at 13:20hrs – The participant who had been separated from her husband had nowhere to stay and on returning to her biological home was also refused a place to stay by her brothers because she had been married out of the family. They told her she was not entitled to any part of their late father's houses: Participant 3, Anambra State FIDA Legal Centre interview held on 13/01/2022 at 13:38hrs- The participant stated that at the death of her husband, her in-laws seized their properties and sold off all the economic trees she had planted.

imbalances as revealed in the sub-themes and there is no framework for financial checks, it is difficult to ensure justice where there is no equity. Where there is a national financial legislative act to provide for family mediation, women have a better chance of not being left out in the cold, in the event of a separation or loss of relationship as evidenced by some of the respondents.⁷⁸⁸ A financial legislation will ensure that women do not remain in abusive environments for welfare purposes. There are countries⁷⁸⁹ where financial legislation is provided to address divorce settlements and welfare of children, Nigeria can emulate such an Act.

Continuing Legal Education

It is necessary for legal practitioners to continue their education in family mediation after being called to the legal profession as family disputes arise in different strata of society as evidenced by the responses from the survey in the call for lawyers to be more educated in family mediation and other forms of ADR.⁷⁹⁰ The survey question had asked: “Do you think lawyers should have mediation training?” The respondents had replied “yes” and proceeded further to justify their answers with some of the following explanations: “lawyers are well experienced in dispute resolution so they should be trained on this too,”⁷⁹¹ “to avoid mistakes when there is no formal training,”⁷⁹² “It’s important for lawyers to have compulsory training in mediation and arbitration,”⁷⁹³ “The end result of litigation is a ‘winner takes all’ situation but mediation seeks

⁷⁸⁸ No 11 of Survey Responses who stated that she sought mediation because her husband failed to provide for their 4 children.

⁷⁸⁹ Family Law (Scotland) Act 1985, Section 8.

⁷⁹⁰ Survey Respondents 7, 8, 16, 21 and more.

⁷⁹¹ Respondent 16.

⁷⁹² Respondent 18.

⁷⁹³ Respondent 21.

a win-win situation. It is a shorter process and less expensive. For these reasons I believe that lawyers should be versed in this process.”⁷⁹⁴

This recommendation though not included as one of the five themes became necessary as a recommendation of this study as a consequence of the responses from the participants from the survey as well as the interviews. There is a need for continuing legal education for legal practitioners in handling special matters such as family mediations.

Importance of ADR Skills as a Foundational Course in legal training

The data analysis from the survey responses revealed the need for emphasis on ADR skills to be part of a lawyer’s portfolio. This is the view of some authors as noted in the literature of this thesis.⁷⁹⁵ It is the recommendation of this study that ADR be made compulsory in the Nigerian law school which is the beginning of legal training in Nigeria. The purpose is to ensure legal practitioners have the required ADR training to understand the best method of dispute resolution for a matter. In the same vein, there should be a framework established by the government towards training judicial officers, mediators, lawyers, and personnel who work in the public sector on handling family disputes. Specialist training for family mediators could be established in Continuing Legal Education (CLE) for lawyers with an accreditation process to ensure quality and standard of mediators. It is further suggested by this thesis that lawyers who embark on family mediation training, include knowledge on gender issues in society.

Family Mediation Handbook for Nigeria

Based on the diverse culture and different ethnic groups which make up the rich heritage of Nigeria, it is the recommendation of this thesis that a uniform mediation handbook be published to regulate family mediation. This recommendation is in accordance with the agitation for a

⁷⁹⁴ Respondent 33.

⁷⁹⁵ Chapter Three, www.fidafederation.org (Accessed 31 January 2023).

uniform legislation to regulate mediation by Carroll as mentioned on page 163. Culture and tradition have a major influence in the resolution of family disputes particularly in informal mediation where issues such as respect for elders would come into play. A precedent of such a handbook is the African Union Mediation Support Handbook which was published by ACCORD in 2014 and serves as a guide for mediation proceedings in Africa. The outstanding feature of the handbook resides in the fact that the focus is Africa which recognises the role of culture and tradition in mediation. The use of the Family Mediation Handbook sensitisation will be adapted to suit the cultural features of the proceedings in which it is being adopted in.

Theme 3: Intimate Partner Violence

Regular Orientation Seminars for Law Enforcement Officers

It is the recommendation of this study that regular seminars on intimate partner violence be conducted for law officers such as the police to address such cases when reported. This will go a long way to affect the consciousness of women and how they perceive police intervention, if they know the police will address their complaints fairly.

The court could also make pronouncements on informal family mediation agreements where there is evidence of intimate partner violence and make pronouncements which will address the power imbalance both physically and financially where there is proper orientation and direction on how the court can intervene. Intimate partner violence can also be financial if the woman is abused financially where she is prevented from earning a living and deprived of sustenance by her husband or partner. Financial legislation such as that provided in the *Family Law (Scotland) Act 1985* can be emulated to prevent financial intimate partner violence.

Theme 5: GOVERNMENT INTERVENTION POLICY

Establishment of Customary Family Courts

There are family courts in existence but no provision for customary family courts. This research recommends the creation of customary family courts as this will provide a platform for the enforcement of agreements from informal mediations. The findings from this study revealed that informal family mediation is regulated largely by culture and practices of the family setting. The establishment of a customary family court will enable access to justice for those who wish to enforce agreements from informal family mediations. This recommendation is supported by the evidence of the participant who called for the government to do more to promote family mediation culturally.⁷⁹⁶

Establishment of National Family Mediation Board

This thesis proposes a national family mediation board to regulate the family mediation proceedings in Nigeria both for informal and formal mediations. The Board will be responsible for overseeing the administration of family mediation proceedings. The Board should be affiliated to the National Judicial Council (NJC) and the federal level and the State Judicial Council (SJC) at the various state levels. For formal mediation the structure of the courts particularly family courts could easily be adapted to align with the Federal High Courts, State High Courts including the High Court of the FCT. In informal mediation, the customary courts and area courts could work with mediation centres for proper regulation and coordination. It is the recommendation of this thesis that the Board be empowered with powers to stipulate the qualifications of personnel who will oversee family mediation proceedings in Nigeria both in the informal and formal sectors.

⁷⁹⁶ Interview with Participant 4 Rivers State FIDA Legal Centre held on 05/10/2021 at 11:46hrs.

Initiation of Women Projects- (The theme of Intimate Partner Violence is the foundation for this recommendation)

It is the recommendation of this thesis that the government embark on projects and programs to review policies and projects on women. This recommendation is as a result of the evidence of the literature on projects such as the feminist judgments as mentioned in Chapter Four of this study. An on-going project which reviews legislation and framework on the progress of women is the foundation for development in complying with the UN SDG⁷⁹⁷ 16 of ***Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions***. Goal 16 emphasises on eradicating threats to fundamental freedoms of people (in this case, women in Nigeria), by promoting strong institutions free from bias and corruption. If the government constitutes a monitoring team on the policies affecting women's rights, it will be able to determine the policies and laws which are effective in the access of justice. This will consequently impact on the legal consciousness of women and further enhance confidence in the processes of access to justice in Nigeria for women. It is the suggestion of this thesis that periodic evaluation of projects on women's rights be carried out by government to monitor the effectiveness of processes on access to justice.

Enlightenment Policies by Government

The core of the challenges Nigerian women experience in access to justice resides in the fact that Nigerian society remains patriarchal and is dominated largely by the male perspective. It is the position of this thesis that the access to justice routes for women in Nigeria be re-structured taking into cognisance the barriers women encounter. This thesis has revealed from its findings in the data analysis, that not all women are aware of alternative dispute resolution routes to access justice. It is the recommendation of this thesis that the government engage in structured policies which enlighten men and women on their rights and their access to justice.

⁷⁹⁷ United Nations Sustainable Development Goal.

It is important for men to be enlightened on the rights of women as this could impact on patriarchal values based on culture and impact positively on women's rights. This study argues that sensitisation and enlightenment schemes on women's rights is a better guaranteed method of ensuring women are informed on the routes to justice. Women also need to be enlightened on what their rights are to know when their rights are being abused. The need on sensitisation of the public on the rights of women and the different routes available to access justice cannot be overemphasised. The relevance of international human rights law as it affects women's rights in particular highlights the importance of awareness programmes which will ensure informed decisions by women. This thesis therefore recommends the highlighting of international human rights laws as they affect women with focus on the UNSDG in policies created by government.

7.5 Conclusion of Thesis

WHAT DID I SEEK TO DO IN THIS THESIS?

This study has shown that where there is no provision for enforcement of agreements resulting from informal family mediation, justice has not prevailed. The purpose of accessing justice is to obtain satisfaction. This thesis has revealed from the data analysis, the reason the women proceeded to formal mediation after informal mediation was lack of satisfaction from previous informal mediation proceedings. Inability to enforce family mediation agreement from informal proceedings often leads to formal mediation. This study seeks to show the gap in enforcement of family mediation agreements in informal mediations.

7.6. Thesis Contribution to Knowledge

The contribution of this study to knowledge resides in the identification of the gap in the law relating to family mediation as a process of Alternative Dispute Resolution. The purpose of family mediation as a process of resolving dispute is to promote justice between disputing family parties. The law is silent on how to enforce mediation agreements especially in informal

family mediation where one-party refuses to comply with the agreement reached at a mediation as shown in the evidence of the participant who stated that her husband moved out of the house after the family thought the dispute had been resolved. It is the view of the researcher that women or men who wish to enforce agreements from Informal family mediation should be allowed to do so by law as it is a resolution reached at mediation. In the case of formal mediation, the courts can enforce the agreement as using the structure of the legal system for civil procedure. The average Nigerian woman will shy away from litigation (as evidenced in the data analysis of this study), because of the challenges they encounter. These challenges range from financial to discriminatory which hinder women's access to justice and consequently leads to the alternative of informal mediation. In some instances, women who proceed to litigation to enforce their rights are labelled as 'troublemakers' even by family members. The women are also pressurised in some situations to withdraw the case in court or from the police station where she has lodged a complaint.⁷⁹⁸ The lacuna identified by this study is lack of enforcement of informal family mediation agreement.

This thesis further contributes to knowledge in the empirical findings of this study which revealed that despite the plethora of laws surrounding women's rights in Nigeria, culture and other factors have made women's rights seem non-existent as it concerns family mediation due to non-compliance of agreement. The participants who narrated how their husbands did not comply with the agreements reached after informal mediation has led to the recommendation that there be a legislation by parliament to enforce agreements reached at informal mediations as a legislation would imply non-compliance will attract a penalty. Enforcement proceedings

⁷⁹⁸ Interview with Participant 4 Anambra State FIDA Legal Centre held on 13/01/2022 at 13:55hrs – The participant stated that her husband beat her up and chased her out of their matrimonial with his people because she refused to close the case, she had reported at the police station. Her daughter had been raped and her husband had collected the sum of five hundred thousand naira (N500,000.00) as settlement from the perpetrator.

can be initiated by the party seeking justice. It is the hope of this thesis that the jurisprudence on family mediation in Nigeria has been enhanced by this research.

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